

Investigation of challenges and drivers in circular supply chain management and their contextual relationship: A stakeholder analysis for maximising sustainability in the food industry of the United Kingdom

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DEDICATION

This doctoral research is dedicated to my husband, Jatinder Singh Sidhu, my mother Pritam Kaur, my father, the Late Rajinder Singh Virk, my mother-in-law Tirathpal Kaur, my father-in-law, the late Surjeet Singh Sidhu and my daughter Niyamat Kaur Sidhu, whose inspiration, guidance, and love made me fulfilled, contented, and a better person each day of my life.

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Love you all

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AUTHOR'S DECLARATION

I, Mandeep Kaur, declare that I am the sole author of this thesis. To the best of my knowledge, no material including ideas, research work, analysis and conclusions reported in my research, Investigation of challenges and drivers, in circular supply chain management and their contextual relationship: A stakeholder analysis for maximising sustainability in the food industry of the United Kingdom, have been published by any other person, except where acknowledgement has been made. This work is entirely my effort. No part of this work has been submitted for the award of any other academic degree or diploma, except where otherwise indicated; this thesis is my own work.

ABSTRACT

The current production and consumption system has set abundance of challenges for humanity. If this trend continues, by 2050 equivalent of three earths will be needing to provide the natural resources to maintain this lifestyle (www.un.org). Circular supply chain management is considered a promising solution to attain the sustainability in current industrial system (Geissdoerfer, 2018). Despite the exigency of this approach, its application in food industry is a challenge because of the nature of industry and circular supply chain management being a novel approach. This research fulfils the perquisites of undertaking industry based systematic analysis of circular supply chain management by examining the challenges for its application, exploring the effects of recognised challenges on various food supply chain stages, and investigating the business processes as drivers.

Stakeholder theory guided the need of considering stakeholder's views in this research and key stakeholders directly from food circular supply chain (product designing, manufacturing, retailing, consumption, upcycling, recycling, and logistics) were identified and interviewed (n=36) following the qualitative methods. Adopting a critical realist perspective, the data is analysed manually as well as with the help of NVivo software, applying an inductive approach through thematic analysis. Six themes and several sub themes yielded from literature reviews and semi structure interviews are presented in the theoretical model. Overall, the study reveals that knowledge, perception towards environmental initiatives and economic viability are the major barriers for circular supply chain transition in the UK food supply chains requires which financial and educational controls from the government as fundamental enablers to drive the change with other organisational-level strategies. This research provides holistic perspective analysing the loopholes in different stages of the supply chain and investigating the way a particular circular supply chain stage is affected from recognised challenges through stakeholder theory which will be a contribution to design the management-level strategies. Reconceptualising this practice would be beneficial in bringing three-tier (economic, environmental, and social) benefit and will be supportive to engage the stakeholders in the sustainability agenda. However, the findings have some limitations related to sampling and methods. Recommendations have been provided for the future scope of research related to circular supply chain management.

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CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The first chapter starts by discussing the scope of this study; it presents the research background to begin with, followed by further sections: The definitions of important constructs and the concept used in this study are outlined in section 1.2, section 1.3 is the research background, section 1.4 describes the statement of the research problem, where the gaps in the literature are identified. Section 1.5 explains the need and development of the topic of the circular supply chain management. Section 1.6 explains the objectives of the research. Then, the methodology that has been followed to answer the research questions and generation of the conceptual model is discussed in section 1.7. Section 1.8 describes the significance of the study. Finally, a general picture of the following chapters is drawn in section 1.9.

1.2 DEFINITIONS OF CONSTRUCTS AND CONCEPTS

Circular Supply Chain Management is the co-ordination of forward and reverse supply chains (Batista et al., 2018a, p. 446) which systematically restore technical material and regenerate biological material towards a zero waste vision through system-wide innovation in business models and supply chain functions from product/service design to end-of-life and waste management, involving all stakeholders in a product/service lifecycle including parts/product manufacturers, service providers, consumers, and users (Farooque et al., 2019, p.884)

The circular economy is a restorative and regenerative production technique (EMP, 2012; 2013; 2014) which contributes in raising productivity (Linder and Williander, 2015; EEA, 2016; Souza-Zomer et al., 2018) and bringing economic and environmental benefits like increasing Gross Domestic Product, net material saving, employment growth (EMF, 2013a; Morgan and Mitchell, 2015) reducing carbon footprints (EMF and MCK, 2014; Pratt and Lenaghan, 2015) by keeping the product components, natural and human resources and material at highest utility and optimum level (Linder and Williander, 2017; EEA, 2016; Souza-Zomer et al., 2018).

Supply Chain Management is systematic and strategic co-ordination of traditional business functions (Mentzer et al., 2001b, p. 22) that helps in management of relationships from upstream to downstream and from end user to original supplier to deliver superior customer value at less cost and to improve the long-term performance of individual companies and the supply chain as a whole (Christopher 1998; Cooper et al., 1997).

Designing in the circular economy is a deliberate business process involving hundreds of decisions (Krishnan and Ulrich 2001), with the intent of developing a tangible, physical product (Petersen et al., 2005; Rauniar et al., 2008; Hong and Roh 2009; Hong et al., 2011) using the strategies of slowing and closing the resource loop, where slowing of resource loops involves increasing the utilisation of products, through extending the product lifetime and through sharing schemes. Closing resource loops relates to ensuring that materials can be recycled in a closed-loop fashion at the end of use (Stahel,1994; McDonough and Braungart, 2002; Stahel, 2010).

Manufacturing in circular supply chain management is a process in which products are manufactured and remanufactured (Batista et al., 2018a) by utilising the variety of capabilities that add value to the material by minimising negative environmental impacts, conserving energy and natural resources that are safer and rewarding for employees, communities and consumers and are economically sound (USD OC, 2012).

Retailing in the circular economy refers to the management of retailing business with environmental benefits (Lai et al., 2010) by creation, utilisation and use of assets with least negative impact (Polonsky, 2011) and has ecological dimensions that pursue the retail value chain by eliminating waste, increasing efficiency and by reducing the cost (Chaudhary, 2014).

Consuming is a set of social relationships, discourses, and practices (Mansvelt, 2017) that focus on the activities of selection, purchase, use, maintenance, repair and disposal (Campbell,1995).

Upcycling is a green practice within the realm of product management (Griskevicius et al., 2010; Lin and Chang, 2012) which encourages the environmentally conscious entrepreneur to create and modify products from used material (Sung and Cooper, 2015) which is of higher quality or value than compositional elements (Sung et al., 2014; Sung, 2017), consumers to engage with

alternatives (Albinsson and Yasanthi Perera,2012) and environmentally sustainable products and facilitate economic diversification and employment opportunities (Khan and Tondon,2018).

Recycling is a critical part of the circular economy which ensures products are valued not wasted or left to pollute the environment (WRAP, 2019), by activities of reprocessing of recovered material at the end of the product life (Worrel and Reuter, 2014).

Logistics in circular supply chain management is a combination of green and reverse logistics processes, which focus to change the environmental performance of supplier to customers (Oksana Seroka-Stolka and Ociepa-Kubicka, 2018) by combining the activities of recycling, reusing, and reducing (Carter and Ellram,1998) and efficiently planning, implementing, and controlling the cost-effective flow of materials, from the point of consumption to the point of origin of the product (Rogers and Tibben-Lembke 1999, p. 2).

1.3 RESEARCH BACKGROUND

The industrial revolution left enormous effects on our environment, which are agitating post-industrial society. This scenario is making the urge to transfer global material cycle (take-make-dispose) to a sustainable cycle. Therefore, circular economy is the method to facilitate the “United Nation Sustainable Goals” for sustainable development by adopting it in practical manner because this model considers business as a pertinent player. Transition to a circular economy need drastic change in the supply chain which jointly termed circular supply chain management (Canning, 2006; Du et al., 2010; Genovese et al., 2017; Nasir et al., 2017, Zhang, 2021). Thürer, et al. (2019) defined circular supply chain management as “*the integration of circular thinking into the management of the supply chain and its surrounding industrial and natural ecosystems*” (p. 884) Circular supply chain management stresses on transmuting manufacturing features from liner to circular by including processes like reusing, recycling, refurbishing and remanufacturing with the flow of products, by-products and waste (Mangla et al.,2018). Circular economy is suitable strategy to bring novel methods for the transformation of linear supply chain to circular (Stahel, 2013, Zhang, 2021) because this approach will be able reduce waste and negative environment impact of production and consumptions processes (Nasir et al., 2017; Genovese et al., 2017).

Application of circular approach in supply chain serves higher level of efficiency in sustainable practices than the traditional methods like closed-loop supply chain which rarely focus on reusing or recycling, whereas with the circular approach in supply chain, it becomes possible to recover the value across various industrial sectors or a single sector of different supply chains (Weetman, 2017; Genovese et al., 2017; Walker, 2021). Circular economy approach is deeply rooted in sustainability science through its branches: industrial ecology (Erkman, 1997), cleaner production (Fresner, 1998) and cradle-to-cradle (C2C) (McDonough and Braungart, 2002). The business community is the most important lever of this approach in every transition (Franklin-Johnson et al., 2016). Hence, it focuses on economic and business opportunities (Velis 2015; Aminoff and Kettunen, 2016).

The circular economy is seen from a broad theoretical and practical perspective (Hobson, 2016; Stewart and Niero, 2018) to alter the linear economic model and help supply chains to achieve an advanced sustainable performance (Ghisellini et al., 2016; Farooque et al., 2019). It is a trending and emerging topic for both scholars and practitioners as it is considered as the most practical approach for businesses to apply in the sustainable development framework unlike other concepts i.e., green economy and green growth, which are too vague to be implemented (Kirchherr et al., 2017). However, the supply chains become excessively complex when integrated with circular economy (Alkhuzaim, 2020).

The Club of Rome contemplated transforming the sustainable development model in such a way as to decrease GHG emissions by 70% along with increasing the demand for labour by 4% (Stahel, 2017). So, there is a need to revise all the production, consumption, and business models by positioning the changes, incorporated in the circular economy model (Xaviera, 2019). The basic idea of the circular economy philosophy is to change the traditional linear (take-make-waste) economic system for reducing the use and waste of natural capital. The resources in the circular supply chain are circulated and recirculated in loops without wasting anything. Each product in the circular supply chain is designed in such a way that its biological and technical components can be separated and repurposed, which gives an idea of the effectiveness of this system (Berndtsson, 2015).

Figure 1.1: Linear V/s Circular

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Circular supply chain management is a novel concept which is still at an exceedingly early stage (Formentini, 2021). The interest of academics towards this transition has grown remarkably (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017; Ünal et al., 2018; Tura et al., 2019). However, scientific research with practical implementation is lagging because of the current linear nature of business processes (Korhonen et al., 2018; Hopkinson et al., 2018; Tura et al., 2019). Looking at the current resources crisis, it is required for policy makers to design their supply chains based on circular economy approach (Andersen, 2007; Besio and Pronzini, 2014; Miliute-Plepiene and Plepys, 2015; Schneider, 2015; Haas et al., 2015; Schaltegger et al., 2016). But its applied management directions are yet to be explored (Hopkinson et al., 2018; Angelis, 2019).

Research on the circular economy concept and the food supply chains may not seem directly correlated and that they are not much studied together. The circular economy is a matter of disconnecting economic growth from resource depletion. It assists in directing the issues of resource scarcity and ecological downgrading in the industrial context (Geng et al., 2009). The circular economy does not particularly focus on economic benefits (i.e., reducing the expenses generated by purchasing of raw material and value creation) but it also connects with sustainable development by environmental and social benefits. For organisations nowadays, “business as usual” or the linear approach (take-manufacture-use-dispose-of) is risky and not an appropriate choice (Williams, 2001). Thus, the whole supply chain needs transformation (Low et al., 2016). As a matter of fact, scarcity of natural resources, increasing commodity prices and environmental concern means the whole pattern needs to be revised.

Redesigning the supply chain according to the circular model requires systematic analysis of obstacles and the drivers (Bressanelli,2018). It requires methods or tools for various stakeholders of companies to recognise the capacity and possibility of product regeneration at each phase of circular supply chain management. Its implementation varies according to the nature of the industry because of the involvement of different types of stakeholders and processes (Farooqe et al., 2019). In essence, industry specific analysis is essential to overcome the obstacles. The need for applying a circular supply chain model in the food industry is a challenging task and seeks close analysis of all aspects which jointly can make it possible. The circular food supply chain is a combination of many key actors who are dependent on each other; any complication at one stage affects all of them so it is particularly relevant to discover the contextual effects of all barriers and find out how and to what extent one issue is influential for all the actors. In this way, the complexity and trend of the circular supply chain makes the topic more interesting to experiment with and ascertain the best possible practices for the successful implementation of “closing the loop” practices.

Proponents of the circular supply chain are viewed as deeper than sustainable development. Sustainable development has been criticised for its limited scope, concentrating only on efficiency. McDonough and Braungart (2013) say that current eco-efficiency strategies are still following linear production system, only extending the internal boundaries. For example, recycling, which is another form of downcycling, works by burning rubbish to produce energy. Rather, the need is to focus on effectiveness. Thus, Braungart and McDonough (2008) suggested the cradle-to-cradle and circular supply chain framework, application to create the structure of eco-effectiveness which applies infinite cycles of materials. Consequently, for businesses, there is a need to design a waste-free industrial system with positive overall results (Berndtsson, 2015).

The circular supply chain is also a technique that contributes to raising productivity, optimises the use of natural and human resources and increases efficiency in resource management (EEA, 2016; Linder and Williander, 2017; Souza-Zomer et al., 2018). It can become a mechanism not only for bringing economic and business growth but also building up prosperity by not depleting any more natural capital (Schulte, 2013; Gregson et al., 2015; Murray et al., 2015) and this framework will be compatible with the principle of inter and intra- generational equity as raised in 1987 in

the Brundtland Commission Report (Ghisellini et al., 2016). Thus, the fundamentals of the circular approach appear to be economic, environmental, and social sustainability (Angelis, 2018).

Growing population, urbanisation, industrialisation, and climate change are all significant drivers to revise the traditional way of arranging organisational, regulatory, institutional, and political structure along with social and economic relations i.e., supply chain, technologies, and lifestyles (Borrello et al., 2017; Chen 2021). Circular supply chain management refers to a restorative production system in which resources enter in an infinite loop for reusing, remanufacturing, and recycling. Circular supply chain management aims to optimise resource utilisation throughout the product lifecycle (Mangla et al., 2018). It has become an instrumental force for supply chain sustainability (Genovese, 2017; Hobson, 2016; Nasir et al., 2017). It provides new and innovative scope to supply chain management. So, moving towards the circular supply chain has become an emergent trend among all the global supply chain leaders, stated in the 14th annual global supply chain top 25 report for 2018 published by Grantner. This report also declares that the future of supply chain is circular not linear (Aronowetal., 2018).

The major stakeholders of organisations are becoming influenced by sustainability approaches and demanding environmental performance along with economic performance (Genovese, 2017). Looking at the situation, companies are keen to recognise the potential for replacing their existing business models with circular economy models so that an expected crisis of materials, price and supply can be mitigated. It has become vital to align sustainability with supply chains while extending the boundaries of environmental concern (Genovese, 2017). But turning towards circular supply chain practices is a challenge for industrial practitioners. There are many factors which are impeding companies to enter in this model, which must be investigated and overcome by possible drivers.

1.4 STATEMENT OF THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

The food industry makes a notable contribution to the UK economy. In 2018, Gross Value Added of the Agri-food sector was 9.4% to national gross-value-added, reaching £121 billion. And the food manufacturing sector is £28.6 billion (Defra, 2018), which has been on an increasing trend. Expansion in the global population every year at an exponential rate needs massive amounts of

food and energy. However, environmental impacts of the food chain are also high. As per the report from The Food Climate Research Network UK, the food chain accounts for 19% of total UK GHG emissions (WWF, 2018). The combination of swift growth in urbanisation and less progress in waste management strategies leads towards amassing food wastage (Ravindran and Jaiswal, 2016). Food waste all over the world adds 8 percent of total anthropogenic GHG emissions, which is notably 87 percent of global road transport emissions (FAO, 2015). Existing studies say that reducing food waste can save £300 billion per year (WRAP, 2015) and to achieve this, there is a need to reduce wastage by 20-50%. So, it is evident that the existing sustainability concept should be integrated with the circular economy which emphasises restorative and regenerating methodology (Batista et al., 2018a).

Food wastage during the supply chain is one of the effects that contributes significantly to the whole of production waste. Globally, food supply chains play a major role in increasing the amount of solid waste (Hoornweg et al., 2013), greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Brundtland, 1987; Genovese et al., 2017), soil degradation, water, and energy consumption (Morone et al., 2019). As per FAO 2011, food wastage throughout the global supply chain is estimated at 1.3 billion tons (one-third of the edible food). Consequently, growing food wastage has become a notable issue for global food security and environmental governance leading to serious impacts on the environment, economy, and society (Farooque et al., 2019). Each activity on all stages of (i.e., manufacturing, consumption, logistic flow, and disposal) (Hobson, 2016) of the food supply chain leaves a footprint on the environment and is a major loss for businesses. This has to be managed wisely to avoid the risk of depletion of natural means, accumulation of waste and a high rate of GHG emissions (Hellweg and Canals, 2014).

The circular economy is the best and the latest effort to conceptualise the combination of sustainability, economically and in an environmentally friendly ways in supply chains with limited resources (Murray et al., 2017). This is the primary requirement of the food industry, where end-of-life management activity is still applied on a minimal basis. It is the industry where all of the aspects (production, selling, processing, packaging, consumption) are responsible for major waste generation and turning the output/waste into input/resource is a big challenge (Mathews and Tan, 2016). Although existing studies provide a valuable input but there is scarce literature on industry

4.0 based circular economy research , hence sustainability impact of industry oriented research is needed (Morteza,2020).

The business community is the most important lever of circular approach in every transition (Franklin-Johnson, 2016). Hence, its focus is on economic and business opportunities (Velis, 2015; Aminoff and Kettunen, 2016). Transformation of circular application can benefit the UK economy by providing opportunities for more than 500,000 jobs, by reducing unemployment by about 100,000 and by offsetting 18% of future losses in skilled employment by 2030 (WRAP, 2015). There has been significant attention given to the circular economy and it has been considered an auspicious approach to promote competitiveness and sustainability through literature, organisations, and policy makers (Murray et al, 2017). China, Japan, the US and European Union, and many other countries have proposed policies to support the circular economy transition (Ghisellini et al., 2016; Winans et al., 2017). However, a bottom-up approach is still needed, urging companies to take the initiative (Bressanelli et al., 2019).

Previous studies related to the circular economy have analysed the concept as a business model (Ghisellini et al., 2014; Vermeulen, 2015; Urbinati et al., 2017; Linder and Williander, 2017; Ünal et al., 2018). The circular economy is studied as a two-dimensional chain: one is the value network, consider the management of supply chain by creating the value for its stakeholders i.e., suppliers, retailers, or manufacturers (Parkinson and Thompson, 2003; Vermeulen, 2015); and second is the value proposition and interface by managing the relationship with customers (Williams, 2007; Tukker, 2015; Ünal et al., 2018). Hence, it calls for systematic analysis from the stakeholder viewpoint to implement a circular approach into organisational process (Stirling, 2011).

Identification of circular supply chain deterrents is a difficult process due to its diversified nature and less awareness in the industries and societies (Stirling, 2011; de Jesus and Mendonça, 2018). The hindrance and enabling circular supply chain management is explored in previous literature in general and different countries context (Bressanelli et al., 2018a; Govindan and Hasanagic, 2018; Huybrechts et al., 2018; Mangla et al., 2018; Ranta et al., 2018). But it is important to explore it on the industry basis (Farooque et al., 2019) and there is no significant research done on the UK food industry for circular supply chain implementation.

1.5 ARISING NEED AND DEVELOPMENT

The approach is gaining momentum among different cultures, and in different social and political contexts (Yu et al., 2015). Rapid growth in science, technology and industrialisation in this era has brought enormous tools and technology to facilitate human life, which have proved to be revolutionary. However, on the other side, it resulted in many negative impacts like environmental damage, climate alteration and depletion of natural resources. The population is also growing globally, income is increasing, and people's disposable income is increasing. People are buying and using more material resources, which can result in many material resources becoming expensive to use, unaffordable or might even be unavailable in the future (Adams et al., 2017). Thus, from the environmental point of view, resource scarcity stems from unsustainable production and consumption patterns. The circular economy can provide businesses with significant opportunities for better management of resources (EMF, 2016; Pomponi and Moncaster, 2017). Hence, economic benefits from the market are drivers for the circular economy revolution (McArthur et al., 2015).

From the environmental perspective, as per Global Footprint Network (2019), humanity is using natural resources 1.75 times faster than the earth's ecosystem can generate, which is equal to 1.75 earths. Earth Overshoot Day denotes the date when humanity's annual demand surpasses what our planet's ecosystem can regenerate in that year. Earth Overshoot Day 2020-21 has been moved to July 29th (overshootday.org, 2021), for the year which is 3 months earlier than 20 years ago. Figure 2 shows the specific Overshoot Day, demonstrating its huge influence on the environment. The Global Footprint Organization (2019) has also developed a Footprint Calculator by which one can get an estimate of one's own personal overshoot day by measuring ecological footprints.

Figure: 1.2 Earth Overshoot Day

Source: overshootday.org,2021

The circular economy, being a theoretical concept, aims to create a restorative and regenerative system (Seyring and Muller, 2008; McDonough and Braungart, 2010; EMF, 2016; Genovese, 2017). China adopted it as top-bottom approach through regulation whereas Europe, North America and Japan accepted it as bottom-top strategy (Winans et al., 2017). In the early development, China was the dominant country to provide the literature background for the circular economy, which flourished after European Commission focussed on the issue of waste management in 2014 (Türkeli et al., 2018; de Silva, 2018).

There is a substantial need for circular supply chain management in industries, which can become an integral part of economies if barriers can be removed. Despite this startling situation, there has been very limited research directed towards circular framework in food supply chains which can find the obstacles and drivers for sustainable development. Both are optimistic and supporting fields of each other. On the one hand, circular supply chain management is an emerging topic for research and ideally its hindrance factors and drivers in industry must be thoroughly discussed and

established. On the other hand, the food industry is an interesting and demanding framework for the application of these transformational practices.

1.6 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

More recently, various researchers and practitioners have studied this subject. Most studies are from the perspective of environment or waste management. The business perspective of the subject has been studied by: Vanner et al., 2014; van Eijk, 2015; Shahbazi et al., 2016; Borrello, 2016; Mont et al., 2017; Pheifer, 2017; De Jesus and Mendonça, 2018; Ritzéna and Sandströma, 2017; Kirchherr et al., 2018; Ranta et al., 2018, Farooque et al., 2019. Borrello et al., 2016; Shahbazi et al., 2016; Mont et al., 2017; Pheifer, 2017; Sung, 2017; Kirchherr et al., 2018; Mangla et al., 2018; de Jesus and Mendonça, 2018; Hart et al., 2018; Farooque, 2019; Sandvik and Stubbs, 2019; Farooque et al., 2019; Levering, 2019 etc., contributed to investigating several barriers which industries are facing for adoption of circular economy practices, from which Farooque et al. (2019) highlighted the barriers in the Chinese in food sector, others are related to automobile, heavy vehicle, fashion and the clothing industry. Xavier et al., (2019) talk about urban mining and in general context. Similarly, the possible drivers have been investigated by: Andrews, 2015; Silva et al., 2018. A study of barriers and drivers is conducted by Rizos et al. (2015) from the Small to Medium Enterprises perspective. Pomponi and Moncaster (2018) review the built environment. Geissdoerfer (2018) proposed a framework including the supply and business model. Heyes (2018) provided an overview of the circular economy in service-oriented companies. Ünal (2018) discussed managerial practices. Amienyo (2012) provided a contribution to sustainable assessment in the convenience food sector. Schmidt (2015) contributed to the beverages sector for sustainable practices.

This research contributes to the existing literature by investigating three objectives:

- It explores the circular supply chain management approach from the food industry perspective.
- It explores the key barriers in Circular Supply Chain Management in the food industry and drivers to those barriers.

- It critically analyses the repercussions of those barriers on each stage (Designing, manufacturing, retailing, consumption, upcycling, recycling and logistics) of the circular supply chain management.

According to the circular economy literature there is limited industry-based research. It is required to analyse bottom-up strategies to implement the circular economy in supply chains incorporating all relevant stakeholders (Mendoza et al., 2019). Researchers need not only focus on technical innovations but social innovations i.e., change in consumer behaviours also need to be considered (Winans et al., 2017; Kirchherr et al., 2017). Conceptual studies can be a valuable step to get conceptual as well as practical implementation (Urbinati et al., 2017; Angelis, 2020). In this way, the complexity and trend of the circular supply chain makes the topic more interesting to experiment and ascertain best possible practices for the successful implementation of “close the loop” practices.

Based on the above objective, researcher try to answer the following research questions:

- What is the circular supply chain management approach from the food industry perspective? How can it be achieved?
- What are the challenges that obstruct successful application of the food circular supply chain management framework and what can be the possible drivers to overcome these obstacles?
- How do these barriers affect each stage (Designing, manufacturing, retailing, consumption, upcycling, recycling, and logistics) of the circular supply chain?

Investigating these objectives will be a positive addition in the current literature of circular supply chain management. This will provide a foundation to the food industry and to the stakeholders of supply chain management to adopt circular economy as a business model. The next section will shed light on the research design and method used in this study to achieve the goal.

1.7 RESEARCH DESIGN AND ANALYTICAL METHOD

This research will use interpretivist philosophy. The qualitative data method is used in research where there is a need to understand feelings, values, reasons, trends, opinions, perceptions, and motivations which underlie and influence behaviour. Therefore, it allows the researcher to study the research problem in more depth and detail through direct quotations and careful description of programmes, situations, events, people, interactions and observed behaviour (Patton, 1987; Thomas, 2003). Consequently, the qualitative method is involved to gather the views, perceptions, motivations, and suggestions of key stakeholders for the transition of circular supply chain management rather than mixed methods or the quantitative approach which utilise mathematical statistical or numerical data (Sukamolson, 2007). This two-way discussion of research will lead toward more understanding of each stage of the circular supply chain of food industry and stakeholders' perception and concern regarding the circular evolution. This methodology is utilised to assess the barriers during the supply chain of food products which gives an indication about where the inefficiencies exist (Acquaye et al., 2011b; Ibn-Mohammed et al., 2014).

The qualitative approach is constructive when the meaning of phenomenon for those involved, the interpretation and their experience are more important than prediction, causal-effect, and distribution of attributes (Meriam, 2009; Lapan et al., 2012). The qualitative method will help in gaining in-depth understanding of barriers and drivers for the adoption, along with understanding the perception, attitude, behaviours and experience of stakeholders of food supply chain for the implementation of the circular approach with the use of semi-structured interviews, which will be more efficient to explain, interpret and justify the theme of the research. It is obvious that the qualitative methodology is well suited for research on novel phenomena like the circular supply chain management, where knowledge of involved actors, strategic processes and the supported network is still limited (Van et al., 2014).

Stakeholder theory guided the selection of participants so that barriers and drivers connected to a specific function should be identified and the supply chain stages can be explored in the context of barriers. The participants identified are the stakeholders of circular supply chain management of the food industry of the United Kingdom. To recognise the barriers and related to the specific stage of circular supply chain, managers for those stages were approached i.e., from the designing stage: research and development manager, from manufacturing stage; planning and operational managers etc. Data analysis is a process of carrying order, structure, and interpretation of large

amount of collected data to discover the relationship between different categories (Marshall and Rossman, 1999). The method used, to analyse qualitative data is “Thematic Analysis” which develop the categories from existing literature and the categories arose from primary data collection.

In this study, the overall validity of the subject under research is vital which needs exploration of perception and views of interviewees (stakeholders) from different perspectives. Thus, it should adopt an analytical procedure which will allow a standard framework, organisation, and theoretical principles to be used from qualitative data and it will enrich the research findings (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Cassell et al., 2006; McGrath and Pistrang, 2007).

1.8 STATEMENT OF SIGNIFICANCE

Investigating the obstacles in circular supply chain management will be helpful for companies, researchers, and institutions. It will further lead towards the drivers, methods, or tools for various stakeholders of companies to recognise the capacity and possibility of product regeneration in each phase of circular supply chain management. It will also be a helpful attempt to gain better understanding of circular supply chain management concept and potential to implement it in the food industry. Overall, this will be a considerable contribution in the theoretical and management field (see full details in chapter 7).

Provisioning food is the most prominent sector of every country because of its benefit of fulfilling the basic needs of the people and contributing to the economy of that nation. The British food and drink manufacturing sector is the biggest industry in the UK which comes before automotive, and aerospace combined. The manufactured food and drinks industry is responsible for contributing £28 billion to the country’s economy and employing 106,000 workers. 4.3 million people are employed in the whole food supply chain, who help in generating £120 billions of added value to the economy every year (fdf.org, 2020). On the one hand, there has been a big rise in the economic contribution of the food sector; on the other hand, the country is also experiencing health issues. About $\frac{2}{3}$ adults in England are overweight and obese (NHS long term, plan, 2016/17). In contrast, a larger proportion of the world’s population is suffering from starvation, hunger, and

undernourishment, especially in developing countries of Sub-Saharan Africa and Southern and Western Asia (FAO, *The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World*, 2017 p. 7).

Moreover, from the environmental perspective, the UK food economy is accountable for more than 32 million tons of carbon emissions. The whole supply chain is responsible for a huge amount of contamination, adding 14 million tons of carbon from direct emissions from the UK agriculture sector, and 2.1 million tons of carbon equivalents from fertilisers. Looking at the UK food manufacturing, distribution, and retail sector, they are jointly responsible for producing 15 million tons of carbon equivalents (WWF, 2020).

Considering the emergent scenario, sustainability is becoming an inseparable part of economies and businesses by ditching traditional practices which the industries were based on for a long time. However, sticking only to sustainable practices is not enough: there is a need to implement tools supporting zero waste management strategies. The circular supply chain is the best transformation model which handles waste minimisation strategies more efficiently and effectively. Economies can gain enormous benefits by efficient policy making and implementation as they provide many opportunities in different sectors i.e., plastic, food supply chain, clothing, steel, and smartphone (Amoyaw-Osei and Agyekum, 2011). This is beneficial for emergent economies providing economic benefits by cost reduction, environmental benefits by reducing pollution and social benefits by providing low-cost products.

The circular food supply chain is a new and propitious field in waste management that calls for zero waste strategies. It needs more contribution in total value recovery from all the actors of the supply chain by utilising waste in making something useful. Consequently, there is a broader scope for adding more research in the area (Farooque, 2019). Companies which decide to restructure their supply chain system to the circular economy, unlike the linear economy, will receive economical (Cucchiella et al., 2015), environmental (Genovese et al., 2017) and social (Ongondo et al., 2013) advantages. Reverse logistics and its configuration play a big role to develop circular supply chain framework, but major hurdles are expected to prevent the attainment of this transition on this phase as well (van Loon et al., 2018). There are existing studies discussing quantity-, quality-, timing- and capacity-related issues in the circular supply chain management (Linder and Williander, 2017), but a much more systematic analysis of challenges, faced at the time of

redesigning a company's circular supply chain is needed, which would complement the initial research (Geissdoerfer et al., 2018). Thus, an exploratory study is demanded (Sandvik, 2019). Literature says that consumer behaviour plays a significant role, therefore examining business to consumer (B2C) factors and rational / irrational motives of customers and methods to satisfy them will play an instrumental role to support circular supply chain management practices (de Sousa Jabbour,2019).

Considering economic, social, and environmental impacts, the food supply chain must be more sustainable and food waste should be planned, recorded, communicated, and organised carefully (Zhao, 2019). The circular supply chain management is a dynamic approach and is not very easy to assess and monitor. For its successful implementation in industries, it is important to examine the threatening indicators it faces on all levels of the supply chain. Because its aspects are interconnected in this way, any variation at one end would affect the whole. Secondly, there is rarely a study regarding the circular supply chain which considers the customer perspective which is one of the most significant and inseparable aspects of the food supply chain (Kirchherr et al., 2017; Elzinga, 2020). So, it is valuable to explore consumer's perspective for its effective implementation. Similarly, the other actors should equally be considered. There is a lack of exploring the list of barriers under theoretical lenses (Farooque, 2019). Thirdly, providing tools, methods and guidelines is required for adopting the circular practices. There follow the research gaps found in previous studies:

- i. Levers and challenges of the circular supply chain management can vary based on numerous factors i.e., industry, company size, role in supply chain and geography etc (Bressanelli et al., 2018; Kirchherr et al., 2018; Tura et al., 2018; Hart et al., 2019; Hussain and Malik, 2020; Keulen and Kirchherr, 2021). There has not been any previous research done on the UK food industry in the context of the circular supply chain.
- ii. Tura et al' s (2018) study on barriers in the circular economy does not address the effect of individual barriers on the whole supply chains so this research will acknowledge the repercussions of each barrier throughout the circular supply chain.
- iii. Furthermore, considering the consumer perspective has also been demanded (Kirchherr et al., 2017; Elzinga, 2020) in previous research.

- iv. Limited research is performed on the conceptual studies for the circular business model to facilitate its practical and managerial implementation (Bressanelli et al., 2018; Howard et al., 2019; Angelis, 2020).

This study provides a detailed understanding of circular supply chain management by exploring barriers and drivers from the perspective of stakeholders. Qualitative research offers flexible framework for this study because perspectives usually vary according to the experiences and positions of stakeholders. This flexible framework is needed to explore human perspective and opinion and to utilise the opinion as research (Hong et al., 2017). The theoretical aspect offers a contribution of theory extension by empirical exploration. This qualitative research gathers data which can be tested through preconceived theories and hypotheses in future research (Taylor et al., 2015). In term of methodology, this research used a multi-disciplinary approach to the circular supply chain management concept as a main contribution of this study to provide a holistic perspective of the domain the circular economy literature.

1.9 ORGANISATION OF THIS THESIS

This thesis is organised into seven chapters along with appendices and references. The thesis is structured as follows:

Chapter I. Introduction

The first chapter discusses the significance, the aims, and the method and the research methods that are adopted and finally continues by presenting the contribution of this study.

Chapter II. Literature review

This chapter is concerned with the relevant literature to the circular supply chain management studies from different perspectives, its origin and evolution with the time. Following its elements along with the barriers and drivers are presented.

Chapter III. Conceptual framework and research hypotheses

Here the theoretical lens used in this research and conceptual model of the research is described.

Chapter IV. Methodology and research design

Research methodology and data analysis techniques employed in the research are discussed in this chapter. The data analysis techniques and ethical considerations are explained in this chapter.

Chapter V. Data analysis

This reports the outcomes of qualitative data outcomes.

Chapter VII. Discussion

Findings from qualitative study are presented in this chapter.

Chapter VIII. Conclusions

The overall summary of the results of this study is presented. It also addresses the importance of findings, research implications and limitation of this study. It suggests directions for future research based on research finding of this study. Lastly, appendices and references are added.

CHAPTER II: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

The current scenario of industrialisation leads to the need for a restorative system, which can be achieved by flow of resources in an innovative manner and for long-term economic growth (Genovese et al., 2015). Circular supply chain management has been considered as a complete or partial solution of sustainable development challenges (Geissdoerfer et al., 2018). It is concerned with creating metabolism for industries in which resources are used again and again and makes production methods self-sustaining (Genovese et al., 2015). The circular economy concept is built upon three pillars – economic, social, and environmental – giving benefits like value creation, savings, environment impact reduction and job creation etc. With the same context, supply chain management yields benefit like cost reduction, better production, products, and customer service (Marsillac and Roh, 2014).

Existing knowledge has a prominent role in the research (Rowley and Slack, 2004). A comprehensive summary of literature is helpful: 1. to illustrate close understanding of the research topic, question, and hypothesis; 2. to recognize the background of the research area; 3. to explore different views on the research topic; 4. to present the scope of the study; 5. to identify the gaps in our knowledge (Booth et al., 2016); 6. to state the research problem; 7. to establish the context of the research problem (Hart, 1998); 8. to relate the ideas and theories with practice (Hart, 1998); and 9. to provide the appropriate conclusion.

Similarly, this chapter provides a comprehensive overview of the background of the circular economy, its role related to strategic management decisions in business (supply chain management) and its importance in the food industry. A range of literature has been reviewed in this chapter to critically analyse the concept of circular supply chain management. This chapter creates a link between what has already been studied, what this research tends to investigate and the gaps in the current existing literature. The circular supply chain management concept is a group of various ideas extracted from some scientific fields, emerging fields and semi-scientific concepts (Korhonen et al., 2018). Circular supply chain management is a combination of many concepts like industrial ecosystems (Jelinski et al., 1992), ecology (Frosch and Gallopoulos, 1989; Graedel,

1996; Lifeset and Graedel, 2001) and symbioses (Chertow and Ehrenfeld, 2012), cleaner production (Stevenson and Evans, 2004), circular material flow (Lieder and Rashid, 2016), Product-service system (Tukker, 2015), cradle-to-cradle design (Braungart et al., 2007), eco-efficiency (Welford, 1998; Huppel and Ishikawa, 2009; Haas et al., 2015) the performance economy (Stahel, 2010; Ellen McArthur Foundation, 2013), natural capitalism (Hawken et al., 2008), resilience of social-ecological systems (Folke, 2005; Crepin et al., 2012), the concept of zero emissions (Pauli, 2010), the circular economy (Carson, 1962; The Club of Rome, 1970; Pearce and Turner, 1990; Stahel, 2016) and supply chain management (Cooper and Ellram, 1993; Harland 1994, 1996; Saunders 1995; Cooper et al., 1997; Monczka and Morgan, 1997; Lumus and Vokurka 1999) and many others.

This chapter explains, in section 2.2, theoretical background; 2.3 the origin and evolution of circular supply chain management; in 2.4, the concept of circular supply chain management; in 2.5, elements of circular supply chain management; in 2.6, barriers and drivers in circular supply chain management; and in 2.7, development of the theoretical framework on the based-on stakeholder theory.

2.2 THEORITICAL BACKGROUND:

Theories play an instrumental role for research to conceptualize the objective of research. Theories are significant to provide meaning and significance to the learning process (Pring, 2000). Nicolini (2012, p7) describe the research as a “performative perspective to offer a new vista on the social world”. Therefore, conceptual frameworks work as paradigms to analyse and interpret the knowledge (Mertens, 2005; Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006). Thus, it is described as a lengthy, complex, incomplete and non-inductive process (Clegg, 2012).

This section provides an outline of theoretical reflection pertinent to the implementation of the circular supply chain management framework. It serves the purpose of understanding Stakeholder Theory which guides the circular economy framework generation by recognizing and analysing its stakeholders’ views and introducing strategic guidelines to get competitive advantage. Stakeholder theory is adopted in this research considering its existing connection with corporate social responsibility and supply chain management concepts (Jamali, 2008; Chiappetta Jabbour et

al., 2020). It is one of the important but not commonly used theories in social environmental and sustainability management studies (Frynas and Yamahaki, 2013; Montiel and Delgado-Ceballos, 2014; Hörisch, 2014). Stakeholder theory encourages to manage the complicated and tempestuous environment of the organizations by providing effective, efficient, ethical, and realistic methods (Freeman, 1984; Freeman et al., 2007). Stakeholder theory has received management literature attention over time due to its nature of explanation, prediction and maintaining relationship of various functions of an organization (Donald and Preston, 1995; Rowley, 1997). Likewise, sustainability studies need collaboration among all participants which can encourage the adoption of such transitions throughout the supply chain (Shou et al., 2019; Tsend et al., 2019a, 2019b; Tsend et al., 2020). This theory is one of the most prominent structures used in the corporate sustainability studies (Montiel and Delgado-Ceballos, 2014) and can become a fundamental driving philosophy for each undertaking in the circular economy system (Gupta et al., 2018). Additionally, “stakeholder theory begins with the assumption that values are necessarily and explicitly a part of doing business. It also pushes managers to be clear about how they want to do the business, specifically what kinds of relationships they want and need to create with their stakeholders to deliver on their purpose” (Freeman et al., 2004, p364).

Stakeholder theory states that successful organizations focus on the management of pressure and demands from their stakeholders (Donaldson and Preston, 1995, Friedman and Miles, 2006; Mani and Gunasekaran, 2018). Stakeholder theory encourages to manage the complicated and tempestuous environment of the organizations by providing effective, efficient, ethical, and realistic methods (Freeman, 1984; Freeman et al., 2007). The theory is established on the belief that values are fundamental and a vital part of doing business (Freeman, 1994). It involves the value creation, trade, and effective business management (Freeman, 2010). To justify the theme of value creation, the theory demonstrates the ways firms can be described through stakeholder relationships and how to manage the relationship by sharing interests and facilitating competitive resources (Parmar et al, 2010).

Stakeholder theory is inherently a management theory (Donaldson and Preston, 1995) with the dominance of stakeholder value maximization. The theory attracts attention for articulating a shared sense of value creation. Its focus is on maintaining the stakeholder relationship to deliver

the purpose (Freeman et al., 2004). The components of this approach gained momentum with the time and were circulated more widely in the 20th century in various disciplines through various theories i.e., games theory, organizational theory, strategic planning by the studies of theory (Aoki, 1984; Mintzberg, 1983; Ansoff, 1965). Freeman (1984) mostly got credit for the development of this theory (Clarkson, 1994; Clarkson, 1995; Donaldson and Preston, 1995; Mitchell et al., 1997; Rowley, 1997; Key, 1999; Sautter and Leisen, 1999; Frooman, 2002; Schwager, 2004; Polonsky and Scott, 2005; Kolk and Pinkse, 2006) presenting theoretical and practical insights. Being the most significant part of this theory, it is important to discuss who stakeholders are.

“Stakeholders are groups who can affect and/or are affected by the achievement of an organization’s purpose” (Freeman, 1984).

A Stakeholder is group of individuals, organizations, or government who are interested in the actions of an organization (Mitchell et al., 1997). The key groups can be shareholders, employees, business partners, customers, the general public, managers or stockholders (Morris, 1997; Preston, 1990; Rowley, 1997). Stakeholding is related to management in a wider sense, as it is able to integrate descriptive, instrumental and normative theories which support managers to make the decisions. Hence, the approach is accepted in the processes of managerial decision making associated with stakeholders (Agle and Wood, 1997; Friedman and Miles, 2002; Frooman, 2002; Schwager, 2004; Damak-Ayadi, 2005; Reynolds et al., 2006; Tsai et al., 2006).

Figure: 1.1 Aspects of Stakeholders’ theory

Source: (Donaldson and Preston, 1995) Material redacted due to Copyright restrictions.

As explained above (Figure 3.1), stake holding becomes more descriptive when all its three elements – normative, instrumental, and descriptive – are viewed as interconnected. The model describes the ways of managing the relationship of stakeholders, the purpose of this relationship and the way this relationship is ethically sourced. The descriptive circle demonstrates organizations' relation with the outer world; it is related to identifying these stakeholders and the basis of their relationship. The descriptive element explains that an organization is a network of co-operative and competing interests (Marwick, 1999; Mason and Gray, 1999; Walker, 2000; Wisniewski and Stewart ,2004) and emphasizes recognizing their relationships rather than understanding the behaviour sustaining that relationship. This nature of descriptive approach led to criticism that the theory is very simple and is not practical (Sternberg, 1994; Argenti, 1997; Barry, 2002; Marcoux, 2003; Sundaram and Inkpen, 2004) because only the identification of stakeholders without reasonable explanation is not justifiable and weakens the theory (Jones and Wicks, 1999; Winn, 2001; Frooman, 2002).

However, from the view of Donaldson and Preston (1995), combining the descriptive process with the instrumental element is an efficient strategy. This assortment gives management a practical

perspective by understanding descriptive (identifying) and instrumental (organizing) stakeholders. As per the instrumental perspective, management of stakeholders in a certain way can improve or degrade organizations' performance (Rodgers and Gago, 2004). Through this approach stakeholders are seen within social science paradigm (Jones and Wicks, 1999). Regardless of its strategic importance view, literature still lacks the studies for an instrumental approach (Lewis et al., 2001; Winn, 2001; Smith and Fischbacher, 2005; Steurer, 2006; Shropshire and Hillman, 2007). The reason for this is the effect of stakeholders on financial performance.

The last and innermost part of Donaldson and Preston's (1995) model is, normative. This element includes moral and philosophical guidelines to manage organizations' stakeholders. According to this approach, stakeholders are the individuals who are interested in organizations' undertakings and have inherent values. Thus, this idea becomes an integral part of corporate social responsibility (Gioia, 1999; Jones and Wicks, 1999; Carroll and Buchholtz, 2003; Kaler, 2003). A number of theories enhanced the normative perspective of this theory. Based on Kantian philosophy, Freeman's (1984) stakeholders model advocates that the stakeholders seek to do the right things revolving around duty rather than emotions (Hummels, 1998; Hinman, 2004), which is emphasized by normative views. The normative perspective is related to the theory of property according to which organizations should not be involved in destructive activities (Donaldson and Preston, 1995). Similarly, Zsolnai (2006) proposed an extended stakeholder theory taking corporate social responsibility and competitive advantage in view, which is connected to the descriptive normative stakeholder model of Wheeler and Sillnapää (1998). Furthermore, some other theories related to stakeholder theory share the idea about trust and principles of common good, proposed by Jones (1995) and Argandoña (1998).

2.2.1 Stakeholder theory and circular supply chain management

Regeneration, restoration, and sustainable business activities are the key components of circular supply chain management. These components ensure the utilisation of available resources efficiently by blending the idea of value creation out of end-of-life products. As organisations have to operate in a harmonious environment involving the internal and external environment, it is vital to recognise these internal and external forces affecting their business operations. Thus,

modification in the fundamental approach of organisation's functions bring a positive change (Gupta et al., 2019). Circular supply chain management being a collective process cannot be implemented effectively in isolation. (Antikainen and Valkokari, 2016). As the results stakeholder's contribution is significant and can provide required framework for the successful implementation of this circular supply chain approach. It provides the structure for value creation based on the characteristics of stakeholder theory.

The axis of stakeholder theory is "relationship management" of various parties involved to fulfil a common goal. Circular supply chain management being based upon three major dimensions (economic, social, and environmental), this theory explains how value can be created for these dimensions by management of the relationship of complex supply chains involving the circular economy concept. The reason for many supply chains' success nowadays is relationship management. As circular supply chain management is still in its initial stage of development, it is important to drive insights from related concepts like sustainability, supply chain management and green supply chain management (Chen et al., 2009). Management of stakeholder relations is extensively studied in supply chain management (Simatupang and Sridharan, 2002). It brings the ideas of co-ordination, integration, competition, or collaboration to apply in supply chains for its efficient management (Flynn et al., 2010; Min et al., 2005). To reap the value of sustainability in supply chains, this approach demands taking into consideration the idea of collaborative efforts of stakeholders including consumers (Sarkis, 2003; Vachon and Klassen, 2006; Gupta et al., 2019). Thus, to maximise sustainability, the relationships of supply chain actors is fundamental.

To gain the benefit of three bottom lines of the circular economy (social, economic and environmental), stakeholder analysis is vital to prioritise the interest and difficulties of stakeholders, which provide the guidance to policy makers. No doubt it is difficult to measure the financial outcomes from this approach (Wood and Jones, 1995; Barnet, 2007; Pelozo, 2009) but it helps to enumerate the poor social performance which can occur from inefficient stakeholder management (Neville et al., 2011; Jia and Zhang, 2013; Wolf 2014). Moreover, from the social viewpoint it helps organisations to be prepared to fulfil the expectations and adversities coming from stakeholders (Jia and Zhang, 2013).

From the environmental side, the complexity of circular supply chains and lack of awareness about the circular economy approach can put a negative impact on the implementation. It is important to know the opinions of stakeholders about taking environmental initiatives, for example customers' willingness to spend on environmentally friendly products can pressurise the manufacturers or retailers to produce or sell the products, make strategies or policies according to their demand or otherwise and fulfil the need of value creation for all the involved parties. This becomes a tool for value creation and social acceptance of environmentally friendly initiatives by facilitating the need of required technologies, education, or strategies.

Finally, the economic element along with the environment initiatives are critical to present. Stakeholder assessment motivates and introduces the ways to reap the financial benefits along with the social and environmental advantages by providing guidelines. Economic benefit is the most important aspect for businesses which all the stakeholders are interested in as the result stakeholders' satisfactions on this aspect is the most significant for the success to circular transition which could be facilitated by stakeholder theory.

2.2.2 Stakeholder theory and circular supply chain management of the UK food industry

Referring to environment tensions in the early 1980s, Freeman, (1984) states that the existing strategic model is not able to solve the current difficulties and deliver solutions. Therefore, it is important to outline the theory which supports to overcome the complexities by providing the solution through collaboration of organizations and the individuals that relate to them and are called stakeholders. The theory gains attention by management scholars because of its nature of explanation, prediction and managing the relationships of diverse functions of an organization (Donald and Preston, 1995; Rowley, 1997). Likewise, sustainability studies need a collaboration among all participants which can encourage the adoption of such transitions throughout the supply chain (Shou et al., 2019; Tsend et al., 2019a, 2019b; Tsend et al., 2020). This descriptive process was widely replicated across various sectors and functions in the 1990s, but it created a degree of confusion, as to whether stakeholder management was arguably about a way to better manage the stakeholders (instrumental), or a way to treat stakeholders more ethically.

Stakeholder theory has been broadly accepted in supply chain context for expressing stakeholder influences on green purchasing (Maignan and McAlister, 2003), supply chain development and alignment matters (Matos and Hall, 2007), roles of different stakeholders within green supply chain practices (de Brito et al., 2008), reverse logistics (Sarkis et al., 2010), and for product design and business model (Franco, 2019). It is established in various studies that to get more environmentally pre-emptive results consideration of stakeholders is vital (Henriques and Sadorsky, 1999; Buysse and Verbeke, 2003; Sharma and Henriques, 2005; Murillo-Luna et al., 2008). Van Ejjik, (2015) highlights the need of a systematic approach by engaging all the stakeholders from the initial stage and motivating them to pour innovative ideas and solutions as a part an action plan to bring the circular economy in practice.

This study has taken stakeholder theory as a theoretical context by considering Freeman's (1984) view that "An organization will maintain relationships with several groups that affect or are affected by its decisions" and "Theory is interested in managerial decisions" (Donaldson and Preston, 1995). There is need to increase the inputs of various stakeholders' perceptions within the industry including consumers to incorporate and regulate the business strategies. Herewith, this study induces substantive theoretical prepositions extracted from the finding into the stakeholders' framework for applying the circular approach in the industry. The circular economy business model demands novel skills from the network of stakeholders due to its requirement of innovativeness. Thus, involvement of multiple stakeholders is crucial (Singh and Ordonez, 2016, Antikainen and Valkokari, 2016; Bocken et al., 2018; Unal et al., 2019). Gupta et al. (2018) give prominence to the prerequisite of communal action from the major stakeholders of the business cycle. Thus, reflecting the circular supply chain management studies from stakeholders' viewpoint is vital to acquire the necessary framework for this transition.

The theory has different propositions; descriptive, instrumental, and normative as discussed in previous section (3.3). As the descriptive viewpoint, the theory works on defining the specific characteristics and attitudes (Brenner and Cochran,1991), the attributes of each stakeholder and any different phase that a firm has reached during its lifecycle (Jawahar and Mclaughin, 2001) and societal information of any corporation (Ullmann, 1995; Culpin, 1998). This study works on

prospective broadening approach to identify and describe key stakeholders of circular food supply chain and their motivation. Hence, this research considers the descriptive perspective of this theory as an initial step in which stakeholders were identified. Stakeholder theory directed towards selection of participants of this study that how stakeholders are affected by the recognised barriers. It contributes to the knowledge, bringing a substantial change. The study began with recognising the circular viewpoint of the supply chain of food manufacturing industry. Figure 3.2 illustrates how an ideal circular supply chain should work (all stages are explained in detail in chapter 2). Unlike the linear flow, the circular supply chain begins from the supply of raw material, the products go through development, manufacturing, retailing and consumption stage and the wastage generated in the multiple forms from all the phases is upcycled or reused and further recycled. Logistics and reverse logistics are the medium to make the products reach all the necessary stages. Emerging this model assisted to ascertain all the key stakeholders which affects and are get affected by the activities in food supply chains decisions.

Figure 2.2: Circular Supply chain of food manufacturing

Source: Developed by author

Taking into account various stages of circular supply chain management outlined above (figure 3.2), the researcher identified its stakeholders. Figure 3.3 supported to reduce the complexity to demonstrate the individuals who are of interest and are interested in the food circular supply chain management of United Kingdom, based on the supply chain process. The stakeholders identified are product developers, manufacturers, processors, retailers, consumers, up-cyclers, recyclers, government workers (discarding some stakeholders has been explained in chapter 6). As per the

words of (Jones et al., 2002) “in order to perform well, managers need to pay attention to a wide array of stakeholders and (...) have obligations to stakeholders which include, but extend beyond, shareholders”. The instrumental aspect of stakeholder theory was introduced by Jones, (1995) brings the attention to manage stakeholders to achieve the business goals like profitability, sustainability, and growth. Stakeholder theory suggests the policy makers to design the organisational strategies cogitating on the interests of their stakeholders based on a claim from Freeman, (1984) that stakeholder demand has intrinsic value, and it is the responsibility of management or authorities to look after their legitimate claims. The reason for organisations to consider these groups is: 1) based on the normative approach managing the interest of linked groups, 2) based on instrumental approach recognising who contributes to and influences value of an organisation (Donaldson and Preston,1995). On the normative side of stakeholder theory both the ethical obligations and economic benefits are taken care of side by side (Donaldson and Preston, 1995). This study being descriptive in nature makes the explorations and brings the recommendations by managing the stakeholders, their connection and reinforcing the circular approach within. Considering these approaches can positively impact the profitability of a firm. Therefore, this study is based on all three aspects of stakeholder theory mentioned in Figure 3.1 and stakeholders’ definitions of Post et al., (2002) as following:

“Individuals and constituencies that contribute, either voluntarily or involuntarily, to its (the company’s) wealth creating capacity and activities, and who are therefore its potential beneficiaries and / or risk bearers.”

Figure 2.3: Stakeholders Map

Source: Developed by authors based on the circular supply chain process and supported by stakeholders' theory

2.3 ORIGIN AND EVALUTION OF CIRCULAR SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT

The traditional economic philosophy (take-make-dispose) is no longer able to balance the consumption of natural sources. This disparity is affecting industrial as well as global sustainability. This is also affecting the international supply chain, which is increasing the economic and environmental fear. The global issue of resource scarcity is leading us towards a circular supply chain (George et al., 2015; Goyal et al., 2016).

The circular supply chain management concept is a collection of various scientific, semi-scientific and emerging fields. The circular supply chain management is a combination of concepts circular economy and supply chain management. Where circular economy is a driving force and philosophical background of circular supply chain management (Ghisellini et al., 2016, Farooqe, 2019). The circular concept is loosely based on a fragmented collection of ideas derived from scientific fields including emerging fields and semi-scientific concepts. Which are significant to

discuss to explore the background and concept of circular supply chain model which is first objective of this study. The collection includes various schools of thoughts (Geissdoerfer, 2018) i.e. carrying capacity (Odum, 1953), industrial ecology (Frosch and Gallopoulos, 1989; Graedel, 1996; Lifset and Graedel, 2001), industrial ecosystem and industrial symbioses (Jelinski et al., 1992; Chertow and Ehrenfeld, 2012). The concepts related to the environment are cleaner production (Stevenson and Evans, 2004), eco-efficiency (Welford, 1998a; Hupples and Ishikawa, 2009; Haas et al., 2015), natural capitalism (Hawken et al., 2008) and the concept of zero emissions (Pauli, 2010). The topic was also discussed as a review on manufacturing systems' circular materials flows and developments to that end (Lieder and Rashid, 2016), product-service systems (Tukker, 2015), cradle-to-cradle design (Braungart and McDonough, 2002; McDonough and Braungart, 2003; Braungart et al., 2007), biomimicry (Benyus, 1997; Benyus, 2003), resilience of social-ecological systems (Folke, 2006; Crépin et al., 2012), the performance economy (Stahel, 2010; EMF, 2013; Stahel, 2016) It was discussed in management literature (Geissdoerfer, 2018; Ünal, 2019; Angelis et al., 2018; Angelis et al., 2021). The accretion of the circular economy with time has been discussed below.

The most common ecological concept related to sustainability is “carrying capacity”, which includes the sense of quality which sustainability does not (Syre, 2008). Carrying capacity was first proposed and discussed by Odum, an ecologist, in 1953, who described the saturation level of resources and environmental conditions related to public welfare. In 1968, Hardin introduced the finiteness and exploitation of natural resources by saying “a finite world can support only a finite population”. After a while, in the 1970s, the term industrial ecology came into existence. It shows the interrelation between the ecosystem of cities and productive processes by developing the mechanism of reusing waste in the terms of raw material (Erkman, 1997). In the 1980s, the foundation for environment management was proposed by the British Standard Institute, 7750 from the business point of view. This may be called the basis of sustainability which was presented in the report “Limit to Growth” published in 1972 by The Club of Rome. Frosch and Gallopoulos (1989) raised the demand for the industrial ecosystem to function as a biological ecosystem technology by using the new industrial model which would transform the traditional linear production system to a more integrated industrial ecosystem. They also suggested to use the effluents of industrial processes as raw material for further manufacturing processes and claimed

the necessity to adopt the circular process. Ayres (1989) consider the industrial metabolism approach like industrial ecosystems. The concept was further strengthened by the Brundtland Report (1987) through the sustainability movement and sustainability development. In 1990, Pearce and Turner relate the concept of the circular economy with four economic functions in their textbook “The circular economy”, considering environment as an amenity value provider, sink of residual flow, a resource base for economic activities as well as a life support system.

Andersen (2006) described the need of the circular economy with the help of the second thermodynamics law of physics. Similarly, circulation of human extracted matter and energy would be the requirement of new inputs in the economic system and will support in delaying the increasing entropy. The principle of the industrial ecosystem, introduced by Frosch and Gallopoulos (1989), further revisited by Benyus (1997) and Bhushan (2009), is known as biomimicry and biomimetics, which means “a design inspired by nature” (Pawlyn, 2011). Similar concepts are also found in the prolific work of William McDonough and Michael Braungart (Braungart et al., 2007; McDonough and Braungart, 1998, 2002, 2013; McDonough et al., 2003). Their work is most known to the public in the form of the circular economy.

The Club of Rome deemed the sustainability development model as the method for reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 70% and will grow the demand of labour by 4% (Stahel, 2017). The circular economy model is one of the most important tools to facilitate the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals by bringing more practicality to work as business is taken as the most important player in it. The circular economy concept was first treated by the Rio+20 summit (United Nations Conference, 2012), as “one of the important tools available for achieving sustainable development”. It is also indicated that the circular economy and green economy “contribute to eradicating poverty as well as sustained economic growth, enhancing social inclusion, improving human welfare and creating opportunities for employment and decent work for all, while maintaining the healthy functioning of the Earth’s ecosystems”.

Furthermore, Huamao and Fengqi (2013) say that the circular economy is an entirety with numerous surfaces. They emphasize to analyse the circular economy based on system theory with a macroscopic view. Later, the design aspect of product durability has also been discussed by Baker et al. (2014). The importance of the design paradigm of the circular economy was also

discussed implicitly by Fischer-Kowalski and Hüttler (1998). However, at that time they concluded that this model applies to only small range of products and processes (Fischer-Kowalski and Hüttler, 1998 p.120). In contrast to this, the view discussed by McDonough and Braungart (1998) is much wider. They developed the framework based on technical and biological loops where resources are kept for the long term without any quality and quantity loss. The current industrial economy is considered to be an open-ended system which is grinding down planet earth and causing immutable changes in life supporting activities of nature (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017). A closed and circular economic system is the best solution for today's scenario to maintain the capital stock of natural resources (Ghisellini et al., 2016; Turner and Pearce, 1990; Rizos et al., 2017).

Some scholars (Octave and Thomas, 2009; Han et al., 2016; Gómez et al., 2017) claim about potential interaction between industrial metabolism and the circular economy and propose some case studies related to metal recovery. The current supply chain (including production and consumption and disposing), as well as business models, need to be completely reorganised, to align with the changes that the circular economy model symbolises. With the emergence of technological and strategic tools in reverse logistics, urban mining can provide the best solution for e-waste management. Earlier approaches of the circular economy such as “closing the loop” or “cradle-to-cradle” were originated in the 1980s to combine biological concepts (Xavier, et al., 2019). McDonough and Braungart, (2013) proposed resource technical cycles by the 3Rs concept, in which “cradle to cradle” is related to a circular approach; the cradle to grave approach is related to a linear conception of the product lifecycle. McDonough and Braungart (2013) noted that there was a “downcycling” (i.e., lowering value) of some products and material instead of “upcycling” (i.e., increasing value) during recycling processes. In addition, they remarked that closing the loop is not a positive event when the reprocessed material or product is toxic.

Today, the circular economy is coalescence of putting all the above-mentioned concepts and numerous other important ideas like cradle-to-cradle, biomimicry, performance/sharing economy and industrial ecology, under the umbrella concept (Berndtsson, 2015). Stachel (2016) suggests that the circular economy should be considered as a framework which moves around a set of paradigms.

2.2.1 Biomimicry Paradigm

The term biomimicry was first introduced in 1962. However, it came into demand recently. It was first described by Janine Benyus in 1997 as “The conscious emulation of nature’s genius”. Biomimicry was later defined by Pawlyn (2011), saying that, “Mimicking the functional basis of biological forms, processes and systems to produce sustainability solutions”. It is a methodology of imitating the nature at all levels or by taking inspiration from them. It can be constructing the buildings with natural amenities such as ventilation or solar energy or constructing the water-repellent materials with leaves or bugs as a model (Benyus, 2002). It puts emphasis on adopting the designs and techniques going back many years which humans abandoned for modern methods that seem more efficient (McDonough and Braungart 2008 p. 83). Dicks (2015), in “The philosophy of biomimicry”, explains the three key principles mentioned by Benyus:

- **Nature as measure:** using ecological standards to measure and judge the sustainability of innovations and designs (Benyus, 1997).
- **Nature as mentor:** look at nature with the notion of what we can learn from her rather than what we can extract and gain from resources (Benyus, 1997).
- **Nature as a model:** studying natural systems to have as a model for forms, processes, systems and problem-solving strategies (Benyus, 1997).

2.2.2 Performance / Sharing Economy Paradigm

Walter Stahel (1976) worked to develop the closed-loop approach for production processes and outlined four main goals: product life extension, long life goods, re-conditioning, and waste prevention. This report highlights the idea of the “functional service economy” and insists on the importance of selling services rather products, that pave the way to a more resource efficient system. It also emphasises moving away from ownership models to an access on-demand model and a collaborative consumption model which focuses on the idea of more interaction between consumers, retailers, and manufacturers (EMAF 2013). Using this model enables the manufacturer to save material expense by using them back in the technical cycle (Braungart and McDonough, 2008 p. 111). This concept received the attention due to the issues of increasing scarcity of

resources, urbanisation, social and demographic alterations (Zilahy, 2016). The following three areas were identified in connection with the sharing economy:

- **Sociological approach:** This approach is based on changing the role of people and the more conscious and responsible consumer behaviour and the growing philanthropic mentality.
- **Economics approach:** This approach believes that the sharing economy puts a positive impact on innovation and give a rise to the competition.
- **Management approach:** This approach talks about the development of new business models and new kinds of entrepreneurship and the service provider method which can enhance traditional industries.

2.2.3 Cradle-to-cradle (C2C):

These theories are considered as the actual origin of principles of the circular economy (Braungart and McDonough, 2008). The cradle-to-cradle (C2C) concept is basically a subject of natural science in which human beings are studied at the same level of other living creatures and the concept makes it clear that misuse of material resources is not only perilous for human life but devastating for all future life (Braungart and McDonough, 2008 p. 3).

However, fundamentally environmental and sustainability approaches within the cradle-to-cradle (C2C) approach were criticized because of their vision on making the industry less immoral by reducing, avoiding, minimizing, sustaining, limiting, and halting and focussing on eco-efficiency rather than doing good things from scratch (Braungart and McDonough, 2008, p. 51). Similarly, Reduce, Reuse, Recycle and Regulate are not ideal and add a negative character to being environmentally friendly. No doubt reduction is significant, but it does not stop depletion or destruction. Reuse is only moral if not toxic or it does not release toxins. Equally, recycling is down-cycling in most cases as materials are not meant to be disassembled and will be of low quality after recycling which also increases the contamination of the biosphere. Consequently, efficiency can be worthwhile if used as a tool within a broad effective system that proposes positive outcomes on a variety of issues, not only economic ones (Braungart and McDonough, 2008, p. 65).

Whereas cradle-to-cradle focuses on eco-effectiveness, which means doing right things with the right material instead of minimising the bad from wrong things, it serves the idea of alternative design and production by promoting a positive programme to produce goods and services. This agenda focuses on industrial systems which target maintaining and increasing productivity as well as quality of materials throughout the subsequent lifecycles (Braungart et al., 2006).

This leads to the following basic principles of cradle-to-cradle and eco-effectiveness:

- **Waste equal food:** There are two types of materials on the planet as per the cradle-to-cradle theories: biological and technical. Biological materials are useful to the biosphere, while technical materials are useful for industrial processes, also known as the Technosphere (ibid p. 93). This principle says that original designs should be created in a way which leads the extracted material to be used as technical or biological nutrients at the end of their life (Ankrah et al., 2015). The aim of designing work must be to avoid any loss of material value of the product that could lead to regular material downcycling, particularly in the technical material cycle.

Figure:2.4 : The butterfly diagram for the circular economy

Source: Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2012

Material redacted due to Copyright restrictions.

- **Celebrate diversity:** The vision of the next principle of cradle-to-cradle approach is to appreciate the design which imitates the nourished as well as the complicated natural

ecosystem where various organisms work together for the betterment of the whole ecosystem. This can only be possible by encouraging bio, social and conceptual diversity (McDonough and Braungart, 2002). Diversity increases the flexibility of a system considering only efficiency would result in the rigid system since there will be limited alternatives if one object breaks down. Therefore, the focus should be on building the system that values and gives importance to all the different flows not to certain parts (Webster, 2013). Socio-cultural diversity can be gained by policies which maintain the equal interaction between the users of a facility and the natural environment. These policies should also promote the health and social wellbeing of workers through its appealing and multidimensional qualities. Similarly, highly adapted, and flexible designs are recommended for attaining conceptual and intellectual diversity (Barford and Ahmad, 2021)

- **Use solar income:** One of the most significant part of the circular economy is to use natural and renewable sources of energy (Preston, 2012). Thus, the third principle of cradle-to-cradle is concerned with using solar and gravitational income run by wind, geothermal, hydro- and bioenergy. Its objective is to design buildings as a source of energy production instead of energy consumption centres so these would be able to contribute to a net positive ecological footprint. Unlike traditional energy sources such as coal, nuclear or other fossil fuels which rely on baseload energy, renewable technologies provide intermediate-load energy (Ankrah et al., 2015)
- **The upcycle:** McDonough and Braungart (2013) carried on their work on cradle-to-cradle and came up with another concept, known as “upcycling”. This idea has a broad vision and is represented with real life design examples. Upcycling emphasizes eco-effectiveness and focuses on receiving only positive impacts rather than simply reducing negativity. This idea is also involved as an integral part of the circular economy (Ankrah et al., 2015).

2.3 DEFINING THE CIRCULAR SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT CONCEPT

The circular economy: Looking towards the foundation cradle-to-cradle concept of “eco-effectiveness” (Braungart et al., 2007; Braungart and McDonough, 2002; EMAF, 2013), the

industrial ecology concept (Graedel, 1996; Frosch and Gallopoulos, 1989) and industrial ecosystem (inter-system ecology) (Korhonen, 2001) have been the most significant. The circular economy is the combination of highly idealized visions such as eco-effectiveness, economic system and natural systems that aims to achieve 100% renewable energy by recycling each resource (Korhonen et al., 2018). So, Murray et al. (2015, p.1) defined the circular economy as:

“An economic model wherein planning, resourcing, procurement, production and reprocessing are designed and managed, as both process and output, to maximize ecosystem functioning and human well-being”.

The circular economy aims to provide the material flow model which is cyclic in nature (EMAF, 2012; EMAF, 2013; CIRAIG, 2015; EMAF et al., 2015) and opposite to the current energy and material flow model that runs a linear system (Frosch and Gallopoulos, 1989). In contrast to the conventional recycling system, the circular economy focuses on reusing, remanufacturing, refurbishment, repair, cascading and upgrading of material and resources. It also emphasizes on solar energy, biofuel, wind power and waste-derived energy utilization during the product value chain and cradle-to-cradle lifecycle (Mihelcic et al., 2003; Braungart et al., 2007; EMAF, 2013; Rashid et al., 2013). The circular economy is considered as a huge change in the way of economic development in human life and called “the first step of realizing knowledge-based economy”. It is the result of humans’ re-knowing behaviour, regarding the aimed regulations and finding new regulations under the negative environment condition and meticulous situation which is a result of traditional economy activities (Huamao, and Fengqi, 2007).

The circular economy substantially is a type of ecotype economy which is an extensive system of people, natural resources, science, and technology. Similarly, it is a whole process from extracting the raw material to production in the industry and then consuming or wasting the finished products (Huang, 2004). The circular economy provides an ecological mandate to support economic activities by balancing the load-support capacity of current society, by utilizing the resources efficiently, reusing and recycling them to the maximum level. Thinking about economic development, the circular economy employs matter and energy to the maximal level with the help of its characteristics like low depletion, low exhaust and maximum efficiency that consequently improve the standard and performance of economic activities (Huang, 2004). The circular

economy helps to achieve a harmonious relationship between the economic system and the natural ecological system and maintains the natural ecological balance.

The circular economy is also helpful for the society to eliminate poverty and bring sustainable economic growth and human welfare by creating opportunities for employment and work as well as maintaining positive functioning of earth's ecosystem. In April 2015, a report was submitted to the Club of Rome entitled "The circular economy and Benefits for Society", which aimed to describe the notable increase in resource efficiency and particularly evaluate the key benefits to society (Wijkman and Skånberg, 2015). The circular economy presented social benefits with various activities i.e., 50% reduction in carbon emissions, 50000 additional jobs and improved trade balance with 1% of GDP with high percentage of renewable energy, 28% reduction in carbon emissions, 20000 additional jobs and improved trade balance with 0.2% of GDP by enhancing energy efficiency and 10% reduction in carbon emissions by deploying the three-fold material efficiency scenario (Wijkman and Skånberg, 2015). The essence of the circular economy development is to gain the maximal advanced benefits with the minimal resource consumption and the lowest environmental prices, to reach unification among economic benefits, environmental benefits, and social benefits, and to realize the objective of sustainable development. It is a basic change to the tradition of "producing in a large scale, consuming in a large scale", and pioneers a harmonious economic development mode of human beings, society, and natural environment.

Furthermore, the circular economy is a dynamic multidisciplinary, demanding concept, chases economic growth from using resources and having social impact (Merli et al., 2018). In theory and practical terms, the circular economy is derived from environmental economics and industrial ecology with equal focus on technological innovation (Ghisellini et al., 2014; xw 2014). Therefore, the sustainable supply chain has been regarded as a vital part of the circular economy (Bocken et al., 2018; Geissdoerfer et al., 2018;) and new strategies (i.e., Product Service Systems) have been developed to facilitate this transition (Tukker, 2015).

The circular economy is operationalisation of businesses processes to apply the concept of sustainable development, which makes it the most popular and most discussed concept among scholars and practitioners (Ghisellini et al., 2016; Murray et al., 2017). It is based on a restorative and regenerative production and consumption system which targets to hold products and resources

at their highest utility and value for as long as possible within the technical and biological cycle (EMP, 2012, 2013, 2014). Schut et al., (2015, p.15), Geissdoerfer et al., (2017, p.759), and (Kirchherr et al., 2017) claims that the most prominent definition of the circular economy was given by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation in (2012) is:

“The circular economy is an industrial system that is restorative or regenerative by intention and design. It replaces the “end-of-life” concept with restoration, shifts towards the use of renewable energy, eliminates the use of toxic chemicals, which impair reuse, and aims for the elimination of waste through the superior design of materials, products, systems, and, within this, business models.”

The circular economy is a paradigm which focus on early phases of product design to determine the material cycle (Ünal et al., 2019). The circular economy is much more sustainable than the conventional linear economic system (make-use-dispose) as its design is based on restorative and regenerative design thinking (Stahel, 2016). It is a method in which output of one production process is converted into inputs for another with biological (natural decomposition) and technical (remanufacturing, refurbishing, and recycling) cycles and entirely stops the waste (EMF, 2013, 2014). It also provides multiple value creation methods which are decoupled from the consumption of finite resources (EMF, McKinsey and Company, and SUN 2015, 23). As per an estimate from EMF, transition could decrease the consumption of resources by 32% by 2030 and 53% by 2050 in the food, construction, and mobility sectors in Europe. That could lead to building up prosperity without dimension natural capital (Schulte, 2013; Gregson et al., 2015; Murray et al., 2017).

The circular economy and supply chain management: the supply chain management concept came into existence in the 1980s due to the expansion of global sourcing to explain the complexity of business-to-business and business-to-customer networks (Cooper and Ellram, 1993), which later started being associated with operation management, more specifically the performance-based control of material and information flow between collaborating organisations (Cooper, Lambert, and Pagh 1997; Hines et al., 2000; Defee and Stank 2005; Hult et al., 2007). The most widespread definition of supply chain management is provided by Christopher in 1999:

“The management of upstream and downstream relationships with suppliers and customers to deliver superior customer value at less cost to the supply chain as a whole”.

Christopher, (1999) puts emphasis on cost and illustrated the traditional way of supply chain, where the system is equipped with a linear way to thinking across input and outputs. Supply chain management focusses on multi-dimensional customer-supplier dyads, which begins from raw material extraction to production and then to the end customers (Harland, 1996). Conventional supply chains focus on high level of efficiency, capacity, and customer reaction (Hoek, 1999). Mentzer et al. (2001) explain supply chain management as a systematic and strategic co-ordination of the traditional business within an organization and across the businesses within the supply chain, which helps in improving the long-term performance of organizations and the entire supply chain.

Looking at the circular economy from the supply chain perspective, consider reverse, open, and closed supply chains. A reverse supply chain contains the functions of collection and recovery of the product in supply chain management. The closed-loop supply chain is designed, controlled, and operated to maximise the value creation over the lifecycle of a product. It ensures the dynamic recovery of value from various types and dimensions of return over the period of time (Guide and van Wassenhove, 2006). The closed-loop supply chain is an integration or network of forward and reverse supply chains. The primary function of product recovery and remanufacturing is carried out by the original product or service provider. Whereas, in the open-loop supply chain, used products are recovered or given to a third-party organization not to the original manufacturer (Gou et al., 2008).

The circular economy is the combination of open- and closed-loop supply chains. The motivation behind the circular economy is to recover the resources without thinking about the party carrying it out. Hislop and Hill (2011) say that the circular economy is a never-ending chain of “closed resources loops” in all economic activities along with the reconnection between the top of the chain and various activity nodes in between. The purpose of the circular economy is to encourage economic production systems which are associated with reusing and recycling systems while keeping a closed loop of materials and energy flows.

Circular Supply Chain Management: Interest and enthusiasm for the supply chain for the circular economy is growing exponentially (Ying and Li-jun, 2012; Aminoff and Kettunen, 2016; Liu et al., 2018; Govindan and Hasanagic, 2018; Bressanelli et al., 2018; Batista et al., 2018b, De Angelis et al., 2018; Batista et al., 2018a, Kazancoglu et al., 2018). The circular economy is an approach in which waste is taken as an opportunity for recycling or recovering the valuable material (Awasthi et al., 2018). There are several concepts introduced in literature linked to sustainability such as sustainable supply chains, green supply chains, environmental supply chain, closed-loop supply chains and occasionally used interchangeably (Gurtu et al., 2015) to present integration of sustainability concepts in supply chain management (Ahi and Searcy, 2015). Batista et al. (2018a) defined circular supply chain management as:

“The coordinated forward and reverse supply chains via purposeful business ecosystem integration for value creation from products/ services, by-products and useful waste flows through prolonged lifecycles that improve the economic, social and environmental sustainability of organizations.” (p. 446)

The more detailed definition constructed by Farooque et al. (2019) is “Circular supply chain management is the integration of circular thinking into the management of the supply chain and its surrounding industrial and natural ecosystems. It systematically restores technical materials and regenerates biological materials toward a zero-waste vision through system-wide innovation in business models and supply chain functions from product/service design to end-of-life and waste management, involving all stakeholders in a product/service lifecycle including parts/product manufacturers, service providers, consumers, and users” (p884).

The circular economy significantly enriches the narrative of supply chain sustainability by integrating restorative and regenerative design thinking. Environmental, ecological, corporate governance and social issues have been largely acknowledged by green, environmental, and sustainable practices (Batista et al., 2018a). Likewise, terms forward and reverse supply chain embrace the closed-loop supply chain (Govindan and Soleimani, 2017). Another important aspect differentiating the circular economy from existing sustainability thinking is its “zero-waste” vision (Veleva et al., 2017). Circular supply chains consider waste as a resource; therefore, they are designed to regenerate natural capital to the biosphere so that biological materials can be used

again and again indefinitely, via subsequent ecological cycles of plants and animals (Farooque et al., 2019).

Supply chain management's associations with sustainability owe much to the early interest in closed-loop reverse logistics, product recovery and remanufacturing literature (Thierry et al., 1995; Fleischmann et al., 1997; Jayaraman et al., 1999; Guide and Van Wassenhove, 2009; Loomba and Nakashima, 2012). Sustainable supply chain management is now recognised as a term in its own right (Carter and Rogers, 2008; Seuring and Müller, 2008) and includes a range of associated topics including environmental and social goals (Govindan et al., 2015), the need to understand value creation as opposed to damage limitation (Krikke et al., 2013) and the importance of strategic supplier partnerships in creating this value (Sarkis et al., 2011; Bell et al., 2013; Insanic and Gadde, 2014).

Carter and Roger's seminal sustainable supply chain management framework (2008) was arguably the first to demonstrate the relationship amongst environmental, social, and economic performance within a supply chain management context. Building on Elkington's (1998, 2004) concept of the triple bottom line, they suggest that at the intersection of all three factors, there are activities that organisations can engage which not only positively affect the natural environment and society, but which result in long-term benefits and competitive advantage for the firm (Carter and Rogers, 2008, 364). Calling for greater vertical integration between buyers and suppliers as a means of reducing uncertainty and resource dependency towards achieving long-term economic sustainability in a period of dwindling resources, the authors draw on multiple theories (e.g., Resource-based view, Transaction Cost Economics) and examples of closed-loop industrial activity.

2.4 THE ELEMENTS OF CIRCULAR SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT

This section explains all the stages of circular supply chain management through which a circular product has to go to get maximum sustainability.

2.4.1 Designing

Design can be defined as: “A deliberate business process involving hundreds of decisions with the intent of developing a tangible, physical product or developing an intangible service product” (Krishnan and Ulrich, 2001, p318)

In the circular supply chain management model, processes like resource forecasting and energy re-circulation highly depend on the design of the product (Carter, 2008; Laurenti et al., 2015; Clark et al., 2016). The designing process in the circular economy contains applications which demand “pre-cycling”, which means taking action in advance to enable the resources to remain as future resources in the economy or in nature. De los Rios and Charnley (2017) and Jensen and Remmen (2017) suggest that products should be designed to be suitable for multiple lifecycles and should keep appealing to potential consumers (Greyson, 2007). Increasing the durability, longevity and recyclability of the product are techniques of enhancing the circularity of products (Earley and Goldsworthy, 2015).

The better the design of the product is, the more durable, repairable, upgradable, re-manufacturable and easy it will be to recover the valuable materials from it (Nowakn et al., 2018). When creating the product or service in the circular supply chain, design needs to be fundamentally changed as it significantly affects the whole value chain (De los Rios and Charnley, 2017; Jensen and Remmen, 2017). Not only the product, but the sustainable packaging design and labelling are considered equally important aspects of strategy (Bovea et al., 2018a; Steenis et al., 2018). Literature suggests that corporate strategies should focus on product design to apply the circular economy at firm level (Bocken et al., 2014; den Hollander et al., 2017; Lieder and Rashid, 2016; Rashid et al., 2013; Urbinati et al., 2017). Therefore, Bocken et al. (2016) recommend classifying and designing the product according to the strategies for “slowing loops” and “closing loops”.

Slowing loops strategies focus on designing for longevity and ease of maintenance as well as repair, where designing for longevity emphasizes durable products that do not break down easily (Bocken et al 2016). These products are further categorised into two types: products designed for short lifetime and long lifetime. Short lifetime products are distributed in a limited area and reach on the high peak of the lifecycle. In contrast, longer lifetime products are distributed in a wider area and go through the lower peak of the lifecycle (Georgiadis et al., 2006; Briano et al., 2010) Consequently, lifetime distribution decides the shape of new product adoption flow and product

demand distribution. Designing for maintenance and repair strategy focuses on maintenance efforts that are required to keep the product in good condition (Mulder et al., 2012). It allows the safe, quick and easy replacement of its components and parts.

On the other hand, design strategies for closing loops brings attention to designing for disassembly / disassembly index and designing for technological cycle / recyclability index that are considered as a vital element for the circular economy transition (Andrews, 2015). As per these strategies, a product is designed in a way that can be easily disassembled brings numerous benefits during its lifecycle such as manufacturing efficiency, maintenance or servicing and recovery at the end of life by remanufacturing or recycling (Gu and Sosale, 1999; Vanegas et al., 2017). Similarly, a product designed with the technological cycle approach facilitates the technical components of a product to be used as high-quality raw material and looped back into industries. This approach rests on “the principle of the degree of recycled material used, by the number of materials used” and their mutual compatibility. Because it is based on the separation process so the less the material is used, the easier it will be to recycle (van Schaik and Reuter, 2007; Franco, 2017).

Food products designed for circularity facilitate organic or contaminant-free resources to be sent to the soil for using as organic fertiliser. Even before this happens, some food by-products provide additional value by creating new food products, fabrics, or sources for bioenergy. These cycles are helpful in regenerating the living system (soil), providing renewable resources, and supporting biodiversity.

2.4.2 Manufacturing

Manufacturing can be defined as:

“Transformation of materials into items of greater value by means of one or more processing and assembly operations” (Groover, 2020, p4).

Manufacturing is a process which converts raw material into a final product, used for some purpose. In the present era, increasing demand of product performance in turn requires a range of new material and new processes (Rao, 2013). The concern of resource efficiency has quadrupled the demand for materials in the last 50 years in manufacturing industries (Allwood et al., 2011).

So, the greater the materials and processes, the more chance of increasing waste. In the past two decades, there has been a great economic and technological advancement but loss of natural resources, over-consumption and loss to the environment are the result (Zhang et al., 2011). Consequently, to mitigate the environmental risk, manufacturing processes need sustainability or circular economy practices (Moktadir et al., 2018). Green manufacturing is widely known as a key strategy for manufacturing industries for sustainable development. Green manufacturing processes accumulate principles like environmental protection, convert energy into production, service activities, industrial waste reduction, non-hazardous practices, economically superior for community and employee energy and resource saving, pollution reduction while accomplishing the production economy (Zhou et al., 2012; Dwivedi et al, 2019). Social, environmental, and economical are known as the three bottom lines of sustainable manufacturing (Dwivedi et al, 2019).

Manufacturing in the circular economy is not limited to the manufacturing process but includes the whole supply chain, various product lifecycles and end of life considerations (Jensen and Remmen, 2017). Applying circularity at the manufacturing stage allows two significant requirements of achieving sustainability. Firstly, it prevents end-of-life products from being regarded as waste, and secondly, replaces the primary resources in the forward supply chain with the secondary resources extracted from end-of-life products (Geyer and Jackson,2004). Therefore, practising the circular economy during the manufacturing process focuses on two principles: 1) to reduce material inputs and 2) to reduce emissions. These principles together are known as cleaner production which is possible using cleaner technologies (Ridura et al., 2018). Applying cleaner technologies in manufacturing brings benefits of reducing emissions, less wastage and cost reduction by limiting the use of resources and by saving cost on waste (Montalvo and Kemp, 2008). Cleaner technologies refer to using novel technologies as well as equipment support and allow sustainable development. Equipment-support techniques here emphasise reusing its own emissions which fulfils the aim of green manufacturing processes (Shan et al., 2012). The essence of these approaches is to take a step towards closed-loop circulation within the production process which aims to reuse all kind of resources, waste, by-products, and emissions among all actors of production processes. Implementing the closed-loop application in the manufacturing process will eliminate the number of resources used and related emissions (Ridura et al., 2018).

2.4.3 Retailing

Retailing can be defined as:

“Process of selling goods and services to ultimate consumers, or those buying on behalf of such consumers, particularly when carried out through store outlets and, when further specified, mail order, etc.” (Baron et al., 1991, p. 163).

Retailing is ultimately the process of handing goods or services to the end users (Dunne and Lusch, 1999, p. 5). Retailing has a major part to play in economies (Tengström et al., 2015). Due to factors like changes in technology, demographics, retailing processes and competition it has become complex to deal with (Evans, 2011) and required ways to create the value for customers. One of the important factors to bring changes in current retailing practices is the need of sustainability (Widlitz, 2020; Vadakkepatt, 2021). In developing countries, 5% percent of total food wastage come from the retailing sector (Mirabella et al., 2014; Rajković et al., 2020). Retailers’ initiatives can benefit the supply chain from top to bottom and from bottom to top.

Retailers are influential actors for implementation of the circular economy because of their position in the supply chain (Ytterhus et al., 1999; Jones et al., 2005b; Grewal and Levy, 2007; Chkanikova and Mont, 2012). Circularity can be applied through retailers by joining upstream (suppliers, manufacturers, processors) and downstream (consumers, up-cyclers, and recyclers). The circular model in the supply chain of manufactures food industry can be achievable by the initiative from retailing companies because of their size, bargaining power, strategic placement, and intersection between supply chain actors (Ytterhus et al., 1999; Jones et al., 2005b). In manufactures present scenario, sustainability by retailers is understood beyond the environmental initiative. It is the important factor for them to gain competitive advantage by differentiating brand, improving brand equity, building customer loyalty, and attracting younger consumers (Mueller, 2018; Vadakkepatt, 2021). Retailers are involved to integrate sustainability-related values in retailer supply chains, for attracting the consumer base (Rakowski, 2018). Yet, due to the interdependencies of all players, the application of the circular model in the retailer supply chain is a challenging task (Hall, 2001; Johnson, 2004; Vadakkepatt et al., 2021).

2.4.4 Distribution

Distribution can be defined as:

“The storage and flows from the final production point through to the customer and end user” (Rushton et al., 2014, p4).

However, there is most widely used term in supply chain management which represents Material Management + distribution and is known as “Logistics”.

Logistics can be defined as:

“The management of all activities which facilitate movement and the coordination of supply and demand in the creation of time and place utility” (Heskett et al., 1973,p8).

In circular supply chain management, when products are produced and distributed in a sustainable manner, considering environmental and social factors, this is known as Green Logistics (Sbhi and Eglese, 2009). There are various elements of logistics where environmentally friendly strategies need to be considered i.e., raw material acquisition, inbound logistics, transformation, and outbound logistics. Raw material acquisition means to deal with all purchasing decisions which provide inputs for the organization (Wu and Dann, 1995). In green logistics, decisions start with demanding environmentally friendly raw material from suppliers (Heinritz, et al., 1991). Likewise, inbound logistics in the circular economy deals with choosing efficient mode of transportation, material handling and procurement which yield economic and environmental value. After inbound logistics, outbound logistics is a part which needs environmentally sound strategies i.e., few shipments, shorter movements, more direct routes, space utilization of finished products. The next phase that needs serious attention in distribution is marketing, as numerous marketing decisions, e.g., more accurate sales predictions and strategic planning products, affect the logistics process to reduce waste and emissions. Finally, after sales service activities, such as installation, repair, return, parts and supplies, are useful activities to decrease the wastage and efficient use of goods (Wu and Dann, 1995).

Besides the above logistic approaches, reverse logistics has been observed as most significant (Farooque et al., 2019). In this process, products are shipped or fragmented from the place of consumption for potential recycling, remanufacturing or disposal (Dowlatshahi, 2000). The

logistics can be defined as “the process of planning, implementing, and controlling the efficient, cost-effective, flow of raw materials, in process inventory, finished goods and related information from the point of consumption to the point of origin for the purpose of recapturing value or proper disposal” (Rogers and Tibben-Lembke,1999). Reverse logistics is a viable solution for sustainable development by saving 40 to 60 percent of manufacturing cost compared new products (Cohen, 1988; Wilder,1988; Toenmeier, 1992;), using less energy (Sturgess, 1992), reducing the environmental impact related to freight or logistics through exhaust and engine efficiencies, model shifts, increasing vehicle capacity and the filling ratio (Dente and Tavasszy, 2018).

2.4.5 Consumption

Consumption can be defined as:

“A set of social relationships, discourses, and practices that focus on the sale, acquisition, use and disposal commodities (Mansvelt, 2013, p1)”

Unsustainable production and consumption patterns are key factors in the deterioration of the environment along with economic activities like resource use and waste production (Calvo-Porrall and Levy-Mengin,2020). The circular economy transition is based on the act of distinguishing value creation from waste generation and resources used for completely transforming the production and consumption system (Camacho-Otero, 2018). As various aspects of circular supply chain management tend to achieve sustainable development, the consumption element is also regarded as sustainable consumption (Calvo-Porrall and Levy-Mengin, 2020). The idea of circular economy inspires the move towards a sustainable consumption model that stimulates the reuse of resources and discourages waste (EMF, 2013). Hence, the circular economy business model is thought to be the solution to resource scarcity and climate change challenges by decreasing the consumption of biological resources and expanding the is recycling system within the economy (Tunn et al., 2019).

Tunn et al. (2019, p325) define sustainable consumption as:

“Shaping and satisfying consumer needs to continuously reduce negative impacts of consumption on the environment and wider society.”

Existing literature emphasises understanding the sustainable consumption patterns in the economy and in society as well (Druckman and Jackson, 2010). Sustainable consumption involves satisfying consumer needs, however, by aiming to reduce the negative impacts triggered in material extraction, production, and consumption (Mount and Plepys, 2008, Cooper, 2013). Bocken, (2017) urges industries to realize the need for changing manufacturing processes and consumption patterns by satisfying consumer needs in a sustainable way and through sustainable models. Studies also highlight the need to examine the link between consumption and sustainable development and the way other stakeholders affect this relationship. The idea of sustainable consumption originated from the political interest in investigating the effects of consumption patterns on the environment which arose with the boom in global consumption and inequalities, and which widened between extravagant consumption and the situation for the poor during the 1990s (Ropke, 2004; Reisch, 2015). However, academic literature concentrates only on consumer choice and behaviour but discussion about the sensitive issues like society inequalities is missing (Ropke, 2004).

Initially, this topic was limited to the consumer and environmental issues but later considered consumer behaviour and economic psychology by a group of researchers, ecological economists, consultancies, and other suppliers who also contributed their input during the late 1990s i.e., Lucia John Thøgersen (1995), Folke Olander (1995), Suzanne Beckmann (1998), and Reisch (1998). Thereafter, with the growing interest in the circular economy, the interest translated into exploring meaning, description, various challenges, drivers, and dynamics of circular consumption (Farooq et al., 2019). Dubuisson-Quellier (2013) adds that “sustainable consumption has become one of the most dynamic fields in the social sciences and best alternative of social action” (Evans, 2019).

Various business models and strategies have been proposed by researchers for green consumption. Product-service-system was among the new streams which focus on dematerialisation and product-to-service-based consumption (Mont, 2002). Furthermore, McDonald et al. (2012) identified three groups’ translators, executors, and selectors for greening the consumer’s lifestyle. They concluded that there are multiple ways to become a green consumer. Translators are keen to change but are not interested in information. Selectors will choose only some aspect to focus on and will ignore others. Executors are the best group to implement green design, however, consumerism is not acceptable for them. Furthermore, the studies have been performed on an industry level as well

such as in the mobile phone market, the food industry, the automobile industry and factors like awareness, consumer perception, sustainability education, cost and quality of remanufactured products came out as the drivers to stimulate the circular economy. Another factor found by Borello et al. (2017), which gives dramatic contribution to increase waste, is consumer behaviour. In developed nations, where resources are easily available and affordable, people do not value them and waste even the edible food.

2.4.6 Upcycling

Upcycling can be defined as:

“The creation or modification of a product from used materials, components and products which is of equal or higher quality or value than the compositional elements” (Sung, 2017, p397).

Traditionally upcycling has been a part of human life, as repurposing or repairing of products, which seems disappearing during 19th century when one-time-use and using products up to limited utility became popular (Fromm, 1976). However, in the last few years with growing concern for the environment, specifically for resource scarcity, the term is being revived (Farrant et al., 2010). Like other elements of circular supply chain management, upcycling or reverse logistics is also a benefactor in achieving sustainable development by increasing material efficiency, eliminating waste, reducing energy consumption and by generating employment opportunities (Sung et al., 2020). It is reflected as one of the best methods to tackle waste throughout the supply chain (Geissdoerfer, 2018). This process is a contrast with recycling (the next stage of circular supply chain management), where the value of the original product is at least partially lost. This strategy is a combination of circular material flow with slower throughput of products and materials as well as slower consumption cycle (Singh et al., 2019).

Upcycling or reverse logistics process begins when the end user thinks that the product, they have bought has reached to the end of its life so needs to be disposed of, specifically food products due to their perishable nature (Ngadiman, 2016). There are three main processes included in upcycling: collecting, sorting, and processing, where collecting is linked with getting the discarded products back from consumer. Then, in sorting, products are inspected and categorized according to their quality and type and, finally, processing is done in various ways i.e., repair, reuse, or redesigning

(Paras and Curteza, 2018). Upcycling in the food industry was regarded as a challenging process because of its delicate nature (Vijayan, 2014). Whereas organizations like Upcycled Food Association (UFA) have successfully started working on transforming the food system through research networking and policy advocacy. They define upcycled food as, “Use ingredients that otherwise would not have gone to human consumption, are procured and produced using verifiable supply chains, and have a positive impact on the environment” (UFA, 2019). Upcycling in food industry is influenced by various factors i.e., consumers’ perception about upcycled food, age and generation and lifestyle (Wainaina et al., 2020).

2.4.7 Recycling

Recycling can be defined as:

“Reprocessing of recovered materials at the end of product life, returning them into the supply chain” (Worrel and Reuter, 2014, p10).

Recycling is basically a recovery function in which waste materials are reprocessed into products, materials or components that can be for original or for other purposes (European Parliament and the Council of European Union, 2008). Material recycling is a vital operation which has not only environmentally friendly properties but also supports the economy and society (Main and Rem, 2015). Undoubtedly, recycling is a waste management strategy, however, it can be used for implementing industrial ecology. It yields improved eco-efficiency by decreasing energy and material usage (Hopewel et al., 2009). An efficient recycling process needs shared efforts from design, manufacturing, end-of-life management and novel technologies for composite material separation or the recycling process (Yang, 2012). A high-quality level of recycling can be attained by recovering non-contaminated material to use as raw material in the production system for similar quality products (Kalmykova, 2018; Zimon et al., 2019).

Recycling facilitates circular supply chain management at all the stages of the production-consumption cycle by recycling waste material throughout various eco-systems to extract new products (Pinjing et al., 2013; Sauvé et al., 2016; Stahel, 2016). It is also vital to assess the working process of recycling loops to understand and develop recycling (Takata, 2012). The renovation process, particularly recycling, can be unsafe, instigating loss or cross-contamination or can be

expensive compared to raw material used in linear manufacturing processes (Geng and Doberstein, 2008; Xue et al., 2010; Mathiyazhagan et al., 2013; Govindan et al., 2014; Shahbazi et al., 2016; Baxter et al., 2017; Despeisse et al., 2017; Franco, 2017; Bouzon et al, 2018; Williams, and Dallison, 2018). Yang (2012) presented a multi-stakeholder analysis that provided technical solutions for food waste management in which recycling is provided as a final solution like feeding animals, creating energy and, finally, compost.

2.5 BARRIERS AND DRIVERS IN CIRCULAR SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT

In previous section, all stages of circular supply chain management have been systematically discussed with the possible strategies of a successful implementation, which advance towards the aim of zero waste generation during all stages. Bringing forward the theme of study, section 2.5 gives a detailed overview of barriers and drivers in circular supply chain management and in section 2.7 the conceptual framework on the basis of stakeholder analysis and circular supply chain management barriers has been developed.

Circular supply chain management is a positive approach to enrich the circular flow of products, by-products and waste caused by the practices and the supply chains of upcycling, recycling, reusing, remanufacturing etc (EMAF, 2014). This is helpful for industries and the economy in terms of saving resources, finance and generating employment opportunities. Despite these benefits, below discussed barriers hinder the promotion of green practices. At the same times, literature discusses similar elements that can work as driving forces. A number of studies have identified drivers (Bressanelli et al., 2018a; Govindan and Hasanagic, 2018; Huybrechts et al., 2018; Mangla et al., 2018; Ranta et al., 2018) and barriers (Govindan and Hasanagic, 2018; Mangla et al., 2018; Masi et al., 2018; Milios et al., 2018; Ranta et al., 2018) to CSCM development and implementation. However, it is noteworthy that drivers and barriers significantly vary by geographic and industrial context. This needs to be further explored for a widespread implementation of circular supply chain management across the globe.

2.5.1 Technical barriers and drivers

To increase the productivity, resource efficiency and to reduce the waste, digitalization of processes and implementation of practices with smarter equipment are the critical success factors

(Tortorella and Fettermann, 2018; Mastos, 2021). “Manufacturing companies need to speed up in shifting the focus towards sustainability and make use of technology like ‘Internet of Things’ (IoT) to meet the organization’s goal” (Manavalana nd Jayakrishna, 2019, p25). In the study by De Jesus and Mendonca (2018) technical factors are considered harder barriers and are most discussed in the circular economy studies. Technical barriers result from restoring and regenerating the circular economy philosophies into supply chain systems (Farooque et al., 2019). De Jesus and Mendonça (2018) consider them as one of the major blockers in circular supply chain management. Production tools and technologies chosen for designing the products for the circular economy decides the waste they will release, energy they will expend and capacity of reutilizing the components during subsequent manufacturing (France, 2019). Insufficient development use and guidance of tools and techniques for designing circular products are given in the literature. It refers to designing products for the circular economy, disassembly, adaptability, information tools and circularity matrices (Hart et al., 2019).

Lack of specific technologies for the circular economy

To create a business model for the circular economy, absence of sharing waste information and technologies is a major barrier (Suocheng et al., 2007; Radamaekers et al., 2011). For better management of the circular supply chain, information and technologies are required to establish a better link between machines, production orders and to monitor the flow of resources (Tura et al., 2018). Overpowering the technical barriers will bring new business prospects in the circular economy (Preston, 2012). Technological barriers have to be tackled in industries before the transition of the circular economy (Borrello et al., 2015). While highlighting technological barriers in developing countries, Mangla et al. (2019) articulate that implementation of circular economy practices need highly developed technologies and updated equipment which are not available. Despite ineradicable ecological and competitive gains, policymakers find difficulties in implementing and promoting cleaner technologies (Montalvo and Kemp, 2008). One of the significant principles of the circular economy is to keep products at the highest value (EMF, 2013a) and enable this value to reach at the highest possible rate, technical challenges need to be overcome (Geng and Doberstein, 2008; Adam et al., 2017). Maintaining the standard of the specifications of recycled material and reused structures is obligatory and is neglected in manufacturing industries (Luscuere, 2016; Hopkinsons, 2018; Campbell, 2018; Hart et al., 2019). Durability, efficiency,

and quality are the vital abilities of reused or remanufactured products which can be attained by optimal technologies and in-depth knowledge.

Hart et al. (2019) relates the technical barriers to the sectoral group. This group discusses the aspects which are vital to construct an environment then combine technical hindrances with the designing stage. Design of the product should contain features like ability to circulate, easy disassembly, adaptability, associated tools that are not sufficiently developed in industries. Similarly, the research performed by Sandström and Ritzén, (2017) also established that quality products must be designed and circulated in a more technical way for the better management of redesigned products. Adam et al. (2017) and Hopkinson (2018) discussed challenges of circular application in the construction industry and concluded that waste management in this industry is a manual process which is more time consuming and less feasible so smarter technologies and business models can be key supporters for the circular economy. Understanding the methods of construction of products is vital to increase the circularity of products. Data security and privacy must also be taken care of while using the products for the circular economy by ensuring data clear activities (Despeisse et al., 2017; Saidani et al., 2018; Whalen et al., 2018).

Lack of Knowledge, Skills and Expertise

Inadequate information, knowledge (Bechtel et al., 2013; Shahbazi et al., 2016) and technology methods compatible to the circular economy encumber the integration of supply chain management. Existing literature (Preston, 2012; Vanner et al., 2014; Shahbazi et al., 2016 and Pheifer, 2017) has highlighted the requirement of significant state-of-the-art in circular supply chain management, with 35% of studies raising concern about it. However, this demand has not yet been accomplished (Wooi and Zailani, 2010; Kirchherr et al., 2017). Today, firms require technical expertise which could assist to identify, assess, and implement superior technologies for the circular economy (Trianni and Cango, 2012; Rizos et al., 2016). Tura et al. (2018) accentuate that there is lack of knowledge about transmuting companies' current methods of product manufacturing into using recyclable materials.

The comprehensive range of technology used in developing the circular model makes a huge contribution to its success (Borello, 2016; Jesus and Mendonca, 2017). The technical capability is

a fundamental requirement of organizations for circular transition to ensure durability, efficiency, quality, and maintenance (Jesus and Mendonca, 2017). Technical resolutions are important for bringing circularity in food manufacturing to use virgin raw material which does not have a negative impact on the environment. Due to the nature of the circular economy, which links it with the thermodynamics, resource degradation is expected but using higher entropy waste resources in place of lower entropy virgin material can be a better solution for bringing a circular approach and to attain sustainability. Material recovery should also be more technically empowered to identify its reusability and recyclability capacities (Jesus and Mendonca, 2017; Adams, 2017). Data collection is another significant lever to make systematic decisions related to the supply chain. Therefore, smart, multifunctional, and adaptive data collection methods and models will be needed to make optimum use of big data so that instantaneous decisions can be made (Zhong et al., 2015; Balaji and Arshinder, 2016); high-tech technologies can be beneficial to attain that integrity in the system (Zhong et al., 2016). A collaborative model for ease of interaction and communication between manufacturers, retailers and customers is recommended (Mangla et al., 2018).

2.5.2 Financial and economic barriers and drivers

Financial risk in circular business model is much higher than linear model due to the complexities involved in remanufacturing and refurbishing in it (Linder and Williander (2017). Financial barriers are substantial factors (Farooque et al., 2019) and commonly discussed barriers by academics. Farooq et al. (2019), who characterized all eight barriers found in their study under various management theories as per their characteristics, have put financial barriers under the Resource based View (RBV) perspective, which deals with organizations' inability to match the strategic resources needed. While adopting a broad viewpoint, Bresanelli et al. (2018) considered the circular economy as a "Servicised Business Model", a model where organizations prioritize selling the service over product. 24 challenges were identified to redesign the circular framework in organisations categorised in different categories according to their nature. Exploring the facts, three major obstacles have been recognized under the "economic and financial viability challenges" label. While dividing all the barriers as hard and soft, Jesus and Mendonça (2017) put financial barriers in the hard barriers category which can be in the form of large capital

requirements, significant transaction costs, high initial costs, asymmetric information, uncertain return, and profit. Kirchher et al. (2018) classified these barriers as market-related and recognised them as the second most alarming factors for policymakers. Whereas Jesus and Mendonça (2018) mentioned these barriers as the second least mentioned barriers.

High cost of products and raw material

From the suppliers' side, companies have to pay the high cost of virgin raw material which supports long-life and re-manufacturability of products, and they have less financial support from government (Geng et al., 2008; Su et al., 2013; Sauvé et al., 2015; Mangla et al, 2018). The time gap between cost and revenue flow should be taken care, while moving towards service selling business model (Barquet et al., 2013). It puts a question mark on the economic and financial viability of circular economy projects. In the product lifecycle, this challenge is faced by the production, retailing and utilization stages. Similarly, manufacturers, distributors and service providers are affected by these challenges. Secondly, in the Serviced Business Model, operational and financial risk start belonging to the distributor rather than the customers (Baines and Lightfoot, 2013). As a result, it puts more financial pressure on the providers, especially when customers suspend contracts before the due time and providers have to bear the operational cost for the solution provided (Bresanelli et al., 2018). Despite being an integral part of businesses, financial innovation has been a neglected area in innovation studies (Martin, 2016). Relatedly for customers, renewable energy is a far more expensive option which leads them to prioritize “brown” supply chains and environmentally harmful activities continue to be carried out. The circular economy initiative promises benefits and growth in the long run but in the short-term organisations have to bear high costs in terms of retooling, repositioning factories, altering the logistic arrangements, training and development of staff. Similarly, maintaining the quality of service and remanufactured material is an additional cost of businesses (Preston, 2012; Liu and Bai, 2014; Eijk 2015; Torstensson, 2016; Jaeger and Upadhyay, 2019)

Investments

Financial investment is an initial step to facilitate the transformation from the linear to the circular economy and it can be expensive to implement (Geng et al., 2009; Smol et al., 2015; Pan et al., 2015; Govindan and Hasanagic, 2018). Govindan and Hasanagic (2018) classified these barriers

under economic issues which affects the circular economy framework internally and externally. Internally, organizations' perspective they must bear high upfront costs (Tura et al., 2018). On the other hand, Hart et al. (2019) relate financial barriers to the market rather than fiscal issues for implementing the circular economy in the construction industry, where it can possibly be in the form of raw materials, property ownership and capital investments from which capital investments are prioritized and rapid returns are expected. This trend predominantly neglects social or environmental projects like the circular economy. Discussing economic barriers, Tura et al. (2018) also emphasize that starting up a business in the waste management industry can be a huge economic risk. Moreover, moving towards the circular economy is a drastic change for an organization involving all stakeholders, their activities and relationships which needs extensive time and investment. All the stakeholders expect less cost and more return on investment. In the circular economy, it seems bit uncertain what the revenue flow will be like and what will be the strategies to generate it (Ritzen and Sandstrom, 2017). Currently, investors are unsure about the outcomes of this transition which prevents them to invest in new technologies and business models.

Profitability

Environmental strategies have fewer financial gains (Lieder and Rashid, 2016) and have high production costs (Palm et al., 2016; Shahbazi et al., 2016). Investment in raw material and new technologies can be unprofitable which is the one of the main objectives of any business (Tura et al., 2018). Finance and investment are obstacles for developing and poorer countries. Where developing countries are reluctant to invest due to unpredictable return on green technology, for poorer nations upfront cost and payback period are an even greater problem to consider (Li et al., 2015).

Another factor recognized by scholars is financial and business management support. Green financial innovation is a novel method for overcoming financial difficulties. Industries should also dissociate the financial flow towards material input and must concentrate on performance of resources (Jesus and Mendonça, 2019). Facilitating business start-ups by issuing business-grants, crowdfunding, loans or providing equipment will be advantageous for the business tycoons who want to adopt circular approach (Sung et al., 2017; Bressanelli, 2018).

2.5.3 Planning and management barriers and drivers

Inefficient management of operational strategy, product design strategy, business model design and policies pose problem for circular opportunities (Bonsu,2020). Unclear business model and design strategies make it difficult for the industries to implement circular business model (Bocken et al., 2016; Mendoza et al., 2017). Management-related challenges are those obstacles in which there is a lack of planning, management of resources and procedures. Numerous barriers of this kind are recognized related to this category in literature.

Lack of management commitment

Mangla et al. (2018) and Farooqe et al. (2019) highlighted the need of upper and lower-level management co-ordination and support, resistance to change, as well as all stakeholders' involvement in organizations to accept the circular model in supply chain management. Ecological improvements and transformation need a committed and dedicated managerial approach to attain sustainability in practices which is lacking in real life scenarios (Giunipero et al., 2012; Zhu and Geng, 2013; Lieder and Rashid, 2016). Effective and efficient planning for the management of natural resources and their unprejudiced distribution is a challenge for organizations (Geng and Doberstein, 2008; Pan et al., 2015; Miemczyk et al., 2016). Circular supply chain management practices aim to design scenarios that ensure the optimum utility of resources (through reuse, repair, recycle and remanufacture). Inappropriate planning and management in all these processes may mislead practices (Geng and Deberstein, 2008; Nasir et al., 2017).

Inappropriate marketing strategies

Marketing management is also a matter for circular supply chain stakeholders to examine as there can be the chance of cannibalisation of a company's existing products by circular ones and this can affect future revenue and sales of the company (Krikke, 2011; Linder and Williander, 2017; Steeneck and Sarin, 2018). Hence, companies are reluctant to market circular economy related products because it will possibly hamper sales of new products (van Loon and Van Wassenhove, 2017). Additionally, the idea of long run products will also lose popularity in the market because of less product substitution rate and loss of future sales (Lewandowski, 2016; Linder and

Williander, 2017). Similarly, advertising to make customers aware of circular products is also a challenge for organizations.

Competition

Increased competition across the globe has reduced profit margins and led to companies being interested in reducing costs through recovery of used products. Current economic, regulatory, and environmental trend pushing the businesses to remain in competition. Managing the competition for environmental benefits needs an efficient strategic planning (Shankar, 2005). But the adverse trend comes when businesses have to bear the potential costs to stay in environmental-related competition (Wycherley, 1999). Supply chains are also becoming more complex due to competition (Majta, 2012; Sheffi, 2018). Increase in global resource consumption is an alarming situation and needs competitiveness for environmental initiatives (Jaeger and Upadhyay, 2019).

Tura et al. (2019) describe competitive pressure as more focussed to gain economic rather than environmental benefits. And businesses do not see economic advantages to adopt the circular economy and results to ignore this approach. The circular economy becomes less prioritized among government and industries at the expense of economic growth. Moreover, for manufacturers, the competition to access critical resources is also a backward step for implementing the circular economy transitions (European Commission, 2014b). As a result, competition leads to less co-operation among the supply chain stakeholders (Grafstrom and Asma, 2021). Rizos et al. (2018) also emphasise the need to raise awareness about the economic competitive advantage.

Encouraging research on the circular supply chain can also work as a key factor for circular economy approaches. Manufacturing firms should allocate funds to research and development (Mangla et al., 2018). Businesses should launch market-based initiatives that could encourage investors to invest in green products. Developing innovative designs will be a foundation to attain sustainability, reduce carbon footprints and create an environmentally friendly business model (Nasit et al., 2017). Therefore, management should emphasise on arranging novel training facilities, apprenticeship schemes and degree programmes to get expertise in circular manufacturing operations (Lacy and Rutqvist, 2015). Due to the complex nature of circularity of

products and its flows, developing new skill sets and competency is also a lever suggested by researchers (Lewandowski, 2016).

2.5.4 Socio-cultural barriers

This is one of the most significant subject areas that can be contested by social scientists in environmental studies. It motivates to change attitudes and lifestyles (Redclift and Benton, 1994). Lack of interest, knowledge and engagement during the supply chain is the crux of the problem and an imperative barrier in the implementation of the circular economy. Without developing the interest and participation of customers and all other stakeholders in circularity, progress will be slow (Geng et al., 2009; Hart et al., 2019).

Lack of awareness and right information

Research done by Adams et al. (2017) articulates that the term the circular economy is often confused with terms reuse and recycling, which prevent employees from understanding what the circular economy actually demands. So, there is a need for precise awareness and commitment from top to bottom management (Borello et al., 2015; Lakatos et al., 2016). It is one of the most discussed barriers in the existing literature. The social awareness of the customer, being a significant and integral part of the supply chain, is a crucial aspect for the success of the circular model. Raising awareness requires alteration in people's behaviour (Lieder and Rashid, 2016). Behavioural challenges are also discussed in the upcoming sections of socio-cultural barriers in existing studies.

Organisation culture

Organization culture has an important role to promote the circular approach. "Disposing is cheaper than using or re-using" this employee attitude is one the biggest barriers to reducing food waste, especially in western countries (FAO, 2011). Therefore, organizations hardly pay attention to investing in new business models and technologies to bring circularity. Resistance to change the traditional mindset and structure of linear supplies has been seen as a hindrance to bringing sustainability (Borello et al., 2015). Companies are hesitant to accept environmental ventures like corporate social responsibility because of their hesitant culture. Thus, the circular economy is a

topic of limited discussion among professionals in organisations (Kirchherr et al., 2018). Reasons for this behaviour were discussed by Friedman (1970) and Christensen (1997) as lack of interest and awareness among consumers which affects firms' decisions and has been discussed in other sections of this category of barriers. In the studies by Singh et al. (2017, p.427) and Kirchherr et al. (2018) it was revealed that the circular economy is becoming accepted by policymakers but not at the other levels of organisations because they do not consider it as challenge. It was also depicted that; however, some companies do accept the circular models at their level, but it is unsure whether it will be embraced by the whole supply chain (Witjes and Lozano, 2016; Dijksma and Kamp, 2016).

Perception, attitude, and behaviour

Changing social behaviour, attitudes and the mindset of people is another major challenge discussed by circular supply chain studies. People are concerned about performance, product life, health, and safety regarding remanufactured products, which make them unwilling to spend on circular initiatives (Lieder and Rashid, 2016). A study conducted by Liu and Bai (2014) revealed that even though there is required awareness about the circular economy in China, people's actual behaviour still varies when it comes to practicality. In addition to those societal dynamics are also affected by the way of policies are implemented in societies, i.e., in China the circular economy is a top-down policy whereas in Europe it is adopted by business as a bottom-up approach (Ghisellini et al., 2014). While reviewing upcycling initiatives specific to the food industry, Zhang et al. (2020) state that studying consumer perception about upcycled food is necessary to promote the products. Consumer perception is highly dependent on people's buying intentions as well as the quality of the products (Saba and Messina, 2003; Williamson, 2007; Barber et al., 2010). Hawkins et al. (2012), Borra et al. (2014) and Kumar and Polonsky (2017) highlight that it is a disturbing situation for businesses who are interested in the circular model because consumers' behaviour is the most difficult part to mould. Thus, struggles to convince consumers to accept the circular model further affects the whole supply chain because of its interdependency.

Customers' involvement in circularity initiatives is crucial (Unal et al., 2019). Geng et al. (2010), Borello et al. (2016) and Borello et al. (2017) raised concerns about public interest and awareness in consumers as well as in businesses. Changing consumer insight is the pivotal effort upcycling

businesspersons need; people must be educated to raise understanding about the value of circularity of products and its environmental benefits (Sung et al., 2017). Talking about food supply chain management, Genovese et al. (2015) bring attention to recognizing, understanding, and implementing product-level impacts by identifying emission profile activities, their reduction opportunities and by associating suppliers into the supply chain. As all the aspects of supply chain are interconnected, so creating the green environment can also be equally effective. It can be done by pursuing green industry culture, green consumption, and green technology innovation (Li et al., 2015; Faraud, 2016). Food take-back campaigns and promotional activities using social media, internet, TV, radio, newsletters, exhibitions, conferences, and workshops should be galvanized around the circular economy and economic benefits like discounts should also be considered (Borello et al., 2016). To sustain it for the long term, the circular economy should be adopted from school education (Genovese et al., 2015; Adam, 2017).

2.5.5 Structural barriers and drivers

An efficient supply chain management requires an association of various actors involved in it (Kazancoglu, 2020). The difficulty occurs in circular model when some companies deny adopting it while continuing ongoing linear practices (Narimissa et al., 2020). Less integrity in various levels, departments of organization and views of various departments and stakeholders lead to the failure of this change (Ritzen and Sandstrom, 2017). This is also known as “silo mentality” and is concerned with all areas of the organization working together and with transparency towards a mutual goal (Ritzen and Sandstrom, 2017; Hart et al., 2019). There are studies understanding the prominence of vertical collaboration of the circular economy participants, though lack of horizontal collaboration should also be overcome (Pomponi and Mocanter, 2018).

Complexity in nature

The circular economy system thought to be of complex nature in the industries where product lifecycles are long and there are less chances to have ownership and control for such long time (Zimmann, 2016; Adams et al., 2017). There is less responsibility and accountability between the actors i.e., product manufacturing, supply chain or administration related to certification (Rizon et al., 2016). The circular economy model works on a broad scale potentially involving all the key

stakeholders. It makes the processes more intricate to handle (Huamao and Fengqi, 2013). Complexity in circular model caused because of the verity of processes from different nature of industries join together in one chain. The relationship between the stakeholders and process should be managed wisely for the success of circular transition. Existing literature reveals that applying the circular economy will be a drastic change in business operations which can lead to instability across the supply chain. It needs a highly integrated model with sustainable processes in all aspects (Gupta et al., 2019). All the stakeholders need clarity of functions and particular resource requirements and subsequent benefits to integrate them to put efforts into circularity.

Lack of collaboration between supply chain actors

Along with the complexity in functions and processes, the circular supply chain model can face less co-ordination from supply chain actors, which can be an alarming scenario. Farooque et al. (2019) explain in the study that the barriers arise when they do not support each other for the implementation of the circular economy because industry structure and policies are still co-ordinated around the linear model (Gumley, 2014). It is vital to understand the interrelationships of all stakeholders in the circular supply chain model, having extra layers of additional stages like upcycling and recycling (Mangla et al., 2018).

Lack of structure

Physical infrastructure such as utilities, buildings, and technology are essential components for the application of circular business model implementation which motivates the companies to utilise opportunities for competitive advantage (Pagano et al., 2018; Russel et al., 2020). Structural barriers to circular economy implementation are lack of appropriate infrastructure and technologies. Infrastructure and technologies are needed for smooth flow of supply chain processes in industries for logistics and reverse logistics to be able to support waste management, upcycling, and recycling processes (Yuan et al., 2006; Xi, 2011, Gomes et al., 2013, Geng et al., 2016, Govindan and Hasanagic, 2018; Ritzen, 2018). Similarly convenient infrastructure, also encourage consumers to accept the circular process. Lack of infrastructure can lead to failure of circular initiatives and prevent others from adopting it (Vadakkappatt, 2021). Inadequate infrastructure is related to almost 20 percent of food product waste (Balaji and Arshinder, 2016; Prashar, 2021).

To facilitate the reverse logistics, it is recommended to perform the forward and reverse supply chain activities within a single firm that will eliminate uncertainties related to resource flow (Rashid et al., 2013). At the same time, to overcome the structural barriers, improving the partnership, customer relationship and belief among all stakeholders, enhancing communication, information sharing, and continuous monitoring is required (Defee et al., 2009; Whalen et al., 2018; Heyes et al., 2018, Unal, 2019). Manufacturing firms can also facilitate sustainability by providing a long-term relationship to their customers to give service guarantees and maintenance on the products, machines, or equipment (Ceschin, 2013). Rental and leasing schemes should be encouraged based on the customers' preferences and customisation (Mangla et al., 2018). The overall structure of the global supply chain needs to be revised to scrutinize the global food supply chain to the maximum level, which demands a new theoretical model, tools, and technologies (Zhong et al., 2016). Moreover, to make the circular approach more efficient, ad hoc strategies (i.e., natural, recyclable, resilient or easy to segregate) on the material (i.e., technical, or biological) handling process is necessary at the development stage of the product (McDonough and Braungart, 2002; Unal et al., 2019).

2.5.6 Institutional and regulatory barriers and drivers

National and international policies and regulations are significant factors to apply circular economy business model (Urbinati et al., 2021; Wralsen et al., 2021). Institutional and regularity barriers are deep-rooted into sustainable and green supply chain management transitions (Raedemaekers et al., 2011; Gumley 2014). These barriers prevent the techniques and methods which are instrumental for sustainability related changes from developing (Li et al., 2015). The challenges are in terms of less government support and lack of suitable rules and regulations.

Lack of supportive law and regulation

Unstable government policies and the absence of circular business model related regulations affect the formation of remanufacturing industries (Shao et al., 2019). It is explored in the literature that government regulations are aligned in accordance with linear supply chains (Al Zaabi et al., 2013), hence, do not support the circular model (Vanner et al., 2014; Rizos et al., 2015; van Eijk, 2015; Pheifer, 2017; Ranta et al., 2017). These regulations include taxation policies (Mathiyazhagan et

al., 2013), lack of smart regulations for waste prevention (Preston, 2012, p.16), or lack of policy framework (Rizos et al., 2015, p.1). de Jesus and Mondeca (2018) position the institutional barriers as the second most pressing barriers by considerable involvement in 23% of analysed studies. In some countries, strict law and regulations prevent the implementation and development of circular supply chain management and compatible technologies. It is a highly time consuming and complex process to get the permit and complete the procedures for developing green technologies (Ecorys, 2010). It is difficult for policy makers to make the policies on common goals applicable to people of various cultures, perception, and beliefs (Keating, 2009). However, in the study done by Kirchherr et al. (2018), regulatory barriers did not appear in the core category of barriers because some of the countries had already started considering the circular economy as part of their policies. Scholars also point out that measures and indicators to trace and control are also missing from government side (Govindan et al., 2016).

Lack of government support

This includes the lack of governmental support with supportive taxation policies, funding, or royalty regimes (Studer et al., 2006; Gumley, 2014). Organizations are always reluctant to begin the circular economy transition due to the financial risk associated with it. There are very rare government policies to provide incentives to bear the risks on investments related to innovative and sustainable businesses. Given the necessity to fulfil the requirement of economic efficiency along with environmental benefits, public incentives are needed (Turner et al., 1994; Qiao and Qiao, 2013; Borello et al., 2015). Providing financial incentives like subsidies, lowering value added tax also required to stimulate circular initiatives (Stahel, 2013; Stahel and Clift, 2016; Preston, 2012, p.14).

A number of studies focussed on environmental regulation, enforcement and governmental policies. Government policies, law and legislation has greatest casual-effect value in applying the circular economy approach (Farooque et al., 2018). Mangla et al. (2018) suggests the comprehensive policy of government on procurement and material handling can be a helpful force to apply circular models. Official pricing strategies and appropriate measures should be encouraged by the institutions towards green supply chain transition. Green practices are usually anticipated by initial costs and the payback period; this risk can be overtaken by the government

by generating monetary incentives for the investors. As Genovese et al. (2015) and Pompoini and Moncater (2017) suggest, to overcome the financial challenges in the circular economy, top-down governmental support should be initialized to support bottom-up proposals. Relevant bodies such as central government departments, Local Authorities and Chambers of Commerce should take the initiative to promote the use of by-products. Government can also ease and boost foreign direct investment specifically in the circular supply chain management area and focus to provide subsidies and tax credit benefits (Gupta and Palsule-Desai, 2011; Faraud, 2016). Along with the implementation, policies should be regularly monitored under stringent compliance (Geng et al., 2012). The impact of uselessness can be overcome by transforming the company culture from scratch which includes changing the entire design approach, production process, marketing practices as well as with total management commitment (Borello et al., 2016; Xavier et al., 2019; Unal et al., 2019).

2.6 DEVELOPMENT OF THE THEORITICAL FRAMEWORK ON THE BASIS OF STAKEHOLDER THEORY

This section presents a theoretical framework to circular supply chain management considering its barriers and drivers and to create the value for stakeholders as a result. The barriers and drivers in this framework are obtained from the existing literature of the circular economy and sustainability studies which provides the dimensions for further descriptive research on all of its constructs. To serve the purpose of the third objective of this research (to systematically examine the effects of barriers on each stage of the circular supply chain management) the framework provides a foundation for analysing each phase of the circular supply chain and related barriers to it. In today's business world it is vital to share the value and share the purpose for long-term orientation, building trust and developing the agility in the system for value creations. "It is not stakeholders versus shareholders, or economic versus social value. In today's business world, "and" is the most important word" (Freeman et al., 2020). The theory-based framework is important to analyse the visions of stakeholders for ensuring the involvement of different stakeholders in the business model. Creating a theoretical framework would add the customer prepositions and involves issues with which and for whom value is created, what constitute the value for involved stakeholders and

how it is created (Freudenreich, 2016). In this framework involved stakeholders are the managers from various the stages of circular supply chain i.e., designing, manufacturing, retailing, consuming, upcycling, recycling and logistics which work together to achieve the purpose of ‘closing the loops and the value denoted for them is the critical factors which hinder the practical application of circular model and how they can be overcome. Moreover, the framework also presents activities for value creation of stakeholders related to individual factors (Freudenreich, 2016).

Value creation extends three fundamental dimensions of circular supply chain management: economic, social, and environmental (Lahen et al., 2020). Value for circular supply chain management for the stakeholders can be best created through a close analysis of barriers the stakeholders face. This research referred to existing literature for a general overview to evaluate the factors affecting the circular economy transition i.e. from general context (van Eijk, 2015; Ritzéna and Sandström, 2017; Govindan and Hasanagic, 2018; Hopkinsons et al., 2018; Jesusa, Mendonça, 2018; Levering, 2019), from SMEs (Rizos et al., 2015, from construction (Adams et al., 2017; Hart et al., 2019), (Ünal et al., 2018) from the office supply perspective, from the upcycling perspective (Sung et al., 2017), from the developing countries (India) perspective (Mangla et al., 2018), from Chinese industry (Farooque et al., 2019); from the European context (Kirchherr et al., 2018) from the agri-food sector (Borrello, 2016), from the manufacturing industries perspective (Tura et al., 2019), Agyemang et al., (2019) from Automobile and Moktadir et al., (2019) and from the leather industry .

Furthermore, to serve the purpose of this research the barriers were re-examined and categorised according to appropriate categories; some the themes were discarded i.e. “long product lifecycle” (Hart et al., 2019) because inappropriate to the UK food supply chains and some of them which share the same idea were combined together i.e. “Lack of preferential tax policies for promoting the circular models” and “Lack of environmental laws and regulations” (Mangla et al., 2018) present inadequacy from government rules, regulation and policies are created as one theme: “lack of supportive law and regulation”. In existing literature drivers are denoted under the same terms as barriers (Russell et al., 2019) and not categorised under the categories (except Hart et al., 2019),

hence, are not generated as separate themes but explored in chapter 2 and in qualitative research (chapter 5).

Figure: 2.4: Theoretical framework considering barriers to circular supply chain

Source: Developed by author

This model provided the foundation to recognise the stakeholder of food supply chains and develop the questionnaire (Appendix 4.2) for qualitative data collection. It also supported to explore the concepts further related to this research's settings through interviews from stakeholders of the food supply chain, adopting stakeholders' theory and to create a final framework (see chapter 6). This research maintained the argument that the resources gained from stakeholders are unique in nature and cannot be imitated or changed. Therefore, it used the stakeholders' analysis to obtain the

challenges and difficulties according to their perception and experiences. As per (Donaldson and Preston (1995) and Friedman and Miles (2006) successful businesses always keep the ability to respond to the pressure and demands of their stakeholders. Companies focussing on financial aspects will ignore their key stakeholders (Friedman et al., 2006). As per the existing literature, clients, governments, stockholders, employees, non-governmental organisations, and media are putting the pressure on firms about sustainability and the circular economy considerations (Mitchell et al., 1997; Sarkis et al., 2010; Silva et al., 2019; Jakhar et al., 2018) including consumers to make retailers and manufacturers supplying environmentally friendly products and services (Govindan and Hasanagic, 2018). Govindan and Hasanagic, 2018, asserts the most important stakeholders as government (Chiappetta Jabbour et al., 2020). Stakeholder pressure works optimistically to drive the circular change by averting the barriers and considering the motivators. As the result, stakeholder pressure can drive circular change by motivating the managers to shift towards the circular economy (Chiappetta Jabbour et al., 2020). It is argued that stakeholder pressure can also affect and improve the circular economy related barriers which grab the attainment of zero waste vision. This analysis can help the companies to recognise and understand the added value of the circular economy initiatives (Jkhar et al., 2018). This can also boost up the exploratory innovation capabilities in the circular model, consequently, engagement of key stakeholders of circular supply chain. Consequently, stakeholders are an integral part for the success of the circular economy application (Russell et al., 2019; Gupta et al., 2019; Ghinoi et al., 2020).

Stakeholders' theory as a part of business and social research originates in a model for management to perform in extremely complex business environments. And later it combined ethics, organisational management, corporate social responsibility aspects (Phillips, 2003). Organisations should acknowledge their stakeholders not for protecting its reputation but also understanding their active engagement towards sustainable undertakings (Wolf, 2014; Fritz et al., 2018). Understanding the stakeholders can be an enabler for policy makers by developing sustainability regulations and sustainability performance (Müller et al., 2009; Li et al., 2014). It carries the ability to manage the network of numerous stakeholders' relationships not just one to one relation (Asher 2005; Nag et al., 2005). The theory facilitates numerous theoretical and practical applications, hence selected for this research.

The theory has been criticised by scholars by presenting the views like, “Stakeholder theory is a valuable management technique (Svendsen 1998; Wheeler and Sillanpää 1998; Carroll and Buchholtz 2003). However, have less theoretical, practical and realistic features” (Argenti 1997; Barry 2002; Marcoux 2003; Sternberg 1994; Sundaram and Inkpen 2004). The challenge for stakeholder theory is that it acknowledges (Phillips, Freeman and Wicks (2003) the mutual interest of stakeholders and encourages the supporters. However, from the critical point of view it is difficult to maintain this interest and possessing one single theory (Donaldson and Preston 1995; Mitchell et al., 1997; Winn 2001). Most of the work related to stakeholder theory is descriptive (Frost 1995; Perrott 1996, Yuksel et al., 1999) which becomes more complex when the phenomenon is novel and takes time to become a body of literature (Winn, 2001) and Frooman, 2002). However, from the quotation of R.S. Lynd (1939) (Freeman, 1984, p. 6), “If praying to the gods for rain does not increase the fertility of our fields, it avails little to redouble our prayers or to make alterations in their wording; we would better turn our energies to the techniques of agriculture”; Freeman focuses on technique rather than theory (Key, 1999). Reflecting criticism from scholars regarding the theory helped in this study to combine stakeholders’ analysis with the stakeholder theory and to analysis the key actors and their roles within the environment, as suggested by Kay, (1999).

2.7 SUMMARY

Circular supply chain management is a novel yet developed field in environment studies. With its recognisability and importance in industries, it has driven management scholars to give theoretical as well as practical insights. Although some of the aspects of the circular economy, like cradle-to-cradle and recycling have been studied by academics for a few decades, circular supply chain management as a management approach is still at the preliminary stage. There are a number of studies to provide a background to the circular economy and factors for preventing and driving its implementation.

This chapter is an overview of stakeholder theory which is used to address the phenomenon under research. The chapter provides an outline of the theory, its relationship with the circular economy

studies and application in the food supply chain management of the United Kingdom. The key stakeholders have been addressed based on the supply chain and the theoretical framework has been constructed considering barriers and drivers to circular supply chain management. This chapter explores the importance of applying stakeholder theory in sustainability studies and also presenting critical views. In the next chapter, the researcher describes the research design, used to explore the theoretical framework developed in this chapter to support the purpose of this research

Furthermore, it identifies six categories of challenges, i.e., financial, technical, management, socio-cultural, structural, and institutional, which prevent businesses bringing circular change in supply chains. Scholars specified the circular supply chain driving factors under the same names as barriers, i.e., financial barriers and financial drivers, and explored the ways by which it can be achieved. The next chapter describes the relevance of stakeholder theory to value creation, which is used as lens to frame the findings.

CHAPTER III: METHODOLOGY AND RESEARCH DESIGN

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter aims to outline the methodological approach implemented in this research. An overview of the research design and rationale of adopting the qualitative approach has been elucidated in this chapter following these sections: Section 3.2 describes the research design in the study along with justifying the selection of methodology adopted. Research design and method of data collection selected in this research has been described in section 3.3. Section 3.4 gives an overview about the qualitative fieldwork and data analysis. In sections 3.5 and 3.6 the validity and ethical issues and summary of this chapter are illustrated.

3.2 JUSTIFICATION OF THE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Realisation and achievement of the objectives of this research, mentioned in section 1.5 need exploratory nature of methodology. This chapter describes the methods and approaches used in this study. Research characteristically engages the empirical and conceptual type of examination of a subject matter (Myers, 2013). While empirical research uses the inductive process in which theories are formulated by observations, the deductive approach is used for deriving new logics from existing facts (Goddards and Millville, 2007). To discover the dimensions and techniques for accomplishment is the most discussed subject area in “sustainable development” research and being a dynamic process, “development” should be evaluated in dynamic parameters (Tretyakova, 2003).

Research is always grounded in few philosophical assumptions like what makes that study “valid” or what methods are used for the development of knowledge. Methodology adopted in the research is based on the paradigms that guide the research (Antwi and Hamza, 2015). The term paradigm was first used by Kuhn (1962) to signify a conceptual framework by the group of researchers which assisted them to inspect the problem and find the solution. Paradigm is a guideline for researchers of a particular stream to decide what to research, how the study should be carried out, and the results interpreted (Bryman (2004), Guba and Lincoln (1994)). Lather (1986) describes that research paradigm characteristically replicates the researchers’ vision about the world in which

they deal or want to deal with. It reflects how the researchers see, infer, and act within that world. Paradigm is a theoretical lens through which the researchers scrutinize the methodological aspects of their study. Denzin and Lincoln (2000), who are said to be the experts of qualitative research, explain paradigms as human constructions which deal with initial ideologies, representing where the researcher is based and to conceptualize the meaning embedded in data.

The paradigm outlines the philosophical orientation of the researcher and contains four interconnected components: epistemology, ontology, methodology, axiology (Guba and Lincoln, 1998), where epistemology is understanding the nature and rationale of knowledge. (Schwandt, 1997). It is used to describe what is considered as knowledge in the world, its nature, kinds, ways to acquire and communicate to the world (Cooksey and McDouals, 2011). Ontology is another branch of philosophy that deals with assumptions (Scotland, 2012) and is advantageous for understanding the objects which comprise the world and seeks the real nature (Guba and Lincoln, 1998; Scott and Usher, 2004). The term methodology is used very broadly and indicates the research design, methods, approaches, and procedures used in the research (Keeves, 1997; Guba and Lincoln, 1998). It articulates how we got to know the world and knowledge about its aspects (Moreno, 1947). Lastly, when defining, evaluating, and understanding the differences between right and wrong behaviour, axiology paradigm is used. It is a philosophical approach of making right decision (Finnis, 1980). Axiology concentrates on 4 principles: privacy, accuracy, property, accessibility.

An association of the researcher and various kind of knowledge which can be acquired through the investigation is known as epistemology in social research (Hirschheim et al., 1995). The leading norms of epistemology are known as the positivism, interpretivism, critical (Deshpande, 1983; Candy, 1989; Cassell and Symon, 1994, Neuman, 2003; Antwi and Hamza, 2015) and pragmatic paradigms (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2003).

Positivism: The positivism approach of research is remarked as the study of causal effect and reality that can be regarded or measured objectively by using scientific methods like experiments or statistics through combining deductive logic and empirical observations which further can be used to envisage general human activity and to get the closest approximation of reality (Crotty,

1998; Neuman, 2003; Marczyk, 2005; Augustyn, 2014). The research guided by positivism approach follows quantitative and experimental methods for testing hypothetical-deductive generalities. The method of examination in this type of approach is characterised by forming research questions and formulating hypotheses for subsequent verification (Amaratung, 2002; Bryman and Bell, 2015). To facilitate the quest for causal explanations and fundamental laws, the positivism approach usually chooses the general to simplest possible element for analysis (Esterby Smith, 1991 Remenyi et al., 1998).

The researcher's role in this type of study is minimal for collecting and interpreting the data (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Researchers working on experimental studies tend to justify how variables interact, form events, and produce results in quantitative form using the positivism approach. Moreover, this approach believes that knowledge is based on direct observations or management of natural phenomena over experimental ways (Lincoln and Guba, 2000; Neuman, 2003).

Interpretivism: From the interpretivism perspective generalities can be conceptualised from the past events to predict future occurrences (Amarantungs et al., 2002). Interpretivism originated from the idea that the social world (people, cultures, social practices, and social institutions) is different from physical science because humans interpret their world and then act on those interpretations (Knight and Cross, 2012; Hammersly, 2013; Bryman and Bell, 2015). Therefore, the framework of qualitative research perceives the world as based on constructed, interpreted, and experienced by the human interaction within the broad social system (Guba and Lincoln, 1985; Merriam, 1988; Bogdan and Biklen, 1992; Maxwell, 2006). The interpretivism approach rely on qualitative methodology in which researcher and the group to be researched come in personal contact for some time which leads to better insight, richness, and intensity to the subject to be studied (Ulin et al., 2004). Due to its nature, data is collected in the form of interviews, focus group discussions and naturalistic observations.

Furthermore, data collected by interpretive method is considered to be sensitive in nature due the use of quotations, truthful reporting, first-hand experience directly from the interviewers (Merriam, 1998). Therefore, data collecting methods employed are of sensitive nature that build

the trust of interviewee to speak in depth (Neuman 2003). It leads the investigator to excavate the phenomenon from the participant's experience.

Table: 3.1: Key features of research paradigm

Source: Easterby smith et al., 1991

Material redacted due to Copyright restrictions.

Transformative: The third group of researchers who criticized, positivism and interpretivism epistemologies is the transformative paradigm. Transformative emerges to address the social, political, and economic matters which lead to coercion, conflict, struggle or injustice (Mertens, 2015). Because this paradigm is concerned with power relationship structure and personal situations are examined of individuals in a specific situation or their social positioning, the research community, professional institutions in education and psychology revised their standard and developed more responsive agendas for transformative issues (Mertens, 2015; Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017).

Pragmatism: When the researcher feels that accessibility of facts of the real world is not possible solely either by positivism or interpretivism, paradigm identified by Tashakori and Teddlie (2010) is used, named pragmatism (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). Philosophers of the pragmatic paradigm

(Alise and Teddlie, 2010; Biesta, 2010; Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2003a, and 2003b; Patton, 1990) indicate that it provides a more appropriate resolution for studying the phenomenon with the combination of methods by understanding the behaviour of participants, belief after that behaviour and results which are likely to come from diversion of behaviours (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). A mixed methods methodology (combination of quantitative and qualitative) is used in this type of research.

To lead towards more precise and accurate results, it is imperative to choose the research methodology on the basis of the research situation. Situations that work as sediments for the choice of research strategy can be type of presented question, behavioural control, elements, and extent of motivation towards historical or modern events (Yin, 1994). Qualitative or naturalistic are the appropriate approaches to inductively and holistically understand the human experience for context-specific settings in phenomenological or interpretivism research. Rather focusing on external causes, this approach tries to comprehend phenomenon (Easterby-Smith, 1991; Remenyi et al., 1998) explained in Table 4.2. Research related to the theme of the circular economy heretofore is concentrated on qualitative methods (Bocken et al., 2016; Manninen et al., 2018). Van Dijk et al. (2014) depict that using interpretivism is an ideal approach for the novel phenomena like the circular economy where awareness about pertinent actors and strategies to form a significant network is very limited to date. Therefore, this research is exclusively based on the interpretivism paradigm to validate the research questions. The qualitative method is significant as well as valuable when research needs the deep insight of the topic in the terms of perceptions, motives, barriers, or emotions (Mesian et al., 2018), and supportive for organizations to discover the back casting techniques, screening tools, eco-designs to redefine the business models (Bocken et al., 2019; Welzberg et al., 2021).

Table: 3.2: Two schools of science

Material redacted due to Copyright restrictions.

Adopting this paradigm makes the researcher accountable to answer the research questions by gaining in-depth understanding of the barriers to circular supply chain management. Qualitative approach gives the real-life and holistic view of the complex problem therefore (Cresswell, 2011) by recognising the behaviour, attitude, and experience of various stakeholders of each stage of the circular supply chain management of the food industry helping to rationalise the effect of recognized barriers on their department in this study. Data extracted from different branches of circular supply chain management is analyzed through thematic analysis which acknowledges the technical viability and wider acceptance of phenomenon to be investigated (Lapan et al., 2012).

Collecting data during a sustained period of time makes it more influential for studying any process. Hence, accumulating data from various stakeholders on the constant time provide generalisability and reliability to the data. Moreover, discussing drivers against those barriers assists organizations to develop the novel techniques and generate business models apposite to the circular economy. Understanding the nature of research is important to make a decision about the paradigm chosen. Thus, the reason behind qualitative methodology (inductive) is that the circular supply chain management concept has not been explored in the wider context in scientific literature more specifically in relation to operations and strategic management and the food manufacturing industry. Secondly, Esposito (2020) illustrates the need of integrating different stages of supply chain for developing the tools, techniques, and models relevant to circular transition. Experimental studies should more systematically focus on the interrelation among challenges and supply chain actors, which would lead to the success factors and managerial implications (Bressanelli, 2018). The study also emphasises the claim of Pomponi and Moncaster (2017) that existing studies are very limited for underpinning the complex nature of transition like the circular economy. Thus, interdisciplinary research is required involving technological innovation, the role of people,

challenges including resolutions and guidance for policy making which needs profound investigation from the foundation level since this study engages food circular supply chain management from all disciplines to discover it from foundation level.

To examine the circular supply chain management extensively and systematically (Pomponi and Moncaster, 2017; Bressanelli, 2018), qualitative method is a more appropriate approach (Geissdoerfer, 2018; Van Dijk et al., 2014) because the subject is at very novel stage and knowledge about related performers, appropriate strategies, tools, and techniques has not been explored on the broad level and needs a theory generation approach. Table 3.3 presents the characteristics of the qualitative approach. Qualitative researchers generally contend that “reality is socially constructed” (e.g., Guba and Lincoln, 1989); social behaviour follows socially constructed norms. Qualitative research can be labelled as problem solving techniques by studying the real complex world in a meaningful manner observing interviewee’s behaviour and encouraging them to express themselves rather than restricting them to pre-decided questions (Lapan et al., 2012; Hemmersley, 2013;). Motivation while discovering, expanding the knowledge about a new area, constructing the hypothesis qualitative approach is considered proficient. Qualitative data is also valuable for validating, explaining or re-interpretating the data from the same settings (REF). In qualitative research words dominates than numbers, used to recognise how people think and react and is a form of problem-solving scenario (Merriam, 2009).

3.3: Characteristics of Qualitative research

Category	Characteristics
Philosophical Roots	Pragmatism Phenomenology
Goal of investigation:	Inductive: understanding Description discovery Meaning Hypothesis generation Process Discovering unanticipated events, influences and conditions

	Inductive development of theory
Epistemology	Subjective
Phenomenology	Hermeneutical/Dialectical
Personal Contact	Direct contact with participants and settings Researcher's perspective and insights are critical to understand the phenomenon
Dynamic system	Attention is paid to ongoing system and settings; hence transferability is approached with caution
Context sensitivity	The social temporal and temporal contexts of the settings are important
Empathetic Neutrality	Complete objectivity is impossible Yet pure subjectivity undermines credibility, so focus is on seeking neutral understanding of the participants, settings and self.
Design	Flexible Evolving Emergent
Design Flexibility	Research design is open to change depending on discovery process
Sample	Small Non-Random Purposeful
Data Collection	Researcher as primary instrument Semi-directive interviews Observation Documents Ethnographies Case studies Narrative research

	Focus group discussion Field-notes Recordings and Filming
Nature of Instruments	Words, images Categories In-depth interviews Participant observation Field notes Open-ended questions
Data Analysis	Use descriptive data Search for patterns, themes ad holistic features Appreciate variations
Findings	Comprehensive Holistic Expansive Richly Descriptive Provision of insider Viewpoint
Final Report	Informal narrative report

Source: (Yin, 1995; Merriam, 2001; Ledens and Moskal, 2004; Antwi and Hamza, 2015)

3.3 SELECTION OF RESEARCH APPROACH

Research objective mentioned in section 1.5, guide choose the research approach in this study, however, researchers suggest that the research question should be used to direct that selection (Saunders et al., 2007). In the natural and social studies two focussed factor are, what and which type the world is (Jervinen, 2000). Consequently, the qualitative approach is reliable for investigating the origin of social meaning and relationship between researcher and theme under investigation (Denzin and Lincoln, 1998). The qualitative approach is effective while capturing collective dynamics of a business, institutions and their internal elements, the stakeholders, and a

socio-environmental system. It involves the use of approaches of data collection and analysis suitable to the particular social actor accordance with social settings while considering human dynamics and vagaries at each stage of the whole research process (Adelopo, 2010; Lapan et al., 2012).

The fundamental assumption of qualitative research has those realities are multiple and socially build (Linclon and Guba, 1985) which denotes that they will be different, between different groups and in diverse social settings and are obliged with time and context (Dahlgren et al., 2004). Hence, results will vary as per the experience and will not be a single truth. Therefore, the researcher is obliged to discover those differences rather than a single truth (Ohman, 2005). Researchers connected with the circular economy in the context of environment, social or economy have widely adopted the qualitative approach (Gronroos et al., 2006; Martinez-Blanco et al., 2009; Arzoumanidis et al., 2014; Falconeb et al., 2016; Mondello et al., 2017).

The current study adopts qualitative methods to collect the data using the general inductive approach referred to by Dey (1993) and Burgess (1994) and to understand and apprehend the mutual dynamics of various stakeholders of circular supply chain management. Secondly, the qualitative method is used because of its nature of looking at things from a wider perspective, examining human choice and behaviour since it is observed naturally in all its aspects. The behaviour and demand of qualitative research is to recognise the dimensions and layers of reality from multiple levels such as the type of people in a group, how they think, how they interact, the type of agreement and norms existing and how these norms approach collectively in the holistic way to describe a cluster (Antwi and Hamza, 2015; Merriam, 2009). The inductive approach supports research findings to emerge from recurrent, leading, and significant themes extracted from raw data without imposing any restructuration (Thomas, 2003; Merriam, 2009).

There is comprehensive series of philosophical underpinnings, methodological approaches, and techniques in qualitative research by which each stage of the research is approached or analysed (Thomas, 2003; Seers, 2012) i.e., grounded theory (Strauss and Corbin, 1990), phenomenology (van Menen,1990), discourse analysis (Potter and Wetherall, 1994) and narrative analysis (Leiblich,1998). The data analysis in this study is carried out using thematic analysis which seek

theory development evident by Strauss and Corbin, (1990). The summary of themes derived from raw data is developed to understand the meaning of complex data, known as the inductive approach (Backett and Davison, 1995; Stolee, Zaza, Pedlar, and Myers, 1999). Data is analysed in the categories constructed from concrete level of data which demands categories to be meaningful and pertinent and should be able to designate the phenomenon under study and each category has its own dimension and properties (Ohman, 2005).

Several considerations were made whilst deciding the qualitative research over any methodology. As per Strauss and Corbin (1990), qualitative methods can be considered as more suitable while investigating the phenomenon about which only limited knowledge is available or to do addition of new perspectives of known facts or to gain thorough knowledge which is difficult with quantitative methods or where interpretation of data is not adequate with quantitative methods. Qualitative research statements are more meaningful as they are occupied with characteristically rich and detailed information and visions of participants' experience of the world (Stake, 1978, p.5). Therefore, the method is well suitable for exploring the topic the circular economy in the supply chain of food manufacturing industries (Tura et al., 2018).

Giving the rationale about adopting the qualitative method, this study is concerned with semi-structured interviews with the managers of various circular supply chain management actors of the food manufacturing industry. The qualitative method was applied to gain in-depth knowledge about circular supply chain management from all the inseparable perspectives. As the circular supply chain management approach is in a very initial stage in the business environment and only minimal research is done in the literature, so it needs to be defined precisely and in greater depth (Miles et al., (2014). Similarly, it needs to be explored as to what hindrance factors get in the way for food industries to adopt this transition and how they can be overcome which is again lacking in existing literature. Most importantly, this research is more department specific; various stakeholders have been approached to discuss the issue under investigation from their own perspective. Therefore, qualitative methods are more appropriate because there unknown or very little attention has been paid to the subject. The following procedure has been adopted to perform the qualitative research.

Figure:3.1: Qualitative data procedure

Source: Developed by author

3.4 QUALITATIVE FRAMEWORK

As current literature lacks the understanding about circular supply chain management for food manufacturing. The study chose the qualitative approach to fill the gap in literature 1) by gaining in depth and conceptual understanding of research area which is at the preliminary stage (Eisenhardt et al., 1989; Bansal and Corley 2012). 2) by developing the vision for the phenomenon under investigation and exploring it in depth so that propositions can be articulated (Eisenhardt et al., 1989; Kohlbacher, 2005; Edmondson and McManus, 2007; Mayring 2010). 3) and finally, by ensuring the flexibility and quality within the research process (Kohlbacher, 2005).

Byrne (2001) emphasises the purpose of research while choosing the sample for qualitative research. The samples in qualitative research should be selected to assist the investigation purpose rather than statistically representing the population (Ritchie et al., 2013). Consequently, this study uses the purposive sampling method and later the snowball sampling method, in which elements of data collection have been decided based on the characteristics they serve and are significant to

the study (Bryman, 2016) and further assisted by the maximum variation technique (Byrne, 2001; Ritchie et al., 2003). Qualitative sampling performs to shelter all the relevant key parameters with adequate diversification within the principles which grants in-depth exploration. It continues to the point of theoretical saturation (Saunders et al., 2018).

The next phase of this research is to decide the study population which can be people, records, images, or documents (Atkinson and Hammersley, 2019). In-depth interviews, observations, documents, and visual images are the basic procedures of qualitative data collection (Creswell, 1994). Figure 4.2 represents the research cycle to conduct qualitative research, showing the need of iterative design and continuous reviewing to enhance the effectiveness of data.

Figure 3.2: Research cycle for qualitative research

Source: Adapted from Ritchie et al., 2003; Hennink et al., 2020; Chai et al., 2021

Ritchie et al. (2003), illustrate that qualitative research has multiple ways of data collection i.e., in-depth interviews, focus groups and observations. Research topic, study population, nature of data and some practical factors like social context or sensitivity of topic are the major factors involved in the selection of data collection method (Ritchie, 2003). Considering the nature of investigation, which is based on several interconnected echelons, semi-structured interview method was chosen which provides the richness and flexibility guarantee over structured or open-ended interviews. Where structured and open-ended interviews come with set of questions with pre-determined answers to gather quantified data or without arranged questions to get an idea what to research consequently, semi-structured interviews are in-depth interviews which involve pre-arranged open-ended questions but not the answers which also differ according to the target group's characteristics and context and ready to be moulded according to the flow of conversations (Saunders et al., 2009; Jamshed, 2014). Application of semi-structured interview methods is described in Table 4.4. To meet the purpose of this research, each stage of circular supply chain management has been approached. The next section explains the planning, management, and interpretation of qualitative data.

Table 3.4: Application of in-depth interviews

In-Depth Interviews	
Nature of data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For generating in-depth personal accounts To understand the personal context For exploring issues in depth and detail
Subject matter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To understand complex processes and issues e.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - motivations, decisions - impacts, outcomes To explore private subjects or those involving social norms For sensitive issues
Study population	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For participants who are likely to be less willing or able to travel Where the study population is geographically dispersed

	Where the population is highly diverse Where there are issues of power or status Where people have communication difficulties
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Adapted from Ritchie et al., 2003

3.4.1 Interviews

Interviews and reflective discussions establish an analytical source of information. They give the researcher a prospect to address and examine relevant issues in a more detailed manner and obtain meaningful descriptions from the interviewees (Gilham, 2005; Silverman, 2006). Semi-structured interviews resulted as an appropriate method to meet the objectives of this research by providing better flexibility guarantee and ensuring interrelated levels of analysis. Interviews served the purpose of this research, to explore the topic to circular supply chain management, to investigate its barriers from stakeholders' perspectives and to suggest the drivers.

Theoretical sampling was considered in this study rather than random sampling to “maximise opportunities for comparing concepts along their properties for the similarities and differences enabling researchers to define categories, to differentiate among them, and to specify their range of variability” (Strauss and Corbin, 1998, p. 149). The quality of the interview instrument also plays a significant role for passing the test of reliability. A study is considered reliable when interview data is consistent without bias and serve the purpose (Sekaran and Bougie, 2003). A pilot study was conducted prior to the actual interview. It helped to detect possible flaws by recognizing potential issues or amendments (Dikko, 2016; Watson et al., 2007). The researcher chose semi-structured interview method for data collection, which made interviewees more flexible and allowed new questions to be added as per the flow of conversation during the interview and increased the richness of information collected. Three pilot interviews were conducted from the different stages of food supply chain and results obtained were used as foundation to conduct actual interviews.

This study conducted 36 in-depth interviews, with various stakeholders of the circular supply chain of food manufacturing industry, which allowed the researcher to gain individual subjective views and improve the validity of results (Saunders et al., 2019). The participants are the managers from the different stages of circular supply chain which starts from product design/ development to recycling. Consumption stage is an integral part of circular supply chain. To gain the perspective of whole supply chain this research has included consumer's point view. In-depth interviews were the best way to address a complex process like circular supply chain management because it provided depth of focus and prospects for explanation and understanding about the topic (Ritchie, 2003). To recruit appropriate participants and justify the number of respondents, the researcher contacted an employee of GI group (an employment agency) and a manager of a food manufacturing organisation for approaching manufacturing companies. The researcher also contacted managers of insurance broker companies requesting to refer participants like recycling or up-cycling companies which are insured with them. and to approach the retailing companies and customers, retailers were directly contacted.

Contact details of 30 people from food manufacturing companies, 10 retailers, 4 upcycling, 5 recycling including council representatives, 10 customers and 2 suppliers were provided. Research contacted all 61 people by email and telephone out of which 4 people from the designing stage, 13 from food manufacturing and processing, 7 retailing managers, 4 from recycling (including 1 government representative council worker), 1 from upcycling and 5 customers, 1 farmer and 1 manager from the logistics stage responded and agreed to participate. Number of participants from a particular stage depends on the area in the industry for example, supplier stage: UK food manufactures mainly use suppliers from Europe and Asia; hence this research being limited to access to supplying stage was limited. Next, product designing and logistics stages which are always a part large manufacturing company. So, the participants are limited to 4 and 1 consequently. Product manufacturing and retailing are the larger unit with numerous departments, contribute to supply chain. Hence, the participants on this stage were 10 and 7 consequently. Similarly, 4 participants from recycling and 5 consumers were included. Food upcycling is on very early stage at present, with very few companies (less than 5) operating as business in the UK. Due to limited access of food products up-cyclers but to get the view of complete supply chain, research included food manufacturing machines up-cyclers.

Semi-structured technique was adopted for in-depth interviews which provided the uniformity and open-ended/prompt discussion between interviewer and interviewee and provides freedom of expression. (Speziale and Carpenter, 2003; DiCicco-Bloom, 2006; Crabtree, 2006; Creswell, 2007; Kirchherr et al., 2018; Sandvik and Wendy, 2019). Because of the absence of face-to-face interviews, research applied some additional strategies for maintaining the interview quality and consistency i.e., sending introductory emails, pre-preparation, and review of the procedure, cultivating rapport, acknowledging the content and concerns of interviewee, and honouring their contribution (Drabble et al., 2016). Additionally, assuring anonymity was also done by stating that the participant's identity will not be disclosed (Saunders et al., 2012, p231). In-depth interviews provided the flexibility and encouragement to the interviewee to talk freely on a variety of topics. "A good qualitative research interview is one in which informant talks and researcher is silently listening most of the time and only probes on things she/he hears during the interview" (Kvale, 1996).

The researcher prepared an interview guide (Appendix:3.1). in which a brief description about circular supply chain management and objectives of the study along with the consent (Appendix4.1) form was emailed to the potential participants for them to decide about the participation and get the confirmation. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, it was not possible to visit the sites and conduct interviews face to face. Therefore, phone calls, Skype and Zoom calls method was chosen as per the convenience of participants (Ritchie, 2003). All the participants opted for phone calls due to flexibility as there is less difference between face-to-face and telephone interviews (Dinham, 1994; Saunders, 2012; Block and Eriskine, 2012; Drabble et al., 2016), so this method was selected. An interview protocol was designed to confirm that all areas are covered (Appendix 4.2). In the first part, seven sections of the interview protocol were to get the deep-insight and empirical views about the circular economy and sustainability and all internal/external hindrance factors which affect food supply chain to adopt it. The second part was area specific to know about the particular industry. Before starting the actual process, a pilot study was conducted to get the experience about interviews (Bryman, 2012) and a few questions were amended from the interview protocol after reviewing. Interviewees were encouraged to give detailed explanation about each subject so that themes and issues could emerge inductively (Saunders et al., 2019). The

interviews lasted from 26 minutes to 1 hour and 29 minutes. All the interviews were conducted in English, recorded in more than one gadget and notes were taken side by side.

The researcher conducted 36 interviews, out of which 1 interview from a supplier and 1 from a consumer were discarded due to data quality issues. Another 25 people refused to take part due to their busy schedule. Although, there was access of more interviews, when themes stopped emerging and saturation was achieved, the interview process was stopped. Saturation decides the criteria of discontinuing data collection in qualitative research (Glaser and Staruss, 1967). It means no further data is being found where researcher can develop the categories. But see similar instance over and over again and become confident that category is saturated (Saunders et al., 2018). Hence, during the data collection process in this research was closed when themes started repeating.

3.4.2 Overview of the planning, management, analysis, and interpretation of data:

Data analysis is considered as eclectic process and there is wide variety of procedures to do it which depends on basic epistemological assumptions about the enquiry (Tesch, 1990; Bryman and Burgess, 1994; Creswell, 1994; Ritchie et al, 2003). Thematic analysis method has been applied to analyse the qualitative data which involves generating analytical categories and theoretical dimensions guided by literature based on the theoretical framework and then the relationships are identified between them (Foroudi et al., 2020).

Researcher's data analysis process started from familiarizing with data. Out of 36 recorded interviews 2 were discarded due to data inappropriateness, when re-listened, hence, were not transcribed. Rest 34 interviews were transcribed on MS word document word by word. Some researchers this this as a key phase of qualitative data analysis process (Bird, 2005). Recorded data was transcribed verbatim for reliability (Appendix 4.3). The length of transcription was varied from 3.5 pages (26 minutes) to 11.5 pages (1 hour 29 minutes). The interview process and transcription were going hand by hand. Transcribed interviews were uploaded on Nvivo-12 for data storage and further analysis process. Computer- assisted qualitative data analysis is an efficient way of data analysis through creating applying and refining categories; tracing linkage between concepts and making comparisons between cases and events (Schutt, 2018).

The next phase of analysis was, open coding by building the codes and constructs extracted from the literature review to explore the circular supply chain management concept, its challenges, and barriers. A theoretical framework was constructed by listing, describing, and categorising previously identified data into set of constructs and sub-constructs which further can be used to index and sort the obtained facts (Ohman, 2004; Chai et al, 2021). This advantages the data by setting the directions and emerging the themes (Guler, 2019). After transcribing the interviews, researchers jotted down the points of the ideas emerging from each interview which helped to group the large data into categories and to give the directions for further investigation (Tesch, 1990; Dahlgren et al., 2004; Bunard et al, 2004; Ohman, 2020). Themes which are observed frequently and reflects the core data, become core themes (Dahlgren et al., 2004; Ohman, 2020). The written themes should be sorted or resorted until researcher have the workable structure. It provides the researcher with a conceptual clarity and avoids the chances of overlapping (Ritchie et al., 2003). Research used three phase procedures for data analysis recommended by Strauss (1990) as open coding, axial coding, and finally selective coding.

Open coding for Strauss and Corbin (1990) are “coding the data every way possible.... running the data open” (p.56). In open-coding, analysis merge and submerge in the data by line-to-line analysis, coding data in several possible ways and remarking the conceptual and theoretical ideas developing during the analysis process. This process of data analysis is rigorous and brings simplification, verification, correction and finally saturation by itself (Glaser, 1992, p.60). At the initial stage, only the core incidents and events are considered. However, when the theory starts building up further data is included to intensify the findings, known as theoretical sampling (Goulding, 1999). Enquirers followed a constant comparative method to look for like to like emerging patterns and themes. The method assists to discover variances and resemblance within current incidents in data and guides to collect further data (Spiggle, 1994). With constant comparison of data, codes are reduced and grouped into significant categories (Goulding,1999). The next stage of coding is to place systematically analysed data together to show dynamic relationships among them (Mogadham, 2006). According to Strauss and Corbin (1990), the motive of axial coding is to put the fractured data back together in new ways “by making connections between a category and its subcategory” (p. 97). This forms the foundation for creating the theory

because axial coding constructs a model which elaborates the particular condition that give rise to phenomenon's occurrence. In this research, during the axial process, constant comparisons were made from the collected data and from the codes extracted from open coding process, axial codes were created based on differences and similarities. This led to four analytical processes a) rapidly relating sub-categories to a category b) comparing categories with collected data c) escalating the properties and dimension of categories to expand the intensity d) discovering variations in phenomena (Brown et al., 2002). All stages of coding process have been mentioned in Table 3.5.

Table 3.5: All stages of coding process

Memoing: Take notes, capturing the thought process	Stages in coding process of Thematic analysis	Description
	Open coding	Identify concepts of interest in qualitative data; code them
	Axial coding	Identify relationships between concepts via inductive reasoning
	Selective coding	Choose a "core concept" for analysis

Source: Adapted from Dillon (2012)

Figure: 3.3: Coding process from NVivo

Source: NVivo 12- Author's coding process

The final process is to re-read and selectively identify the themes and core themes of same dimensions and contents, which is called selective coding (Strauss and Corbin 1990; Dahlgren et al., 2004). Strauss and Corbin (1990) define selective coding as “the process of selecting the central or core category, systematically relating it to other categories, validating those relationships, and filling in categories that need further refinement and development” (p.116). This is the process of integrating and refining the theory (Strauss and Corbin,1998, p143). The researcher completed the final task of coding process by axing and relating the core category / themes with all other categories (Walker and Myrick, 2006). After setting the categories into a series, researcher can start to cover broad range of consequences of variety of situations (Brown et al., 2002). The outcome of this stage is a theoretical model, a theory or hypothesis. Therefore, cuts among categories are not seen as a link or correspondence from the statistical viewpoint.

Along with the coding process, the researcher followed superfluous rule of disrupting the coding process over and over and create the memos rapidly (Kaiser, 2006). Memos are distinct type of written ideas and thoughts that how researcher arrived at the codes (Stuckey, 2015). It keeps track of the analytical process and enhances the audit trail. Hence, helped the researcher to see it from the analytical perspective (Strauss and Corbin, 1990). Memos can also be in the form of diagrams and assist to recognise the relationship between concepts from the data (Maxwell, 1996; Strauss and Corbin, 1998). When there was satisfactory map with required themes, next step was of final analysis or discussing the findings (see chapter 4). It was ensured that each of the theme is optimally evidenced from the data (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

Furthermore, to ensure more efficiency in the analysis process, the researcher used extra techniques: 1) Piloting: which means going backward and forward from collection and analysing process, review and recuperate where necessary, 2) Co-coding: arranging frequent meetings with the supervisor and experts discussing the codes to confirm the consistent application, fitness, and relationship of codes (Busetto, 2020), and 3) Meta-narrative: to review the research question to understand more about it. This made the researcher able to delve into the concept of the circular economy and scrutinise the challenges for the food supply chain to adopt the circular approach.

To manage and analyse the data in a more efficient way, the researcher used Computer-Aided Qualitative Data Analysis Software. Researcher used NVivo version 12 to integrate coding with qualitative linking, shaping, and modelling (Chandrasegaran et al., 2017). The software was useful for creating, applying, and refining categories, tracking relationship between concepts and for juxtaposition between cases and events (Morrill et al., 2000) and for data storage and retrieval (Easterberg, 2002). Along with the manual method, NVivo is an ideal technique to find the tendencies, identify themes and derive the conclusions (Hilal and Alabari, 2013). With the use of information retrieval function, it allowed the researcher to make the connection between nodes (themes), develop advanced categories and articulate assertions which fit into data and test those assertions for applicability (Fielding,1994). Using this software made the researcher able to accomplish an abstract assessment of meanings and connections between data which enhanced conceptual density of the study by working thoroughly and systematically with more attentive manner. NVivo comprises with variety of features by which data can be manipulated, browsed, coded, interpreted and accessed in more effective and efficient way with the help of documents,

nodes and attributes (Richards, 1999). It has tools for recording, storing, retrieving, linking, shaping, and modelling the data that assist to pursue novel theories and respond to the research questions. It “offers many ways of connecting the parts of a project, integrating reflection and recorded data” (Richards, 1999, pp. 4). Hence, it is advantageous for a researcher to use, NVivo to improve the quality, reliability, accuracy, and transparency of the research.

The coding process in this research was done repetitively to attain the holism and inductiveness. To ensure the quality of any research, meticulous attention needs be paid to the evaluation related issues (Amaratunga, 2002). Validity and reliability are significant aspects in qualitative work, where researchers’ subjectivity must screen the interpretation of data (Brink,1993). The value of any research originates from the validity of its outcomes and the degree of its contribution to the knowledge. This corresponds to the question that “How can an inquirer persuade his or her audiences that the research findings of an inquiry are worth paying attention to?” (Lincoln and Guba, 1985, p. 290). Thus, Patton (2001) states that these two factors should be taken care of during designing the study, analysing results, and judging the quality of a study. “Trustworthiness” is crucial element to ensure the reliability of a research (Golafshani, 2003). Seale (1999) illustrates “trustworthiness of a research report lies at the heart of issues conventionally discussed as validity and reliability” (p. 266). The conception of deceiving truth through processes of reliability and validity is verified by the view of trustworthiness (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). To enhance the rigorousness in the study, multiple strategies been employed.

The investigator applied the “Triangulation” approach to escalate the validity of this study by merging the information from various sources rather concentrating on one approach. Triangulation is application of more than one method or sources to develop a broad understanding of phenomena (Patton, 1999). It is possible in four different ways 1) method triangulation 2) investigator triangulation 3) data source triangulation 4) theory triangulation (Denzin, 1978; Patton, 1999). The researcher employed theory triangulation to analyse and interpret the data by applying thematic analysis as analysis approach and stakeholder theory as theoretical lens. The researcher also involved diversity of population, for data collection to gain manifold perspectives and validation of data. Besides this, multiple methods of data collection were involved, which includes existing

literature, interviews, and field notes. Table 3.6 explains the techniques used in this research to improve the trustworthiness.

As peer briefing enhances the trustworthiness and credibility of a research project (Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Spal, 1998; Spillett, 2003). A qualified peer researcher was employed with the considerable qualitative research experience to review and evaluate the transcripts, themes, and findings of the study. To gain the reliability through thematic analysis, coding process was done iteratively (Weber,1985)

Table 3.6: Meeting the criteria of trustworthiness

Traditional criteria.	Techniques employed	Trustworthiness criteria
Internal Validity	Credibility	-Multi-Triangulation 1) method triangulation 2) data source triangulation 3) theory triangulation -Peer debriefing -Constant comparison -Pilot study
External Validity	Transferability	-Detailed description of the research setting -Multiple cases and cross-case comparison
Reliability	Dependability	-Theoretical and purposive sampling -Participant's confidentiality protected - Iterative coding
Objectivity	Confirmability	-Precise records of contacts and interviews -Keeping observational and field notes carefully -Word-by-word interview transcription -Keeping the notes of theoretical and methodological idea regularly

Source: Based on Lincoln and Guba (1985)

Consequently, encapsulating thematic analysis with stakeholders' perspective elaborates the factors like value, perception, attitude, experience, behaviour, and relationship about the variables from manifold dimensions to pursue the purpose of this study. The foundation of qualitative

research is constructive and directs towards understanding what is happening (Bryman, 2008; et al., 2012, p172). Exploratory studies are beneficial to achieve compressive view of a vague issue (Saunders et al., 2012, p.172). This research elucidates the concept of the circular economy by providing well-defined vision, in the context of food supply chains. Since the subject is at the preliminary stage of management literature, an exploratory approach was accepted with the support of semi-structured interviews to disclose the experiences, feeling and beliefs of the stakeholders, develop in-depth understanding and to investigate the barriers and drivers. The interviewee details are illustrated in Table 3.7.

Table 3.7: The details of in-depth interviews with key stakeholders of circular supply chain

S. N.	Supply Chain Stage	Gender	Organisation	Position	No. of experience in the industry	No. of years on the position	Interview duration
1	Supplier	Male	NSD	Farmer	11	11	20 minutes
2	Designing	Male	Kerry	Technical Manager	11	4	52 minutes
3	Designing	Male	Kerry	R & D Manager	20	3	1hr 5minutes
4	Designing	Male	Kerry	Chef Manager	9	3	58 minutes
5	Manufacturing	Male	Anonymous	Operations Manager	13	4	1hr
6	Manufacturing	Male	Nomad Foods	Operations Project Manager	26	1.5	1hr 10 minutes
7	Manufacturing	Female	Kerry	Planning Manager	7	3.5	50 minutes
8	Manufacturing	Female	Nomad Foods	Manufacturing Manager	10	1	38 minutes
9	Manufacturing	Male	Kerry	Technical Manager	6	2	44 minutes
10	Manufacturing	Male	Bakkavor	Operations Manager	10	4	48 minutes
11	Manufacturing	Female	Kerry	Supply chain Head	15	5.5	56 minutes
12	Manufacturing	Male	Kerry	Demand Planner	6	2	1 hr
13	Manufacturing	Male	Kerry	Senior National account manager	1	3	35 minutes
14	Logistics	Male	Bakkavor	Despatch Manager	17	4	1hr 25 minutes
15	Retailing	Male	Anonymous	Floor Manager	20	1.5	30 minutes
16	Retailing	Female	Greggs	Manager	8	2	31 minutes
17	Retailing	Female	M&S	Head of international supply chain and Logistics	6	4	48 minutes
18	Retailing	Male	Morrison's	Floor Manager	7	3.5	1hr 15 minutes
19	Consumer	Male	Consumer	Consumer	-	-	55 minutes
20	Consumer	Female	Consumer	Consumer	-	-	30 minutes
21	Consumer	Male	Consumer	Consumer	-	-	40 minutes
22	Upcycling	Male	Coffee Cup Ltd	Director	5	5	1 hr 29 minutes

23	Recycling	Male	Cymru Lan holdings Ltd	Director	3	3	30 minutes
24	Recycling	Male	Biogen (UK) Ltd	Business development manager	4	1	58 minutes
25	Manufacturing	Male	Noon Products	Vice President	27	10	27 minutes
26	Manufacturing	Male	Bakkavor	R&D Head	9	2	47 minutes
27	Manufacturing	Male	Ginni Ent. Ltd	Director	29	29	30 minutes
28	Designing	Male	Anonymous	R&D Packaging Lead	5	2	47 minutes
29	Retailing	Male	Tesco	Supply chain manager	7	1	35 minutes
30	Recycling	Female	Council	CSO	6	3	30 minutes
31	Recycling	Male	Household recycling ltd	Managing Director	13	13	45 minutes
32	Consumer	Female	Consumer	Consumers	-	-	40 minutes
33	Manufacturing	Male	Anonymous	Health & Safety Manager	3	1	33 minutes
34	Consumer	Female	Consumer	Consumer	-	-	30 minutes
35	Retailing	Female	Morrison	Sales manager	7	2.5	43 minutes
36	Consumer	Male (Not included)	Consumer	Consumer	-	-	30 minutes

Source: The researcher

3.5 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Academic research raises the ethical considerations about the moral principles of the research. In this research these principles are based on the guidelines provided by University of the West of Scotland “School of Education and Social Sciences Ethics Guidelines” October (2020). Considering the type of interaction held between the researcher and participant in qualitative studies, it can be ethically challenging task for the researcher (Sanjri et al., 2014). The researcher

must consider that the research is taking place in apposite manner. This study comprises of four major ethical principles mentioned by Sheldon (2013). 1) Research merit and integrity: appropriate methods have been used to design and progress through, is based on existing literature, ensures respect to participants, conducted, and supervised by people with qualification and experience and includes peer review for research merit. 2) Justice: No one is under pressure to participate; selection and recruitment of participants have been done and described fairly and research outcome will be accessible to participants. 3) Beneficence: Participants' wellbeing is utmost, and benefits have been clarified to them and research design minimises, any risk involved. 4) Respect: participants beliefs, perception, customs culture has been respected. Privacy, confidentiality, feelings, own decision making has been regarded. Additionally, a consent form is provided to the participants with an overview of research objectives, which helps participants to make independent decision (see Appendix). Interviews are done online rather face-to-face due to the Covid-19 pandemic and the methods are chosen as participants' preference.

3.6 SUMMARY

The perspective, approach and methodology used in the research has been presented in this chapter. The nature and dimensions of various research paradigms have been discussed, along with the rationale of choosing the interpretivism paradigm. Qualitative method has been used to explore the concept of circular supply chain management, its hindrance factors, their effects on various stage of circular supply chain and remedies have been explored.

Based on the themes extracted from literature review, an interview protocol was designed. Three pilot interviews were conducted, and the questionnaire was amended according to the responses, which led to the actual interviews. Considering stakeholder theory as a theoretical lens, the qualitative study was conducted from 36 stakeholders of the food supply chain in the form of semi-structured interviews. The data collection process was based on phone interviews (due to Covid-19 restrictions, face to face meetings and site visits were restricted). Data analysis has been performed on the basis of thematic analysis and the step-by-step procedure has been described comprising open, axial and selective coding. Lastly, ethical considerations have been denoted.

CHAPTER IV: QUALITATIVE FINDINGS

4.1 INTRODUCTION

The former chapter explained the significance of methodology used in this study. The qualitative research facilitates the perspectives for new insights by allowing the interviewees to choose their own elucidations based on their experiences (Aaker et al.2001). The concept of circular supply chain management is worthwhile discovering looking at its ability to turn waste into resources, while connecting all the phases of supply chain, yet has not been acknowledged by industries considerably. This section discusses the views, perceptions, attitude, and beliefs of food industry stakeholders based on the results obtained from 34 (as 2 interviews discarded) semi-structured interviews with reference to below objectives.

The study focusses to gain in-depth understanding of the circular economy in the context of food supply chains involving all stages from the development of product to recycling. The hinderance factors faced by the stakeholders have been recognised, shifting towards the circular approach along with the possible drivers. Choice of methods, planning, management, and data interpretation are explained in Chapter III. In section 4.2 the analysis about the circular supply chain concept is presented, in section 4.3 the analysis of barriers to circular supply chain is presented, section 4.4 is stakeholder analysis in the context of barriers, in section 4.5 driving strategies are analysed and final remarks are made and finally the summary of the section is given in 4.6.

4.2 FOOD CIRCULAR SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT FROM STAKEHOLDERS' PERSPECTIVE

Circular supply chain management is perceived in numerous ways by its stakeholders. To fulfil the first objective of this research, this section explores the strategic viewpoint of the circular supply chain management concept, its dimensions were decided through the guidance of literature. The idea and prospects of its achievability were discussed with participants through semi-structured interviews.

Figure 4.1: World cloud - circular supply chain implementation

Source: NVivo 12 through words frequency query

Outcomes from the qualitative study directed that the scope of circular supply chain management is very broad. The textual analysis from interviewees unveil that it can be adopted as a business model that has profitability, economic and ecological aspects in it. Additionally, it should be an integral part of a company's strategy. The following comments from a food manufacturing company's manager demonstrates the fact:

“It is completely different responsibility, would be driven down [by] teaching [the] management for circular supply chain. [That is] driven by the environmental [aspect]. So, it is marginated by the corporate strategy.” (BK)

Circular supply chain management brings the numerous advantages including economic, employment, material savings, less risk of price fluctuations of material (EMF, 2013a; Morgan and Mitchell, 2015; EEA 2016; Adams et al., 2017). A manager from an anaerobic digestion plant also adds in the above, saying:

“It is [the] combination of [numerous approaches]. Obviously, we benefit the business in terms of, offer[ing] the cost saving, it’s the green way of disposing [of] the waste, it gives them a bit of CSR in the terms of saying, look! what we do with it. They [are] not going to be contributing towards unnecessary emissions of greenhouse gases.” (MP)

The Director of an upcycling company also adds saying,

“So yes, I must say we are heavily involved in it, umm and its great. I completely agree, its good, it reduces carbon footprints. Because less import and export [as]we are importing less coffee machines from Italy. So instead of employing people in Italy, we are employing people from here [in the UK] to refurbish the machines”. (AF)

These quotations support the arguments of the circular economy and circular supply chain management authors (Potting et al., 2017 p 5; Genovese et al., 2017; Kirchherr et al., 2017; Nasir et al., 2017; Mangla et al., 2018). They state that circular supply chain management is assisted by the business models and consumers, benefiting environment, society, and the economy of a country. A planning manager from a food manufacturing company incorporates similar views, urging to bring it as a business model including economical characteristics and leads towards environmental strategy:

“I guess how we can make a business model to say how can we save money though we need to ummm we need to do that to make sustainable (...) future, logically and economically as well, for the people who work for us, to support their families. So, I think it’s kind of I think you lead it to the business model and then it becomes the environment Strategy.” (EGD)

An interviewee asserts the prospect of its acceptance that:

“It should be a business model, this is how the economy should work, this is how manufacturing of the product should work. This is how businesses should work. It is [the] need of hour. Right from the beginning to end stage of product. Encompassing everything (...) it should be in- built in [the] company’s processes. Because not only it saves up on the resources which benefits the businesses but saves environment also. So, it is everything I guess, it is an environmental model and should be built into a business model [considering company’s] turnover things like that. So,

there is a lot of money to be saved with it and benefits nature as well. So, I think, [it] should be both general economy nature, environmental as well as businesses [model]”. (VS)

And a research and development manager in packaging says:

“I will take is an economy strategy, obviously where few manufacturers, one of the large manufacturers in the UK, are taking it massive seriously. As I joined the company about five years ago, and we are working ever since and trying to climb all three of those things [economic, environmental and sustainability]. It has been fully adopted by the leadership team in terms of something that we need to address. Start the wider business is implemented, a programme called there “Beyond the Horizon” and which is a total sustainability strategy. However, within foods, whereby we put products in the front of consumer, we have developed strategy. But it is embedded totally within the business now. It is regarded as one of the key success points for the future going forward now. It is built into the environmental strategy; it is built into the sustainability strategy it’s done from an environmental perspective. So [in] that way (...) it has been brought out around genuinely doing the right things rather than performing any sort of greenwashing type activities whereby we trick the consumer level. I think all the work that we do is [science and data based] and we do the analysis. This is based on trying to fundamentally find out what is the best packaging solution for example, we put in the market to reduce the impact as much as possibly we can.” (NR)

In addition to that, a manager from a retail organisation came up with the view that it works as marketing strategy for the companies, saying that:

“From the company’s point view, it’s like gaining the credibility from the customer [s] like [the company is] responsible. Because if they will follow this strategy, then consumer will think that the company is responsible as they are concerned about the environment and reducing carbon footprints and all.” (KD)

A “closing the loops” approach is attainable to various extents on different levels of the food supply chain. Food matter, reusing and utilisation of food is possible to achieve partially, and appropriate measures are needed on all the stages (Jurgilevich, 2016). However, on the flip side the following comments from stakeholders share the opposite views:

“The idea of the circular economy to have nil wastage in food, will not work. It will never work. You can try to reduce it, you can try to minimize it, but it will not come to a stage, you can say that this product will not have wastes”. (AK)

Similarly, from the retailers’ perspective zero waste vision is an aspiration because

“Zero waste, OK I don’t think because there is no movement if [there is] zero. I don’t think you are going to get zero but I’m not sure. I think there are probably certain supply chains you might I think, you probably can play with certain product types (....). We have to be able to get to zero food waste (....) [and that] we have a moral obligation (.....). Something like food waste (....) I think you have to be able to know whether that’s going to charity as an exit and not to landfill we have to be able to do everything. Are you going to cut plastic out completely? No, but again was it a type of plastic to be able to recycle”. (HM)

echoes with the statement of a retailing manager who states that:

“As an environmentally friendly person, I would want it to be achievable. (.....), but right now, I don’t think it is possible immediately. Because the companies do not have enough resources, they don’t have a clear vision as of now, where they want to go with that? So yes, they are trying to reduce the waste as much as much as they can. But there [are] a lot of barriers to the circular economy”. (PG)

Similarly, from the packaging perspective, the research and development manager in packaging adds that the circular economy in their department is certainly achievable as they are focussing on creating infrastructure and collaboration with world’s major manufactures.

“Within certain application, it will certainly be achievable. From packaging perspective, creating a circular economy, probably one of the biggest agenda we have for next five years. Addressing back, we try to create an infrastructure (....), whereby all of the leading companies across the world are going to try and tackle how we can create a circular economy for packaging consumption from the packaging perspective I think that there is a lot of effort behind it now.

Potentially, there is a future for it, big companies are working on it. But when you look at products and food might still in linear but yes, from packaging perspective it is effective (NR)”

The quotations confirm the views of various circular economy authors who say that the circular economy usually involves a rounded approach in a company’s business model or demands to create a new business model (Bocken et al., 2016 and Manninen et al., 2018). Correspondingly, Lewandowski (2016) also recommends industries to have a new vision and strategies supporting long-life solutions and reconceptualization of product concepts, service offering and networks.

4.3 BARRIERS TO CIRCULAR SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT

Qualitative research aims to probe the depth of issue rather than breadth. This section divulges the outcomes of qualitative data by yielding the themes and sub-themes through literature review and thematic analysis. Figure 4.1 presents six main themes of the factors that impact circular supply chain management, 21 subcategories that share the same features as those themes, classified under those six themes and including the drivers. All these components are discussed in this thesis. For instance, barriers and drivers related to finance were discussed by researchers (De Jesus and Mendonça, 2017; Bresanelli et al., 2018 ; Farooque et al., 2019), technical aspects were identified in (Borrello et al., 2015; France, 2019; Hart et al., 2019), management were recognised by literature (Geng and Doberstein, 2008; Nasir et al., 2017; Rizos et al., 2018), socio- culture was explored in the studies of (Geng et al., 2009; Hart et al., 2019;), structural context was uncovered by (Adams et al., 2017; Pomponi and Mocanter, 2018; Prashar; 2021) and regulatory and institutional sides were examined in the research of (Rizos et al., 2015; Govindan et al., 2016; Ranta et al., 2017). How each stage of the supply chain is affected by these barriers is also the result of discission with participants. All the participants stressed the necessity of transforming towards the circular economy by overcoming the related issues. With the connection of literature review (Chapter 2), interviewees highlighted the inevitability of shift towards circular supply chain and established that it has not been applied in the industries completely and how can it be ameliorated by making the changes by various stakeholders.

Figure: 4.2 Graphical representation of themes and sub-themes (Barriers)

Source: NVivo 12 Mind map

Following section demonstrate the factors which are a hindrance to implement the circular approach in food supply chains.

4.3.1 Technical barriers

New techniques and technology are the major factor for any transition to become successful. Innovations are always encouraged by the organisations to get the competitive advantage. The key factors to lead towards the circular economy approaches are science and technology (Geng and

Doberstein, 2010; Kaushik et al., 2014; Ritzéna and Sandströma, 2017; Mangla et al.2018, Farooqe et al., 2019; Tura et al., 2019). According to Preston, (2012, p10) “the [CE] opportunities are huge if technical barriers could be overcome.” The major technical challenges for circular supply chain management are, to incorporate it with existing food supply chains, limited technologies and lack of technical skills etc. (Shi et al., 2008; Geng and Doberstein, 2008). Supported by stakeholders of the food supply chain stakeholders

“It is the very spear target yea it should be a spear target; I wouldn’t say it is achievable in the current environment but may be in the future if the right technology, right invention, a new process, the future looks good but the zero waste is an aspiration to it.” (BK)

Participants comments are also consistent with these factors, to bring the circularity in the food supply chains, there are numerous types of technical and technological barriers which become hindrance for organizations to accept it. Some are exclusive to the food industry; however, other are applicable to different industries. The core technical factor mentioned by stakeholders is Shelf-life of finished products and raw material.

Shelf-Life

In the food industry the connection between shelf-life and sustainability is very complex. A great degree of food is wasted due to biological properties (Amani and Gadde, 2015 and Guillard et al., 2018). Economic, environmental, and social characteristics of food supply chains are highly affected by the perishability factor, yet it is not considered as an important strategic decision of the organisations (Esteso et al., 2021). Limited shelf life is the reason of almost 50% of food waste during the supply chains (Blanke, 2014; De Laurentiis et al., 2018; Ciccullo et al., 2021). With regards to the food waste and loss, “shelf-life” has been mentioned by various stakeholders of the food supply chain as a contributing factor. For instance, “I think shelf-life is one of the key things in food industry”, “we keep looking into the techniques, how we kind of can increase the shelf-life of the food products”. The findings are consistent with the researchers (Hebrok and Heidenstron, 2019; Canto et al., 2021). The following quotes reflect the idea:

“So, I don’t know, with short shelf -life product, how that would work. I totally see [this working] with something like bread waste or Pasta waste (....). When you get into the term short shelf-life into protein, you would have to be able to prove. Like that particular product came from this

company for example where that company got the chicken from, the rice and the spices come from. Because there is food safety element to it. So, without technology (...), I don't think that can [be] used from human consumption unless that is vegetarian that can be used for animal feed" (DE). "In the food wastage it very-very difficult to position until or unless, you have product which has got a long life that sort [of] things. Yes, you can hold it, um... the business we are in, we are called a business of short shelf-life." (AK)

Additionally, participants state that having more shelf life on the products can increase the opportunity of reusing, reducing and regenerating capabilities of food products which are aligned with 3 basic principles of the circular economy proposed by McDonough and Braungart (2013).

"[The] key for sustainability is all down to life of product, the more life you can give [to] the product, less waste you will generate. Because the other problem you have got from commercial is, we produce a product have 10 days lives and retailer wants at least 7 days when it gets in there. So, I can have product which then can have lack of sales, it still got 6 days life because it doesn't fit with retailers, they won't take it. If the same product had 14 days, then I got 4 days to sell off, it would naturally go down to [the] waste. That's where technology comes in (...) to drives down the waste. If you give me more life of product then I will have more chance of selling it." (RJ)

"At the time of trials, I need to talk to the buying team that for first trials I only need [limited quantity of raw material], get me [less quantity only] and pay more. Because the 2nd trial is going to happen in 1 months' time and short shelf-life products are not going to last for 1 month. And I am not using that in any other product so it's going to go in waste." (SKV)

Hence, one of the fundamental factors which hinder the circular supply chain implementations in food industry is shelf life of the product. Until there are not any techniques introduced in the food supply chain which can increase the shelf life with minimal side effects or techniques by which product can be utilised to the maximum in its life.

Lack of the circular economy specific technologies

The findings from this study also emphasise looking into the circular economy specific technologies. It can be in terms of adding value to waste by-product durability, using by-products as input, waste reduction and management, energy production, product take-back system

machinery, increasing shelf life and equipment renting, and repair or information and communication technologies (Preston, 2012; Vanner et al., 2014; Shabazi et al., 2016; Pfeifer., 2017; de Jesus and Mendonça, 2018, p81; Kirchherr et al., 2018; Lopes de Sousa Jabbour et al., 2019; Franco, 2019; Hull et al., 2021).

Participants from all the stages of the food supply chain stated the need of innovations and technologies by which organisations and environment can both benefit. A demand-planning manager specifically mentioned the type of technologies required for the circular economy transition by saying “technology has to be sustainable first”. Following comments from other participants share the same idea.

“I think it is more to do with innovation from my department, like I said, you know, we need more development, need product research [and] how we can stop the waste. Obviously, we have to make things and maintain food safety, that’s the key. Like I said, it is innovation, people need to think out of box, different ideas.” (BR)

“So, technique or technology, if can help in that thing that we can get the product life increased and not affecting taste and texture. Because end consumer needs the product for human consumption and that there has to be taste, texture and likeness of the product”. (PK)

Also, a manager from a retailing company and manufacturing company consequently urges to introduce technologies to increase transparency between supply chain stages of retailing and consumption for maximum utilisation of food products stock and transparency of information on benefits using sustainable products and to extend the life of products or reuseable techniques.

“I suppose you could have some technology around people having visibility, But I think, it’s really difficult.” (HM)

“I have ordered the product based on sales and forecast. Sales have come in half. For argument’s sake customer says, they want 100 tons of chicken, so I have ordered my 100 tons of chicken and sales comes in half, 50 tons. If the customer doesn’t order what they asked for then I have got chicken which is out of date. [we] can’t extend the life span of it. (...), I cannot utilize the chicken past the expiry date. Even if the order comes on next day or I think of doing upcycling or generate any further product, I am not in position to use that chicken as [it] no longer valid to use.” (JR)

The above comments from managers of manufacturing companies highlight that the food production system still lags behind in the technologies to increase the product life or utilize the food product waste in useful ways having a health and safety aspect.

Lack of Knowledge, Skills and Expertise

Knowledge and technical skills are very significant factors, moving towards the new transition in any organisations (de Jesus and Mendonça, 2018). “(...) what determines the “possibility” of reuse for a material is the extent of knowledge that has led to technological innovation for reuse.” (Park and Chertow, 2014, p. 47). Yet, knowledge, skills and technical expertise specific to the circular economy transition are deficits in the existing industrial system. The factors have been given importance by academics (Ritzéna and Sandström, 2017; de Jesus and Mendonça, 2018; Hart et al., 2019; Mendoza, 2019; Hull et al., 2021) as well as in grey literature (EMF, 2012, 2013, 2015a).

The following comments from interviewees also support the argument:

“I think the biggest one at the moment that exists is around clarification of one of these is actually, what we are trying to achieve. At the moment, all the big business are on the way to work on their own agenda trying to make sure they are appearing to be, green as possible to consumers. Not actually doing what is genuinely right. Like for example, I’ve just completed a study of plastic trays that we use. The board tray and actually a plastic tray comes out on top on 17 environmental and the circular economy matrices. From all 17 matrix, it comes out on top, but we still got a perception the consumers hold plastic and board is right”. (NR)

A stakeholder from a packaging department shares his experience that the circular economy being one of the main agenda of today’s businesses, people do not have the right knowledge to follow the right procedures.

“They just don’t have the skills or the time or mainly “The Know” that how to do it. how to work out [on] this own, what it would look like, how it needs to be.” (EGD)

“I think it’s just people have to be more creative and think out of the box. What we can do and how we can reduce the waste and different ways to deal with” (BR)

Similar to (Bechtel et al., 2013; Shahbazi et al., 2016) and the above quotations there is a lack of information about what and how the circularity can be achieved in food industries i.e., implications on what are the techniques, how products can be upcycled etc. The below quotation on the upcycling stage of stakeholder emphasises the requirement of highly skilled workers and knowledge for machinery repair and refurbishment.

“Umm obviously we are here totally maintaining the used equipment’s, we have to sort the parts and [the] engineer must know how to fix the machines so as that’s the technology.” (AF)

Additionally, from the consumer perspective, consumers do not have knowledge about the procedures to follow to achieve the zero-waste target. The general public has inadequate knowledge about the practices to adopt for the achievement of circularity.

“There are a lot of channels or ways to make everyone aware but the information about how we can achieve the circular economy is limited, specially at consumer level” (RM)

As per the following quotation from the participant to implement it as the business model it is significant to have technical skills and experts to practice:

“Like I say if I don’t necessary have the time or the knowledge. Without (...) having experts in these areas I would not have plans to do that. (... ..) do you know the phrase Jack-able phrase. I have to understand a little bit about 100s of areas. But I don’t have the specialist knowledge to work further and deeper in the circular supply chain. I will facilitate the conversation, but I would need an expert” (MC)

Hence, in the above examples it is evidently recognised that at present knowledge and skill are major blockers to initiate the circular economy revolution. Ritzéna and Sandström, (2017) remark that understanding and the level of knowledge about the circular economy is very limited in the industries which is an obstacle towards its happening. A participant remarks, similarly, “So that is another reason for failure and lack of knowledge and lack of knowledge how to implement it.”

Orders and forecasting inaccuracy

Another technical factor for the food supply chain that emerged during this research is fluctuation in forecasting and inaccuracy in orders. These factors prevent the supply chain actors, mainly manufacturers and retailers, to control the huge amount of processed waste as well as waste ingredients. So, to have a more efficient demand-forecasting system is necessary for industries. In the following, a supply chain head of a retailing organisation shares its views:

“For retailer I supposed, to have [a] system [that] demands correctly, [Because] right at the back end there isn’t really much we can do from a system. [if] you have ordered the wrong amount and it sat in stores (...). So, creating a better demand, put the right amount of stock on the shelf, in the first place, rather wasting it on the later stage.” (HM)

Similarly, the following comments show the concern from a manufacturing perspective:

“(...) We have to be so far ahead with our orders before they come through you know you could end up with so much [extra] rice that you don’t need, you don’t have orders for that. You have to play a gamble, is like you are in casino, you have to play gamble with how the orders were coming (...) obviously you can give it to charity. But still it is cost to the business because you [have] paid for the ingredients, you [have] paid for to cook it and paid for to pack it and you are not getting anything for it.” (EGD)

In the above comment a planning manager from a manufacturing organisation explains how the current system of orders and forecasting followed by retailers does to fit with the circular economy model and prevents manufacturers to adopt it. Similar, a quotation by a chef manager echoes the above views.

“For example, for day after tomorrow, I need to cook today. But here the issue comes, the retailer[s] [keep] changing their forecast to final very frequently. Because from last 10 years of data they thought they will sell 500 but they couldn’t because this year situation was different. However, I [have] order[ed] my ingredient according to your forecast, your estimates but right now I am being penalised because you are not buying it. So, that is where we should challenge the retailers.” (SKV)

“With all the goodwill in the world, with all the forecasting systems, all the retailers as well as our forecast systems. There is always a gap between where you end up having X amount of wastage and that [cannot be utilised in production]. That is not in system.” (AK)

To summarise, the above quotations show that for a perishable goods industry like food, how it is important to have an efficient demand-forecasting system in place for optimum utilisation of products and raw material. Although it has not been explored much in circular supply chain management literature, demand forecasting is a vital factor for industries to implement these types of proactive strategies (Nowak et al., 2018, p.127). It is one of the main issues faced by food supply chains to bring sustainability (Ravi and Shankar, 2004; Vijayan; 2014).

Table 4.1: Technical barriers

Nodes (sub- themes related to technical barriers)	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Nodes\\Challenges in the circular economy\\Barriers to CSCM\\Technical Barriers\\CE Specific technologies	8	8	7	7
Nodes\\challenges in the circular economy\\Barriers to CSCM\\Technical Barriers\\Knowledge, skill and expertise	19	19	13	13
Nodes\\challenges in the circular economy\\Barriers to CSCM\\Technical Barriers\\Order and forecasting	11	11	8	8
Nodes\\challenges in the circular economy\\Barriers to CSCM\\Technical Barriers\\Shelf Life	14	14	10	10

Source: NVivo 12 Nodes comparison

4.3.2 Financial and economic barriers

Financial and economic factors have been extensively cited in studies for bringing circularity and sustainability in supply chain systems. Sillanpää and Ncibi (2019) discuss the planning and implementation of circular economy practices as “Stakeholders who can cope with the financial burden of the slow and often costly implementation process of sustainable production units using renewables, until becoming profitable. (.....) For obvious reasons, such bold and costly strategy could be adopted and implemented by big companies, either genuinely committed to the circular economy principles, or partly (....).” Companies are very much concerned about revenue generation strategies and return on investment and uncertainty about these factors makes companies reluctant to take sustainable decisions (Ravi and Shankar, 2004; Ritzéna and

Sandströma, 2017; de Jesus and Mendonça, 2018). Finance and economic related barriers are predominantly discussed by interviewees in various standpoints like “Financially, it is very painful”, “Absolutely, that’s what it is at the end of the day that how business can make the money”, “I wouldn’t say that it can’t be done but finance side would be a real struggle to have that happen.” Following are the various finance related aspects to prevent the application of a circular model in the food supply chain:

Profitability

Profitability is a vital aspect to bring any types of changes in the organisations and because ecological or sustainability initiatives are thought to be less attuned with the “raison d’être” of businesses (Ramus and Steter, 2000), industries find it critical to adopt them (Pagell, 2009; Gattiker et al., 2014; Ünal et al., 2018). Similarly, the below comment from a retailing manager explains the expected vision of circular supply chain transition in the food industry.

“[There] also has to be a kind of profit lens with it. Because you know, you have to make strict note in the current climate that our margins are so small, in the food industry in particular. You have to have a commercial advantage for doing anything. I am sure you can just do things because they’re nice to do, nothing wrong (....). But it has to be commercial”. (HM)

Relatedly Lieder and Rashid, (2016) and the director of an upcycling company raises the concern that even being an upcycling business are focussed on ecological gains, but financial gains are fundamental for them.

“So, if you have business falling of these categorise like our one where obviously number one priority is to make profit but also like to do best to help the environment so it involves [s] two phases. It needs to be beneficial to the business otherwise, it’s not gonna happen, isn’t, isn’t it?” (AF)

A manufacturing manager also raised the concern that the profit margin in the food industry is very low and considering the related cost manufacturing of circular or remanufactured product would not generate profit for manufactures as the new products or linear processes do.

“So, food you know we deal with pence’s you know it’s a pound or pence or whatever it is so you are getting massive amounts for meal. So, your possibly profit margin is again in pence not pounds.” (BR)

The research and development manager from a new product development department of a manufacturing company describes his concern in a distinct way that cannibalisation is a fear in the market which prevents accepting the circularity of products, coherent with Mont (2008); Bressanelli et al. (2018), Frei et al. (2020). The following quotation describes:

“Ummm.... Finance side, I will definitely see, I mean, if you start reducing waste out, obviously finance should be an element that needs to workout upon, to be very honest. But the challenge, I would see from finance side, will be that it will be hampering the sales of [original] products as well. We will be giving more options to the people, then obviously, when we are convincing more on the [upcycled or sustainable product] side then it will a big challenge to be very honest. So, finance will be the biggest challenge.” (VS)

It was echoed by another stakeholders as:

“If things need investment, it needs return if that return is low, then it becomes difficult. even if it is for very very-very good cause. That becomes a pilot. (.....), there would be financial barriers and people need seeing the asset that will be required is worth the umm ... worth the output book.” (DE)

Therefore, circular supply chain model seems to be less feasible along with the profit-oriented approach of businesses. The quotations are correspondence with the circular economy authors Sehnem et al., (2019); Guner (2018).

High cost of products and raw material

In the previous section consideration of financial gain has been discussed. Cost is an aspect that puts high impact on the profitability of the corporations. The circular economy solutions can be expensive alternatives for stakeholders (Andrew, 2015; Li et al., 2015; Foroudi and Palazzo,2021). This factor is a hurdle for most of the stakeholders as reflected in the following:

“It does [affect]. Difference in price, if people have got a lot of money, then they will go for it but if they haven’t! Organic is good example. Lots of organic curries carries different price tag[s] (...). You won’t sell as much as organic material because of price point. I think price is the king” (RJ)

“Nowadays, I see a lot of bamboo containers in my shop, people [should] use bamboo product instead of plastic, so Bamboo is a product, it can be reused again and again. the biggest barrier in those products is the price.” (PG)

In the previous comments, a national account manager and a floor manager raise the concern of high price of sustainable products which is neither acceptable for sellers nor buyers. The time gap between cost and revenue flow, while moving towards service selling from product ownership companies have to finance the capital cost of the solutions since revenue flow get delayed (Barquet et al., 2013).

“Giving the example of [name of a cost-effective store] that everyone wants to be ethical until they see the price. So here [is] the challenge, how the businesses are or how the businesses turn this into PR and selling point. So, let’s the retailers or the supply chains make it the same price which is a big-big question. If you can’t make it the same price you’re always going to come behind. Obviously, a lot of people who can but people who cannot be able to choose in the current climate in the current challenges as we are going towards biggest recession we’ve ever had probably.” (HM)

Unluckily, corporations in Western countries hold the attitude of “Disposing is cheaper than using or re-using” (F.A.O., 2011). A related comment was made by a managing director of a medium level food processing company:

“If you talk people like us, we don’t have time, we can’t do it, we have to put it in the normal waste. If gonna do it, then we will have to employ more people, will be costly, to segregate it and manage it” (YB)

And a business development manager from an anaerobic digestion plant shares his experience that it is challenging for recycling companies to get the business due to the unwillingness of manufacturers to pay for sorting their waste.

“We frequently get the customers move away because of the price” (MP)

Consequently, circular economy solutions are expensive for stakeholders, whether it is from the cost point of view of virgin material that companies have to bear (Shahbazi et. al., 2016) or the price of sustainable products that the consumer has to pay for (Lieder and Rashid, 2016).

Minimum Order Quantities

To cover the high set up cost and other overheads firms use economies of scale and minimum order quantities approaches during the supply chain (Porras and Dekker, 2006). The circular economy approach is a combination of reduce, reuse, recycle, recover, redesign, and remanufacture activities (Yuan, Bi, and Moriguchi 2006; Kim and Goyal 2011; Govindan et al., 2016; Lu et al., 2012; Ying et al., 2012; Dowlatshahi 2005; Wu et al., 2016; Diaz and Marsillac 2017), Though, reduce being the foremost and initial factor, is not taken seriously by food supply chains actors. Minimum order quantity is a standard method applied by suppliers or retailers to sell their product in greater quantities, which also becomes cost effective for buyers but becomes unsustainable by wasting the unrequired material. The fact has not been studied specifically in the existing studies of circular supply chain management as a challenge. However, it has been referred to significantly by supply chain stakeholders during this research.

“Then buying team and all group[s] merge to decide if I need to buy a sour cream, what is your MLOR, (minimum life of receipt) and what is the quantities you can supply. The supplier would say I can only supply 500 kg pack. I can’t use 500 kg because this is a new product and the demand for new product is less and I would only be using 200 kg per week. But the supplier says I have only 500kg packs or 20kg packs. But 500kg packs are a lot cheaper. Then finance thing comes in and say we should go for 500kg packs which only cost us for example £1 kg. But practically this not the true picture, when it comes to manufacturing, I will be wasting 300 kgs because my requirement is only 200kg so 300 kg is actually going to the bin and that is creating hustle in the landfill. At the same time, we are losing our revenue.” (SKV)

“As customers we all like to have deals because we can buy more in less price and without realising the real requirement of buying the fruits, vegetables pre-packeted, other multi-buy like eg. £1 can get you 1Kg Potatoes, most of it goes unused and as soon as roots start to grow on them, we make it part of waste.” (RM)

In the above quotation, a consumer also highlighted that because of the minimum order quantities approach of retailers, consumers are bound to buy extra quantities of food which ultimately leads to abundance of food waste.

Supported by the next comment by an operations project manager.

“I mean, it starts right from the day, the day we actually get the brief from the customer that this is what they want and of course you know that they want to save money, they will never give you the true figures. If the figures are inflated right from the beginning, just to save money and cheaper price. If you go and say that I need 100 articles. Of course, the price for 100 articles will be different [than] 1 product. So, that is there, I think the majority of the issue lies.” (NB)

Implementation of the circular economy model is subject to the environmental and economic benefits associated with it (Geng et al., 2009). Thus, while getting the financial / cost benefits from current practices, companies are averse to adopting the circular model throughout the supply chain.

Investment

Furthermore, it is propounded that environmental investment (Geng et al., 2009; Mittal and Sangwan, 2014; Shehbazi et al., 2016; Farooque et al., 2019) and risk associated with investment is a negation for existing businesses and new investors. Investment for research and development and to update the technology and infrastructure are considered an additional cost (Pan et al., 2015; Hart et al., 2019) and is a challenge for companies operating in the current linear environment.

“I am working on a project on the packaging, that is, it is very new concept. It is fully biodegradable. (.....) Though, [the packaging manufacturer] are not new to packaging industry but they are very new to this idea. I mean, it is so expensive at the moment but understandable because they are investing in new technology, everything is going to be new for them and they don't know how the market is going to behave. it is really expensive, but somebody has to bite the bullet to start with. (.....) I mean we have all those things technology is there, but it is who can actually invest in that technology and then keeping up with it is another challenge. I mean, if you have invested in something which is, which is new to the business new to world now, in the year

to come that's gonna be old. [There] will be something new on fast pace and keeping with it, I think the biggest challenge.” (NB)

In the above remark a project manager, who is working on fully bio-degradable packaging describes that investing in the circular economy supportive technologies is an extra cost for institutions and maintaining it for the long-run is a surplus cost. Similarly, following a director of a recycling plant, a manager from retailing and an upcycling company reflects in their comments that investment is a big question for start-ups looking at the infrastructure requirement, current business trends and awareness.

“I don't think many can start up on their own anymore. I think [only] big national companies that will be the leaders in recycling. Not all the companies, because of the cost of the insurance, cost of infrastructures and technologies, cost of the adds. When I did my business, before the regulation came in. you got to get drainage [from government], you will need all the facilities in place [now by yourself]. You need [to] look couple of million pounds now to start up.” (AB)

“Like doing research and doing something new will be a risk from investors part as well. People may be reluctant to try something new in the beginning so that will be barrier as well. So, investment will be a barrier from financial point of view.” (KD)

“It [will be] bigger operation site, you might need bigger premises, you might need bigger workshop, bigger warehouse, an extra desk in the office and will more investment have needed on the machines. (.....) which I heard from many people that many big companies started to do, didn't work out very well.” (AF)

The idea of the circular economy is not considerably recognised in the industries and due to the risk associated on investment, the high cost of infrastructure and less returns on investment in the short term become the obstacle for the investors to take this initiative. As per Table 5.2, the high cost of the product and the raw material factor was mostly discussed by the stakeholder which prevent them to adopt a circular approach.

Table: 4.2: Financial barriers

Nodes (Sub- themes relate to financial barriers)	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Nodes\Challenges in the circular economy\Barriers to CSCM\Financial and economical\High cost of products and raw material (2)	26	26	14	14
Nodes\Challenges in the circular economy\Barriers to CSCM\Financial and economical\Investment	14	14	11	11
Nodes\Challenges in the circular economy\Barriers to CSCM\Financial and economical\Minimum order quantity	6	6	5	5
Nodes\Challenges in the circular economy\Barriers to CSCM\Financial and economical\Profitability	21	21	14	14

Source: NVivo 12 nodes comparison

4.3.3 Planning and management related barriers

Positioning the resources along with their objectives is a significant role of management (Ünal et al., 2019). In this study, management barriers are related to the deficiency of the supply chain actors to align the resources and procedures or actions with the circular economy model. These actions can be marketing activities, competition or management’s own actions for commitment. Management related barriers are substantially addressed in existing literature by Zhu and Geng, (2013), Mangla et al. (2018), Govindan and Hasanagic (2018), and Ünal et al. (2019). Circular supply chain management practices aim to design the scenario that ensures the optimum utility of resources (through reuse, repair, recycle and remanufacture). Inappropriate planning and management in all these processes may mislead the practices (Geng and Deberstein, 2008; Nasir et al., 2017). Three types of management related barriers for the circular food supply chain are below, out of which the “lack of management commitment” factor was frequently discussed.

Lack of management commitment

Stakeholders need management’s complete support and dedication to employ the circular supply chain management model, which seems to be missing in the current industrial system (Mangla et al., 2019). Lacking management seriousness and support limits the development of dynamic capabilities to take revolutionary decisions like the circular supply chain (Farooq et al., 2019). This factor leads to the absence of interest to apply the circular economy within the organisation’s

strategies and policies (Govindan and Hasanagic, 2018). The following views from participants co-relate with this indication:

“There is partial blame on management side as well that how they deal with the situations, or they are more about money making business by achieving the targets or achieving the goals.” (VS)

“Companies do the talk about carbon footprint and all these things, but to be honest nobody is working towards it. I mean they are, but whatever they’re doing is not enough.” (PG)

In a quotation, an interviewee shares the experience where upper management seemed to be reluctant about a waste management initiative taken by an operations manager.

“The company, I used to work before, I reduced [X amount] of waste in a year. All I did was to put the money we are losing and (...) showing them that this is the amount we are throwing a week. They asked not to escalate people’s thought process of employees.” (BK)

On the other hand, some quotations from participants show that they do not consider “management” as a rigid factor for the UK food industry. Management is obliged to follow what is regulated by the government and the loopholes are on the regulatory side.

“Company management in this country (UK), I don’t think it is [an] obstacle. Here, rules are strict, management itself is obliged to follow whatever is given by government. Yes, if you talk about developing countries like (...), yes, it’s gonna be an issue there. Rules are in place there as well, but nobody follows it.” (YB)

“Management can easily be moved. I don’t think management is barriers. Management is not self-driven, they are driven by the business requirement, by the business operating model. (...). I think not the management but the legal and set standards, rules and clauses added over the years. (...). So, management is not the big issue. Bigg issue is all scenario when become the routine life and people start going by that like you cannot do this you can only do this.” (PK)

Hence, leadership and management are vital aspects to consider bringing circularity into practice of food supply chains to motivate the other stakeholders (Kumar et al., 2018; Jabbour et al., 2019;

Moktadir et al., 2020) yet driven by countries' rules and regulation. There is a need of combined effort for the circular economy shifts.

Inappropriate marketing strategies

The circular economy provides us with effective solutions like upcycling to reduce the food waste, but marketing strategies are not in place for those products to reach to the consumer's expectations (Zhung et al., 2020) or to make them aware of them. A manufacturing manager from food manufacturing adds this:

“You have the key and you have right way of marketing through, then yes, the product will be successful. If you don't market right, it through to right consumers, you don't market it to whoever it will be sold to or you are generating it very extensive way, not generating enough revenue to sustain yourselves then it will not be successful.” (BR)

The circular economy demands to ascertain market-based initiatives (Mangla et al., 2018). However, in the current supply chain the policies are more profit driven (Pagell, 2009; Gattiker et al., 2014) and leads to unsustainable practices followed by the supply chain actors. Project managers explain in the following quotation:

“I have seen many times food restaurants and shops giving marketing deal like buy one get one free. People only eat one and second one is dumped; they just bin it. So why to work on [these] deal, why can't they simply give discount. It saves their gas, electricity, save on dough whatever, that all can be saved. Of course, it is the people are in business are responsible for these strategies.” (NB)

A quotation floor manager from retailing also highlights the point:

“My store is doing a mistake with marketing strategies they are adopting like farmer's milk. Straightway, like you know you keep one flat price and why not just give the money direct into that farmer without advertising it. Because they want to advertise it, there's so much of wastage, just for their advertisement. There is no scope for the circular economy or sustainability in this sort of environment.” (PG)

The circular economy connected supply chains required a proactive marketing approach to influence the minds of customers to adopt circular products or services. And at the same time, it needs a close analysis and control over existing marketing strategies to reduce the waste and regenerate or recycle the products.

Competition

The economy cannot flourish in circular systems because the current market is more competition oriented rather than efficiency based (Ghisellini et al., 2016). Competition is a well discussed factor in supply chain management and circular economy literature for being an obstacle for the effectiveness of sustainability (Flynn et al., 2010; Min et al., 2005 Gupta et al., 2018). Business model innovations are also organised by taking competition as a basis, not environmental sustainability, thus it is difficult in the competitive world to survive with a circular system. A participant from the consumer phase depicts “Retailer are creating so much of waste in the shed of competition”. The below mentioned quotes from participants explore how competition leads supply chains towards more linear practices. A manager from a retailing company shares his understanding that for retailers to compete, companies like Amazon need more and more flexible policies for customers by ignoring the environmental impact.

“The competition is one of the biggest. I would say the competition between the retailers. The biggest barriers in reducing any kind of waste like you have a giant like Amazon entering. So, Because Amazon is entering retail sector, an Amazon is a big company, and these retailer like Asda, Morrison’s or Tesco, although they are big, but they’re not big enough like Amazon, Amazon. Yeah, at the moment. Only the only, the only way they can fight Amazon is by latterly by becoming flexible. If they are 100% flexible now, they have to be 200 percent flexible with the customer in order to compete with Amazon even you shop online, add shop on Amazon as well. there are no questions asked over there. If you don’t like it, get the money back. If you don’t want it, you can just send it back even your shipping is free. So, in order to fight Amazon, the retailers are definitely going to be more than what they are right now. If they are going to be more flexible which means food waste is going to be more, increasing overall wastage.” (PG)

This puts impact on the manufacturer as mentioned in the following comment and retailers expect manufacturers to be equally flexible by fluctuating their orders and forecasting leading to inappropriateness for not adopting the circular economy initiatives.

“However, when you look at the retailer’s model and the interest from retailer um, they want to make sure they are hitting the target annualising, reacting to market trends umm or responding the retailer’s market because its competitive market. So, it is very difficult for us to encourage them to narrow down the plan” (PJ)

In addition to the competitive pressure from retailers, manufacturers themselves need to be in competition for the growth of their business. They need to be adopting experimental processes that later become the reason of the huge amount of waste or overlooking sustainable perspectives.

“First thing I would say is to use your current resources, current ingredients. It will not be the case every time because we need to keep on growing. If don’t use new techniques, do innovations and experiments, we cannot compete in the business. If as a company use old styles and don’t want to explore, you are not going to be there in the future, because as business you need to grow” (SKV)

Hart et al., (2019) explore those competitive instincts playing an important role for business to implement circular supply chain policies. There is a discussion about top to bottom collaboration but horizontally still consider each other as competitors and prone to overlook the circular factor. Additionally, this transition requires alteration in marketing strategies by making them focussed on zero waste. Lastly, it also requires dedication from management to make the circular economy a strategic goal to achieve jointly (Giunipero et al., 2012).

Table: 4.3 Planning and Management barriers

Nodes (Sub- themes related to planning and management barriers)	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Nodes\Challenges in the circular economy\Barriers to CSCM\Planning and management\Competition	5	5	5	5
Nodes\Challenges in the circular economy\Barriers to CSCM\Planning and management\inappropriate marketing strategies	13	13	10	10
Nodes\Challenges in the circular economy\Barriers to CSCM\Planning and management\Lack of management commitment	17	17	12	12

4.3.4 Socio- cultural barriers

“Change is a double edge sword. (.....) When asked, how they feel about change, people often describe anxiety, fear, danger, loss and panic as well as excitement energy, exhilaration, risk taking and improvement” (Fullan, 2001). The circular economy is not an established model in industries as in societies (Ritzéna and Sandströma, 2017), which makes people reluctant to accept it intentionally or unintentionally. Whether it is organisations or the general public, there is very basic awareness about the circular economy practices (de Jesus and Mendonça, 2018), its need as well as its demand in the current scenario. Likewise, the other main challenges to apply circularity method at present are organisation culture, lack of interest and preference in the circular economy resolutions (Ravi and Shankar; 2004; Tura et al, 2019). Customer buying behaviour is an essential factor for implementation of the circular economy (Mostaghela and Chirumalla, 2020). Supported by authors Kumal and Malegeant (2006), Benton et al. (2015), Pan et al. (2015), Mangla et al. (2018), Hart et al. (2019), de Jesus and Mendonça, (2018), Farooqe et al. (2019), numerous cultural and social related barriers are discussed by the participants.

Lack of awareness and right information

Awareness is another prominent barrier that emerged during this research. Awareness about the circular economy is very minimal among the customers and industries (Sung et al., 2017; Mangla et al., 2018; Tura et al., 2019). For instance, four of the participants mentioned, “you are the first person talking with me about this thing”. A participant also emphasised availing of the right information.

“Other than that, there is an element of educating the people as well. For example, in [the] business[es] we have seen all supermarkets are throwing the plastic out and using more of cardboard packing. But nobody realises this fact that if we compare with the model of the circular economy, plastic packaging seems to be much better. Now people have those things in mind that its only plastic [which is] destroying the climate. There is need to educate the people, need to educate our retailers, tell them that the carbon footprints, which are getting the card [boards] are much more than plastic trays.” (VS)

Here in the above quotation the participant shed light on the fact that although businesses are moulding people about sustainability and consumers are following what companies present to them, the question is, is that the right information? Giving the example of plastic and cardboard trays, an interviewee described that information should be factual and should lead towards the right strategies.

“Awareness is the key point. People are not as aware as they should be and that is because we don’t message them hard enough. I mean, umm (...) there were a number of television programme that shows the conditions in which chicken eggs were produced. So, the condition in which the chicken eggs [were] produced, they were basically [kept] the cages, gel on their eyes and hazards and it shocked a common people, because in their heads they thought it comes from the farm, picked [from] the ground and they are having a lovely life and the eggs are collected and I don’t think people [knew] totally the industrial methods we use [d] to take those eggs. Now, if you go into a supermarket, there is a clear sign on it, that whether that chicken is from free range or barn chicken or caged and if you look at the numbers on all the types, there has been a massive swing towards free range. Where previously, it was other way round. There was a tiny amount of [free range]. That’s how bringing the awareness in the population, the fact is Helmond’s and etc all moved, how long that would be 10 years ago 11 years ago to start free range in their products, lots of free-range eggs, onion[s] in their products, Waitrose free rage eggs onions on their products. That was massive shift and that came with the awareness. Activist and television programs came and started talking like did you know this is the way your eggs come from. People should be aware what is going into their bodies and then they can make their decision. Awareness plays a key factor, if people are more aware as a consequence as what they did then everybody will make different decisions.” (DE)

The above explanation from a head of supply chain of a food manufacturing company is coherent with the opinion of educating and emphasising raising awareness among the general public. Awareness is a critical aspect for the success of the circular supply chain model which is about playing with people’s mindset (Lieder and Rashid, 2016).

Organisation Culture

Daily and Huang (2001) stated that execution of environmentally friendly practice highly depends on embracing in organisational culture. Practices like circular supply chain management entail the transformation on each aspect for closing and narrowing the loops. Companies' traditional and rigid processes are major encounters emphasised by authors Xavier et al. (2017), Hart et al. (2019), Hartley et al. (2019), Mendoza et al. (2019), and Tura et al. (2019).

“Unfortunately, part of the game is, there is bigger picture over there we still stay with the same mentality to do the things in certain way. It will take a while to understand. For instance, if we cook the rice, we have to cook 400 kg rice, out of which we will use only 100 kg and 300 kg will go to the bin and the is purely for the factory trials. So, there is an element of educating the people, that 300 kg which you waste is a bigger picture not something very small thing. This is the example of only one trial. If I go with the numbers and calculate the numbers for all through, the numbers are far-far bigger.” (VS)

In the above comment a manager pointed out that employees in old organisations where certain ways and processes to perform the tasks have been going on for a long time, it will be an arduous task to do things in a circular way until it becomes an integral part of the company. The below comment from the floor manager from a retailing company states:

“I think the company should have and maintain high standards to implement the circular economy. There should have some set standards, what they want to achieve in sustainability. They have to make it a part of their culture, that's what I want to say.” (KD)

Hence, the circular economy will not be a positive change until adopted by the management as a corporate strategy and then policies are made on the basis on of it. The objectives need to be set on that basis and should be part of processes and everyday routine. the below comment from a manager is consistent with this:

“Again, as the culture of the people being a lot more aware they want to have brands that are more socially acceptable, don't they? And setting that culture can't be done overnight it takes time [to] create a culture. The same point on the management side, it has to be [not] just someone decides today and we going to be ethical company. You have to live and breathe it every day, you can't just write on a form and say that's our core values everybody. Everyone has to live and breathe it, because of which It takes time. very old well companies, a 120-year-old company has

legacy culture, they have to recognise and move with the time and that [will] take a bit longer maybe.” (HM)

Therefore, as the circular supply chain is a joint approach, combining stakeholders from numerous institutions which have different cultures, it is critical to perceive the circular approach taking everyone together in the current scenario.

Perception, attitude, and behaviour

Consumer perception has an imperative role to follow sustainability practices (Bovea et al., 2018). An empirical study conducted in China among 157 firms reveals that despite having the awareness about the circular economy, people’s actual behaviour in practice is still different due to cultural and contextual factors (Liu and Bai, 2014). These contextual factors can be regional or from the level of awareness. In regard to circular supply chain practice, these elements affect in two ways: firstly, is following the right processes to reduce waste, and secondly adoption of circular, regenerated, upcycled or recycled products. “I think it is what needs to change, people’s mindset”, an operations manager describes. “I think the most barriers that you would be gonna come across is you know humans at the end of the day”, a supply chain manager state

“Aa mm, I think consumer has big part to play in it, I am about it now, the desire of people, I mean you only have to see people buying absolute a shed of foods during Christmas for one day celebration. People are also key to it, they [should] only buy what is actually need[ed] which have potential impact on it” (RJ)

This is mentioned by a national account manager depicting consumers’ purchasing habits. Similarly, a manager from a retailing company describes how buying behaviour of consumers leads to a huge amount of waste indirectly when they pick up unwanted items and then leave from their shopping bag later in the wrong sections i.e., frozen food in non-freezer section.

“You see people, they pick up whatever they see. When they come on the till, they leave half of the shopping bag. That shopping has product that has been taken out from the fridge, maybe two and maybe an hour ago. So, by the time you reach [to]this, it’s waste” [PG]

“The first reaction was like “ewe” I don’t want to use these trays. [Later] they understood it is a mix of different base material[s]. So, I think there [are] some mental barriers about

recyclability or reusing the materials. But as we educate people more about it that how it is the need today and how the waste is destroying the planet. People are listening but slowly and gradually” (SR)

This experience is shared by a technical manager from the new product development department of a manufacturing company when they introduced recycled tray for their meals; consumers’ feedback was very negative seeing something different than they usually buy. So, consumer attitude become a challenge for other stakeholders to introduce upcycled products, accepting circular procedures.

Demographical factors

Relatedly, demographical factors i.e., buying power of consumer, are notable issues raised by the majority of the participants. In developed countries where things are easily available, the consumer does not think hard while buying extra items and wasting them. A consumer state:

“I could understand and relate to this concept to [name of a developing country] which is developing country with majority of population is middle class. Being from that country, it was understood that elder’s clothes will be passed over to youngsters etc. While growing up, I saw many shops like TV repair, fridge repairs and list goes up to repairing of slippers, utensils which made a consensus person towards natural resources. But with modern times, Repairing is almost obsolete as everything is easily available and not many professionals are interested in those tedious trade due to time consuming and many a time it is not successful and rewarding as to selling a brand equipment with less hassle.” (RM)

“Those countries which are not that developed for example India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Asian countries which are not that much developed yet. And still on development stage. They are very circular; I would say they are ahead then the developed countries. So, developed countries people although there have more resources to enjoy their lives and their lifestyle. But because of different reasons, I would say because there is poverty, so they don’t have that much money (...). Everyone is self-dependent and earning a good amount of money to live a good life. If he or she is working minimum hours. he got a good life. He can buy food. He can pay his or her expenses an all expenses. They can bear right. And sometimes even. I need only one kg of something and two KG on offer or something. It’s promoted by co. and I’m taking two days. I’ll do another kg which I

bought extra is going in bin state way. But still, we are buying it and people sometimes not bother. it is just one pound so don't worry about that. Yeah, so at one side is positive because I can bear my expenses and I'm living good life but on the other side flipside of the coin I would say I'm wasting, I do not value of that that one pound. Exactly, so the country, like the other side. If you see India, they are struggling for their basics. so they know the value of single rupee. So, when you will, you will try to buy even two cagey in place of one. You will try your 150% to use that another, because otherwise it will. It can affect massively on your budget whatever you were trying to do.” (JSS)

Table 4.4 Socio- Cultural barriers

Nodes (sub- themes related to socio-cultural barriers)	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Nodes\Challenges in the circular economy\Barriers to CSCM\Socio-Cultural Barriers\Demographic factors	10	10	7	7
Nodes\Challenges in the circular economy\Barriers to CSCM\Socio-Cultural Barriers\Lack of awareness	25	25	16	16
Nodes\Challenges in the circular economy\Barriers to CSCM\Socio-Cultural Barriers\Organisation Culture	16	16	12	12
Nodes\Challenges in the circular economy\Barriers to CSCM\Socio-Cultural Barriers\Perception and attitude	34	34	22	22

Source: NVivo 12 Nodes comparison

In the above examples participants strongly agree that consumers' perception and attitude make a huge impact to bring positive circular changes in today's system. It is an alarming factor for industries while taking initiatives of the circular economy. The factors have been explicitly discussed by de Jesus and Mendonça, (2018) as soft barriers and by Sung et al. (2017) as key support needed by entrepreneurs for upcycling businesses. However, how demographical factors of consumers, like purchasing power and their purchasing habits, can be a blocker for the attainment of the circular economy model has not been explored in existing studies.

4.3.5 Structural Barriers

There are blockages found in circular supply chain management studies related to the way it is formed and the relation between its actors from various stages. The need to introduce innovative technologies has been discussed by Rahman et al. (2019) in relation to the application of the green supply chain. Due to the unconventional nature of the circular supply chain model, there is an absence of appropriate hard and soft infrastructure. Correspondingly, the complexity of its processes is blockers (Gumley, 2014; Hart et al., 2019) which can further lead to less integration and less collaboration between its actors (Ritzen and Sandstrom, 2017; Pomponi and Mocanter, 2018). These challenges have been elaborated by participants in the interviews below.

Complexity in nature

The ideal model of circular supply chain management in the food industry is a combination of numerous organisations, processes and stakeholders which work together to close the loops on each phase. So, its highly dynamic nature and procedures are complicated to handle (Hopkinson et al., 2018; Estes et al., 2021). This has been discussed by authors Hart et al. (2018) in the circular economy studies in the context of different industries; barriers related to food circular supply chain management are explained by stakeholders as follows:

“I definitely think it is a very complex thing. It is about challenging your core ways of working. It is about challenging the social behaviour of staff. There will be many aspects where you need to educate the staff. It is not an easy thing, when you see implementing the circular economy.” (VS)

“I just think probably, manufacturer, we are manufacturing a lot of ways and are manufacturing for a number of years like that. We started bringing new material is more complex required procedure that [is] additional sort of complexity [and] can be sort of barrier at the production level.” (NR)

From the organisation perspective, complexities can be from fragmented supply chains, administration, or production processes (Rizons et al., 2016; Hart et al., 2019). It will be difficult to scrutinise the combination of supply chains from different nature of companies (i.e., retailing, manufacturing, recycling) together and apply the same model to achieve a common goal in the food industry. Explaining about the nature of food industry Indicating towards food industry a manager says, “this industry is more focussed, highly sophisticated, and complex”. So, applying a circular model seems a challenging task.

“Ummm, I think it needs to be as easy as possible, (.....) So may be the engagement. There [can be] something like a complex supply chain from another plant [join] together to your supply chain, is not stable. Then that would cause the problem.” (DE)

“Application! this is all the way seems complex. Start from people to the organisations to the industry, it’s very-very complex especially in food industries.” (JSS)

A consumer also escalates the fact stating that applications of the circular model led to complexities on all the stages. Combining the supply chains from different companies will give rise the intricacy. The findings from this research show that for positive application of the circular economy supply chains less interaction, miscommunication, non-corporation, complexity in functions and processes are the barriers. As the name suggests, circular supply chain management works as a loop so merging various processes as well as supply chains in a loop becomes complex to handle. Additionally, triggering the new systems of working and adding new processes will make the traditional processes more complicated.

Lack of collaboration between supply chain actors

The next structural type of barrier found during this research is less collaboration of different actors. The organisations are inter-reliant (Finkelstein, 1997). The food supply chain is a group of numerous processes like designing, manufacturing, packaging, labelling, retailing, procuring, etc., which are dependent on each other. In relation with circular supply chain management, where there is a demand to have extra layers of upcycling and recycling processes, it is almost impossible to do that arrangement in-house (Mangla et al., 2018). Hence, it becomes compulsory to involve more organisations and daring to make them follow the one mutual decision.

“Thinking from sustainability point of view, industry will come back in the way which you, “the supply chain” with retailer [have] to work together to sell the product[s] and I think that is the biggest thing.” (RJ)

The above quotation turned out to be supporting the view of Farooqe et al. (2019); it is a difficult task to make them work together on the same stream to follow the one goal whilst supporting each and everyone. Next, a project manager from manufacturing explains how their activities are

dependent on the retailers and their demand (lack of accurate demand/ forecasting has been discussed in section 4.4.1.4).

“We do work together to minimise the retailer’s waste and supply waste as well, but it is also currently, inherit in manufacturer and supply chain and retail. For manufacturer obviously the waste is inherited[ed] in batch sizes. With this constant risk, from the manufacturing side, we never gonna get support from retailer from that perspective, not in the current world, or certainly not. How they will support us without our pushing supply chains. We produce according to our efficiencies, and they take what [is] available on agreed week or whatever” (PJ)

A demand planner elaborates the issue of less support from retailers in the above quotation which leads to batches of wastage on their end. It happens again because of the mismatch of demand and forecasting issues. Following, a director from a recycling plant emphasizes the reason and importance of collaboration of manufacturers. While talking about the food packing aspect, he raises the fact that different types of plastic which are used by manufacturers become problematic for recyclers as the film used on the food trays is not recyclable plastic; similarly, the labels on recyclable bottles like cola bottles are made of oil-based plastic are not recyclable. He cites that there is need for collaboration of food and packaging manufacturing to decide to use one type of plastic.

“If these manufacturing companies have got clarity of right functions. They should not mix the plastic. (.....). Basically, for the food industry, they should use only one plastic. So, when they are recycling there is only one plastic to recycle not different plastics (....). So, until the manufacturers make it very simple or simplify it. It’s always gonna be a problem (.....). So, umm yea till all the big manufacturers come together and make the plastic simpler, not using oil-based plastic, there will always be a problem.” (AB)

Moreover, a chef manager and dispatch manager also say that lack of collaboration from various departments in one organisation can lead to the failure of the circular economy model. Hence, interaction between the department is highly demanded.

“So, [there is] need to see, why can’t you cook 2- or 3-days production in one go. Like for today and tomorrow, you cook together because it can be rotated for 4 days. Again, it’s not only cooking, but you also need to see the capacity of packing, cartooning and dispatch and so need smart way

of thinking considering every department. Like I can cook it but if packing can't pack it, it will go to the waste again. So, the end-to-end should be very clear.” (SKV)

“Because everybody is under pressure, raw material is under pressure, technical, planning, production but we are all linked that's how circular chain be working together and more we interact and integrate in that chain, it makes everyone's life easier. So basically, I just need to tell, what risk going on and be positive as well and what can we do together, lots of thing you can do, you need to have positive mind.” (AZ)

Circular supply chain management is a joint process merging various stakeholders and involves combined effort from within and the outer boundaries of organisations to scaling it up as a business model (Angelis et al., 2018). Hart et al. (2019) also highlighted that lack of collaboration between businesses is a commonly discussed barrier.

Lack of structure

To ensure the smooth flow of processes and material, structure plays an important part while applying the circular economy model (Silva et al., 2018). This aspect has been given a significant importance in sustainability and circular economy studies. The lack of structure factor has been expressed as numerous contexts in a profusion of studies i.e., Yuan et al., (2006); Xi (2011), Gomes et al. (2013), Geng et al. (2016), Govindan and Hasanagic (2018). During the interviews from supply chain stakeholders, it was divulged that the current supply chain lacks behind in soft as well as hard structure and can lead to collapse of circularity implementation. The following quotation from a national account manager expresses the importance of structure in the circular economy implementation:

“Structure is important because I need support to do this thing. Like I say if I don't necessarily have the time or the knowledge. Without the company structure behind me and having experts in these areas I would not have plans to do that. Structure is vital. So, for example, do you know the phrase Jack-able phrase. I have to understand a little bit about 100s of areas. But I don't have the specialist knowledge to work further and deeper in the supply chain. I will facilitate the conversation, but I would need an expert which the structure would provide and actually to implement anything” (MC)

Apposite structure should be there in organisations to accelerate the circular economy transition that can guide the stakeholders about the right tasks and procedures to follow.

“Yea the biggest impact is actually having a structure that will focus on circular approach or sustainability or something like that. The business that will do well will have it. I am in the sustainability stirring group, but I don’t have time to focus on that you know what [it] is like. You know the hours [we] work. It’s nice being on it built. There is no time to implement. If you have structure in place that has a sustainability director and [in] each-each business area [like] R&D supply chain manufacturing, commercial had a sustainability lead, that is obviously then way of business showing its really important.” (EGD)

“Right now, there is bias to directly contacting the producers or the suppliers on behalf of the organisation and then depending on it, (...). To Start with, I believe that the organisation can make a kind of separate division within those buyers, whose job will be just to hunt for the sustainable or upcycled or innovative producer” (MG)

The above comments from a planning manager of manufacturing and a retailing manager express the need of re-aligning the structure of organisation apposite to circular model. “I think none of the company do have that type of structure in the business, where there is dedicated team to do it”, a research and development manager also comments. Along with intangible organisation structure, unavailability of infrastructure has been mentioned by participants as a hindrance factor.

“In terms of issues or barriers in most of the food companies now will [be] recycle their food waste. obviously, it isn’t a separate food waste kind of collection from the site, it’s going in the general waste and then once you take out the food from your general waste you know you’re decreasing your costs massively there because food is probably the heaviest thing you could put into general waste. (...) But if there’s no way [to] take it, or there’s not sufficient space to be able accommodate all of it. What do you do with it then?” (MP)

“Because many a times people don’t have facilities to dispose them off separately or the place, they are living on doesn’t support that. Separate bins have not been provided by councils or people don’t have time or may be many other things you know. They don’t have required knowledge and the structure.” (GW)

“And then the third piece which is challenges around [is] the infrastructure does not exist at the moment. So, yeah, when we put your stuff back in the bin away, its certain percentage of probably going to get recycled for those that drive. (...) infrastructure so for these processes [do] not exist as of now”

There is a need of adopting the circular economy as part of organisation structure and that will further direct towards recognising infrastructure to facilitate the closing loop processes on different supply chain phases. Table 5.5 shows that “lack of structure” was predominantly discussed by the supply chain stakeholder in this category.

Table: 4.5: Structural barriers

Nodes (sub-themes related to structural barriers)	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Nodes\challenges in the circular economy\Barriers to CSCM\Structural barrier\Complexity in nature	8	8	7	7
Nodes\challenges in the circular economy\Barriers to CSCM\Structural barrier\Lack of collaboration	12	12	8	8
Nodes\challenges in the circular economy\Barriers to CSCM\Structural barrier\Lack of structure	31	31	13	13

Source: NVivo 12 nodes comparison

4.3.6 Institutional Barriers

The next category of barriers instigated in this research relates to institutions and regulatory bodies. These challenges have been widely discussed in previous studies i.e., Goyal et al., 2016; Zhu et al., 2017; Jesus and Mendonça, 2018; Kirchherr et al., 2018; Hart et al., 2019. Detailed laws and regulations have not yet been introduced by the UK government, which enable circular supply chain transition in the food industry. The following quotation from interviewees shows the prominence of government initiatives.

“Nothing is unachievable. but again, to think to write and to implement there’s a big difference so if as I mentioned before sometimes that if there [are] rules regulations in place for other things why can’t they put rules and regulations for the circular economy. And I’m not talking about rules and regulations but with the implications. With the reflection, with the penalty. because in the

world or in corporate world I'm not sure there are any rules introduced which will regulate the management decisions or lead them to achieve their goals from waste management. but in other industries or other let's say for example driving, if there are rules but if you break that rule then you will get the fine. Yes, and that's why probably we have proper regulated traffic and all other things related to the traffic's. So, I think that kind of model will work in waste management as well" (AM)

"So, now the only way to control, which is I would say is only the system. (...). For example. We drive a car on the road. If there is a red light, we must stop. If there's a green light, then we go [and] our brain is now designed in that way. So, anything, is controlled by the government, we go well with [that]. Make the systems like that first, then only it will be possible. [As] at the moment everything is directly linked with finance directly linked with these things, your graphs, your budgets, everything is now controlled by electronics. I would say or by government and data and these kinds of things. But only thing will work is systems." (JS)

These most entrenched barriers found in the circular economy are institutional barriers (Gumley, 2014). Implantations of a circular approach predominantly depends on government's awareness about the matter (Ilic and Nicolic, 2016; Xue et al., 2010). Current law and regulation are not in favour of the circular economy in supply chains (Radamaekers et al., 2011; Gumley, 2014), for example the current system does not have favourable policies for sending policies across the border where needed (Bechtel et al., 2013) or rigid taxation policies etc. (Studer et al., 2006; Gumley, 2014) From the above comment of participants, it is obvious that the best way to initiate the circular economy transition is government taking rigorous actions. Other obstructions from the government side which do not favour circular supply chain management are discussed next.

Lack of supportive law and regulation

Hill (2015) states in his research that "largely ignored the upstream consequences of resource extraction... particularly if those are outside UK border" and a similar concern was raised by Pheifer (2012, p.6). It also involves insufficiency of global agreements for circular supply chain management favoured policies, lack of laws for landfill diversion, handling, and categorization of waste (Pomponi and Moncaster, 2018; Hart et al., 2019), lack of smart regulations (Preston, 2012 p.16), and lack of a supportive policy framework (Rizos et al., 2015, p.1). "Obstructing laws and

regulations” is the most persistent barrier in the circular economy literature, ranking number seven from the main fifteen barriers (Kirchherr et al., 2018). Undermentioned words of food supply chain stakeholders give a glimpse of this issue.

“It’s government policies, need to bring down to work rather than spoken about. Like current ambition is to bring carbon emission down by checking down and all. That process can be from the centre and could be affecting all of us massively through the economy, but I don’t think it has brought forward to about it by educating all. What about the self-less vehicles currently running on the road, you not going to scrap that? It is a bit of deathly topic right now”. (BK)

“Businesses have to adopt it for sure but no one else can make it happen in better way than government. They will have to regulate to make other stakeholders to adopt it practically. Currently, priorities of rules are different I think.” (MG)

The above remarks made by interviewees raised the concern similar to Preston, (2012) and Rizos et al. (2015) that government instructions are more in writing rather than practically implementing by providing guidance.

“No, the government is not helpful because they are going on about recycling and hitting the recyclers. Where [they] should be looking at the start of the problem. There should be focussing on starting bit not the ending of it. As a person you will not hand over the keys of your car to the wrong person. You can’t stop him afterwards, when they hit somebody or may stop him before it happens [s].” (AB)

A director of a recycling company felt that government is only working at the ending parts resolving the issues which already exist but the hierarchy of work should be to start with the right strategies according to circular economy framework and adopting a proactive approach. For example, a research and development manager express in his words There are not any controls in place by government on the industries on the amount of waste manufacture produce or throwing away.

“Government can make it happen by controlling the food wastage itself. I am not very close to it, but I don’t think we have accountability on how much food we throw out. Is that what council picks up with us? There [are] many times [that] food oil or food itself goes by the drain, we have fines,

huge fines are imposed by the council but other than that there is nothing. If you put those examples in the picture.” (VS)

“we said, could we have a recycling one and general waste one, so we bought the recycling one, we got some discount. We started using it and then we noticed that when they are emptying them, they were emptying them in the same lorry, so we asked what’s going on, they said [they] sort it out when they go back. We said ok, we not gonna believe that obviously we don’t believe that so umm now we still got the recycling bin which is a couple of pounds cheaper but everything is just, there is no point.” (AF)

The following words from a participant demand regulatory bodies to make rigorous rules along with introducing the roadmap.

“Government is the most important. They are the prominence regulatory bodies from them every initiative is regulated and followed by. Now the question is, how strict they are to make circular supply chain happen, how they are driving it. No matter what targets you are setting, what policies you are writing, it will not drive the change until or you have the framework, roadmap, and the strategies with enforcement. Your regulations should be hard enough to drive this change. UK government is lacking behind in introducing appropriate rules and regulation for circular chains.” (JH)

So, from the above discussion it is established that the UK government is lagging in taking preliminary, viable actions and required control on the practices and work as of now. Government is setting the standards for sustainability but not the adequate rules to enforce it.

Lack of government support

Another barricade from government side, recognised during the research is non-existence of financial support to the existing business or the innovators (Kircherr et al., 2018). High investment and cost of product have already been discussed in section 4.4.2 which stops the investors and business to take circular supply chain management initiatives. Previous studies have also discussed this as daunting factors. Hart et al., (2019) illustrate the fiscal and regulatory barriers comparing with the carrot and stick approach. “I think lagging and taxes will definitely work.” Experts think that there is not any support from government to embellishment of circular supply chain management initiatives in the form of tax benefits, investment benefits or awareness campaign.

“When AD was a new technology, the government used to provide subsidies for, basically they used to incentivise the business which [would]go forward in it. So basically, what they are is all of the site that tied into terms called feed-a terrace which basically you get additional amount of money from the government for every kilowatt of electricity which is fed back into the National Grid. So, all of these sites which were built between that period when they were offering these is locked into those long-term agreements, but those sorts of incentives were removed a couple of years ago now, which then doesn’t make it financially viable to build an AD plant. (...) without that incentive, it doesn’t make financial sense to build an AD plant but saying that you know with the local authority or going to start collecting the food waste from the 2023 that will see bring, you know, a large proportion of tonnage into the market which potentially isn’t going to be capacity for. So, obviously the government is then, will need to introduce something like this” (MP)

Financial incentives for start-ups and help to deal with the large quantities of waste following government’s waste reduction plan by 2025, are the examples discussed by the business development manager from an anaerobic digestion plant. It is also pointed out that government is even taking out the existing benefits from businesses which used to be there in the system that is kind of a de-motivational matter for businesses. “I think this probably things that spooked like straight away, I think, how the government help organisations to achieve it”, mentioned by a retailing manager shows the significance of government intervention in circular supply chain management plans.

“If you look at the example 10 year ago Spain had less recycling rate in all of the developed world. Legislation after legislation was changed to address that and they brought in taxes, and they brought in regulations, and they brought in infrastructure and recycling capabilities and put money into it. Glad the money that was coming from the charges and the season regulations and that is one of the best circular economies at the moment. So, if you rely on this course that will meet the competition will drive it, might happen eventually over the years. But it really needs government incentives behind it to make it genuinely happen” (NR)

Participants referred to sustainable initiatives in Spain, how government there made the framework with incentives for stakeholders which worked well and made Spain one of the most sustainable

countries in Europe. It has been recognised from the interviewees that other help sought from the government is to raise the awareness on a comprehensive level. This can be explained by next comments from the participants.

“The government is implementation vehicle. But people have to made others aware. And the government has to work around what is in the limelight or which is seen as working to makes people’s life better.” (PK)

“Yes, this is achievable of course, because it is for everyone’s benefits but if not, it will be only because if enough attention is not paid by upper level. Where there are not enough policies and, framework to drive the policies and incentives to support the framework.” (BD)

“That is difficult. Until or unless people are not aware, knowledge is not there the general public, and it has not been imposed by government bodies it will be a challenge in food sector” (WY)

Transitions like the circular economy need new interventions. Andrews and Devaulty (2009); Eckelman and Chertow (2009); Kirchherr et al., (2018) suggest that government has a central role to play in it. Government support from the awareness point of view is also missing. As discussed, earlier, awareness is key, and participants urge that regulatory bodies are the best drivers to bring the awareness among people.

Post-Brexit trade

Another challenge that emerged during this research is effect of Brexit that can put adverse effect on circular supply chain proposals. Existing studies have no evidence about this factor but have been discussed significantly by the participants in the following way.

“The government of course plays a big role in any country’s economy, and they can bring a lot more changes at faster speed than anyone else. Recently I have come across in news that UK government is looking to do “Free-Trade” deal with Australia, one hand the deal shows a lot of advantages for UK economy, but some UK farmers have concerns there will be no meaningful safeguards in place to stop them being undercut by cheap imports. (...). According to the UK’s National Farmers Union, Australian farmers are able to produce beef at a lower cost of production and could undercut farmers in the UK. On one hand, this deal should boom the export and will help the economy but import from Australia could have adverse result on health, local farming and will lead to more wastage and carbon footprints.” (RM)

The above quotation from a participant is evidence that Brexit is putting pressure on the government to arrange business deals outside Europe that will accumulate the difficulties of fair practice for circular supply chains by increasing the carbon footprint and increasing the domestic wastage and by diverting government's preference from circular initiatives. Another stakeholder demonstrates this by analysing as follows.

“On the top of my head what I think is trading deals, import and export which are moving out of EU or towards far east countries. Now the trading standards which used to be mutual for UK and EU, there can be contradiction in the quality, in the standards or in the rules. It will be a rise on the CO2 emission side by importing from far Asian countries rather than EU. As I said earlier product should be manufactured for long term use, moved the trades out from EU might be a compromise in product quality. Again, let's see, it depends, let's hope for the best” (TS)

In addition to the business deals Brexit is becoming the cause of food waste. In the next comment a participant describes that due to the closed border legal requirements of import and export have increased and non-fulfilment of those requirements leads to a whole lot of food going to waste.

“Another thing I would like to add, I was watching a video today. Because of Brexit There's a lot of food wastage .so I was interested to watch this video on YouTube. [They] said because of Brexit why there is food wastage. So, what's happening [is] due to the Brexit there is a lot of documentation needs to be completed before any food pass[es] from UK to European countries. And there is some there are some food [products] or categories which has a shelf life and because of the documentation even if you have one documentation left, the whole lot of that food is going to waste. but I'm sure if government can notice that or put into the agenda, to avoid that wastage. I think government is not serious about food wastage.” (AM)

Buyssee and Verbeke, 2003 depict, when there are proactive environmental strategies, it pressurizes stakeholders to react voluntarily. The UK food economy is currently lacking in this respect. Government is currently working on reducing carbon emissions, waste management and reducing wastage, even though rules are not strict enough or have not been communicated to the consumers and industries. The majority of the participants across the supply chain raised the issue of this need.

“Government has a part to play or practically everything, I guess. Whether it is by way of encouraging or by way of regulating or imposing”. “I would say the problem is the governments are not entirely ethical. So, they are worried about their selection. Unfortunately, they are more concerned that if they can remain in power”. Kirchherr et al. (2019) consider government as a significant player to tackle the most persistent barriers like price of virgin material and high investment through incentivising. However, some participants share different knowledge that government is playing its part very well and that there are other barriers such as techniques and awareness should be tackled first to apply the circular economy transition in the food industry.

Table 4.6: Institutional Barriers

Nodes (sub-themes related to institutional barriers)	Number of coding references	Aggregate number of coding references	Number of items coded	Aggregate number of items coded
Nodes\Challenges in the circular economy\Barriers to CSCM\Institutional and Regulatory Barriers\Lack of government support	12	12	10	10
Nodes\Challenges in the circular economy\Barriers to CSCM\Institutional and Regulatory Barriers\Lack of supportive legislation	25	25	18	18
Nodes\Challenges in the circular economy\Barriers to CSCM\Institutional and Regulatory Barriers\Post- Brexit Trade	9	9	9	9

Source: NVivo 12 nodes comparison

The above section discusses challenges for a food supply chain to implement a circular approach. The factors discussed in existing studies i.e., lack of technologies, lack of government support, lack of infrastructure, lack of awareness, inappropriate marketing strategies were analysed and analysed through qualitative research. The research brought out some new themes like demographical factors, post-Brexit deals, minimum order quantities which are significant factors for circular supply chain implementation and have also been discussed in this section. This study adopted stakeholder theory as a theoretical lens to closely analyse the factors affecting various stakeholders on their supply chain stage in adopting the circular economy transitions. Stakeholder theory is about how the network of customers, suppliers, employees, managers, investors, and all other parties who affect and get affected by business, co-operate to create value for it (Parmar et al., 2010). With the benefits of raising morals, creating values, and evading the potential harm of individuals, stakeholders’ relationship management is an efficient way for businesses to endure in

a capitalist system (Phillips, 2003). Like stakeholder theory, sustainability management fosters economic and societal value (Schaltegger and Burritt, 2005, p. 195). Hence, looking at the aspirations of circular supply chain management of providing social, environmental, and economic value, it is apposite to analyse the stakeholders' standpoints. This section is an analytical interpretation of viewpoints regarding challenges and drivers of stakeholders from various stages of circular supply chain management.

4.4 EFFECTS OF BARRIERS ON STAKEHOLDERS

The research followed a circular supply chain process to determine the participants from the food industry, i.e., suppliers, product developers, manufacturing companies, retailers, consumers, upcycling companies, recycling plants, and local council to gain practical knowledge besides the theoretical understanding from literature. The involvement of all stakeholders helped to inspect the issue from a multi-perspective to drive the resolutions. However, not all the identified stakeholders were included in the study. Exclusion or non-participation of some stakeholders have been discussed in detail in the limitation sections of final chapter. The selection of individuals and professionals was based on several criterion such as: 1) directly or indirectly affects or get affected by the changes in food industry, 2) are aware about reverse effects of industrial activities like climate change, carbon emission, scarcity of resources, 4) are aware about the features and loop-holes during the supply chain lead to wastage, 5) living or working experience in United Kingdom and 6) are familiar with the circular economy or sustainability concept and its role in food industry. However, not all the stakeholders have to be met with each criterion.

4.4.1 Effects on designing stage

To facilitate the circular practices, the designing concept requires a fundamental change (Rio los Rios and Charnley; Jensen and Remmen, 2017). Product development processes contribute towards sustainability and circularity by reducing waste during the development process or by designing the product apposite to longevity and circularity (Carlsson et al., 2021). Out of 34, 4 participants from product and packaging development / designing were contacted, who discussed challenges for the circular strategy implementation as per the results presented through matrix analysis of themes versus coding percentage covered by participants in Table 5.7. The most

discussed factor by participants was lack of the right awareness for adopting right practices for circularity of products. A participant highlighted:

“Obviously, it all comes down to numbers and money making. Most of the management has started realizing its importance but it is not from the perspective of the circular economy but from the perspective of sustainability. So, it will be an element that how can you make people more educated about the circular economy. (...) you are aware of the wastage, you are aware of the suitability, but nobody picturizing it that how this model will fit into the circular economy. You might be doing this, but you do not know what are doing is right thing to do. I might have different impact. Ok you are not filling up landfills by the plastic but are you aware of the impact you are having former. Like from the Carbon emission side of it that is the one thing of it that it is not landing into the landfill.” (VS)

The issue is evident from the research of Mendoza et al. (2019) regarding implementation of the circular economy in educational institutions that lack of understanding among the staff cause non-application of practices. Hilletifh and Eriksson (2011), Ülkü et al. (2012), Abbey et al. (2015), Pero et al. (2015) also explore the positive link between right awareness and circular product design. The capitalist environment business model is only successful if it is generating the profit for the institutions. Mostaghel and Chirumalla (2021) demonstrate the direct relationship of awareness and product purchase intention. A research and development manager from packaging iterates from his experience that to attract the customers towards green purchasing they must have the right knowledge about the concept.

“I think the biggest one at the moment that exists is around clarification of one of these is actually what we are trying to achieve. At the moment all the big business are on the way to work on their own agenda trying to make sure they are appearing to be, green as possible to consumers. Now actually doing what is genuinely like for example, I’ve just completed a study of plastic trays that we use. The board tray and actually a plastic tray comes out on top on 17 environmental and the circular economy matrices. From all 17 matrix, it comes out on top, but perception the consumers hold plastic bags and board is right.” (NR)

Table 4.7: Designing stage barriers frequency

Barriers in circular supply chain management	A: Supply chain actors: Supply Chain Stage = Design= Barriers frequency %	A: NR	B: SKV	C: SR	D: VS
1: High cost of products and raw material	4.2%	2	0	0	1
2: Investment	1.89%	0	0	2	0
3: Minimum order quantity	9.51%	0	4	0	0
4: Profitability	4.91%	0	1	0	4
5: Lack of government support	1.61%	1	0	0	1
6: Lack of supportive legislation	8.82%	2	1	2	1
7: Post- Brexit Trade	3.33%	1	1	0	1
8: Competition	1.55%	0	1	0	0
9: inappropriate marketing strategies	5.49%	1	1	0	1
10: Lack of management commitment	3.03%	1	0	0	1
11: Demographic factors	0%	0	0	0	0
12: Lack of awareness	10.65%	3	0	0	6
13: Organisation Culture	5.79%	0	2	0	2
14: Perception and attitude	6.54%	2	0	2	1
15: Complexity in nature	2.45%	1	0	0	1
16: Lack of collaboration	8.35%	1	0	2	2
17: Lack of structure	9.42%	5	1	0	0
18: CE Specific technologies	0.34%	0	0	0	1
19: Knowledge, skill, and expertise	1.87%	1	0	1	0
20: Order and forecasting	4.67%	0	3	0	0
21: Shelf Life	5.57%	0	2	3	0

Table 1: NVivo 12: Matrix analysis

Hence, whether it is food products or packaging to instigate and embed circular supply chain management into organization practices, it is a precondition to make all the stakeholders aware of the right practices and procedures to follow. Furthermore, the next most significant challenge for the development stage of the food industry is the lack of circular economy supportive legislation.

To make the product able to reuse, demolish or upcycle in a circular way, they need devolution from higher authorities (Bovea et al., 2018). All 4 participants raised concerns about inadequate legislation for the circular economy.

“What sort of ideas they have they will come in brief so that is their requirement and when it comes to the design team then they need to look into end-to end and how we can do it. That is how the whole process starts, most of the factories and most of the companies lacks this one because we are not penalized at any stage. Like if you are send [ing] it to landfill, the waste and everything, who bothers. They follow health and safety and pay and everything so, its ok” (SKV).

The above quotation from a chef manager of a manufacturing company sheds light on the point that like other regulations i.e., health and safety, for organizations to think and initiating a circular design or circular process there is no obligation from the government. Hartley et al., 2020 prominently depicts, “Numerous interviewees indicate that existing legislation classifies waste only as waste rather than as a potential secondary resource”. Hence, in the rigorous health and safety regulation environment, reusing or upcycling the food products is an impediment factor for circular product development (Rood et al., 2017).

“If you see in my department itself, I will take bigger picture over here. I will put it in the developing of products altogether. Right now, there are some technical standards like how to buy the things or how to do the things and how you justify the things that element has thought us to be more efficient in regard to controls. So, let’s say for instance producing the meat product we sherd out the bones, we sherd out the fat and just use proper lean piece of meat but what happens to that waste so if a supermarket and authorities allow us to use those things or start include in the recipe then outcome can be better in the terms of the circular economy.” (VS)

Additionally, lack of structure, perception and attitude towards the circular products and practices, lack of collaboration from all the actors, inappropriate marketing strategies and short life of the products and ingredients challenges were considerably pointed out by the participants from product designing departments. Oghazi and Mostaghel (2018), Hankammer et al., (2019) highlight the need of all stakeholders’ assurance for an effective circular business model.

“Another barrier is, procurement the buying teams so their targets are keeping the customer aligned as much as we can and their targets are maintaining relationships with the existing

suppliers and my job is quite opposite, my job is to bring more expensive and different suppliers that's kind of a barrier that they trying to go right opposite to where I am going. (...) Third piece which is challenges around, the infrastructure does not exist at the moment. So, Yeah, when we put your stuff back in the bin away, [only] certain percentage of it is probably going to get recycled for those that drive (...) consider the way in your definition and management same as infrastructure so for these processes” infrastructure does not exist as of now. (NR)

The circular supply chain is a network of multiple stakeholders. The above quotation from a participant describes that designing circular packing solutions requires new ventures with suppliers having circular technologies which go against the relationships of existing stakeholders thus the resistance comes from the designing stage. Additionally, the circular economy being a novel model there is absences of required infrastructure. Another factor is short shelf life of the food products which has not been discussed as a challenge in existing circular economy literature. However, looking at the legalities regarding food safety and hygiene measures, it is recognized as one of the major factors during this research that prevent almost every stakeholder adopt the circular model. Shelf life is a factor every stakeholder of the supply chain is interested in (Dominic Man, 2015) but is a challenge for designers to design the product for longevity, regeneration, and remanufacturing in short shelf-life environment and control the wastage. Short life of food products was discussed by 3 out of 4 participants as a challenge for circular design.

“I think shelf life is one of the key things in food industry and requirement of the trials and the scaling up from small batches to big batches is a huge area as well. Also, some element, components, often get dumped because in the factory we have only 48 hours WIP life which is low. I guess if we have the longer WIP (work in progress) life, how that could be achieved that is a question” (SR)

The customer's attitude, habits, emotions, and belief have a strong impact on their purchasing decision which coerce the retailers to sell the products according to customer choice (Fishbein and Ajzen, 2010; Elzinga et al., 2020; Mostaghel and Chirumalla, 2021) and further for manufacturers to manufacture and designers to design the products (Nes et al., 2010). Similarly, customers' behaviour for buying, consuming, and disposing of the products drives the circular transition by

making the product as per the preference of consumers rather than environmentally friendly products. The factor is considerable discussed in the research by the participants.

“Like ready meal trays, we put into the bag, we have to rinse it, when we put into the recycling otherwise, they [are] contaminated. But certain people just put them in the bin straight away. No one can be bothered to do that, if you put a barrier in front of me, I am not intervening more if it taken up, I can be levelled. As soon as you do that irrespective of people who say, they will show but generally the vast majority of people are lazy, and they don’t care.” (NR)

Consequently, the above comments, observation and analysis suggest that the product development stage is highly impacted by lack of awareness about circular products and procedures in all the stakeholders whether they are employees or consumers. Law and legislation are also not very supportive at present that can affiliate and make the food manufacturing organisations to follow the circular economy model. Designing phase of supply chain demands the involvement of horizontal as well as vertical collaboration across the food industry to overcome these challenges. Moving forward minimum order quantities, cost of raw material, profitability, marketing strategies have less direct influence on designers to move towards circular decisions. While other factors do not have major and direct relation with product development phase and no challenges related to demographic factors were discussed by managers.

4.4.2 Effect on manufacturing stage

The manufacturing or processing phase of a supply chain is one of the highest contributors to the carbon footprint (Parashar, 2020) through various elements i.e., machines, processed or unprocessed food, packaging and labelling, energy consumption etc. The nature of this segment makes it difficult for industries to apply the circular economy model. 13 different department managers of food manufacturing organisations were interviewed to ascertain their opinions and experience regarding circular food supply chains. Interviews mostly referred to lack of supportive legislation as a hindrance factor, followed by high cost of products and raw material and lack of management commitment shown in Table 5.8 matrix analyses. However, consumers’ perception and attitude were considerably mentioned by several participants.

Circular supply chain management needs drastic change in manufacturing and remanufacturing processes (Batista et al., 2018a) along with coping with the environmental regulations pressure

and market risk (Linder and Rashid, 2016). It is a crucial stage to get sustainable measures because policies which lead towards less environmental damage hardly exist in current business models (Upadhyay and Jaeger, 2019). Being tightly bound in the health and safety regulations, it is a challenge for food manufacturers to originate the remanufacturing practices for closing the loops. *“The other thing is, for legislation point – you had some chicken, some sauce and some vegetables which in your own house combined together and consume. We are not in position of selling those products as legislation requires us to make ingredient and nutritional declaration, I need shelf-life information. In your house, you will never worry about it, we are not in position to use the surplus, excess stock in a way in your own kitchen.” (RJ)*

An operations manager reflects in the comment.

“The whole process is aligned in the way that there will be zero process waste. No one going to say that there will be wastage, they are expecting that nothing [will] be wasted. So that’s where the circular supply chain management is not into that kind of open strategy.”

A managing director of a UK based food manufacturing company enhances the argument that current legislation and policies are not designed by taking the circular economy into consideration which can guide the manufacturers to follow the right procedures.

“Government makes legislation, and we have to live with it. But none the legislations are basically to reduce the wastage, but it is targeted to recycling, avoiding landfill all that kind of things but I haven’t come across by any initiatives where they tell how you can reduce the wastage. There is nothing specific as of today.” (AK)

Table 4.8: Manufacturing stage barriers frequency

Barriers in circular supply chain management	A: Supply chain actors: Supply Chain Stage = Manufacturing	A: AK	B: BK	C: BR	D: DE	E: EGD	F: JH	G: MC	H: NB	I: PJ	J: PK	K: RJ	L: SM	M: YB
1: High cost of products and raw material	10.51%	0	0	4	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	2	0	3
2: Investment	3.46%	0	3	0	1	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0
3: Minimum order quantity	3.02%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
4: Profitability	3.56%	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	1	1
5: Lack of government support	1.19%	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
6: Lack of supportive legislation	10.77%	1	3	0	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	0	0
7: Post- Brexit Trade	1.35%	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
8: Competition	0.76%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
9: inappropriate marketing strategies	5.12%	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	1	0	0	3
10: Lack of management commitment	8.53%	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	5	1	0	0
11: Demographic factors	1.58%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
12: Lack of awareness	7.62%	0	1	0	2	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	1	0
13: Organisation Culture	3.04%	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
14: Perception and attitude	6.19%	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	2	1	0	2
15: Complexity in nature	0.74%	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
16: Lack of collaboration	2.68%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	1	0	0
17: Lack of structure	6.38%	0	2	0	0	2	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	1
18: CE Specific technologies	3.37%	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	1	0
19: Knowledge, skill, and expertise	6.11%	0	2	1	0	3	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	0
20: Order and forecasting	7.66%	1	0	0	0	3	0	2	1	1	1	0	0	0
21: Shelf Life	6.36%	3	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0

Source: NVivo 12: Matrix analysis

“It is financial more than technology in my opinion”; the impression of a participant is consistent with the views of Tura et al. (2019) and Farooque et al. (2019), who consider the high cost of technology and cost of material as a challenge for circular economy initiatives. For the food manufacturing industries, the circular economy is an expensive solution by the way of bringing

innovative technologies and recyclable packaging solutions. A participant shares his experience in following quotation:

“If I give you an example like we are working on sustainable non-plastic packaging. But it is going to be quite bit more expansive, but retailer is going to support it as they know which right thing is to do. That’s what their customers want. So that’s how the retailer will support it.” (NR)

Correspondingly, another participant views the circular economy will be an additional cost for small-medium organisations when changing and disposing of existing materials to sustainable or recyclable which stakeholders are reluctant to do.

“If government ask you to change it, this [would] cost lot of money [because] we [will] have to hire the bailing machine to bail them and they have to collect one by one, we have to bail them so that they can just come and take it away. That is another job and cost for us, and storage cost” (YB)

For manufacturers, segregation of waste for re-manufacturing, logistics or reverse logistics cost, additional cost of raw material are the substantial challenges (Mangla et al., 2018; Grafstrom and Aasma, 2021). Success of circular economy cannot be guaranteed until some costs are internalised (Grafstrom and Aasma, 2021). The circular economy has low engagement from management to make it a part of a company’s integral strategy and there are not any targets set up by management to set a route (Grafström and Aasma, 2021). Agyemang et al. (2018) and Mangla et al. (2018) established that the reason for less engagement from the management’s less involvement could be that the circular economy does not fit in incentive schemes. Comparably, during this research this challenge was noticeably pointed out by manufacturers. An operations manager shares his experience that the circular economy types of change is hardly suitable to management’s agenda therefore they are highly reluctant to bring it to the organisations.

“There is streamline definitely, I will be very blunt on this line that you [will] be looking yourself redundant” (BK)

Another important reason is that management do not consider waste as a part of practice therefore the waste management and circularity concept is not considered while aligning the strategies. This investigation is consistent with Bechtel et al. (2013), Liu and Bai (2014), Tura et al. (2019) who

concur that issues occur when management fails to develop understanding, support employees and stay in the silo systems with less flexibility.

Successful circular supply chain solutions can be created with association of supply chain partners i.e., Fortum's Horsepower development with the joint efforts of UPM and BMH (Tura et al., 2019). Circular supply chain management needs combined effort; the contradictory scenario was discovered in food manufacturers where less cooperation from the retailers in terms of forecasting and ordering can lead to breach of the circular supply chain management model. Food circular supply chain management demands streamline in demand – forecasting system in ordering from retailers (Prashar, 2020), misalignment of which is not an ideal scenario for the circular economy model.

“The biggest thing that is impacting us, the reliability of the customer and their forecast and order window and we used to have to get the orders today and out loading it tonight for Sainsbury's so for us which much harder to control and recently we change the order window think, the biggest impact we have the longer order window. So only we will be cooking thing according to the final order. I don't know if it answers your question or not. (...) Again, it's the customer's orders, if they drop, or if they increase, we already started cooking them, then we need to do something with it. It's just customers and what agreement we have on life. For example, noodle, we have to cook today and have to use today and if we don't use it today, it will go to the bin.” (EGD)

Moreover, lack of structure, shelf-life, less knowledge or skills and perception or attitude of stakeholders were respectively mentioned by manufacturers. As the current system and policies are not designed by taking the circular economy into consideration, there is unavailability of required structure such as accountable department, technology and other infrastructure. For food manufacturers, it is critical to think about utilising the products to the maximum because of shorter life, mixture of ingredients and having food safety constraints with it. “So, in food manufacturing, food shelf life is the main thing”. On the manufacturer level, it will be extremely supportive if techniques can help to increase the life of products by not affecting the taste, texture and nutritional value of the product. At the same time, skills and knowledge for remanufacturing of food products and awareness among customers to accept or promote those products are essential for the successful transition of circular supply chain management. Lastly, the complex nature of the

circular model, competition and demographic factors are least mentioned as challenges for manufacturers.

4.4.3 Effects on retailing stage

Retailers are seen as significant intermediators for sustainable revolutions because of their dimensions, position in the supply chains which make both parties manufacture as well as consumers to impose the sustainable policies (Ytterhus et al., 1999; Jones et al., 2005b; Chkanikova and Mont, 2012). Implementation of circularity on retailing stage is an important resolution for the transformation of circular supply chain due to consumers' progressive attitude towards it as well as pressure from the regulatory bodies (Upadhyay et al., 2021). 6 participants from various retailing companies were interviewed to identify the challenges in their operation to apply the circular economy transition. Matric query was run on the coded data, which obtained the results as table 5.9. Retailers discussed that perception, attitude, and behaviour of customers towards the sustainable practices is prevalent challenges for retailers. It can be in the way of adopting right practices or appropriate product or consumer's daily practices on the basis of their behaviour. Consumption is a psychological, social, and cultural process of choosing goods (Zukin and Maguire, 2004). It is challenging to regulate the consumer behaviour and that affects efficiency of circular business model (Singh and Giacosa, 2018). As retailers are directly affected by nature and behaviour of consumers, consistent views were shared by a floor manager.

“In retailing, culture [is] very much affected by consumers. Here I would add consumer has big role to make this model successful. Have you heard about this term called hoarders? some people who just keep on buying stuff, even if they don't need it. They just hoard it. Even if they have it still keep on buying. It [is] also a recognised disorder but not everybody has that disorder. Some people just can't resist it. People in this country has power to buy and use this to buy a lot of stuff without giving a thought that if they actually need them. Also, sometimes retailers' policies like return policies or promotional offers make them to buy unnecessary. And leads to huge amount of food wastage. So, I see that consumers definitely need to be educated and no one else to educate the consumers better than the retailers.” (MG)

Table 4.9: Retailing stage barriers frequency

Barriers in supply chain management	Supply chain actors: Supply Chain Stage = Retailing	A: B	B: BSK	C: HM	D: KD	E: MG	F: PG
1: High cost of products and raw material	7.9%	2	0	3	0	1	1
2: Investment	1.27%	0	0	0	1	0	0
3: Minimum order quantity	0%	0	0	0	0	0	0
4: Profitability	6.82%	1	0	2	0	2	0
5: Lack of government support	3.67%	1	0	0	0	0	1
6: Lack of supportive legislation	1.83%	1	0	0	0	1	0
7: Post- Brexit Trade	0%	0	0	0	0	0	0
8: Competition	5.47%	1	0	0	0	0	1
9: inappropriate marketing strategies	2.08%	0	0	0	1	0	1
10: Lack of management commitment	10%	0	1	1	1	0	2
11: Demographic factors	3.64%	0	0	1	0	0	2
12: Lack of awareness	2.29%	1	1	0	0	1	0
13: Organisation Culture	8.71%	0	0	3	1	0	1
14: Perception and attitude	24.07%	0	1	1	2	1	4
15: Complexity in nature	2.21%	0	0	0	0	0	1
16: Lack of collaboration	0%	0	0	0	0	0	0
17: Lack of structure	12.8%	0	1	1	3	0	3
18: CE Specific technologies	0.81%	1	0	0	0	0	0
19: Knowledge, skill and expertise	2.26%	0	0	0	0	1	0
20: Order and forecasting	2.18%	0	0	1	0	0	0
21: Shelf Life	1.99%	0	0	0	0	1	0

Source: Matrix Analysis retailing stage

An interviewee also depicts in below quotation:

“The consumers actually have a huge role to play in this. They have to be taught in way so that message can go to them that they need to change. Because some consumers over here are horrible. They are very pampered, and they have been very spoiled for choices.”

The second most discussed challenge from the retailers is lack of structure specifically lack communication between departments and no responsible team. A floor manager depicts “There’s no particular department or a particular process to be followed.” Which means the circular economy is not a part of company’s structure that can guide through the organisation to follow the specific actions. Therefore, an efficient information system is crucial if decision-makers are to find more environmentally and financially beneficial ways to plan and manage their resources and structures. Unlike manufacturers who demands to have technologies and infrastructure, participants from the retailing companies only referred to intangible structure as need to apply circular supply chain management on their part of supply chain.

Consumers and retailers have transactional relation with each other. Consumer’s behaviours affect the retailer to adopt circular and sustainability practices similarly retailers’ business or promotional activities affect the mind of consumers which ultimately lead to the loads of wastage from both sides of the parties. Another important factor discussed by retailers was non- acceptance of ecological, upcycled or sustainable products. Consumer’s long-learned habits are important factor to refuse the circular supply chain management model. A participants share the related observation:

“It’s also about personal opinion, like some people think they need things from companies which are ethical and who are sustainable and who are more concerned about environment and all. But not everybody is like that. So, I think it’s about personal opinion as well. In the beginning, sales of upcycled product might be very low, I think it will be quite challenging because not all people think in that way. They might have doubts like health and safety or how it is done, and they might not accept it in the beginning, but you don’t know” (KD)

As a result, Hopkins et al., (2018) urge not to limit the circular change to management policies but this practice should be marketed to consumers with providing the awareness and consequences. Altering the organisation culture from traditional supply chains to more advanced and with

efficient measures is a challenge for incumbent firms. Structure, processes, and values of those organisations are designed according to traditional systems which they find difficult to amend (Anastasiadis and Poole, 2015). Germany and France have strongly developed cultures and systems to return products; whereas in the United Kingdom, it has been normal practice to throw them away (Hopkinsons et al., 2018). Along with consumer side of culture, changing the organisation culture was equally highlighted by the stakeholders from retailing. A head of supply chain from Marks & Spencer clears the argument in following quotation.

“Company’s culture has massive role of that’s what makes the company into. That’s what stands companies apart is ultimately their culture isn’t it. When everybody is selling the same thing so there’s only a few things that are sold apart and that’s the unique selling point of the brand and what that brand stands for (...). A very old well company, a 120-year-old company has legacy culture they have to recognise and move with the time and that takes a bit longer maybe” (HM)

Their structures and processes deviate from those considered typical of SCM widely encountered in advanced economies. Changing business culture and practices from traditional market behaviour to more efficient and coordinated supply chains is a challenge for many incumbent enterprises. Next important factor discussed by retailers that affects circular model from their end is high cost of sustainable solutions. For retailers’ the circular economy transition is costly and time-consuming process in the way of disposing off wastage biologically, reverse logistics or cost of environmentally friendly products (Keulen and Kirchherr, 2020). So far there is not any financial support scheme being introduced by the government to encourage the retailers and customers to bend toward sustainable systems. Dependency on the private or existing funds make it difficult for companies to change the existing systems (Yalçın and Foxon, 2021).

“See at the end of the day everyone is concerned about money. Consumer will only follow the ethical practices if consumer do not end up paying extra for those products. And retailer will only consider the product which consumer prefer to buy.” (BD)

“Again, money factor comes in retailers have to pay to utilise the waste which nobody wants to so, sending it to landfill is [an] easier and cheaper option, especially for small retailers.” (MG)

For circular model to get established in food industries it is important to be financially viable along with fulfilling health and safety requirements with concrete policy addressing the financial benefits for all parties involved in it. On the other hand, factors like profitability and competition

were remarkably stated by retailers as challenge. Whereas supportive legislation, investment, requirement of technologies, minimum order quantities, post-Brexit trade and less collaboration have very low to nil impact on retailers to apply circularity in their supply chains according to this research.

4.4.4 Effects on Consumption Stage

The circular economy is an emergent topic in the literature of supply chain management and sustainability. Consumers being an integral and most important part of practical implications of circular supply chain, has not been addressed significantly in the previous studies (Van Weelden et al., 2016; De los Ríos and Charnley, 2017; Mugge et al., 2017; Murray et al., 2017; Singh and Giacosa, 2019). Consumers are the stakeholders of circular supply chain who ultimately affects the decisions of other stakeholders. Therefore, it is important to dig down their side of challenges. During this research 5 consumers were contacted who are professionals and have significant interest in sustainability practises. Most challenging factors referred by consumers were lack of awareness, perception and attitude, demographic factors i.e., income or buying power and lack of supportive legislation shown as matrix analysis table 5.9.

Table 4.10: Consumption stage barriers frequency

Barriers in circular supply chain management	Supply chain actors: Supply Chain Stage = Consumption	A: AM	B: JK	C: JSS	D: WY	E: RM
		1: High cost of products and raw material	12.68%	0	0	1
2: Investment	2.83%	0	1	0	0	0
3: Minimum order quantity	2.63%	0	0	0	0	1
4: Profitability	0%	0	0	0	0	0
5: Lack of government support	0%	0	0	0	0	0
6: Lack of supportive legislation	14.24%	3	0	0	0	0
7: Post- Brexit Trade	13.94%	1	0	0	0	1
8: Competition	0.61%	0	0	0	1	0
9: Inappropriate marketing strategies	0%	0	0	0	0	0
10: Lack of management commitment	0%	0	0	0	0	0
11: Demographic factors	15.25%	0	1	2	0	0
12: Lack of awareness	10%	1	1	1	1	0
13: Organisation Culture	0%	0	0	0	0	0
14: Perception and attitude	11.26%	1	0	1	0	2
15: Complexity in nature	4.19%	0	0	2	0	0
16: Lack of collaboration	0%	0	0	0	0	0
17: Lack of structure	0%	0	0	0	0	0
18: CE Specific technologies	6.01%	0	1	0	0	0
19: Knowledge, skill, and expertise	1.31%	0	0	0	0	1
20: Order and forecasting	0%	0	0	0	0	0
21: Shelf Life	5.05%	0	1	0	0	0

Source: NVivo 12 matrix query

Awareness and sense of urgency are considered as important factors which become barriers to adopt circular actions on the consumer level (Masi et al., 2016). Bressanelli and Scccani (2018) consider it as one of the seven major categories being challenge for redesigning the supply chains. It is prerequisite to have awareness among the people about value retention, regeneration and design innovation (Braungart and McDonough, 2009; Romero and Molina, 2010; Lacy and Rutqvist, 2015; Forlin and Scholz, 2017). Consumers share the views about the type of awareness required for a successful circular model.

“That is difficult. Until or unless there is knowledge in the general public, and it has been imposed by government bodies it will be a challenge in food sector.” (WY)

“Talking about awareness, you are aware of the wastage, you are aware of the sustainability, but nobody picturing it that how this model will fit into the circular economy. You might be doing

this, but you do not know what are doing is right thing to do. It might have different impact. you are not filling up landfills by the plastic but are you are aware of the impact you [are] having [like] carbon emission. Like from the Carbon emission side of it that is the one thing of it that it is not landing into the landfill.” (JK)

Another consumer quotation gives more transparency about the fact:

“First the awareness is [that] how important it is like to first of all to save the food rather than going into waste things. but if it is going into waste things what else we can do. To save it. can we feed to the hungry mouth?”

The above comments from customers demand making the public aware about the basic idea of the circular economy, environmental implications of not accepting it or not adopting the right procedures along with the possible alternatives, solutions or strategies. There was discussion about demographic factors like education, income and status of consumers being disinclined from circular solutions. One of the consumers raises the concern that the more buying power people have, the less they tend to have concern and control about buying and wasting. Whereas another consumer shares that the more the societies are well to do, the more they can spend on education about the environment and raising awareness about the circular economy.

“Additionally, I would say awareness is actually about who you are, what is your education, what is your background like I would say the more educated you are, more aware you are and if you don’t have worry about what you’re putting into your plate, more you will be involved with sustainability things. This is the reason that countries like Germany are doing better in recycling and all because people are more educated and financially settled.” (JK)

“Everyone is self-dependent and earning a good amount of money to live a good life, if he or she is working minimum hours. He can buy good food. He can pay his or her expenses and all expenses, they can bear right. And sometimes even. I need only one kg of something and [there are] two KG on offer or something. It’s promoted by company; I will buy two Kgs. What I will do with another KG which I bought extra is going in bin straight away. People sometimes do not really bother. it is just one pound so don’t worry about that. So, at one side [it] is positive because

I can bear my expenses and I'm living good life but on the flipside of the coin I am wasting, I do not value of that that one pound.” (JSS)

Like the other stages of the supply chain, less involvement of government in terms of apposite rules and regulation and perception and attitude of customers were another important matter of discussion by consumers. A participant urges the government to take arduous actions regarding the circular economy by introducing the charges for not following environmentally friendly practices.

“I am sure if government can notice that or put into the agenda, to avoid that wastage. I think government is not serious about food wastage. They should step up and they should introduce some kind of rule regulations the way they introduce it for the environment as a ULEZ zone. They're charging the fines, not fine I would say charge. Charges are working, people are avoiding going to central London they prefer to going for the public transport. So, I don't think any reason why govt is not stepping it up introducing a rule, where food wastage is considered as I mean it will lead to a penalty.” (AM)

“As a society, we all should play part to achieve sustain[able] economy. We need to have changes in shopping habits” (RM)

And another participant from the consumption phase reflects on changing behaviour towards products and shopping which can lead towards circularity. Additionally, dynamics like post-Brexit trade, the circular economy specific technologies and complexity in nature were discussed by consumers but in the context of industries. These factors do not directly impact the consumption stage of circular supply chain management, whereas investment, competition, minimum order quantities aspects have very minimal or indirect influence on consumers.

4.4.5 Effects on Upcycling stage

Upcycling is a stage of circular supply chain management which facilitate closing the loops process by modifying or renewing the product of same or higher quality before it goes for recycling (McDonough and Braungart, 2013; Armstrong et al., 2015; Sung et al., 2015; Moreno et al., 2016). Hence, to justify this research empirically, it is important to explore the challenges at this stage of

the circular supply chain. Food-product upcycling is not a widespread process in the industries at present, so a director of machines upcycling (food industry) company was interviewed. The most impeding factors discovered at this stage of the circular supply chain are demographic factors i.e., spending power of individuals or an organisation and perception and attitude towards upcycled products. Upcycled products are not preferred due to suspicion towards used material and fear of breakdown (Singh et al., 2019).

“But customers really depend on demographic factors, and I think the attitude is different depending on the demographic and financial ability in companies, you find it harder to convince people that why they have to spend little extra money for an environmentally friendly alternative.”
(AF)

The above quotation from a participant is consistent with Yoo et al. (2021) that there is always an uncertainty with upcycled products and associated financial risk to it about these products not meeting the expectations of users and having potential failure. It makes customers not willing to spend on upcycled products. Mitchell and Papavassiliou (1999) illustrate, elements like similarity of products and uncertainty of information make the customers difficult to have green products as choice. As these operations have not been very established in food related industries, having financial risk associated with it, investors are less likely to invest in ventures in the environment where upcycled products are less of a priority for customers. It creates investment and profitability as a challenge for businesses.

“So, if you have business falling of these categorise like our one where obviously number one priority is to make profit but also like to do best to help the environment so it involves two phases. It needs to be beneficial to the business otherwise it is not going to happen.” (AF)

“I can see there going to be risk to up-step to businesses, So, instead of imposing taxes as punishment, government can have reward for the opposite” (AF)

“So, if you have business falling of these categorise like our one where obviously number one priority is to make profit but also like to do best to help the environment so it involves two phases. It needs to be beneficial to the business otherwise it's not going to happen, isn't it?”

Linking to investment, the participant promotes the government interventions to provide financial support and motivate the ideas (Ünal et al., 2018). The analysis observed the barriers highlighted by Klewitz and Hensen, (2014) that upcycling requires high technicalities, skills and process innovation. Products and services related to upcycling should be convincing to be able to become established in the market (Sung et al., 2019). Therefore, upcycling need support from higher authorities as well as from common people.

Table: 4.11: Upcycling stage barriers frequency

Barriers to circular supply chain	Supply chain actors: Supply Chain Stage = Consumption	A: AF
1: High cost of products and raw material	0%	0
2: Investment	10.42%	2
3: Minimum order quantity	0%	0
4: Profitability	8.17%	1
5: Lack of government support	9.78%	1
6: Lack of supportive legislation	15.38%	1
7: Post- Brexit Trade	4.97%	1
8: Competition	0%	0
9: Inappropriate marketing strategies	0%	0
10: Lack of management commitment	0%	0
11: Demographic factors	22.92%	2
12: Lack of awareness	0%	0
13: Organisation Culture	0%	0
14: Perception and attitude	16.35%	1
15: Complexity in nature	0%	0
16: Lack of collaboration	0%	0
17: Lack of structure	0%	0
18: Lack of CE Specific technologies	5.13%	1
19: Knowledge, skill, and expertise	6.89%	1
20: Order and forecasting	0%	0
21: Shelf Life	0%	0

Source: NVivo 12 Matrix query analysis

To sum up, stakeholders from the upcycling stage get affected by the demographical factors like spending power on environmental solutions, perception, and attitude towards upcycled and remanufactured products, lack of supportive legislation barriers directly and immensely. High investment government support, profitability knowledge and skills and post-Brexit trade were also discussed in the context of upcycling business. However, other factors were not mentioned at this stage.

4.4.6 Effect on recycling stage

The last stage for a product in the circular supply chain is recycling or downcycling. Recycling of products expedites the aim of the circular supply chain management to have restorative and regenerative systems in place (De Angelis et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2018; Husain and Malik, 2020). To investigate the managerial issues at the recycling stage, the researcher contacted four individuals from the recycling stage. All the participants are from areas of food recycling including an anaerobic digestion plant, household waste recycling, a food packaging waste recycler, and a local council worker. The challenge discussed by the greatest number of participants is lack of knowledge, skills and expertise, whereas lack of structure is mostly discussed as a challenge by a business development manager.

“I guess now it does also come down to kind of personal in terms of you know who’s in charge of doing what kind of thing. You know, in terms of making sure that the right solution is put in place that helps with the buying. You know if it’s if it’s a complicated process in terms of you know, and it makes their job a bit harder to do something in terms of both in the food. You might not then get applying because it might be the guys are on the floor to say, if doing this, costs couple of saving a couple of minutes so you know it’s making sure that the right kind of processes are in place for the site to be doing the right thing. you know it’s easy for the guys just to quickly do it into making it as easy as possible for you otherwise you might not get those buyers.” (MP)

“Knowledge is important and right knowledge. People who are into it already or they might know what it exactly means and what to do exactly but very rare, I think. People do not really know what actually to do. In the food industry there is health and safety, and risk is higher, I think.”

As per the above respondent, food waste management in the bigger scale industries is a complex process and need to have a clear structure in place including well defined roles to sort the waste material for the recyclers to able to take and reuse it efficiently. Undoubtedly industries and policy makers are moving towards accepting sustainability and the circular economy transitions but lacking behind in knowledge, resources, and infrastructure to make it happen practically Sivaprakasam et al., (2015); Govindan and Hasanagic (2018); Mangla et al., (2018). Furthermore, recyclers believe that they do not get enough support from the government in the way of providing financial and economic instruments (Su et al., 2013) and there are fewer collaborative policies that lead all the circular economy stakeholders towards common goal. There is unclarity about tasks on the specific level. There is need to scrutinize each region specifically and need to make policies according to the requirement of those regions (Govindan and Hasanagic, 2018).

“No, the government is not helpful because they are going on about recycling and hitting the recyclers. Where there should be looking at the start of the problem. There should be focussing on starting bit not the ending of it. As a person you will not hand over the keys of your car to the wrong person. You can’t stop him afterwards when they hit somebody or may stop him before it happens.” (AB)

Table: 4.12: Recycling stage barriers frequency

Barriers to circular supply chain	A: Supply chain actors: Supply Chain Stage = Recycling				
		A: AB	B: GW	C: MP	D: TS
1: High cost of products and raw material	6.34%	0	0	3	0
2: Investment	9.71%	1	0	1	0
3: Minimum order quantity	0%	0	0	0	0
4: Profitability	1.56%	1	1	0	0
5: Lack of government support	14.54%	3	1	0	0
6: Lack of supportive legislation	0%	0	0	0	0
7: Post- Brexit Trade	5.22%	0	0	0	1
8: Competition	0%	0	0	0	0
9: Inappropriate marketing strategies	0%	0	0	0	0
10: Lack of management commitment	0%	0	0	0	0
11: Demographic factors	0%	0	0	0	0
12: Lack of awareness	10.93%	0	1	1	0
13: Organisation Culture	3.07%	0	0	1	0

14: Perception and attitude	5.66%	0	0	4	0
15: Complexity in nature	0%	0	0	0	0
16: Lack of collaboration	9.56%	1	0	0	1
17: Lack of structure	20.39%	0	0	5	0
18: CE Specific technologies	0%	0	0	0	0
19: Knowledge, skill and expertise	13.02%	1	0	3	1
20: Order and forecasting	0%	0	0	0	0
21: Shelf Life	0%	0	0	0	0

Source: NVivo 12 matrix query analysis

“Taking example of councils, there is no coordination between the boroughs and central policies are not same which lead them to follow the same rule specially in the terms of recycling or the circular economy. We here in Hounslow have different process of waste collection, segregation than the next borough Hillingdon. Why there cannot be same standard everywhere. Policy makers should come together map it out. It is ineffectual model at the moment, the circular economy is not feasible in this scenario” (TS)

Interviews from recycling stage revealed that highly crucial factor in the circular economy and the reason of it not embedded into system from recycling side is, less awareness of right practices among people and framework and structure has not been provided by the government.

“Getting people to do what you need them to do. Getting people to use the right bin, not throwing the food in general bin or removing the packaging properly before putting the food into food bin that sort of stuff because people aren’t that interested. You’ve got all these things that you could/should be done but you can’t make them happen. There are lots of issues, people are not aware that how dangerous it could be if the trends go like this. Firstly, people don’t think while buying, then don’t think while using or utilising and then disposing them off. They buy a lot, sometimes intentionally some time unintentionally, then use in unplanned way like food which is gonna go off soon they keep and keep them and dispose them off. And as mentioned earlier they don’t segregate them carefully again sometimes intentionally sometimes unintentionally, because many a times people don’t have facilities to dispose them separately. Separate bins have not been provided by councils or people don’t have time or may be many other things you know. They don’t have required knowledge and structure.” (GW)

Apart from aforementioned challenges, there are financial challenges which affect the recycling stage. There is huge investment needed for opening a business in recycling and there is not any financial support provide by government. At the same time recycling being an additional cost for food industries, they find it difficult to follow the circular economy model. Additionally, other elements have very less or no direct impact of recycling stage.

4.4.7 Effects on logistics stage:

Product in supply chain becomes able to circular through the various stage through logistic process. Ideal processes for circular supply chain management are green logistics and reverse logistics. To explore the issues faced by logistics stage in the circular supply chain model, a dispatch manager from a food manufacturing company was interviewed. The main challenge current structure of supply chains is not appropriate to enable green and reverse logistics. It includes geographical location, less capacity of companies as compared to the volume of production infrastructure of the organisation or lack of communication.

“Loophole is you have to know your capacity as a company. In the manufacturing process we know how many meals we can make a week. making about 1.2 million meals a week and we are running flat out. so, this also social responsibility of the company to look at the base model we cannot handle more than 1.1 million meals.” (AZ)

The following quotation from a dispatch manager exposes the need of amendments in structure of companies to be able to get less environmental impacts:

“We have an issue of location, when the vehicles enter the same way and the exit as same way because we are on the dual carriageway, it becomes the reason of Co2 addition and inefficiency of logistics.”

Above concern in the comment from a respondent was recognised in the literature by (Lenzen, 1998; Hugo and Pis-tikopoulos, 2005; Duchin 2008; Benoit, 2009; Chen et al., 2010; Pantavidis, 2012; (Sutthichaimethee and Tanoamchard, 2015), stating that consumers are looking for more consumption in less budgets and businesses focus on maximizing their profit with less investment but cost of over-consumption and over – production to environment is neglected by both of the parties. Over- production led to huge amount of Co2 emission and food wastage due to lack of space and handling in food industries.

Correspondingly, because of industries restrictions and cost saving approach with minimum order quantity, it becomes a challenge for managing the space for finished goods. Furthermore, while consumers have more variety and buying options it contributes to more unsold products, rate of returns and ultimately more wastage. For reverse logistics activities, perceptions and attitude of consumers was highlighted by logistic stage in following comment.

“I think, the consumer is getting really clever now. They don’t [only] want value for money but they are also looking outside the box, the packaging and other facilities.” (AZ)

Table: 4.13: Logistic stage barrier frequency

Barriers to circular supply chain	A: AZ	A: AZ
1: High cost of products and raw material	0%	0
2: Investment	3.76%	1
3: Minimum order quantity	12.4%	1
4: Profitability	6.91%	2
5: Lack of government support	0%	0
6: Lack of supportive legislation	0%	0
7: Post- Brexit Trade	0%	0
8: Competition	0%	0
9: inappropriate marketing strategies	0%	0
10: Lack of management commitment	10.67%	1
11: Demographic factors	0%	0
12: Lack of awareness	0%	0
13: Organisation Culture	11.18%	1
14: Perception and attitude	13.52%	1
15: Complexity in nature	2.24%	1
16: Lack of collaboration	0%	0
17: Lack of structure	35.16%	3
18: CE Specific technologies	0%	0
19: Knowledge, skill and expertise	0%	0
20: Order and forecasting	0%	0
21: Shelf Life	4.17%	1

Matrix Analysis: Logistics Stage

Infrastructure, manpower and change in organisation structure are fundamental requirement for reverse logistics to implement the circular economy in supply chain (Ravi and Shankar, 2005). Lack of structure

was similarly emphasised by logistic stakeholder. Perception and attitude of consumers about over buying and returning the products is challenge for logistics for the management of circular processes, minimum order quantities make the business to buy raw material and products which is problematic for logistic to handle and ultimately go to waste in food industries because of limited life, organisation culture and management commitment also need a serious concern. Other factors have minimum and no direct impact on logistics stage of the circular economy.

4.5 DRIVERS TO OVERCOME THE BARRIERS

The vision towards nil wastage and nil emission would be exigent yet attainable (Heyes et al., 2018). This section is a profound analysis of strategies which can lead the food industries toward the innovative approach, circular supply chain management. Drivers discussed in this research are the key activities which have been suggested by the experts and literature, to overcome the challenges examined and illustrated in the previous section. Corresponding to the six types to barriers, drivers have been categorised in different segments. Analysis of challenges indicates that the factors affecting the transition of circular supply chain management are interconnected, determinant of each other and work as a chain reaction to make it unsuccessful (Kirchherr et al., 2018). Hence, the discussion of drivers is in the sequence of relevance and priority.

Figure: 4.3: Graphical representation of themes and subthemes (drivers)

Source: NVivo 12 mind map

4.5.1 Drivers to institutional barriers

From existing studies of circular supply chain management and the participants of this research, it was established that government is the most prominent driver to apply this revolutionary change. “Government has a part to play or practically everything, I guess. Whether it is by the way of encouraging or by way of regulating or imposing”. Shahbazi et al., (2016) explains that eco-efficiency strategies are more concerned with high level of policies and service measures for which government is responsible. Government has a primary role in the development of green solutions (Li et al., 2015).

Assisting and Incentivising:

All the participants agreed and shared the ways by which government can be a supportive body for transforming the linear food supply chains into circular. Correspondingly, an entrepreneur from a recycling plant shares his experience about his invention for sorting plastic waste, for which he also appeals for government assistance.

“Then, I invented the way how to get plastic out of water and how to stop plastic make so much pollution. I went in London and then I [got] it registered for patent of attorney If I need to break the wall, I need help from the government, how to get up the step of ladder. If this idea was put in the hands of right people, it would do good to many (...) So, yea we are still hoping it will come up. Then you will see my picture in the newspaper.” (AB)

There was also a discussion about rewarding the stakeholders, who are contributing towards circularity practices. Rewarding will motivate the stakeholders to accept risk and apply the circular model.

“It’s again the government can give subsidies to the companies for reducing their waste companies, some kind of incentives. Like some fruits and vegetable can be used as a manoeuvre by farmers. You don’t need artificial fertilisers all the time. You can use this as manoeuvres for the fertilizers. So, if the company give wasted food back to the farmers and depending on how much they [are] doing, the government can actually give some kind of incentives to the to both the

farmers for taking it and the companies, retailers for giving them. That would you know motivate companies to do these things and they are a lot of food that can be used as fertilizers”. (PG)

“I can see there gonna be risk to up-step, So, instead of imposing taxes as punishment they can have reward for the opposite.” (AZ)

Participant explains in below quotation the type of incentives industries looking for:

“Without that incentive, it doesn’t make financial sense to build an AD plant but saying that you know with the local authority or going to start collecting the food waste from the 2023 that will see bring, you know, a large proportion of tonnage into the market which they are potentially isn’t going to be capacity for. So obviously the government is then, will need to introduce something like this.”

Government being a main player must take the initiative to financially support the environment related ventures (Pompoini and Moncater, 2017). This can be by reducing taxes, providing subsidies, zero percent loans, motivating the research, development, and innovations.

Designing a circular framework:

This study represents that current regulations are not appropriate and are not aligned with the circular model. Government can establish a new marketplace for the circular economy with instituting and revising the current practises and conveying to interested parties that will create the demand and opportunities for a circular system (Tura et al., 2019; Harteley et al., 2021). Rigorous rules and regulations along with the strategies based on the circular supply chain framework have been demanded from the government. “Currently, priorities of rules are different I think.”

“If government starts putting or imposing good fines on the supply chain thing or on the manufacturing about what they are wasting and how they are wasting and controlling their waste then definitely it will sort some part of it.” (VS)

“So, now the only way to control which is I would say I’ll be agree only “the system”. So, system will definitely work. for example. we drive a car on the road. If there is a red light, then we have to stop. If there’s a green light, we have to go to. Our brain is now designed in that way. Anything

is controlled by the government will go well, so make the systems like. first of all, then then only it will be possible.” (JSS)

Participants demand that creating the systematic framework for the circular economy for industries and the public, regular control and introducing fines for those who do not accept and follow it will be a top-bottom driving method.

“Government is the most important. They are the prominence regulatory bodies from them every initiative is regulated and followed by. Now the question is, how strict they are to make circular supply chain happen, how they are driving it. No matter what targets you are setting, what policies you are writing, it will not drive the change until or you have the roadmap, and the strategies with enforcement. Your regulations should be hard enough to drive this change. UK government is lacking behind in introducing appropriate rules and regulation as compare[d] to many EU countries.” (JH)

Aforementioned drivers are equally prioritised in the literature by Amrina and Yousuf, (2012), Pejunen et al., (2012), Pejunen et al., (2013) and Murakami et al., (2015) in the way of maintaining required standards, providing financial support and development of circular thinking.

“Definitely, I think that is the key. You know there are rules and regulations, legislations, that will play huge impact like for e.g., Giving businesses grant or giving business somethings like saying re use your waste, to be inventive. Basically, you are not producing waste and landfills. I think business will also want to be responsible for everything they produce” (BR)

“The government needs to set targets for this and conduct ... as their own. There might already be sustainability targets, but it needs to be tightened up on all areas not just fields or resources, they need to look food as resource as well.” (DE)

These statements are consistent with existing studies by Adams et al., (2017); Potting et al., (2017); Pomponi and Moncaster, (2017); Silva et al., (2018). The designed framework should be target based and the circular economy needs to be part of short-term and long-term plans along with road maps.

4.5.2 Drivers to socio-cultural barriers

Socio-cultural factors are related to the consumer and company culture. The barriers found in this category are lack of awareness and right information, organisation culture and perception, attitude, and behaviour of people towards this transformation or products or services. Socio-cultural factors, specifically awareness is the strongest factor. The majority of academics as well as participants in this study argued to increase awareness about circular practices in supply chain processes. “The awareness is there but awareness is not regarding the circular economy. So, the awareness around the customers is stopping the food waste and recyclability.”, and “That is how management comes into picture that management might not be aware of it”. It reveals, whether it is companies or consumers, that the right awareness is the foremost driver to apply circular supply chain management practices (Tura et al., 2019).

Educating through school curriculum and social media

There are several ways discussed by food supply chain professionals and consumers that can develop understanding of the circular approach. Out of which the most discussed is part of education. Experts urge the circular economy to be part of the school curriculum.

“The circular economy needs to be a part of school education, I believe. Like other subjects, this should be a core subject from where it will be originated. This is the best way to convey the need of sustainability, various ideas will come in this way from the innovative minds which can be applied in the businesses and societies. And we as parents will also listen and follow to the kids rather any other method.” (JH)

“Global Warming have become daunting yet imminent, therefore we all have taken active part whether as parents, teachers, counsellor we should do more efforts to make children, students aware of recycling, utilisation of resources”. (RM)

Along with school education, participants suggest required training and development for employees to educate them with the consequences. It will be helpful to bring cultural change in companies. An interviewee stress:

“Other barriers might be internal education so if the people within the business try to understand the implication and why we [are] doing something specific and they can get [it]. Because they don’t want change otherwise because they don’t consider it as benefit.” (NR)

Here, the interviewee stresses that people are always resistant to change, either because of attitude or lack of awareness that what benefits the new process can bring. In the context of food circular supply chain management, all stakeholders need to have knowledge about the reasons and advantages of adoption which will drive change in a positive way. For the sustainability of this model in the long run there needs to be continuous education programs (Farooque et al., 2019).

“Government should be educating the circular to people to make their mindsets. I think it take big plans, probably make it for inline [with] the requirement of the people those company’s supply. So, for example a retailer turns around and say 90 percent of your waste, your food waste is used for the purposes for X, Y or Z. Then, there will be real drive to make that happen, may be not achieve it but to make it happen until in the pass way in the 5 years planning process. So, its bit like whole recycling thing. Every business recycles initially or recycle until the retailers and bit education needs to be there. Initially when these things like reducing plastics started. There used to boards where we used to see how the elusions are getting filled out and animals are getting killed, I mean it can be done for the circular economy as well. In the way of making people more aware not just. And finding the people who want to do it.” (JK)

Stakeholders also request the government to intervene by doing the campaigns, educating thorough social media, movies documentaries. It will be best way to reach the general public. People should be aware of the results of not accepting this transition and the benefits to accepting it.

“Maybe government can run the campaigns. Like the polios and all that. Like they are right now, they are running for Covid-19 and all that. Why not do for the environment. I mean they have it but they [are] all silent, they are not as open. If there’s a World Cup tomorrow here, they’ll be running another campaign for God knows for how many days. If there is football league, they will be running for months and months. So, they are wasting so much money in those campaigns, why not here? Maybe they can do it in their movies, you know, because the movies have a big soft power, they can do that”. (PG)

“That is difficult. Until or unless there is not knowledge in the general public, and it has not been imposed by government bodies it will be a challenge in food sector.” (WY)

Making it a part of education system will drive the positive change.

“I think people nowadays, from including schools or how we educate our kids in developed countries like our requirement is on how we are going to sustain and sustainable farming. It will depend on how we educate ourselves and how we going to teach people around us and bring up the culture.”

The head of supply chain shares its practice:

“You have to live and breathe it every day, you can’t just write on a form and say that’s our core values everybody. Everyone has to live and breathe it”

Interviewees revealed in the above quotations that government can be a pertinent player to spread the awareness among the public and the medium can be social media, advertisements, or campaigns with information regarding the consequences for not adopting it and benefits of adopting it. Since knowledge and awareness have a huge impact on people’s attitude (Mostaghel and Chirumalla, 2021), it will be an initial step in the circular supply chain model by bringing environmental awareness, brand awareness, ethical product awareness to change consumers’ perception towards green solutions (Ko et al., 2013; Chen and Lee, 2015)

Embedding in processes

Another aspect to overcome from cultural barriers is altering the company policies to be more ethical and making the circular economy value for stakeholders. The sustainability business model collaborates in ecological and social outcomes which benefit all the stakeholders (Freudenreich et al., 2020). The circular economy-based model will bring an optimistic change when it is embedded in the processes and culture with the clear vision of valuing each stakeholder and communicating it to stakeholders. The following statement of a participant supports this opinion

“I think it comes very much from the top. Kerry as a company have it a net zero by, I think 2030, umm without that kind of culture if my company did not care about sustainability, I would have no

support working on these projects, I think. Having a support from this company, if my manager comes back to me that he does not care about sustainability then actually, I will be only thinking about sales number.” (MC)

“Like in my company, whatever we do, we have some standard set of doing things. They call this Greggs way, even a small thing. I can’t do like you know, I will do this way and you can do it this way, No. It does not work like that we have specific way [s] of doing things. So, in that case they should add sustainability part in that culture, culture of the company. Then people might take it seriously and will focus on it more. Like if you give them a choice, they might not follow it but like if the company say, this is the standard set of doing things and this should be done only like this and it’s our culture, then may be everybody follow it.” (KD)

To make this transition integrated and successful value creation, it should be created for each of the stakeholders (Freeman, 2000) and consistent with the above comments, creation of value effectively requires activities to be arranged in organisation processes (Johnson, 2010; Lambert., 2012; Abdelkafi et al., 2013). When these initiatives are part of companies’ everyday process and employees are aware about the values it provides to them, there will be less chances to breach and refusals to accept it.

4.5.3 Drivers to finance related barriers

The significant factor that could led to ineffectiveness of circular supply chain model is finance difficulties on different stages. Finance related barriers classified in this research are investment, cost of material, the profit generation approach and return investment. Participants from each stage of the circular supply chain emphasise the need of government support in different ways to overcome from finance related challenges. The most discussed driver for financial barriers is incentivising the circular economy initiatives.

Competitive pricing strategies

From the retailing side, the suggestion made by a manager is to make the price of sustainable and normal products the same, to make the people able to buy them.

“So, let’s the retailers or the supply chains make it the same price which is a big-big question”.
(HM)

Moreover, the participant mentions the cheap cost of products and technology should be driven from the consumer side, which would pressurise from the bottom to the top side, beginning from consumers through retailers, manufacturers and then the government.

“Umm., I think if we [are] talking about circular supply chain here., there has to be umm an upside for the consumer to ask in the reduction in the price, technology has to be sustainable first and technology has to cheap umm which I dare to begin with its not going to be. But this is part on it. it’s the technology, it’s the way of things, it’s worth starts out cheap umm providing there is cost incentive then I think it could grow.” (PJ)

Stakeholders also suggest a bottom-top up process of forcing price reduction. If the public is aware about the 3 layers of benefits (social, environmental, and economic) for following the circular model it will be a positive force for the circular economy.

Carrot -stick approach

Another factor raised by the participant is to drive this agenda from the incentive in helping investors with the cheap loans option, who specifically have innovative ideas and willingness to spend.

This strategy is evidenced from the existing study of Hart et al., (2019), that fiscal and regulatory carrots and sticks should be applied by providing tax incentives and public procurement.

“I think this probably two things that spooked like straight away, I think, how the government help organisations to achieve it. Whether are funding, grants, to get cheap loans to be able to invest (...). To get cheap loans to be able to invest. That will help. So, I think grants and then what points they make for all companies hit to the regulations. what point you regulatory to keep things consistent” (HM)

A participant suggests:

“Again, it is incentivizing, what is in for industry that makes it worthwhile. So that’s tax rebates are there, is driving us profit” (RJ)

Furthermore, sharing an example of electric cars, a manager from a retailing company appeals to the government to back the retailers in financial terms to motivate them to go for sustainable practices.

“Companies can be some kind of incentivised, or the government can introduce some kind of subsidies for companies to use the sustainable products in their manufacturing more. So, because you see, when we think about sustainability, we straight away think about retailer’s role. But what is the government doing to motivate those retailers, they need some kind of motivation from the government as well. What is the government doing for them? I don’t think they’re doing anything as far as I know. For example, government in India is providing a lot of subsidies on electric cars. because of that There is a boom in India in manufacturers to go on electric, so they are motivated. So, they are motivat[ing] although the infrastructure in India is not doesn’t support enough electric cars right now, but there is a motivation. That is why a giant like Tesla is planning to move

in India. They are motivating both the manufacturers and consumers go for electric by giving them subsidies. Depending on the cost of your car the government is subsidising the car, so the price goes low. So, maybe something like that can be done in food sector or in retail sector to [be] safe.”
(PG)

However, on the other hand a participant enhances the fact that providing financial inducements to boost up circularity in the food industry is going to be tough task from government due to the size of the food industry.

“Looking at the size of incentives to encourage businesses, once you put down it to national level, umm, if you [are] talking about, for example tax deduction, umm it would be enormous and determinantal to the country. Because of the size of the industry” (NR)

This interview discussions reveal that stakeholders look for a financial benefit for doing any transformations in the existing systems. The carrot and stick approach should be adopted by the government to encourage investment in circular technologies, products, and business models. But the question is, how viable is it for government to provide these benefits.

4.5.4 Drivers to technical related barriers

Technical factors referred to here are the factors which provide immersive facilities to organisations. Barriers found in this category in relation to the food industry are short life of products, technologies to facilitate circularity, order forecasting and shortage of technical skills. This research suggests drivers for technical issues are to facilitate product traceability, measurability, techniques for product life extension and big data.

Product Traceability

This research exposed the enablers that can service the circular supply chain model to overcome these challenges are technologies for extending the life of products and easing sharing facilities. Literature accentuates the importance of technologies in the circular supply chain with the features of traceability of material used and production technologies, to decide a product’s pollutants elements during its lifetime (Tsoufias and Pappis, 2006; Rashid et al., 2013; Franco, 2019). The

consideration echoes with stakeholders' responses. Equally, a manager from the manufacturing stage gives an example about taking the green / ethical policy initiative with the traceability factor to ensure the sustainability factor throughout the supply chain.

“There also ethical bit. we have to find the right suppliers to get the raw materials in. And the social responsibility like where rice comes from. Does that come from the third world? or is [there] any people any workforce abuse[d]. Are we paying people the right amount of money? because they've got families to sustain, if you will think about it, is circular things. Certain[ly] everybody, the people who pick the rice if they are not happy in the workplace and you don't pay them the right amount of money you [are] failed on the first step.” (AZ)

The head of supply chain from food manufacturing and from retailing recommends traceability as possible solutions respectively.

“So, few things sticked me, the traceability and shelf-life. Specially looking and at mix kind of products, so we can take and send the products out.”

In food products, because of health and safety concerns, it is important to know the origin and the from where product has come to be able remanufacture them during processing or after consumption (de Sousa Jabbour et al., 2019)

Measurability

Ravi and Shankar 2005 state “Work not measured cannot be managed”. Based on this notion the research suggests devising a measurability feature. For the application of circular model, measurability should comprise of end to end. It can be measuring long-term benefits of the circular economy (Tura et al., 2019) or measuring effects for its non-application.

“I am not sure what is output in term of the circular economy at carbon footprints so some researcher like you could be working on it. At the end, how can it be assessed or measured”. (PK)

“Another thing is its quite difficult to measure carbon footprints. If the companies are carbon zero, I am not sure how they measure it. Yea, so, that's all I can think of.” (AF)

“I think we have to be able to measure it. That has been also quite a challenge in the past when we’re trying to set some of our internal kind of targets on these things. The obvious ones [is] waste to landfill which is, which is not common target. But again, how do we’re looking at you know, how do you see Co2 emissions. Well, actually how do you measure [it]”

Measurability on the organisation and product level is a significant driver for the circular supply chain framework. The loopholes are easy to control when affects are measured and transparent to the users. Companies should be able to measure and communicate the environmental and financial consequences of wasting a particular product. Techniques like lifecycle assessment are helpful to know the environmental impacts of products during its lifespan.

Product life extension

Another supporter for enabling circularity, extracted from this study, is innovating technologies for extending the life of products having health and safety as an integral aspect and not deteriorating in taste and texture of the food products. Participants reflect in the interviews as below.

“I would also add If we were successful in creating fresh nutrition meals, umm. via pasteurisation or retort which was palatable um and good on the eye or accepted by change by the time actually”
(PJ)

“So, technique or technology, if can help in that thing that we can get the product life increased and not affecting taste and texture. Because end consumer need[s] the product for human consumption and that there has to be taste, texture and likeness of the product. But yes, it[s] end result is nutrition value so legally and ethically that required. So, the food I [think] mainly taste, texture and likeness. So, the food we are making we should consider if it [is] attracting the end user. So if those umm kind of ingredients increasing the shelf life and not affecting the taste, texture or colour or eye appeal of the customer, I think this help massively in this industry.” (PK)

In above comment, a manager emphasises the importance of the product life extension technique which does not have any negative impact on taste, texture, and nutrition value of the product.

“We have concepts like zero-waste, fully circular products are kind of aspirational rather than necessarily in practice what would happen. In food industry circular aspect is tricky because food has a shelf-life thing attached to it. It is not like any other industries like clothing industry that we over buy and keep possessing them or like metal or furniture industry that it is easy to upcycle because no life restrictions are there. So, it needs technicalities, to increase the shelf life or make optimum use of the existing shelf life it’s like that (MG)

A stakeholder from the manufacturing stage of the supply chain also highlights to develop planning systems to facilitate product life extension.

“Ummm, there was planning system to predict the future. There is possibility, it was discussed a while ago back and I don’t know where it got to. There was discussion on add on things like nanopore technology for packaging, key for sustainability is all down to life of product, the more life you can give the product, less waste you will generate. Because the other problem you have got from commercial is we produce a product have 10 days lives and retailer wants at least 7 days when it gets in there. So, I can have product which then can have lack of sales, it still goes 6 days life because it doesn’t fit with retailers, they won’t take it. If the same product had 14 days, then I got 4 days to sell off, it would naturally go down to waste. That’s where technology comes in and to drives down the waste. If you give me more life of product, then I will have more chance of selling it.”

Professionals in the food industry suggest developing, modifying, or upgrading retort, pasteurisation techniques or nano technology in packaging to use to increase product shelf-life that maintains equal value of the product like the original, will be a revolution in the food industry for circular supply chain management.

Big data analytics

Furthermore, another expediter in the circular supply chain model to be added is technology development to enhance the “sharing of food” giving the example of a mobile application called “Too good to go”. This mobile application is currently used by food restaurants and shops on a small scale to used up left-over food. Developing such applications or data sharing facilities on a larger scale can reduce a huge amount of food going to waste and reduce the carbon emissions.

“Like the app I was taking about is a fantastic app, I go and buy from that app. The name of the app is “Too good to go”, that I am using. So, if you use that app and put your location, they find out your nearby small restaurant like Costa and all. You have to pay them certain amount £3- £4 whatever is required, and the box of goodies will be given to you. We do know what is there in the bag you just pick up the things which about to go to the waste. So that is the brilliant idea. So, these are the factors which can be looked into” (VS)

“You can have the best machines in the world, but the people have to be trained and understand, the elements of production, dispatch, technical, whatever field you are working in, because it affects everybody” (AZ)

The circular economy model requires tools, technologies and capabilities to facilitate life extension, transparency, measurability and sharing economy technologies (De los and Charnley, 2016; Poppelaars et al., 2018; Sinclair et al., 2018; Wastling et al., 2018). Technologies can help retailers and manufacturers to share data about the products which are going to be expire and help share those products and raw materials among firms which can be waste for one but can be useful for others.

4.5.5 Drivers to structural barrier

Circular supply chain management is an integration of numerous processes, working hand in hand to achieve the zero-waste target. For the accomplishment of this vision, circular supply chain management stakeholders have to have solid networks and coordination among all the players to control the externalities and outflows (Antikainen et al., 2013; Gupta et al., 2019).

Collaboration

Barriers related to structure in the circular model are complex in nature, less relevant infrastructure, and lack of coordination. These barriers can be overcome by assigning a department to the circular economy and the relationship model including coordination and communication supported by infrastructure.

“So, need to align with the production, with the commercial. Again, its not only cooking, but you also need to see the capacity of packing, cartooning and dispatch and so need smart way of thinking considering every department. Like, I can cook it but if packing can’t pack it, it will go to the waste again. So, the end-to-end should be very clear.” (SKV)

An ideal circular business model involves commitment and value network of all the stakeholders. Value network infrastructure has a critical role to play in circular business models (Geissdoerfer et al., 2019) because of a mixture of resources and collaborative forms (Zucchella and Previtali, 2018; Brent et al., 2019). Existing research confirms that research on sustainable business models is derived from creating value from waste, designing products from waste material, adding reverse logistic processes, efficient communication, and collaboration.

“Structure needs to be nature specific. Taking example of councils, there is no coordination between the boroughs and central policies are also not same which lead them to follow the same rule specially in the terms of recycling or the circular economy. I think central government should intervene here to make the circular economy model applicable to everyone. We here in Hounslow have different process of waste collection, segregation than the next borough Hillingdon. When people moved around or have to live on different places in different boroughs, it takes time for them to follow those rules. Why some regional councils don’t make it necessary to follow sustainability. It is ineffectual for models like the circular economy.” (TS)

An interviewee explains:

“It can be done if councils and other stakeholders start working on it together even if they give double pounds for that but that can reduce lots of landfills. These are the ways to change the mind sets of the mass of the public, so I think food industry has big focus on the waste because expenses

and ingredients or transport is expensive. So, drive is massive and focus very deep. But there is a lot of work needs to be done on various stages.”

As per the quotations from different stakeholders from different stages of the circular supply chain, it is well-defined that the network of the circular model is nested in a way so that gaps in one part can lead to wastage in all parts and failure of the model. It exposes the type of model that the circular model required is, co-operating with each department of the supply chain so that processes can be aligned looking at the capacity of all.

Sustainability / the circular economy division

The research suggests having a separate division for the circular economy in the structure to manage the processes effectively and efficiently. Next, a remark from a head of the supply chain of a retailer company explore the importance of having a specific structure for such prototypes because it will make the management of that department place required energy, resources, and efforts to lead towards progressive results.

“I think it leads back to the management question which is I think you have to have a structure that shows the importance of that area so if try and say, this is our biggest objective and this is our KPI on it and then put no resource to it so it’s not going to be delivered. Structures needs to be an appropriate resource attributed to it. The widely depending on how organisations are set up a lot of supply chains are kind of integrated supply chains. So, you end up having different departments may be looking after different things so somehow, you’ve got to just again just certain supply chain but how do you integrate, buyer might decide what’s the right thing to do, can stream any action you’ve got to consider the whole, end to end in the way, its structured. But that’s difficult when all designs necessarily put in silos little bit.” (HM)

Furthermore, the statement of participants from retailing describes the way sustainability departments in organisations can work concerning circular economy practices. Participants suggest allocating a circular economy specific team in companies which would hunt for innovative ideas and would provide guidance if any information is required.

“To start, I believe that the organisation can make a kind of separate division within those buyers, whose job will be just to hunt for the innovative producers. Who are doing something different than other producers and they can get the samples badge on those producers and place it in some of their stores to see how these products are hitting the market? Is there enough demand that is being cultivated rather than just the consumer giving the feedback to the retailer and then retailer pushing it forward? Retailers themselves can actually have a division within their organisation structure that these are some products that are quite innovative and quite different, are environmentally-friendly and they hit our target of reducing the waste.” (MG)

“I think they should add a separate department for that as well, a specific department. Whatever the communication is there regarding sustainability, you should be able to get all the information and communication from that department. So just like we have marketing department and finance department, I think there should have one more department. So, you can get all the necessary information and guidance from them. Again, there should be more transparency between all the departments of the company” (KD)

“Like in food restaurants and I think in whole food industry, there is food hygiene rating things are there, sustainability factor can also be introduced as fine structure. Look fine structure is very important, everything can be cured with fine structure.” (WY)

Participants also suggest the circular economy division should be from top (government) to bottom (operational) level. Regulatory authorities should set the standards for companies similar to food hygiene rating; there should be sustainability / circular economy ratings.

4.5.6 Drivers to management related barriers

Some of the participants believe that management is committed to prerequisites of sustainability, and it is the rules and regulations which must be more specific and circular economy oriented. However, some partakers suggest that management should design their strategies concurring with circular supply chain management; they should set objectives and targets to achieve success (Ravi and Shankar, 2004).

Developing key performance indicators

Participants suggest that management of companies must consider the circular economy as their objectives, set the targets, and plan the strategies according to targets and incentivise the employees.

“I think the way people get managed about the way they measured on. I think, if you don’t set someone an objective on this or KPI, it will not work. You can only manage something you can measure. So, for me, as management you have to set it as an objective that’s just important as you cost related objective or your service metrics anything like that. It should be coming from the top. You have to have your boards directors, in your senior leaders have to have these objectives as well. It can’t be just like four tiers of management has the objectives and the board doesn’t have it’s the CEO doesn’t have an objective that’s true.” (HM)

“So, umm really, I would say it is better way how can it be used into the business model, it needs to work as fundamental business model that it is beneficial for the business and the environment. Then I mean if it works, I mean if it can be implemented, it will work. The people are incentivised the profit, the same profit. Part of the practice rather than having the established business that are cracking a lot of waste and then there is no um the only incentive is an ethical incentive because obviously it’s gonna be slower to act on that.” (AF)

The circular economy should be embedded in the culture of the organisation. Companies can measure and control it better if these initiatives are part of key performance indicators. It is recommended to have these key performance indicators from operational to board level.

Decentralisation

Due to the real time nature of food products, the circular economy in this industry requires real time decision making. Therefore, it is perquisite to have firm-based decision-making agreements for manufacturers so that waste can be utilised before going to waste.

“If you are implementing some kind of waste policy for your company you should analyse the amount of waste at certain or particular store is generating. Depending on that there should sub-divided policy to reduce the waste they are producing. For the simple reason, there might be a bit the amount of waste in that store must be high because they don’t have staff. So, I think that they

should be tailor made policies especially regarding certain things for the stores, not top to bottom, I, I believe it's kind of outdated right now. Because we are not living in a normal world anymore.”
(PG)

From a retailer's perspective policies should be store oriented as per its capacity and amount of wastage they generate rather than one centralized policy for every retail store. Decision making in the food industry requires firm-based decision-making capabilities to utilise the amount and nature of waste a firm has.

4.6 SUMMARY

The purpose of this chapter has been to answer the main research questions of this study through qualitative analysis. To achieve this objective, data is analysed based on the research questions. Data collected from 36 interviews (2 excluded) was transcribed, coded, and analysed manually and with software NVivo 12. To answer the first question this analysis provides numerous factors which became barriers for food supply chain stakeholders. These factors originated from the theoretical framework developed through literature review of previous studies. Four new factors (demographic factors, post-Brexit trade, shelf life and minimum order quantities) also emerged as a result of the interviews with stakeholders which are not discussed previously in the circular economy studies as barriers. The data was cross justified by running comparison queries on nodes. It provided a clear idea of the factors which are most alarming among the different categories; results are then interpreted. The analysis shows that consumers' attitudes and perceptions were the most discussed factor by participants followed by lack of structure, high cost of products, lack of awareness and lack of supportive legislations. To answer the question, this study performed a stakeholder analysis in which 7 phases (design, manufacture, retail, consumption, upcycle, recycle and logistics) of circular supply chain management were analysed separately. This section guides about the value creation from the circular supply chain management model through its stakeholders by answering the second question of this research, how recognised hindrance factors affect different supply chain stakeholders. The analysis was supported by matrix query on NVivo to see what percentage of a code (themes) was discussed by a specific stage of circular supply chain. The analysis shows that for logistics and recycling stage inappropriate structure is the most critical hindrance factor, demographic factors were highlighted by upcycling and consumption stage,

designing and manufacturing stage emphasised on lack of awareness and for retailers the perception and attitude of consumers are the major hindrance factors. Lastly, the chapter discussed 14 driving strategies which should be implemented across the supply chains to achieve a positive implementation of the circular economy model.

CHAPTER V: DISCUSSION

5.1 INTRODUCTION

The structure of this chapter is as follows: section 6.2 presents the general overview of the study, in which exploration of the concept circular supply chain management has been discussed. It is followed by factors which affect the implementation of circular supply chain management (section 6.3) and its effects on various stages with the lens of stakeholder theory has been explained in section 6.4. Drivers with the view of management strategies have been described in section 6.5. The outcomes are substantiated with existing literature. Finally, the summary of this chapter is explained in section 6.6.

5.2 OVERVIEW OF STUDY

This thesis explores the concept of circular supply chain management. It also acknowledges various factors which affect the implementation of circular supply chain management in food industries and how these barriers become a hindrance for various stages of circular supply chain management and how that can be overcome. Looking at the current need of resource depletion from industrial growth, (Geng et al., 2009) the concept of circular supply chain management is significant to study from the management perspective to help the industries to adopt strategies to supply the circular supply chain model effectively (Govindan et al., 2015). Circular supply chain management is a way of industries to get environmental, corporate-social and economic benefits (George et al., 2015; Goyal et al., 2016) and is the most effective driver to bring sustainability (Genovese et al., 2017; Hobson, 2016; Nasir et al., 2017). Hence, it is trending among global supply chain leaders (Farooque et al., 2019) and provide the opportunities for the companies to gain competitive advantage and economic benefits (De Anglies, 2020). Despite this prerequisite, circular supply chain management has not been synthesized from a strategic point of view (Urbinati et al., 2017).

The research is one of the initial attempts to study the circular economy concept focusing on its implementation in organizations with management implications by accomplishing three objectives: firstly, to explore the circular supply chain management approach from the industrial perspective; secondly, to systematically examine barriers in circular supply chain management in

food industry; finally, the effects of those barriers on each stage of the circular supply chain management and drivers to overcome those barriers. To justify these objectives, a qualitative methods approach was adopted (Easterby-Smith, 1991; Remenyi et al., 1998; Creswell;2003). The study started by probing the vision of this concept and then general barriers and from different settings were investigated from existing literature.

For the theoretical assessment of the phenomenon, this study used stakeholder theory and stakeholders were the managers of stages of circular supply chain management of the UK food industry. It intended to gain a comprehensive stance from diverse backgrounds to achieve a common goal. It has shown that circular supply chain management is a network of interrelated elements which work together to get environmental, social, and economic benefits through remanufacturing and recycling practices (Genovese et al., 2017; Nasir et al., 2017; Geissdoerfer et al., 2018; Mangla et al., 2018). The research is an inclusive analysis of all those related elements with qualitative assessment, through which the researcher gained close and practical insight of the topic of interest. Mendoza et al. (2019) suggest that engagement of stakeholders will be relevant to analyze the effectiveness of bottom-up strategies.

Circular supply chain management is demanding yet rarely accepted by industries due to the traditional linear nature (Tura et al., 2019) and by academics as management study. Therefore, the qualitative method was adopted to discuss implications of the circular supply chain management concept, the hindrance factors to adopt from the food industry perspective as per stakeholders' experience and perception which has received less attention from industries and academics to date.

This study explored the scope and practical implementation of circular supply chain management which demonstrates that it can be adopted as a business model and contributes towards optimization and better management of organizational as well as natural resources to increase the productivity and paying towards companies' value proposition, value creation and value capturing (Linder and Williander, 2015; EEA, 2016; Geissdoerfer et al., 2018; Souza-Zomer et al., 2018; Sehnem et al., 2019; Schroeder et al., 2019). Participants confirmed the adoption of the circular supply chain as a business model.

However, on the other side while enquiring about its implementation, Bohringer and Rutherford, (2015), Pieroni et al., (2021) depict that application of the circular economy demands a fundamental change in social, industrial and consumption systems. The circular supply chain has started receiving significant attention from researchers but uncertain from the practical implementation (Schutle. 2013; EMF, 2013; Lacy and Rutgvist, 2015). The concern has been widely explored in chapter V.

Following this disquiet from existing studies, a theoretical model was developed from the results of literature that explain various barriers and drivers for the circular economy transition. The framework, further revised resulted from qualitative data collection, consists of 6 themes and 17 sub-themes, which specifically relate to the UK food industry. All the barriers (sub-themes) were allocated to 6 different themes (financial and economic barriers, technical barriers, management barriers, socio-culture barriers, structural barriers and institutional) as per their nature and practice in the industry. After introducing the research methodology, additional depth into these literature-based categories is provided by discussing how they have influenced the development of business case in the firms.

Thematic analysis method was adopted, with CAQDAS, NVivo12 suggested (Creswell,1994). Themes developed from the literature review were explored from the stakeholders of the UK food industry. It gave origin to 4 new sub-themes as barriers specific to food circular supply chain management. As suggested by Freeman and Mcvea, (2001), the relationship with stakeholders should be explored to develop business strategies; all the stakeholders were incorporated to recognize their association to those challenges. Matrix analysis was used to support the argument about which challenges are the obstructions of the stage of circular supply chain management and how they prevent them to apply the closing loop model in their operations. Finally, the drivers specific to those challenges were suggested as a view of business strategies for successful implementation of the circular transition.

5.3 CIRCULAR SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT AND BARRIERS FOR IMPLEMENTATION

The motivation for this study was the need for evaluation of circular supply chain management as a strategic and management concept and its implementation in the industries. The concept is

actively gaining the interest of academics, policy makers, practitioners, and businesses (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017) yet not defined well scientifically in management literature (Korhonen et al., 2018; Ünal et al., 2018; De Angles, 2020). The preliminary definition of “circular supply chain management” and the concept was explored in Chapter II, following the barriers of its application in businesses. To date, there is inadequate research of circular supply chain management engaging relevant stakeholders including consumers (Mondeza, 2019). Essentially it is worthwhile to have a holistic view of the circular economy including multidimensional evaluation i.e., end to end supply chain and social to management perspective. To accomplish this requisite this study began to critically evaluate the circular economy concept from its social and environmental origin towards business development.

Circular supply chain management is conceptualised as sociological, economic, and environmental approaches and scholars have started studying it an integral business part today's business world. Qualitative interviews were initiated to get the preliminary insight from stakeholders about the extent and scope of the circular supply chain in the management of the food industry. Findings supported the insights from literature that circular supply chain management can be incorporated into the business model (Geissdoerfer, 2018; de Sousa Jabbour, 2019; Hofmann, 2019; Franco, 2019; Sehnem, 2019; Pieroni et al., 2021; Keulen and Kirchherr, 2021) of an organisation and applied as an environmental, social (Mostaghel and Chirumalla, 2020), corporate (Franco, 2019), marketing, economic, management (de Sousa Jabbour, 2019; De Angelis, 2020) as well as a sustainability strategy (Farooque et al., 2018). However, restraints in the current linear ecosystem, economic and business system were considered as major blockers to accept it as a successful business case (Jurgilevich, 2016).

Implementation of the circular supply chain as a business model needs an edge-to-edge approach involving not only policy formulation but entailing a drastic strategic change for product design, process, commercialising, consumption, and recycling (Winans et al., 2017; Franco, 2019). Hence, this study attempted to gain a holistic view from all the dimension of the circular supply chain. As suggested by Geissdoerfer et al., (2018), engagement from multiple supply chain stakeholders is prerequisite to complement the existing studies and this co-operation through the supply chain network can effectively drive this transformation in social, economic, and environmental aspects (Gupta et al., 2019). And followed by stakeholders' theory (Freeman, 2000) that “in capitalism

stakeholders do not act in a moral vacuum but cooperate around values. Based on these values, stakeholders have to negotiate to create mutual interests.”. Therefore, outcomes of this study present the model from the data extracted from literature combined with empirical substances from the managers from seven stages of food circular supply chain management in the form of six categories of barriers.

The first category of barrier instigated in this research was “**technical barriers**”. This category defined lack of techniques and technology which was further categorised into factors related to shelf-life, lack of technologies, lack of skill and expertise and order and forecasting inaccuracy, out of which the most dominating theme was lack of knowledge, skills, and expertise (Bechtel et al., 2013; Rizos et al., 2016; Adams et al., 2017; Tura et al., 2019). It was ascertained from the interviews that knowledge about the practices to follow to close the loops is at a very early stage among the stakeholders.

Life of products is the second most discussed technical challenge to attain circularity in the food industry “I can’t see how the circular economy would work in short shelf-life environment.” It results in almost 50% of food wastage during supply chains yet has not been reviewed, ominously, in the circular economy studies but stated as a prevailing factor for circular supply chain management in the food industry. Furthermore, it is seen from analysis that ordering and forecasting inaccuracy is another big challenge for the food supply chain. Uncertainty about the demand from retailers enormously affects manufacturers and suppliers. The demand-forecasting issue has been explained in a comment below. And lastly the lack of technologies concept is recognised as a major challenge in literature (Trianni and Cango, 2012; Tura et al., 2019; Farooq et al., 2019; Mangla et al., 2018) in various industries however indications from data analysis of this study support the comment of a participant “I don’t think his world lacks technology” and this was the least alarming technical challenge evidenced for food supply chain management.

Current order and forecasting systems followed by retailers and manufacturers were recognised as an obstacle to apply the circular model. Manufacturers receive estimates from retailers well in advance, on the basis of which they order their raw material, but the actual order mostly varies then the estimate. Going by this trend, it seems impractical to apply circularity, which is mainly based on real time decisions in the food industry.

The second construct, established in this research is “**finance and economic related barriers**”. The circular economy transition required time, investment and the most panicking factor for capitalist business is uncertainty about financial outcomes and the return on investment for accepting the environmental innovations (Ritzén and Sandström, 2017). As per the view from food supply chain managers, without the financial gain, circular transformation will lose the interest of businesses. The most discussed finance and economic related challenges derived from this study are high cost of sustainable solutions and products (Andrew, 2015; Li et al., 2015), following by profitability (Shi et al., 2008), investment (Geng et al., 2009; Pan et al., 2015; Hart et al., 2019) and minimum order quantities respectively. Out of which the first three issues have been significantly stated in previous studies.

The last element “minimum order quantities” has not been scientifically reconnoitred by scholars however, discussions with supply chain handlers believe that this is a major restriction imposed by stakeholders on each other to get financial and economic benefit but does not lead to a successful circular transformation. Order quantity restrictions make manufacturers, retailers, and consumers buy in bulk and waste at the end due to limited use by dates.

The third group emerging in this research is “**planning and management**” and the hindrance factors are lack of management commitment, inappropriate marketing activities and competition in the market. Commitment is a psychological condition to represent the individuals’ interaction with an organisation’s dimensions (Ünal, 2018); previous arguments from researchers signify management’s commitment is more with profitable projects than sustainable solutions (Meyer et al., 2002; Mangla et al., 2018). Without management commitment it is difficult to align the right strategies like closing the loops and making employees follow them precisely where each step has to be scrutinised.

In the same instance, some participants did not agree that management is a barrier as they think that management is always dedicated towards sustainable practices, but it is the rules and regulations or techniques where organisations are lagging behind. The second element is companies marketing strategies which are obstacles in two ways: firstly, the existing marketing activities to attract the consumers’ attention and boost the waste; and secondly, sustainability or upcycling is not marketed on the required level (Mangla et al., 2018; Zhung et al., 2020). Finally,

this research reflects that the current market is competition based and competition promotes more linear practices rather than circular. Competition between the linear and circular model was also highlighted as a challenge in this study.

The next category developed during this study is “**Socio-cultural barrier**”. It was established that consumers as well as professionals are not very well-aware from circular approach yet (Ghisellini et al., 2016; Mondoza et al., 2019). Awareness is fundamental lever to bring circular change (Lieder and Rashid, 2016; Hartley et al., 2019). There is discussion about public awareness in the studies from which majority focus on China, this qualitative research established that awareness is a similar level challenge in the UK. Above the awareness the additional factor disturbs the application is consumer behaviour, attitude, and perception (Hartley et al., 2019). This study reveals that circular revolution needs a drastic change in consumer behaviour (Planning, 2015) to alter their buying habits and to accept the sustainable products and to reduce the waste.

Like consumer side culture, an organisation’s traditional culture is difficult to mould. Manufacturing industries which are following some practices from many decades, are ready to accept the obsolescence (Xavier, 2019). The last socio-cultural element found in this study is the demographic factor which includes education or buying power. Some participants unveil that the more the people have buying power, the more they will be unsustainable as they do not value the things, and this is the reason western countries have higher rates of wastage. While others think vice-versa giving the evidence of European countries that the more they are wealthy, the more they can spend on educating the society and to avail the solutions and that it can be evident from countries like Germany where recycling is on a high scale.

Further aspects arose to prevent organisations and societies to accept circular supply chain management are “**Structural Barriers**”. Circular supply chain is a combination of 3Rs (reduce, reuse, and recycle) (Zhu et al., 2010), intangible structure (responsible team, organisation structure, allocated time) and tangible structure (deposing off facilities) do not exist to make these processes happen (Xi 2011; Silva et al., 2018). The findings indicate that despite the emergence of the situation, circular initiatives are not an integral segment of organisation structure because of which it does not drive the success. There is also a requirement to develop controlled infrastructure

to segregate and dispose-off the waste material in industries and for households (specifically high-rise flats).

Undoubtedly, circular supply chain is a web combining multiple processes and multiple stakeholders. It was obtained from previous studies as well qualitative analysis of this study that it is difficult for companies to make each stakeholder to follow the same goal with each having profit gaining vision. Finally, from structural barriers it was acquired that ideal model of the circular economy specifically in food industry is complex where innumerable actions i.e., upcycling, recycling or reverse logistic are taken to close the loops (Hopkinson et al., 2018; Estes et al., 2021) and becomes difficult to manage and control. The complex nature of the circular model is discussed by scholars in different settings i.e., complexity in administrative tasks or supply chains (Rizos et al., and Acharya et al., 2018); lifecycle of products (Adam et al., 2018), nature of built environment (Hart et al., 2019).

The sixth and last group of hindrance factors was classified as “**Institutional and regulatory Barriers**”. Issues that came into existence under this category are lack of supportive law and regulation, lack of government support and post-Brexit trade to make circular evolution less efficient. A study by Jesus and Mendonça (2018) shows that regulatory barriers are second more discussed barriers by with 23 percent of analysed literature. Scholars as well as interviewees believe that government is the most important driver to drive circular changes but at present it is more written propaganda rather than a practical approach. Government is lacking in aligning their policies apposite to the circular economy that can enforce the businesses and a common person to follow it as a rule.

The argument portrayed by van Eijk, (2015, p33) “Government incentive are still in the favour of linear economies” resemble with the next theme appearing in this study. Interviewees demand the support from government in the way of raising awareness and facilitating financially. Without that support it will be a risk for existing businesses and for investors. Finally, a new construct originated in this category is post-Brexit trade. As discussed by participants, Brexit has been a priority for government in the last few years rather than the circular economy; secondly business agreements with Far East countries will be incremental to carbon footprints and wastage due to product life restrictions and product quality.

To sum up, despite the fact that sustainability is becoming a pillar in the food industry of the United Kingdom, findings demonstrate that challenges like perception, attitude and behaviour, lack of structure, high cost of products, raw material and solutions, lack of awareness, lack of supportive legislation and profitability etc. are encountered as crucial barriers, putting high impact on stakeholders and are consistent with literature of Geng and Doberstein (2008), Rizos et al., (2016), Kirrherr et al., (2018); Keulen and Kirrherr (2021). There are 5 additional barriers originated from this research: shelf-life of food products, forecasting and ordering inaccuracy, minimum order quantities, post-Brexit trade and demographic factors which equivalently affect the implementation of circularity proposals in the food supply chain. Next, how these factors affect different stages of circular supply chain management has been explained in following section.

5.4 IMPACT OF BARRIERS ON SUPPLY CHAIN STAGES

This research is grounded on the stakeholder theory which consider human as actors and their interface, to generate the value (to limited to economic) for institutions including aligning the values, norms, and ethics for the prosperity within and among the organisations (Freeman et al., 2020). Entrenched in stakeholder theory this section is a close analysis of circular supply chain stakeholders' (from each phase) scrutinized interaction about its barriers and successful implementation. A circular supply chain originally starts with supply of raw material. Suppliers and farmers were contacted initially but due to data quality, this stage was discarded, and data collection was not proceeded at this stage. So, the process was started with designing progress through manufacturing, retailing, consuming, upcycling, recycling and includes logistics.

5.4.1 Designing

It is recognised that business strategies should be directed towards circular product design (design for longevity, design for maintenance, and design for recycling and business model looking at the need of sustainability (Bocken et al., 2014; den Hollander et al., 2017; Lieder and Rashid, 2016; Rashid et al., 2013; Urbinati et al., 2017). Franco et al., 2017 and Franco et al., 2019 engaged the research on circular product design and introduced a design model with limitation of product complexity and long-time delays in product use and returns. This research recognised the challenge on wider range related to food product designs. Participants reflect that circular product design in the UK food industry is highly impacted by stringent legislation and lack of awareness. There is minimal awareness about the circular possibilities as well law does not allow them to take decentralised decision due to the nature of industry. (Rood et al., 2017; Bovea et al., 2018; Hartley et al., 2020). Because of the variation in many decisions from traditional processes, managers face negative response from other related stakeholder which prevent them to take circular based design decision. For the new product developer lack of infrastructure affiliated to circular business model and due to limited life of products it is thought to be very complicated to apply these models in food manufacturing. Furthermore, consumer behaviour and attitude drive the designers to drive the change and how remanufactured produced and marketed by retailers which are not in the favour of circularity or sustainability due to lack of education. Sustainable resolutions, whether they are technology or raw material is restriction for developer because of the high cost with having less transparency about the profitability to business from this novel framework. Interviewees from designing stage are also getting obstructed by Brexit, as they raised concern about delay in deliveries, raw material qualities, and product life of raw materials.

Whereas dynamics like investment, government support, competition, lack of knowledge were also described by the design phase. Moving forward minimum order quantities, cost of raw material, profitability, marketing strategies have less direct influence on designers to move towards circular decisions. While other factors do not have major and direct relation with product development phase and there were no challenges related to demographic factors were conferred by managers.

5.4.2 Manufacturing

It is evidenced from data analysis that the circular economy requires a radical change in legislative framework (Kopinina, 2018). Lack of supportive legislation was the most discussed challenge by managers from the manufacturing stage. The results were corresponding to the study of Wu and Paggell (2011) that the sustainable supply chain management process is directly influenced by government involvement. It was revealed that no revolutionary policies have been introduced by UK government in terms of legislation specific to the circular economy which can get the manufacturers to be involved in this model. On the contrary, rigorous food health and safety regulations do not allow them to take ecological initiatives. Parashar et al., 2020, elucidates the relation of legislation and sustainability that regulations back corporations on the negotiations related to environment, health, safety, and social risks. Manufacturers and processors seemed to be concerned about additional high-cost of technologies, packaging solutions, cost of sending the waste to anaerobic plants for further processing and cost of virgin material which customers are not willing spend. Cost of waste separation, remanufacturing, reverse logistics are the substantial overheads for manufacturers to implement the circular supply chain framework (Mangla et al., 2018; Grafstrom and Aasma, 2021). Participants also highlighted estrangement of management from sustainable targets. Due to the ambiguity of benefits, additional cost, transformations are existing processes and need of cultural changes, circularity is not the preferable model for management in the current industrial environment. A critical part from the manufacturing management side is that the strategies are aligned by presenting that there will be no wastage during the processes rather taking it as a part, allowing the flexibility and finding the solutions to utilize it. Participants reviewed that organisation culture can be shaped with management policies.

Circular supply chain management works as a chain reaction, actions of one stage affect the others, so the manufacturers demand retailer's co-ordination to set more accurate demand-forecasting system to allow them to take precise decisions. Additionally, shelf life and work in progress life of the raw material and processed food reduce the feasibility of circular model in food supply chains. Preserving the silo structure, less knowledge and skills, customer awareness plays a significant role in influencing manufacturers for developing circular thinking and behaviour. Alternatively, factors like investment, lack of government support were mainly discussed in relation to the new ventures. Competition, lack of marketing strategies and minimum order

quantities affect the manufacturers through retailers. Demographic factors, post-Brexit trade and the complex nature of processes were less debated factors. However, Brexit trade can generate an alarming situation for sustainability in the future.

5.4.3 Retailing

Transition towards the circular economy is demanding but challenging undertaking for retailers (Mostaghel and Chirumalla, 2021). Because of direct dealing with consumers, hampered issue for retailers was recognised as perception and attitude of consumers. Due to consumers' psychological and cultural elements, the circular economy does not exert as a positive transition on consumers' minds (Singh and Giacosa, 2019; Grafstrom and Aasma, 2021).

Applying circular supply chain management requires to overcome the retailers from structural barriers by making it an integral part of retailing companies' structure. For retailer gap in the communication from to bottom level, less staff committed to sustainability practices, lack of flexibility and agility to react, information systems, inappropriate arrangements to avoid and segregate food wastage are the issues discussed by retailers in relation to structure. Sustainable practices strongly depend on the interactions of culture and management processes (Daily and Huang, 2001; Farooque et al., 2019). Participants from retailing firms additionally experience that upper management is less committed to sustainable initiatives. It is neither an objective based approach nor is being communicated through the structure. Similarly, it is crucial to be implanted into organisation culture for old established companies which have been following linear practices for many years. Keulen and Kirchherr, (2020) show the financial aspect to follow the circular economy model for industries as a cost-effective model for stakeholders, similar views were shared by retailers as sustainable products being less price competitive for consumers and less profitable for retailers are not preferred. To be in competition is another factor for food retailers to follow unethical practices like online shopping or return policies. Supply chain stakeholders from food retailing industry remarkably indicate demographic factors, shelf-life, complex nature as challenges. Moreover, demands for government support, more accurate ordering and forecasting systems, awareness movements, education, eco-friendly marketing strategies are stipulated for accepting this transition. Finally, it was obtained that less collaboration, post-Brexit trade and minimum order quantities disputes do not directly impact the retailers to accept circular change.

5.4.4 Consumers

Green buying is a way of consumers transferring their environmental concern into actions (Moser, 2016). Systematic decisions made by consumers can be a foremost positive step towards circularity. Data from consumers demonstrated that there is a strong influence of awareness factors on the consumer stage for circular economy initiatives. Awareness is at a very basic stage among consumers about its consequences and the right practices to follow.

Demographic factors like level of education among societies and spending power are prominent dynamics for the success of sustainable ascendancies from many dimensions. It was established from qualitative analysis that the more nations are financially established, the more they will be able to spend on educating the society about environmental issues. Whereas some participants explained that countries which have more buying power, people tend to contribute more wastage. Participants from the consumption phase demands more stringent regulations from the UK government for food supply chain management as it is done for pollution controls and traffic guidelines. Consumers stresses to change the buying behaviour, attitude and perception, minimum quantity buying restrictions.

5.4.5 Upcycling

Upcycling is an integral part to reach in closing the loop aspiration of circular supply chain management (McDonough and Braungart, 2013). The greatest hindrance factor explored by this stage of interviewees was the demographic factor (education) which affects the decision-making power by changing the behaviour or perceptions of people towards spending on upcycled products. Less control over the material separation facilities by legislation, Investment on technologies and government support in the term to incentivising proposals like upcycling are causes for less acceptability of proposals among the business owners. Additionally, participants emphasised having profitability aspect as follows, along with background to make upcycling a part of business model.

Moreover, the research reflects that having upcycling as business require the technologies and high skilled workers to be able to make the products to compete in the market. The intrusions like upcycling business are possible if initiated by government and education bodies. It needs extra

effort to present it to general public to make it first priority and gain long term success which is possible if initiated by government with the collaboration of local authorities. (Sung et al., 2019).

5.4.6 Recycling

There is a need of drastic transformation for the economies to be able to reach the targets of recycling (WRAP, 2021). This study observed that for recyclers related to food industry most important element for ineffectiveness are knowledge, skill or expertise and lack of apposite structure. Similar to other segments of circular supply chain management, recyclers feel that there is less awareness and understanding around the practices to follow and technical knowledge to be able to design the model for longevity on all the stages of the supply chain which ultimately affects the recycling processes.

Beside knowledge, there is not pertinent infrastructure in place for industries and household waste deployment (Grimm et al., 2014) because of which recycling cannot contribute efficiently towards the circular economy. To make the recycling more effective in the food industry, it is demanded to have coordination between food manufacture with packaging companies to use a single type of plastic that can be recycled easily and efficiently. Similarly, government needs to work with regional councils according to the amount and nature of waste and align the strategies regional basis. Moreover, looking at the increase of recycling trends, economies need additional infrastructure which in turn requires investment. Information obtained from participants from recycling companies indicates that there is a requirement of financial support from higher authorities. It was also observed that getting recycling resolutions are an additional cost for other industrial stakeholders, do not get along with profitable approach. Other factors like organisation culture, perception and attitude for recycled products, factors indirectly affect the recycling companies to adopt the circular economy approach.

5.4.7 Logistics

Information from the logistics phase portrays the barriers are primarily related to geographical location of businesses, insufficient infrastructure, under-capacity as compared to increased volume of orders, less recognition of logistics processes and less communication of management of companies with logistics administrators.

Consumers' behaviour of over-buying was depicted as a reason for making logistics more complicated. Similarly, to get cost benefit companies' higher order volumes of raw material contribute to more carbon footprints and leads inefficient handling of finished goods which increases the chances of wastage (Sutthichaimethee and Tanoamchard, 2015), was highlighted by manager from logistics stage. Finally, profitability approach of management is challenge by the way of making the management to be less committed for eco-friendly logistics processes. Life of food products is another restriction as it gives limited period to logistics for distributing the products from manufacturers to retailers without harming.

5.5 DRIVERS TO BARRIERS

Previous sections identify the challenges in food supply chain management and examine its effects on different platforms. This section discusses the themes emerged to resolve these barriers. In previous literature enablers are general overview and named under the same themes as challenges. This study systematically discovers the strategies for identified challenges to enable effective circular economy transition under different themes.

5.5.1 Drivers for institutional barriers

Institutional challenges are related to law, legislation and regulatory authorities which are classified as lack of government support, lack of supportive legislation and post-Brexit trade. This study introduced different strategies discussed in literature and suggested by participants to take the control over institutional challenges. Government being a principal driver should actively work towards promoting Co2 emission reduction (Zhu et al., 2005; Aikins and Ramanathan, 2020). First strategy is, *assisting and incentivising*, participants demand for urgent intervention of government to assist the innovative ideas by providing necessary guidance and framework to work in. Financial help in the form of incentives and rewards for contributors can be a driving force for who are reluctant to get involved. Participant explains in below quotation the type of incentives industries looking for:

“Without that incentive, it doesn’t make financial sense to build an AD plant but saying that you know with the local authority or going to start collecting the food waste from the 2023 that will see bring, you know, a large proportion of tonnage into the market which they are potentially isn’t going to be capacity for. So obviously the government is then, will need to introduce something like this.”

“Of course, it is achievable, nothing is unachievable. but again, to think to write and to implement there’s a big difference so if as I mentioned before sometimes that if there are rules regulations in place for other things why can’t they put rules and regulations for waste management. and I’m not talking about rules and regulations but with the implications. with the reflection, with the penalty”

In relation to sustainable activities, legislative structure provides the directives through restricted environment provided for industries (Lieder and Rashid, 2016). Another strategy from higher authorities is *designing a circular framework* for the whole industry and aligning strategies, introducing strict rules and regulations with the implications. Regulatory restrains are responsible for ensuring social and green activities in supply chains (Prashar et al., 2020). The circular economy needs be a part of countries’ long-term plan with introducing industry specific road map. Post-Brexit trades should be part of circular framework which will provide insight for environmental benefits for adopting local or international suppliers.

5.5.2 Drivers for socio-cultural barriers

Challenges ballooned in this part were lack of awareness and right information, organisation culture and perception, attitude, and behaviour of people towards this transformation or services. This research introduced strategies in the context of societal and industrial environment. The circular economy needs to be part of *Education through school curriculum and social media* which will strengthen the foundation among society. Education plays an important part to raise interest, awareness, and knowledge for revolutions (Farooque et al., 2019).

Furthermore, government initiatives are demanded at this stage to raise awareness in society through advertisements and social media platform like YouTube or BBC. Moreover, adopting the stakeholders’ theory, the research recommends *embedding circular economy in the companies’ values*. The circular business model should be an integral part of everyday processes of business

and for the advantage of each stakeholder (Freeman 2000; Freudenreich et al., 2020). It will support to create a circular culture in the business.

Thus, coherent with research communities Stenmarck et al., (2016); Stensgård and Hanssen, (2016); WRAP, (2017), who mapped cultural drivers for food waste, drivers suggested for socio-cultural barriers are to rising the awareness, knowledge and education as well changing the consumer culture with company policy revisions.

5.5.3 Drivers for financial barriers

Financial enablers for stakeholder to adopt the model positively is providing the financial benefits and avoiding the financial risks. Stakeholders state that the circular model is an additional cost for the existing businesses, customers, and a risk for new investors, where they have to spend in technology, expensive products and new infrastructure. It will be a risk on the investment which should be shielded by a *carrot-stick approach* by government through providing financial support (carrot) (Hart et al., 2019) like subsidies on investment, zero percent loans. A business development manager from anaerobic plant highlights government's new target of sending household waste into energy generation which needs an additional infrastructure for the anaerobic digestion plants. If government intervenes in the way of supporting in investment for infrastructure, that will be a positive drive for the circular business model. It is pertinent to adopt *price competitiveness strategies* such as tax rebates for those who contribute whether they are industries or consumers; it will offer affordable prices on technologies and on sustainable and upcycled products (Borello et al., 2017; Farooqe et al., 2019).

Consequently, incentive alignment is foremost and essential to get people to collaboratively progress through the circular supply chain (Rota et al., 2018; Hussain and Malik, 2020). It should be initiated by industries for their customers (manufacture to retailer and retailers to consumers) and by government to industries.

5.5.4 Drivers for technical barriers

Technical factors for availing circular supply chain management suggested in this research are *Traceability* of product origin and pathways (Leder et al., 2020). In the food industries, including

traceability techniques will enable the reuse and remanufacturing by examining the quality, cross-contamination, work environment and keeping the controls where possible. It is suggested to have end-to-end *measurability* of consequences (pollutant, CO2 emissions) on a product basis and on an organization basis. It will give a clear visualization to the stakeholders about the significance of taking prompt and corrective actions.

This research recognized technical enablers for product sustainability, longevity, optimum utilization, and reusability, are *product life extension* and *big data analytics*. Life can be extended through technologies similar to pasteurisation or retort, but these technologies are not preferred by consumers due to adverse health effects. It is required to innovate the life extension technologies without infringement nutritional, health, safety, taste, and texture of products. Introducing packaging solutions like nanopore technology for life extension are also recommended to reduce food waste and decrease environmental impact (Gutierrez, 2017).

To aid the product sharing, transparency and collaboration, big data establishes a real time data framework through combining data arising from multiple sources (De Mauro et al., 2015). This technique including a traceability aspect will accelerate product and raw material sharing between manufacturers, and product sharing (between retailers-retailer and retailers to consumer). To plan the model of circular supply chain volume and reliability of data is an influential factor (Jabbour et al., 2017). Big data techniques can utilise the integrity of process, sharing resources, understanding operational implications (Gupta et al., 2019).

5.5.5 Drivers for structural barriers

Challenges related to structure that oppose circularity in the food supply chain impede the communication and coordination of stakeholders, make the process more complex. *Collaboration* is a fundamental driver to involve and manage the complicated network of processes. An efficient circular business model demands stakeholder commitment and value network and collaborative effort (Mostaghela and Chirumalla, 2021). Rota et al., 2018 recognised three main branches of collaborative circular model as information sharing, decision synchronisation and incentive alignment (Rota et al., 2018). Analysis of this research gives the same essence.

Secondly, an enabler from the structure side is to introduce a specific *circular economy division or department*. Having a department in place and the circular economy KPIs will make organisations closely examine the gaps, set the objectives, dedicate time, resources, and effort to work towards circular goals. To implement the circular model successfully, it should be part of companies' structure with a dedicated team and time. As per a planning manager's words:

“The biggest impact is actually having a structure that will focus on circular approach or sustainability or something like that. If you have structure in place that has a sustainability director and then each each-business area R&D supply chain, manufacturing, commercial had a sustainability lead that is obviously then way of business showing its really important because there are investing on the people also spending 37.5 hours a week or 60 hours”

5.5.6 Drivers to management barriers

Management challenges, like lack of commitment and competition, can be overcome by collaboration strategy (mentioned in previous section) of different parties. *Managements and policy makers should be committed* to pursue environmental endeavours considering it equally important as profitability. It should be a vital part of a company's long-term and short-term plans and objectives which need to be set periodically involving collaboration, communication, traceability measurability and marketing strategies.

Finally, *decentralised management policies* rather than a generalising strategy was presented from literature and information extracted from participants. It reduces the intermediate complexities, information leakage, financial cost and time to adopt the circular processes (Dierksmeier and Seele, 2020). In food industries enabling closing of loops needs real-time decision making. Following decentralisation, it is recommended to design firm-based policies and decision making rather than a traditional top to bottom approach.

5.6 SUMMARY

The foremost step to the circular economy is to design the products for longevity and remanufacturing. More importantly how those designed products are marketed, consumed, and disposed of are the aspects of its implementation strategies (Lewandowski, 2016). Therefore,

circular business model innovation leads organisations to go beyond the sustainable business model which only focuses on efficiency, productivity, and green supply chains (Bakker et al., 2014; Geissdoerfer et al., 2018). This study strengthens the outcomes of previous literature which reveals that the circular economy not only needs technical innovations but social revolutions as well (Winans et al., 2017).

The purpose of this analysis was to answer the research questions and fulfil the gaps in previous studies. To achieve these objectives, data was analysed taking stakeholder theory as a lens so that it suggests the ways from the stakeholders' point of view to overcome the barriers with top-bottom and bottom-top strategies. The data was analysed in 3 phases starting from getting a general overview of the challenges in the circular economy. The analysis suggested that organisations are still working in traditional/linear ways and have numerous challenges depending on the operations and duties multiple stakeholders perform. Therefore, the second phase was to analyse each operational department of the circular supply chain. The barriers were linked to the different stages and explored the ways they affect the circular operations on the particular phase. Focussing on the stakeholders' view, perception and experience is important to prioritise the strategies and policies as per the requirement, rather than applying a standard set of strategies in every case. In the third phase, drivers in the form of strategies were suggested explicit to the type of challenges and finally a theoretical framework was developed merging various concepts in Figure 6.1. Discussion, conclusion, and implication of results are discussed in the next chapter.

Figure: 6.1 Final theoretical model

Source: Developed by author

CHAPTER VI: CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

6.1 INTRODUCTION

This research is an empirical study to closely examine the barriers and enabler for accepting the circular supply chain management framework in the context of the food industry of the United Kingdom. The research is bound with the diversity of experiences, perspectives, and perceptions of a series of circular supply chain actor related to the food industry including product designers, manufacturers, retailers, consumers, up-cyclers, and recyclers. It is anticipated that this qualitative investigation fulfils the research gap by using critical perspective of practices (challenges) emerging in organisations throughout the supply chain averse to the circular model, their repercussions on the stakeholders and enablers (strategies) to overcome those deterrent factors. The foundation of this study is set on stakeholder theory, to facilitate the transition of the circular supply chain model, involving the stakeholders' perspective to create value with and for them (Freeman et al., 2018).

The research is based on the qualitative approach, using semi-structured in-depth interviews with a range of circular supply chain managers from the UK food industry. Research originated from existing literature by which initial themes were generated and theoretical framework was developed, further supported by interviews from circular food supply chain stakeholders. Themes were analysed and reconceptualised through thematic analysis using NVivo software.

A prime contribution of this research is development of a theoretical framework with systematic evaluation of each element that restrained and contributes towards circular supply chain management. This evaluation from each phase of the circular supply chain represents that being a novel approach there are numerous challenges for stakeholders to initiate and adopt this model which affects individuals in different ways. This research adds distinctive drivers in the form of strategies to eliminate the impact of those challenges. Furthermore, this study adds an optimistic view for academics and practitioners to attain circularity in food supply chains from stakeholders' understanding. However, it needs to be adjusted to different setting and contexts.

The discussion on the results leads to possible direction of future research and limitations of this research are noted. The study delivers managerial implications for the organisation who actively wish to adopt the circular model. It provides the direction for future research to further explore the phenomenon. This chapter reviews the theoretical, managerial, and practical contributions in detail. The next section outlines the implications of research findings. Section 7.3 discuss the limitation of study, including recommendation and implications for future research prospects arising from present study are obtained. Finally, in section 7.4 some conclusions are drawn.

6.2 IMPLICATIONS OF THE RESEARCH FINDINGS

Based on the critical and comprehensive background of the UK food industry, this study presents a unique and rich perspective for the emerging concept of the circular economy, hindrance encountered and drivers to adopt the change from the stakeholders' view. The major contribution is aligned on the basis of gaps found in literature i.e., "What are the barriers in the way of adopting the circular supply chain management framework?" "How do they affect the stakeholders?" "What can be the possible driver?". Literature gaps are reviewed as: The circular supply chain management is still an emerging field and require research related to its various functions (Farooque et al., 2019). Secondly, challenges and barriers vary on the basis of industry, company size or geographical location etc., it is a requirement to explore the circular economy barriers in specific business sector, propose the enablers, refine the theoretical framework and to provide insight for policymakers for the possibilities of successful transition. To the best of the researcher's knowledge so far there is not any systematic study performed in UK food supply chains in this context (Bressanelli et al., 2018; Kirchherr et al., 2018; Tura et al., 2018; Hart et al., 2019; Hussain and Malik, 2020; Keulen, and Kirchherr, 2021). Third, there is a lack of exploring the list of barriers under theoretical lenses (Farooque et al., 2019). Fourth, limited research is performed on the conceptual studies on the circular business model to facilitate its practical and managerial implementation (Bressanelli et al., 2018; Howard et al., 2019; Angelis, 2020). Fifth, in the previous studies, in-depth analysis of the consumer perspective for the circular economy is neglected (Kirchherr et al., 2017; Elzinga, 2020). This study has been conducted to fulfil the above research gaps.

Due to the evolving nature of the subject, this study started with introducing the background and its evaluation with time i.e., biomimicry paradigm, performance / sharing economy paradigm and cradle-to-cradle. The theoretical lens of stakeholder theory assisted to find associated actors in circular supply chain management. This discussion provided the settings for identifying challenges and drivers on which the overall thesis rests (see chapter 2). This detailed review delivers strategic and managerial implications for adopting the circular supply chain model as per its three major dimensions of contributing towards social, environmental, and economic benefits of organisations.

In response to the first objective, this research extracted challenges specific to UK food supply chain management. The themes related to challenges were categorised and complement the existing literature (Ritzéna and Sandström, 2017; Hart et al., 2018; de Jesusa and Mendonça, 2018; Kirchherr et al., 2018; Farooque et al., 2019; Mangla et al.2018) that revolution of the circular economy perceives technical, financial, management, socio-cultural, structural, and regulatory types of barriers which are further enhanced more closely and precisely. Along with challenges explored in existing studies from the general context, different industries and from different geographical contexts, some novel themes were originated i.e., shelf life, minimum order quantities, demographical factors, and post-Brexit trade. Hence, the contribution of this research is to instigate factors which affect the circular transition specific to UK food supply chains. So far, this is the first study from a management perspective to analyse UK food supply chains for circular economy applications. It explored that perception, attitude and buying behaviour towards circular change and remanufactured products were the dominant themes. Lack of infrastructure and less supportive legislation was evident throughout the supply chain. Stakeholders exposed their interest and understanding about sustainability and waste management. Whereas research revealed that there is very basic awareness in the industry and the society in connection with circular supply chain management processes. With the empirical findings, this study provides broader insights into the field of the circular economy literature while offering significant contribution to existing knowledge.

In response to the second research objectives, circular supply chain revolution is not merely based on managing the relationship of supply chain stakeholders for efficiency, productivity, and greening (Bakker et al., 2014; Geissdoerfer et al., 2018). It scrutinises each of the steps to close the loops i.e., the way product is designed, processed, commercialised, consumed and put back to

the reverse chains to attain the sustainability in economies (Franco et al., 2019). Empirical observations revealed that barriers to adopt the circular economy are wide-ranging yet specific to the industry. All affect the stakeholders in different contexts, depending on the actions they perform on their platform. This qualitative study assessed the perception and experiences of its players from each phase including customers views on how the current practices followed in their businesses are opponent to adopt this transition. Circular supply chain management is a network of processes, different stakeholders perform distinct activities to achieve the zero-waste vision and get affected by different causes in distinctive way. Hence, challenges were explored on the functional level. The product development stage and manufacturing are mainly affected by lack of supportive legislation from government by the way of taking decision and developing product on real time basis. For retailers, people's behaviour, perception, and attitude are the biggest blocker because of their buying habits and psychological unacceptability of circular solutions. Demographical challenges put more impact on consumer and up-cyclers due to imbalanced societies and due to less education, which prevents up-cyclers to be part of a customer's buying option. Recyclers and logistics need infrastructure to hit the quantities and targets of recycling. Similarly, the impact of each factor was closely analysed. Because of unavailability of existing research on functional level analysis, there is no direct comparison to be made with previous literature.

Finally, this study presented strategic drivers to those challenge. Contribution from the government bodies was most influential enabler by providing financial support and incentives, rigorous legislations, raising awareness among the societies and aligning the road map. Collaboration, education, value creation and functional level drivers such management commitment, competitive pricing strategies, product traceability and measurability etc. are significant proposals. Circular supply chain management needs integration and collaboration from stakeholders, i.e., government, management, and consumers, and from processes like technology, communication, and awareness for value creation (Leder et al., 2020).

Research contribution is the most important aspect of a doctoral thesis by arising the significance of performed research towards the discipline being studied. In the next section, the contribution of this research is presented which expands the boundaries of knowledge. To start with, theoretical

supposition, followed by managerial interference and then environmental contributions are presented.

6.2.1 Theoretical contribution of study

The study puts forward four research questions: What is the circular supply chain management approach from the food industry perspective? How can it be achieved? What are the barriers or challenges that come in the way of successful application of the food circular supply chain management framework? How do those threatening indicators affect each stage of the circular supply chain? What can be the possible drivers to overcome those barriers? brought forward from three objectives of this research which are: to explore circular supply chain management approach from the food industry perspective, to investigate the key barriers in circular supply chain management in the food industry and drivers to overcome those barriers, to systematically examine the effects of those barriers at each stage of circular supply chain management.

This finding contributes to the circular economy literature and several other fields of academic research. This thesis expands the circular economy literature by providing new theoretical findings through a new regional background, by exploring the potentials of implementing the circular economy model in the UK food supply chain, by critically assessing previously known and recognising new barriers, investigating, and exploring the repercussion on stakeholder level and suggesting the drivers.

The first contribution of this research shows that circular supply chain management is novel and demanding field in the UK food industry and the academic field. Current literature of the circular economy mainly focusses on China (Geng and Dorberstein, 2008; Geng et al., 2012; Su et al., 2013; Liu and Bai., 2014; Farooqe et al., 2019), in general context (Govindan and Hasanagic, 2018) and other context i.e., construction or fashion industries or different countries (Mangla et al., 2018; de Jesusa and Mendonça, 2018). Studying this concept from UK food industries give more specific and deep insight to its application. The study is prerequisite because of the difference in market and legal structure different countries. China is the first county of the world to execute the circular economy as legislation as the part of its national development strategy (Farooqe et al., 2019). Whereas there is no such imposing framework introduced in United Kingdom, on the contrary food health and safety regulation are more rigid than other countries. Subsequently, lack

of supportive legislation is found as one of the most discussed barriers in the current study. Moreover, it is an attempt to address the gaps and calls from previous literature (Bressanelli et al., 2018; de Jesusa and Mendonça, 2018; Farooque et al., 2019; Kirchherr et al., 2017; Howard et al., 2019; Angelis, 2020; Elzinga, 2020).

As suggested by de Jesusa and Mendonça, (2018), an empirical and systematic analysis is another major contribution of this study. Including relevant actors can offer more effectiveness to bottom-up strategies for the circular economy by getting relevant feedback (Mendoza et al., 2020). Thus, this research setting on the stakeholder theory, is first empirical study to include relevant stakeholders (product designers, manufacturers, retailers' consumers, up-cyclers, recyclers, and logistics) whose contribution is pertinent to create the value for this transition. Involvement of stakeholders in this research aided in offering more rational strategies as drivers to create value for stakeholders and the organisation while accepting environmental ventures in business.

This study is also a refinement and integration of enablers suggested in existing studies of the circular economy. It is mandatory in the circular economy theories to define “what is required to put the enablers into practice and accelerate uptake of the circular economy” (Hart et al., 2019). There is a plethora of studies to suggest the enabler for this transition (Hart et al., 2019), no systematic attempt to combine the necessary strategies to those enablers is made. This is the preliminary attempt to contribute sectoral based strategies to overcome from barriers to circular supply chain management transformation in food industry of the United Kingdom. Thus, it is an inclusive and theoretical attempt towards the circular economy literature.

This study proposed a comprehensive framework exclusive to food supply chain management of the United Kingdom by deconstructing the practices and avail the stakeholders a guide towards the circular economy agenda. The proposed framework includes main factors (financial, technical, management, socio-cultural, structural, and institutional) suggested by (Ritzén and Sandström, 2017) with barriers and drivers related to these factors. Some of the barriers like lack of legislative support, lack of awareness, lack of knowledge and skill, lack of management commitment, complex nature etc., are repeatedly described in previous studies. Since, this study is exclusively performed on the stakeholders of the UK food industry, the additional perspective to be explored in the terms of challenges is provided to UK based factors i.e., post-Brexit trade (see chapter 5) or

for the food industries product shelf-life (chapter 5). Elements like demographic factors provide the insight for comparison of different level of societies for accepting and implementation this transition. Moreover, these challenges are related to the organizations on the early stage of adopting the circular economy and sustainability model. Therefore, this transition is overall affected by challenges: lack of awareness, lack of legislative framework and lack of infrastructure and need major involvement of government (Su et al., 2013). Due to the perishable nature of this industry, technical innovations on the operational level to reuse and remanufacture the products and acceptance from the society (mental barriers) to be tackled.

For fulfilling the gap discussed by Hart et al., 2019, this research introduced practical strategies to different categories of barriers. Government was uncovered as the main driver by providing a carrot and stick approach in which carrots refer to incentivizing the innovation, infrastructure support, tax relief to contributors, subsidies, zero percent interest loan schemes, and sticks refer to the rigorous rules with implications and fines. Collaboration among stakeholders, process, and specific department for sustainability is vital throughout the structure of circular supply chains. Traceability (Tsoufas and Pappis, 2006; Rashid et al., 2013; Franco, 2019), measurability (Tura et al., 2019), product life extension technology and big data analytics are demanded strategies for technical challenges of food supply chains. Management commitment and decentralization for real-time decision making (Dierksmeier and Seele, 2020), can actively help close the loops. For overcoming social or cultural barriers, government can initiate awareness programs; introducing the circular economy at the school education level can be an effective strategy. Creating the value for stakeholders and embedding into existing values leads towards cultural change from a linear mindset to circular. Integrating all integral and interconnected elements, this research presents a model to existing body of knowledge that can be tested further. The framework based on this model was initially developed in chapter III and further updated in chapter VI.

6.2.2 Managerial contribution

Besides the theoretical implications discussed in previous section which contributes towards theoretical embellishments, this study offers managerial contributions for the industries, policy makers and functional level managers who are aspired to adopt circular business models. The results illustrate understanding of the circular economy approach in the supply chain, guidance for

managers about its potential for implementation in food industry and the challenges organizations face when adopting it practically. More specifically, it assists stakeholders by examining the repercussions of challenges on their functional level and suggests strategies to remove those challenges.

For developing the understanding of managers, this study provides a comprehensive overview of different paradigms towards sustainability. Literature suggests the circular economy as most demanding and aspirational for current business scenarios while providing three dimensional benefits (social, environmental, and economic) (Accenture Strategy, 2017; MGI, 2017) towards which managers must be inclined. However, due to the nature of the food industry the hindrances for business for not adopting it as a business model is a matter of discussion. Analysis of this study shows that managers are reluctant to accept this transition due to high investment requirement (Geng et al., 2009; Smol et al., 2015; Pan et al., 2015; Govindan and Hasanagic, 2018), their profitability approach (Palm et al., 2016; Shahbazi et al., 2016), longstanding organization culture (Borello et al., 2015; Kirrcher et al., 2018), less support from legislative bodies (Vanner et al., 2014, Rizos et al., 2015, van Eijk 2015, Pheifer, 2017 and Ranta et al., 2017), complex nature of process (Zimmann, 2016; Adams et al., 2017), and some technical factors (France, 2019). Managers also think that one of the reasons towards less favourability of this model is unacceptability from the end consumers (Liu and Bai, 2014).

By analyzing the technical aspect, this study reveals that food industries are lacking behind the knowledge and skills about the practices to be followed, options and possibilities to re-use the products (Ritzéna and Sandström, 2017; de Jesus and Mendonça, 2018). Product life is the prime concern of managers to apply circularity strategies. Due to health and safety concerns, circular products are not acceptable to the consumers. For food supply chain, there is an incongruity in the demand and forecasting from retailers to manufacturers. That leads to huge amount of food waste and less possibility to apply real time approaches like closing the loops. This study demands innovations regarding product life extension techniques or strategies for the products to be used for an optimum time without affecting nutrition value, taste, texture, and eye appeal of the product. It needs advancement in the demand-forecasting system through techniques, strategies or through co-ordination.

Environmental transitions in the business should have financial property attached to them. It will not be acceptable until it is profitable for the business (Lieder and Rashid, 2016). For instance, sustainable solutions are an extra cost for business by the way of getting virgin material or investing on new technologies (Shahbazi et al., 2016). On the other hand, consumers are not ready to spend extra money for the sake of the environment only while having other priorities. Thus, the circular economy strategies do not fit with the need of end consumer. An opponent factor discovered in this research against the circular economy is the rule set by businesses of “buying limit”, buying more for less, which customers find economical but does not get along with the ideal picture of circular supply chain. This research suggests that industries and government should start this initiative by educating and spreading awareness among societies by showing the results for accepting it and consequences of carrying out linear processes (Genovese et al., 2015; Adam, 2017; Sung et al, 2017). The most effective instrument suggested is social media networks. Providing financial support to these endeavours can also lead to a change.

Environmental models are found less favourable by management because of less financial gains Kirchher et al., (2018). Literature shows that monetary benefits can be achieved for adopting as model by reducing the waste, less inviting on the raw material as upcycling, remanufacturing, and reusing are significant elements of the model and by getting competitive advantage (Wijkman and Skånberg 2015; Merli et al., 2017). Therefore, management should consider circular achievement as part of company’s long-term plans and should design the strategies on that basis. Products should be marketed wisely by presenting positive impact of it (Hopkinson et al., (2018). Organisations can target the customer group on demographic factor such as younger generation is getting more inclined towards environmentally friendly practices. On the flip side this study also demonstrates that management is committed to current sustainability trends of the market, but it is the awareness that needs to be brought in (Borello et al., 2015; Lakatos et al., 2016).

Moreover, the study evidence that companies running from many decades have set of standards to perform the tasks, which is more incline towards liners supply chain, amendment to which cannot be done overnight but can be enabled by embedding this approach into the (Key Performance Indicators) KPIs of companies and through the value creation of the stakeholders. The findings on this aspect will hopefully assist the managers to design their strategies for marketing this concept to customers and motivating the employees to accept circular supply chains (van Loon and Van

Wassenhove, 2017). From the management to public, there is very basic awareness about this occurrence and even where there is familiarity, right practices are hidden. Awareness is an instrument to slope the individual's perception and attitude. However, this study also presents contradicting view that organization culture is not difficult to change but finance is more critical factor.

The formation of the circular economy must be resilient which can be facilitated through availing infrastructure by the way of providing waste separation and disposing of infrastructure or technologies to facilitate product reuse and remanufacturing (Vadakkepatt, 2021). It must be easy to manage. This study recommends addition in the structure of companies by adding an independent department to manage the circular economy responsibilities. These tasks should include setting the goals, aligning the policies, ensuring regular control, marketing and hunting for circular ideas. There should be collaboration of all the stakeholders to follow factual and integrated practices, communication and coordination and transparency to bring about positive change (Pomponi and Mocanter, 2018).

While analysing the institutional environment, this study urges paramount involvement of government (Al Zaabi et al., 2013). Industry representatives reveal that the UK government is lagging behind from many European countries for circular supply chain adoption because it is not part of the government's political agenda. The circular economy is not introduced as an obligation in the country. Government being more involved first in Brexit and then Covid-19, progress in environmental initiatives is not prominent. Post-Brexit trade is also exposed as an emerging challenge for the UK the circular economy initiatives. It is recommended that policy makers should introduce a country-based framework and a road map including various industries with the allocated budget. Providing education can be an initial point, followed by monetary support, stringent rules with penalties including the implications. For the food related enterprises UK legislation is discovered as more rigid.

The study findings also divulge that circular supply chain management works as a matrix, each of its elements are interconnected and affected by each-others (Huamao and Fengqi, 2013). New product development department is highly impacted by the demands and requirements of retailers about the products, trials, or packaging. It prevents them to follow the circular economy-based

designs. Which are thought to be less favourable by consumers due to minimal awareness or their attitude. Managers from designing stage of supply chain requires coordination from other stakeholders to design the circular economy-based products and process including technologies in place to serve long life of products.

This research explores that manufacturing and processing of products apposite to the circular model is an additional cost for the businesses by investing in new tools, techniques, ideas, training, raw material, and packaging, hence, not acceptable, and not supported by regulations (Ritzen and Sandstrom, 2017; Tura et al., 2018). Retailers' stream of forecasting and ordering does not match well along with the circular model in the supply chain because it leads to difference in estimated and actual orders, becoming a reason for generating a huge amount of wastage which is not suitable to these initiatives. Management is less dedicated to creating environmental initiative because less financial gains. The study suggests having circular vision with set targets, knowledge, expertise, allocated time, structure, and close control over the processes to implement circularity.

The retailing stage finds consumers perception, attitude and buying behaviour are the alarming factors because of they affect retailers' decisions directly (Zukin and Maguire, 2004). Retailers require particular department and tailor-made, stores-based policies, with adequate number of staff who can manage and control the process efficiently with effective communication. Retailers also get impacted by competition which make them keep environment as secondary task and follow the market trends. Retailers have to pay high to cost for sustainable products which are less prefeed by customers. Whereas factors like government support, order and forecasting, knowledge and skills, shelf-life, complex nature, inappropriate marketing strategies and lack of awareness has moderate impact of retailing organisations.

This research discloses that demographic factors affect the circular initiatives in two ways. From one side, nation with more strong financial background can spend on education for society. As a result, environmental practices are more followed in these nations. Whereas from the other side this research provides a critical aspect that societies with more buying power make people extravagant and where they do not care the environment. It was established that for cost of products, legislation support, post-Brexit trade, perception and attitude and shelf life are important factors to apply circular change. This provides guidance to industries while aligning the circular

economy related factors affecting consumers should be equally considered. Thus, the research provides cross-functional practice approach for the implementation of circular supply chain model.

Upcycling of food products on industrial level is very novel concept all over the world. Only few companies have instigated this practice in food sector. However, businesses are involved in metal, fashion industry, furniture and machine components upcycling. The close analysis from a coffee machines upcycling company disclose that people (customers) do not have positive attitudes to buying upcycled products. People prefer to buy new products rather the upcycled because of psychological or financial reasons. In some instances, due to less small size of production, product turns out to be more expensive. These conditions are not satisfactory for business to business as well as business to consumer business. Applying this framework on a large scale can provide economies of scale to business and cost /price benefits to customers. Additionally, whether it is machine or food products, upcycling need highly skilled worker, professional and accurate knowledge (McDonough and Braungart, 2013; Sung et al., 2015).

The study suggests that infrastructure and less government support with have increasing volume of business are the challenges. The findings suggest that recycling needs financial support from governments for the business development. Its complex nature should be managed with having appropriate structure in place. i.e., reverse logistics. There is still less awareness about recycling which influence the whole circle of supply chain be sustainable (De Angelis et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2018; Husain and Malik, 2020). Ideal model of circular supply chain management includes logistics and reverse logistics, there needs to apposite structure, to make this on-going process happen (Govindan and Hasanagic, 2018). From the manufacturing perspective capacity of production is a major factor to handle the finished good. Geographical locations of companies to apply circular supply chain management is important element to avail sharing economy.

Along with the enablers discussed earlier, this research provides the strategic contributions by introducing strategies to drive circular change. Circular supply chain management can be perceived in the society by education. It should be the part of school core curriculum. To embed it into organisation's culture, it is required to make it the part of 'Key performance Indicator' to measure and control it. Moreover, the price of circular economy influenced product should be competitive to price of other products. Government should adopt traditional carrot- stick approach

by incentivising and applying the rules (Hart et al., 2019). There should be traceability aspect attached with it. So that origin and pathway of the product be obtained to make the reuse more secure. Traceability will also help to analysis the life cycle assessment of product (Tsoufias and Pappis, 2006; Rashid et al., 2013; Franco, 2019). Effects of circular supply chain management should be measurable and transparent to everyone. Which means stakeholders should know how much their practices affecting the environment. Adopting knowledge management and big data analytic can facilitate the product and service sharing for circular economies. It should be adopted on the industry level as well so that waste of one firm can be utilised by another. Circular supply chain stakeholder should have freedom of taking decision to of designing and remanufacturing the products on their own level.

Circular supply chain management needs drastic change in the way the current economy is working. The main purpose of this concept is to transform the ways of business operations to be more sustainable by closing the loops but not the creating the cycles of material recovery and energy flow which is mostly highlighted in the literature (Fogarassy and Finger, 2020). From the contradictory perspective, it is important to analyse whether the circular economy model leads towards growth of economy and benefit for society. Is it worth putting so much effort into it? How feasible is the zero-waste vision is in the current business environment specifically in food industries? Because of its novel nature, society and business have less experience with so far. To answer this question, more research and development is demanded. Analysis of this thesis came up with plethora of challenges, which needs to be overcome to apply it in the current environment, considering its 3 dimensions: society, ecology and economy and close assessment of costs involved in it.

The circular business model is mainly concerned about value circles which need collaborative efforts from all the stakeholders, supportive technology systems like big data, artificial intelligence to supports its processes. Contribution from reverse logistics mandatory throughout the chain for bringing the material back into cycle. The circular economy focuses to put the material into multiple cycles again and again to get the best value out of it. It needs highly efficient materials and technologies. Which can be visualized in packaging and machinery but is a big question for food products itself. This efficiency from reused and remanufactured materials is difficult to serve. Circular supply chain management works on (3Rs) for products to be reduce, reuse, remanufacture

and recycle. Acceptance of this approach from the societies by changing mindset of people is necessary yet stimulating.

6.3 RESEARCH LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This exploratory research is preliminary step to gain deep insight into the circular supply chain management topic, due to the less availability of literature in food industry in the United Kingdom, where application of such approach is demanding yet imminent from practical as well as theoretical perspective. This study comes up with the framework of implications incurring challenges and drivers for it. The finding of this study needs interpretation of limitation that are relevant for future research. These limitations are related to sampling, methods discussed in following sections.

6.3.1 The method of sampling/analysis

The present research followed specific methods for sampling and analysis, limitation related to which should be drawn. This research is carried out in a specific setting limited to UK context and limited to food industry. Application in the different settings can obtain different result to this. Research is limited from the sampling size of 34 participants. Although it brought valuable insights for the circular economy implementation, but large sampling including quantitative empirical studies are recommended to validate the findings.

Based on the stakeholder theory, this study is conducted involving the stakeholders directly involved in the food supply chains. However, the supplier stage is first included then discarded due to data quality and relevance issues. Similarly, there is only one participant involved from upcycling because of less availability of food upcycling companies. Future studies can be performed by involving these stakeholders.

Furthermore, the participants involved in this research are directly related to food supply chain. But context of stakeholders who are indirectly related i.e., institutional bodies and academic, can be different and worth exploring for same settings.

This study includes companies related to food industry which are involved and interested in sustainability practices, but the circular economy is not applied as business model. Further

empirical study should be conducted from comparative perspective with the findings of this study with the companies where it is applied as business strategy.

Purely qualitative design is another limitation this research. This study conducted semi-structured interviews with the stakeholders for exploring experience, feelings, perceptions and understanding of the circular economy approach to develop the framework. In which respondents bias could not be entirely limited. Future research can should include quantitative methods to validate qualitative the findings.

This research presented challenges and explored their repercussions on various phases of supply chain. The way they affect the stakeholders. To provide the additional understanding on the context specificity of challenges to supply chain stages and to different industries and business environment can be tested with quantitative methods.

This research has taken stakeholder theory as a lens to create value for stakeholders and is one of the few research studies of the circular economy from a management perspective. Future research can be conducted through other management theories and model.

Strategies are introduced to overcome the barriers come on the way to accept the circular economy transition. i.e., traceability, big data, measurability. The findings are significance for the whole supply chain management. Further research can investigate the effectiveness of these strategies on different levels of supply chain.

Due to Covid-19 restrictions data collection process was restricted to online (telephone interview) method (Opdenakker, 2006). Which has disadvantages to “lack of social cues” and “No view of the situation”, future research can be conducted involving face-to-face interviews and industry visits.

6.3.2 Future research avenues

This study explored the circular economy, its barriers, repercussions on supply chain and the drivers has unlock many doors for the possibilities of future research. The following are some

suggestions to extend the current body of knowledge in the circular supply chain literature and its business and management context.

This research has used stakeholder perspective as theoretical glance and propose holistic framework for adopting circular supply chain approach considering challenges and barriers to its different stages. A different theoretical approach can be perceived to analyses the concept. Further research can be performed on various geographical locations and industries. As suggested by Ketokivi and Choi (2014), a mixed method approach (qualitative and quantitative) can be applied to test research objectives.

This study has explored the circular economy from UK food supply chain settings. Researchers studying circular supply chain management can explore and validate it in different settings. This thesis is a first attempt to carry out systematic analysis of various challenges from circular supply chain stakeholders' perspective who are directly related to its processes. It should consider institutional and academic perspectives. In this respect future studies can integrate the views of government representatives and academics. It could be interesting to study the different combinations such as inter-organisational comparisons (different manufacturers, different retailers, or recyclers).

It should also be helpful to focus on one aspect of the supply chain such as designing and testing the findings of this research using quantitative methods. Direct conceptual relationships of challenging factors and supply chain actors can be explored, tested, and validated. Future studies can also explore how companies can implement suggested strategies for value creation.

There are new themes originated from this research related to the food industry i.e., post-Brexit trade, minimum order quantities, shelf life of product and demographical factors. Further research can explore and test these factors for validity and reliability in different settings.

6.4 SUMMARY

This research is a contribution towards circular supply chain management literature for better understanding of the concept, its potential to for implementation, challenges to apply in the food industry and repercussions of challenges on various supply chain stages and the drivers to support

the implementation. This is exploratory research, and the qualitative methods approach has been adopted to systematically explore the phenomenon and obtain the findings. A theoretical framework is developed resulted from thorough analysis of data collected from supply chain stakeholders directly related to the circular supply chain. The thematic analysis method is applied for data analysis. The main findings indicate that circular supply chain management is daunting due to its novel and critical nature yet attainable in the food industry. There are numerous challenges faced by industries to adopt this practice throughout the food supply chain and affect in different ways on the different levels. Finally, drivers in terms of business strategies are suggested. Since this is the first research to systematically analysis the way different phases of UK food circular supply chain get affected by recognized barriers and suggested business strategies for all categories of barriers, there is no theoretical justification included from existing literature.

Finally, limitations of this study are discussed, based on which possibilities of future research are suggested. Future research can be employed using different management theories and models using the findings of this research. This research suggested that future studies should validate and test the relationship of derived barriers to specific supply chains actors, different industries or geographic locations using a mixed methods approach.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 4.1 Interviewee Sheet

Introduction:

My name is Mandeep Kaur. I am currently a Doctoral researcher at University of the West of Scotland, London Campus, UK. I am MBA and M.Sc. in Management with Project Management. I have professional experience in financial sector for 6 years and currently work as a personal line account handler in Bryan James insurance & Co. Ltd.

Title of the study:

Investigation of challenges and drivers, in circular supply chain management and their contextual relationship: A stakeholder analysis for maximising sustainability in the food industry of the United Kingdom.

Introduction:

You are being invited to take part in a study. Before you decide whether to do so, it is important that you understand the study that is being undertaken and what your involvement will include. Please take the time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Do not hesitate to ask us anything that is not clear or for any further information you would like to help you make your decision. Please do take your time to decide whether or not you wish to take part. The University's regulation, UPR RE01, 'Studies Involving the Use of Human Participants' can be accessed via this link:

Aim of the research:

This research is concerned with recognizing the challenges to accept the circular economy concept by food manufacturing industries in the UK. It explores the factors that come on the way in the circular supply chain management. Furthermore, the aim of research is to find out the possible drivers which can help the organizations to make the operation management decisions for circular supply chain management. The study aims to fulfil following objectives.

- To explore the key barriers in Circular Supply Chain Management in the food industry.
- To systematically examine the contextual relationship between those barriers and each stage of the Circular Supply Chain.
- To investigate the key drivers for the success of the circular economy in the food industry by overcoming those barriers.

Do I have to take part?

It is completely up to you whether or not you decide to take part in this study. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. Agreeing to join the study does not mean that you have to complete it. You are free to withdraw at any stage without giving a reason. A decision to withdraw at any time, or a decision not to take part at all, will not affect any treatment/care that you may receive (should this be relevant).

How long will my part in the study take?

If you decide to take part in this study, you will be involved in it for the maximum of 60 minutes (1 hour).

What will happen to me if I take part?

Firstly, you will be asked to familiarize yourself with the participant information sheet and return your consent form. Before the interview begins, the interviewer will explain and reassure you that all information discussed during the meeting will be confidential unless there is concern for safety of yourself and others. You will be asked to turn your camera off as the meeting will be recorded for transcribing purposes. By taking part in this study, you agree to audio recording, but your consent can be withdrawn in writing at any time without giving a reason.

What are the possible disadvantages, risks or side effects of taking part?

There are no physical risks associated with taking part in this study. You will only be asked general questions about your views on circular supply chain management implementation. The researcher will not pressure you to discuss any personal or confidential data of your organization. If you feel uncomfortable at any stage of the interview you can refuse to answer a question without stating the reason and your wishes will be respected. You can also withdraw your consent at any stage of the study, or the interview and you do not have to give a reason.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

Your participation will help to the food industries to attain the sustainability in their organizations. Various barriers and their possible relationship with each stage of circular supply chain management coming on the way to successful implementation of green manufacturing of food products will be discussed. And the drivers to overcome those challenges will also be provided. Therefore, by taking part in this research, you are given an opportunity to be the anonymous voice for food industries.

How will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?

Yes. Personal details such as name and email address will be anonymized prior to storage, and only participant's profile and position in the company may be mentioned during the interview, paper notes, transcription and final manuscript. Participant has the right to ask the researcher to

keep any additional data confidential. Should that be the case, the participant's wishes will be respected. The researcher will not disclose any personal information beyond this study, except in the event where it is suspected that the participant is at risk of harm to themselves or to others.

Audio-visual material

The interview audio will be reordered. Please note that the video will not be used in the study beyond the interview stage and only your voice recording will be accessed to transcribe the interview. Whenever you do not feel comfortable about recording something, I can pause the recorder. Whatever issues you may not feel comfortable talking about, we can move on to other issues or topics.

What will happen to the data collected within this study?

The data collected will be stored electronically, in a password-protected environment, for a maximum of 12 months, after which time it will be destroyed under secure conditions.

The audio data will be anonymized, transcribed, analyzed for common themes and written up as a final report which will explore the findings of the study.

Documents containing personal details, such as consent form and participation information sheet, will be password-locked and stored electronically on the researcher's personal computer. The documents will be stored for the maximum of 1 year after the end of the project, and then deleted/destroyed under secure conditions.

Any hard copies containing personal details will be given to the project supervisor and will be stored in a locked filing cabinet at the University of the West of Scotland for 1 year then destroyed under secure conditions.

Will the data be required for use in further studies?

The data will not be used in any further studies.

Who has reviewed this study?

This study has been reviewed by the Ethical Committee of University of the West of Scotland.

Factors that might put others at risk

Please note that if, during the study, any medical conditions, or non-medical circumstances such as unlawful activity become apparent that might or had put others at risk, the University may refer the matter to the appropriate authorities and, under such circumstances, you will be withdrawn from the study.

Who can I contact if I have any questions?

If you would like further information or would like to discuss any details personally, please get in touch with me by email:

Thank you very much for reading this information and giving consideration to taking part in this study.

About the interviewee

Title:

Interviewer:

Position

Personal responsibilities:

How long have you been with the company?

In how many different cities/ provinces does this company currently operate? (How many Campuses or Branches does this organization has?)

Name of organization:

Date:

Appendix 4.2 Interview Protocol

RQ1: What are the barriers that come on the way of successful application of the CSC framework?

<p>Circular Supply Chain Management</p> <p>Definition: Circular Supply Chain Management is the co-ordination of forward and reverse supply chains (Batista et al., 2018a, p. 446) which systematically restore technical material and regenerate biological material towards a zero waste vision through system-wide innovation in business models and supply chain functions from product/service design to end-of-life and waste management, involving all stakeholders in a product/service lifecycle including parts/product manufacturers, service providers, consumers, and users (Farooque et al., 2019, p.884)</p>	
	<p>What is circular supply chain management to you? Business Model or environmental/ sustainable strategy?</p>
	<p>Would you please explain the supply chain management process of your company?</p>
	<p>What sustainability and waste management goals you have in your company?</p>
	<p>How do you work with business models connected to sustainability?</p>
	<p>To what extent, do you think application circular economy model in the supply chain of your company can help to reach towards zero waste vision and to achieve sustainability goals?</p>
	<p>How would you explain the application of circular economy among all departments such as product development, manufacturing, logistics of your company?</p>

<p>Does the less advancement in technology and innovation make it difficult, for the linear supply chain to be replaced with circular? Borrello et al 2016; Shahbazi et al. (2016) Jesus and Mendonça,</p>	<p>What technological barriers are related or come on the way of accepting the circular supply chain model?</p> <p>Can you please explain, how do technology and digitalization play a role in the circular supply chain management process?</p> <p>Which technological challenge or barrier do you think are the most inauspicious for the UK food industry and your company?</p>
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2017; Pheifer (2017); Kirchherr et al 2017; Mont et al. (2017); Hart et al, 2018; Mangla et al, 2018; Sandvik and Stubbs W. 2019; Farooque et al, 2019; Hart et al, 2019

Does the business, who think about environmental issues, will have to scarify the economic value? Heyes et al 2017; Hart et al, 2018; Mangla et al, 2018; Farooque et al, 2019

Do less effectiveness in planning, management and designing of a scenario for the optimal utilization of resources prevent the supply chain players to focus on a critical issue in the circular supply chain? Mangla et al, 2018; Andrea and Chiaroni, 2018; Farooque et al, 2019;

Do the company and consumer culture are the major issues for the circular supply chain to become part of the company's strategy and

As per your perception, what are the economic and finance-related barriers come on the way of accepting a circular approach?

How do financial and economic aspects divert the organizations to adopt a circular supply chain management approach?

Do you think, your company also has economic-related barriers for accepting the circular supply chain management model? If yes, what type of barriers they are?

Do you think there are management barriers which stop the successful implementation of CSCM practices?

If yes, what the management related barriers are and how they affect the circular supply chain management?

To what extent, you think planning and management of the company put the impact on CE initiatives?

Do you think the company's culture plays an important part to bring any changes in the company?

How do cultural factors help in making strategies and policies and to set the vision and mission of an organization?

<p>mission? Vanner et al. (2014); Van 2015; Mont et al. (2017); Ranta et al. (2017); Pheifer (2017); Kirchherr et al 2017; Jesus and Mendonça, 2017; Ritzén and Sandström, 2017; Hart et al, 2018</p>	<p>What cultural factors do think come on the way to accept the circular economy model for an organization?</p> <p>Do you think recognisability of cultural factors on the priority basis can help in bringing a circular supply chain in your company?</p> <p>Do you also think that social factors on the consumer side can also be barriers? If yes, what those factors are?</p>
<p>Does less the integration between sustainability in functions and between hierarchical levels of the organization, will be a stronger barrier to circular supply chain transition? Ritzén and Sandström, 2017; Hart et al, 2018</p>	<p>Can you please explain, how organization structure plays an important role to bring a circular approach in the supply chain management?</p> <p>What structural barriers come on the way to circular supply chain application in your organization?</p>
<p>Do lesser motivation and support from the government, will be a harder barrier for circular supply chain transition? Rizos et al 2015; Van Eijk (2015), Pheifer (2017); Mont et al. (2017); Ranta et al. (2017);Mangla et al, 2018; Farooq et al 2019;</p>	<p>As per your perception, does the government play a part to make the circular economy a successful transition?</p> <p>Do you think current law and regulations are inadequate for bringing revolutionary changes supporting CE activities?</p> <p>What are those barriers?</p>

RQ2: How and which threatening indicators affect each stage of CSCM?

Barriers on design stage:

<p>Circular Design: Definition: Designing in the circular economy is a deliberate business process involving hundreds of decisions (Krishnan and Ulrich 2001), with the intent of developing a tangible, physical product (Petersen et al., 2005; Rauniar et al., 2008; Hong and Roh 2009; Hong et al., 2011) using the strategies of slowing and closing the resource loop, where slowing of resource loops involves increasing the utilisation of products, through extending the product lifetime and through sharing schemes. Closing resource loops relates to ensuring that materials can be recycled in a closed-loop fashion at the end of use (Stahel, 1994; McDonough and Braungart, 2002; Stahel, 2010).</p>	
	How would you define the designing stage of circular supply chain management?
	Can you explain, reverse and closed-loop strategies?
	To the best of your knowledge, how is it possible to design the product, suitable to reverse and closed-loop strategies?
	From the barriers discussed earlier, which barriers prevent the products to be designed for a circular supply chain?
	Are there any other direct or indirect barriers faced or can be faced by designing department in your organization?
	Are there any policies made in your organization to encourage the circular designing of products, specifically for your department?
	What are the other possible drivers?

Barriers on manufacturing stage:

<p>Manufacturing Definition: Manufacturing in circular supply chain management is a process in which products are manufactured and remanufactured (Batista et al., 2018a) by utilising the variety of capabilities that add value to the material by minimising negative environmental impacts,</p>

conserving energy and natural resources that are safer and rewarding for employees, communities and consumers and are economically sound (Hauschild,2014).

	How would you define manufacturing stage of circular supply chain management?	
	What are the potentials in implementing circular economy during the manufacturing process?	
	To the best of your knowledge, how is it possible to manufacture the product by minimizing negative environmental impacts, conserving energy and natural resources and closed loops?	
	From the barriers discussed earlier, which barriers prevent the manufacturing of products in the circular supply chain?	
	Are there any other direct or indirect barriers faced or can be faced by the manufacturing department in your organization?	
	Are there any policies made in your organization to encourage sustainable manufacturing of products?	
	Can you suggest any other drivers from the manufacturing stage support circular supply chain?	

Barriers on Retailing stage:

Retailing in the circular economy refers to the management of retailing business with environmental benefits (Lai et al., 2010) by creation, utilisation and use of assets with least negative impact (Polonsky, 2011) and has ecological dimensions that pursue the retail value chain by eliminating waste, increasing efficiency and by reducing the cost (Chaudhary, 2014).

	How would you define retailing stage in circular supply chain management?	
	What measures can be taken to ensure green retailing practices?	
	Are there any other direct or indirect barriers faced or can be faced by the logistics department in your organization?	
	Are there any policies made in your organization to encourage the sustainable distribution of products?	
	Can you suggest any other drivers ensure green retailing practices?	

Barriers on consumption stage:

Sustainable consumption

Definition: Consuming is a set of social relationships, discourses, and practices (Mansvelt, 2017) that focus on the activities of selection, purchase, use, maintenance, repair and disposal (Campbell,1995).

What is sustainable consumption mean for you? What are your personal views on it?	
How is it possible to shape the consumer needs according to circular economy strategies?	
From the barriers discussed earlier, which barriers prevent the sustainable consumption of products?	
What are the other barriers you think a customer face in accepting CE practices? And How?	
How is it possible to overcome this? What can be the possible drivers on this stage?	

Barriers on upcycling stage:

Definition: Upcycling is a green practice within the realm of product management (Griskevicius et al., 2010; Lin and Chang, 2012) which encourages the environmentally conscious entrepreneur to create and modify products from used material (Sung and Cooper, 2015) which is of higher quality or value than compositional elements (Sung et al., 2014; Sung, 2017), consumers to engage with alternatives (Albinsson and Yasanthi Perera,2012) and environmentally sustainable products and facilitate economic diversification and employment opportunities (Khan and Tondon,2018).

How would you define the upcycling process?	
How is it possible to apply upcycling practices in the food industry?	
How does upcycling help create economic diversification and employment opportunities?	
From the barriers discussed earlier, which barriers are faced in the upcycling process?	
Are there any other direct or indirect barriers faced in food upcycling?	
Can you suggest any drivers overcome the barriers in the upcycling process?	

Barriers on Recycling stage:

Definition: Recycling is a critical part of the circular economy which ensures products are valued not wasted or left to pollute the environment (WRAP, 2019), by activities of reprocessing of recovered material at the end of the product life (Worrel and Reuter, 2014).	
	How would you define recycling process?
	Can you explain the reprocessing of used food products?
	How recycling is important in bringing the circular economy into practice?
	How do you think recycling can be done in the food industry?
	What are the challenges faced in implementing recycling practices during circular supply chain management and how?
	Are there any strategies or policies made by your department to make this possible?
	What are the main drivers for the application of circular economy practices during the recycling process?

Barriers on Logistics stage:

Definition: Logistics in circular supply chain management is a combination of green and reverse logistics processes, which focus to change the environmental performance of supplier to customers (Oksana Seroka-Stolka and Ociepa-Kubicka, 2018) by combining the activities of recycling, reusing, and reducing (Carter and Ellram,1998) and efficiently planning, implementing, and controlling the cost-effective flow of materials, from the point of consumption to the point of origin of the product (Rogers and Tibben-Lembke 1999, p. 2).	
	Can you define the logistics process of your company?
	What practices are important for green logistics?
	What are the challenges faced in implementing green and reverse logistics practices during circular supply chain management and how?
	Are there any strategies or policies made by your department to make this possible?
	What are the main drivers for the application of green logistics practices?

Appendix 4.3 Interview Transcriptions

Interview AB (Director Interview duration 30 minutes)

Can you briefly tell me about your company's work related to food recycling?

I don't do it personally, but we do know the person who does it. He takes the food wastage to the AD plant to make the gases and then we pick food plastic. Then it goes to you know like a big pressure cooker all the plastic is taken off from the latch and 4 percent goes to biofuel uhm about 3 or 4 percent go for making new pound money, the new 10- and 20-pounds note. It goes into making those soaps and something as well.

Do you think there are any challenges to bring circular economy in supply chain of foods?

There are loads. Umm um because the guys from the agency are not very helpful at times when they come around at your place you ask them because they do not know themselves, they do not ohm let's look into it and how can we help you. They just say, they turn nasty on you. We are here money, not to help you not turn. And then the other thing food packing there is a plastic film. I don't know what its name is you know ummmm ready meal they have got the dish and film on the top of it if you take it under the light, you will see there are 2 sheets of the films are put together. You can't recycle it. So that's another one. Umm It might change in next 20 years.

What is your view about government?

They don't care. I don't know what to tell you when it comes down to government. umm They imposed laws on big manufactures. Without facilities about recycling or information on how what the prospect actually is. We used to recycle washing machine for Hot points. We did that job for 7 years and did about 4000 washing machines. You know when you looking to your washing machine you only see steel drum We used to recycle the plastic which holds the water of the drum and metal barring as well. Now that plastic was quite valuable plastic because was poly poplin but 30 percent class films, but it did not matter so much for poly- poly poplin. Because some of them are like lot of many variations of the If you look into the dashboard of your car you see PPP (poly).

Do you remember when we were children, we used to get the famous PPP chairs, the plastic chair and then I used to send it to Sister lead who were car manufacturer there. And they couldn't get enough of it and then I don't know what tell you.

No, the government is not helpful because they are going on about recycling and hitting the recyclers. Where there should be looking at the start of the problem. There should be focussing on starting bit not the ending of it. As a person you will not hand over the keys of your car to the wrong person. You can't stop him afterwards, when they hit somebody or may stop him before it happens.

I then invented the way how to get plastic water and how to stop to plastic make so much pollution. I went in London and then I get it registered for patterns of If I need to break the wall I need help from the government, how to get up the step of ladder. M sure you will see somebody like me holds the list you will say wow and when I went to see the patent of attorney in London. I said to the lady pls help tell me it will work me. If this idea was put in the hands of right people if would do good to many.... So, yea we are still hoping it will come up. Then you will see my picture in the newspaper.

Do think there are hindrance factors from consumer side?

What I am saying is the consumer must look after when they have a chance. If these manufacturing companies have got clear function. They should not mix the plastic like coco cola bottle. The bottle and it has got a lid and the plastic wrap around it. Instead of having one plastic. They should make it simpler ways. Basically, for the food industry they should use only one plastic. So, when they are recycling there is only one plastic to recycle not different plastics. And that goes for tyres, paints you name it any industry. At the end of the day how long a piece of paper you would need you end up writing everything whatever you see is oil-based plastic. You will see oil-based plastic is everywhere. So, until the manufacturer makes it very simple or simplify it. It's always gonna be a problem. You know with micro plastic its crazier. When you think about it when it comes to water, your fleeces when you go out that is made out of recyclable bottle. But that breaks down when you put it in the washing machine. when you went down the river end. You will see micro

plastic in the Thames. So umm yea till all the big manufacturers come together and make the plastic simpler there will always be a problem.

What are your views about management?

Yes, umm, it is same as everything comes to money. Everybody wants cheaper and more profit. But at the end of the day when they simplify the things, you know give them feedback.

When you have building work at your home, then you get rubble bags of sands and gravels, when you go to one of those bags now you cannot recyclable. Because when you at it with the telescope or magnifier glass how these all are woven, and the sand and gravel go in between them in those woven patch and it's because of the machine. This is called journey to the moon. If they said they were having if cut down the plastic, each country has 3 different types of plastic to complete with There will be easier to complete with types of plastic. It will be easier for haulage and logistics and everything. Now all subs like council are at different places. They are having only small quantities; it looks like a large volume, but it is not viable in this weight. All is not burnt but goes to the landfill. Because although the logistics and freights can place at the end of the day if there are 3 plastics in the country the logistics will be different and for the travelling to the other countries. The carbon footprints will be smaller and logistically better. It will be a better place.

Is finance a barrier?

I don't think many can start up on their own anymore. I think it's big national companies that will be the leaders in recycling. Not all the companies, because of the cost of the insurance, cost of the adds. When I did my business, before the regulation came in. you got to get drainage, you will need all the facilities in place. You need look couple of million pounds now to start up. You have start up like I did gradually like.

What is the biggest barrier for you or a recycling company you think?

I would say government is the biggest plus if you add all the challenges together you get fair size cake of headaches. Each one is a problem and they got their contribute towards more problems.

Interview: 2 AF (Upcycling-Director Interview duration 1hr 29 minutes)

What is your view about circular economy?

It's great. This is obviously, what we need to be doing. Umm, for me personally, I read about this terminology after I first spoke to you or read your email, then I thought yes are the part of circular supply chain. And then I started thinking about other examples like when you are on holiday, they say you buy this and if you bring the bottle back you will get 10 cent back. And that is another example of it. So yes, I must say we are heavily involved in it, umm and its great. I completely agree, its good, it reduces carbon footprints. Because its quite .. import and export because we are importing less coffee machines from Italy. So instead of employing people in Italy we are employing people from here to refurbish the machines. But we did not set out the company considering zero carbon emission or less carbon emission or to be ethical. We started considering the environment. The company was started in 1996 and last thing of mine now is circular supply chain that our business model falls into circular supply chain. We are kind of proud of that. My farther started it in 1996 and my farther designed the business model including growth and profit. He was working as a coffee salesman, and he had experience in rental industry which is actually Linen. So actually, this is actually another supply chain. Linen for the hotels. So, my dad spent most his career working with Linen. Linen for hotels and for restaurants, I guess. So, the tablecloths and napkins, they deliver them on Monday or whatever the day is, pick up the dirty ones clean them, pressed and it goes back to them. So that is another rental and the circular supply chain. SO, my dad was involved in it. It was obviously, 80s or 90s. He was thinking this great because you get a fixed income out rental, and you don't need make another sale to get the income every month. SO, when everybody pay, you do not make the sale but you still get money. That's what attracted him, rental that used to be actually circular supply chain. So, there is not fairy tales, trying to save the planet but we are delight that. So In line with umm umm most ethical people, me, my father and my brother in the last 5 years have started being more mindful of the environment. We are doing the things like everybody does and should think how this network works. And we have started telling the people that we are the green company, and we sell our coffee machines and there are less carbon footprints. So, it was a happy ageism.

Yes, it was a great insight that time. Nobody would have thought about circular economy that time but it is a demand of era now.

Actually, he knew, he knew, the plan was, he swatches coffee machine. He had some engineering experience. As a mechanic, he saw the machine and he saw that everything on this machine can be replaced so it can be recycled. So, he did know that it was going into the circular supply chain but it was slightly different instead of greenery, it was more about sustainability of the business with profit involved in it. So that was the main reason. So, he didn't know that it was not that circular economy reason or carbon footprints. It was slightly different reason.

Do you set up any sustainability goals in you company?

No, not really. Very small thing, we have 2 ordinary bins. we called up our waste disposal company. We said, could we have a recycling one and general waste one, so we bought the recycling one, we got some discount. We started using it and then we noticed that when they are emptying them, they were emptying them in the same lorry, so we asked what's going on, they said sort it out when they go back. We said ok, we not gonna believe that obviously we don't believe that so umm now we still got the recycling bin which is a couple of pounds cheaper but everything is just, there is no point. So, you know that's the small you know an idea we had three years ago as I said we have become more you know more reacting to it. So, we also thought we should sort our waste out but that never happened.

What is the supply chain model of your company?

So, we order the coffee machines from Italy. Umm it arrives few weeks later. And umm Its brand-new machine it does not need much work it goes out to the customer. Our customers pay us fixed weekly price. So, when we are renting the actual equipment, we include our service contract because the machines are prone to breakdown quite a lot after they have bit of use because they got scale in the water so specially in London. As well as the actual equipment they actual equipment they can call us. We have engineer ready with the equipment, who go to the site and fix the machine for them. Therefore, people use, that the quick response when there is a breakdown to the equipment. So, the machines goes out, goes out on an average umm between 3-5 years after which the breakdown become more frequent because of the scale that build up in the coffee

machine. We remove the machine umm either the machine remove I mean the customer cancel the contract and decide to buy the machine lease one you know something like that or umm we just bring the another machine. So, the one we bring them is most um, when the machine comes to the workshop umm umm we have three we actually got 4 workshop engineer. Were we are in West Malden? We have 6 work benches to work on coffee machine 4 of those machine engineers work on refurbishing coffee machines, 2 of the benches got refurbished engineers for the machines we got on site. So, machine come back it goes on the shelf on the ware house and red tag will go that just to show it needs to be refurbished. That's obvious we you look at them because customers don't necessary look after them and even they do look after, in 3-5 years. Engineers take the machine, take it to the bench, takes it apart. Umm all the copper parts, most of the pipes and boilers are made up with copper. They descale it chemically, the frames so obviously there is frame in the machine that umm sometimes has closing on it. Which might not look very nice so that frame and some other parts of the machine go to our massive refinishing company that's not our company, we outsource a local company. So, the frames they re-dip ink and they come back looking absolutely fantastic like they are brand new. It not cost much money. They collect them and they redeliver them. Um they do the similar things for some other parts of the machine. There are some parts which need re-chroming because those parts are dented, and all the chrome is gone away. So, they are re-chromed. So, they call the groups the parts. The copper parts are descaled, don't need any further refurbishment other than that. There is another part that is, so there is electoral wiring system so that is removed from the frame. Now the frames we have pool of frames, that are already come from the supplier so there are already frames in the pools because when the machines is taken apart we don't want that to awaiting the frames week with the bits and pieces with the frames come back. So, the frames got to the end of the workshop, so they go and get the machines so the when crack on and rebuild in the coffee machines.

So, the coffee machine starts very carefully rebuilding, the electrical wiring would just be cleaned. It's a very old machine so some of the machine will go back to the customers and be refurbished for 4 or 5 times. So, if we got machine which is 20 years old it needs to be cleaned, worst case scenario that it needs new wiring, because sometimes plastic shooting around the cables get brussels that does not look right and for health and safety. So umm worst-case scenario they change the whole wiring or part of it because we have all the components, and we can change it. So that gets refurbished. So all the perishables parts like rubber seals or soft lid and the components that

are prone to breakdown they aren't very expensive, some of them might be prone to breakdown but they are very expensive parts so we wouldn't actually change that, things that cheaper and are prone to breakdown we will definitely replace them. They are basically very carefully the panels are big challenge ummm that sort of what the customer sees umm the end customer sees so umm the painted panels are sent for spraying, outsourced to sprayers, the professional companies. They come back resprayed; it actually improves the look of the machine because you can change the colour of the paint as per the current trends. Many people like nowadays 'Matt Black'. This is quite fashionable now, a semi-matt rather than a high gloss. It comes back resprayed in matt black; we tend to keep matt black for everything. Obviously we not gonna have our machine sprayed with lots of fancy colours because obviously we will keep it acceptable to us as many customers as possible. So, they go, and they come back in a big batch. They are going to have in pool of panels as well as ... we have pool of panels. They are checked and stays away upstairs in the ummm where the panels are. So, the engineer goes and get fresh panels. There are metal panels as well made out of semi-steel and they covered in scratches, when they come from the customer, and we surface them in the workshop ourselves. It needs a little bit of ummmm quite a lot of experience, practice, and technique. Its good making the panels almost as good as when they were new by removing all of the scratches on it. That's done by the engineer, instead of having pool, that's done by ourselves. We are not relying on anybody to do something for us. We try to keep the panels on the same machines that are re serviced. Umm then the machine goes on to test its plumbed in, hooked up to the electric system. Um the workshop engineer goes to the checklist, check everything has been done, check safety on the pressure system. So, on the coffee machine there is a pressure system, which is umm falls under umm regulation, an HSE regulation, pressure system safety regulation 2000. So that's ensured. Worst case scenario machine is bit slow because boiler with an element in it and it closed boiler, there is no vent in it. So, the machine is settled with ummm what it called, protective device, turns the element on and off. It turns the element on when the pressure in the boiler reaches a certain level, reaches a certain high- a right pressure. There is gate, then it gives the umm release the pressure and pressure, pressure up. If the pressure fails as safety, the pressure release faults. Then they will put it on the test, there is former test. Then the engineer test the machine in the workshop and sign it off because they are the one who will be servicing the machine.

So, then the machine has green label and goes on to the shelf and sent to the customer and its same, very similar, there is actually an equipment that's alongside the Espresso machine, the grinder so that grinders the coffee as separate item. One of the engineers at our workshop, specifically does the grinders. So, there is no water in the grinder, there is no scale, its slightly easier job. It takes about 1 week to the engineer to refurbish an espresso machine and it takes about few hours to refurbish the grinder. So, it gets stripped does the frame will get sprayed, then tested and collaborated, apart from it everything is same. Basically, the machine goes out to the customer then engineer install the equipment. It absolutely looks fantastic, you can tell it's not new because it's not the new model and umm a car form 2000, even it has been stored in the garage it will still not be a new car. With Espresso machine, from the time we start like mid-nineties until now, the technology hasn't really changed. But look of the machine. Um, um of it goes out to the customer and when we get enquiry from the customer, sometimes they ask if it's a new machine, we say umm obviously it's not new explains to them, what I have explained to you, obviously the shorter version. We say its refurbished on very high standard and wouldn't really tell the difference. And um I don't remember anybody saying, no they want the new machine. It doesn't happen very often. When I see the machine, any concern they have, they forgotten because the machine looks really great. Even machine looks good inside as well the frame, the wiring. Because when an engineer takes off the panel of a coffee machine, sometimes I have to take panel to instal it, they have the panel off when fix it. First thing the customer does is, have a look inside it. There are 2 reasons obviously it needs to look good, but it looks good mechanically good. As I said. We include the maintenance of to the customer service. That's our interest that it is very fairly refurbished. So, I think that's it.

What are the challenges for a up cycler?

In our case, I assume in most of the circular business, you are purchasing less from the original manufacturer, and you are remanufacturing yourself using the variety of other local suppliers. The main challenge is quality control. People in your own workshop, we find it quite easy. Like in our type of business quality of the panels that comes from the sprayers. Umm so we have problem with that. So I would say quality control from the companies outsource, we use for special refurbishing. Mainly the panels, the panels are most important because this is what which needs to look best on the machine, what comes back looking the worst and what the most damaged part.

Umm so because the metal panels we do it ourselves, it's easier for us to keep an eye on what's going on, for the quality control rather than the painted ones which we get back. So, when we receive the batch of say 30 panels, we inspect each on individual check, check the painting etc. and put green label on it. If there are 2 or there that are not good, we have to put red label on it and send straight back on to them. So, they know that can't get away declining standards. So that is one of the main ones.

And you have stock a lot of parts, order lots of parts, you have cancelled a lot of part every year, you know from your account. Umm the admin for all the parts, you are employing more people you are employing more workshop engineers, more people to manage, more people be off sick more people full to each other you know the general problems which come. It's a bigger operation site, you might need bigger premises, you might need bigger workshop, bigger warehouse, an extra desk in the office and will more investment have needed.

The way we started it, my father bought one coffee machine and rented it out then he bought another one and then another one. He was working full time to start with and then he went part time and when we had about 50 machines to rent out, then he was able quit his job. So we build it very organically. He did go out and say let's rent out 300 coffee machine, which I heard from many people that many big companies started to do, didn't work out very well.

How and what role technology play in an upcycling company to adopt circular supply chain management approach?

Umm obviously we are here totally maintaining the equipment's, we must sort the parts and our engineer must know how to fix the coffee machines so as that's the technology. There is quite health and safety we have keep on the top. Umm, umm now other types, we have fleet of vans, we have 3 machines um otherwise, we just use computer and WIFI.

The best way of doing thing is best tools, most of the tools we use, we pick up DIY stores some of a little bit more specialist than that and you will get on from the internet. Everything can be bit improved. Umm the decaling of the machines that can be improved if we are looking into. Then there are different methods of descaling coffee machines rather than using chemical. There's um electrical current to agitate the coat from scale. But started looking into it and it says you still have to use chemical as well. It's not very urgent. We use anyways using chemical but its bit messy, so

we have to have health and safety things on the place. As it is not in list of urgent things to do, it hasn't paid attention to.

The engineers and workshop engineers, continuously experimenting and that with many umm to make the machines look good. They are continually experimenting to reduce the use of new panels and parts that we don't need to be replaced. So, yea this is the aesthetical issue they are continually experimenting on it. And we give them the freedom to do that because we want that to do by ourselves. Umm sometimes we see anything and oh we want them to crack on the machines. Because we let them to do that, that's why our machines look great. We give them time to experiment with. As we have 4 main engineers not many, we don't have anyone else come and teach how to do it. So, like for example if some come and I am ordering new sanding pans to see if it is running better, I say ok. It cost only little, but when they come and say look at the difference it made all the panels look great so yes.

What are your views about management?

If you are talking about food manufacturing, the only thing you can put to recycle is packaging. Umm well I mean if you trying to shoe home a umm way of working into your business way it does really lend itself for that that you not going to have than its really difficult and its not gonna work. Umm if you a business where umm you have to make it beneficial for the business. It can't just be we going to umm. So obviously there are few different types of businesses one is of criminal, and one is that stays in the law do things everything can do in that hour. Then you got people like which trying be ethical with go to work to make money and the you got people who obviously build their business, to be sustainable business and then you get charities as well. So if you have business falling of these categorise like our one where obviously number one priority is to make profit but also like to do best to help the environment so it involve to phases. It needs to be beneficial to the business otherwise it's not gonna happen isn't it.

I would be manufacture of food then packaging, we would try, recyclable kind of 'A' material and produce obviously English recyclable. The equipment they use, obviously they produce umm package the food, they might be outsourcing the packing um I don't know yea. That equipment can be more than what we do, they can use equipment as brand new. Umm I am not what's available to them then umm. I would assume, they already trying to make their equipment running as long as possible because food manufacturing equipment costs 100s 1000a pounds, its massive

industry and obviously they can have their own team. One engineer or team of engineers to do that so that is the situation beneficial to them. It's good for the businesses to keep the machinery running as long as possible and it's good for the environment. And they using part employing local label obviously not going to go out and spending 100s 1000s pounds. They use cheaper equipment as well umm you know equipment that the equipment that cost £100 or £1000 that might be disposed little bit more readily than they could do.

So umm really I would say it is better way how can it be used into the business model, it needs to worked as fundamental business model that it is beneficial for the business and the environment. Then I mean if it works, I mean if it can be implemented, it will work. The people are incentivised the profit, the same profit. Part of the practice rather than having the established business that are cracking a lot of waste and then there is no ummm the only incentive is an ethical incentive because obviously it's gonna be slower to act on that what it makes me to feel bit of angry, when you see packaging of ready meals in the super market, instead of having a black plastic container they started they started making it like brown, it seems like it is made of paper or card so that envying, that envoys me because they try to trick people making them think that they are using recycled products by changing the colour.

So, the only umm the other thing is if ummm umm the companies are really forced to be, then obviously thing can be different. Another thing is its quite difficult to measure carbon footprints. If the companies are carbon zero, I am not sure how they measure it. Yea so that's all I can think of.

Are there barriers related to culture? Company or consumer culture?

Umm, umm I don't think there is problem improvising it in the company as long as employees are concern, as long as they are paid the same amount. and then it doesn't mean they have to more work or it made their job difficult or longer hours. There is no problem there.

umm obviously the more problem someone has as per experience umm um making bit of umm um I guess the people who are less well-off not make much of effort ethically environmentally as people who are wealthier. Because people with less well-off has more enforces to deal with like looking for the job, putting food on the table and its quite understandable but last thing on their mind is environment. But the people who are wealthier they have already achieved their goals and they have time to worry about the environment. Umm so what I am trying to say is for employees

attitude shouldn't, other things do not affect as long as , the work that they have to proceed to that normal but consumers really depend on demographic factors and I think the attitude is different depending on the demographic , you find it harder to convince people that why they have to spend little extra money for an environmentally friendly alternatives.

Obviously, you got the umm, obviously the demographic makes the difference, obviously you got the different people, you got very environmentally friendly people in same demographic and there are very unethical people in any demographic. So, the government enforcing the companies to reducing their carbon footprints. So obviously it is bit of challenging as well to find the other solutions so from the consumer end, the same thing, it necessary the unethical consumer, where it would be better if they work even like 10p back whatever the bottle or carrier bags. There is unethical people still pay cash and still the use bags. And obviously it was 5p and then 10p and then 20p, so I don't know how many other ideas are there, so can't solve any single problem at once, one at time isn't it.

How structure can be a barrier or driving force?

Structure like having targets for all departments and people within the structure of the company, or to incentivise the specific managers rather than the business as whole. One manager can't just hide behind the carbon footprint of the building as the, of the business as whole. There specific targets of their own specific department and get them umm motivated. Another example in restaurants like the tip is shared among all the waiter and waitresses rather than going to actually bigger supervisor. Umm obviously the structure needs to be slightly different. So, like with us we are doing more manufacturing, we have more employees but we have less assets at the back so there will less depreciation.

Would you like add something from government, law or legislation? What and how are they barriers?

As I said I was in school when our business model was created, and we don't have any issues from the government side. The things are it's a little bit harder for us to buy it because of Brexit. We are little bit concerned, how long our special machines will take to be delivered. Umm they, they arrive in record amount of time, we shocked because there were no customs. We ordered 8 coffee machines, big boxes, quite bit cash, quite bit value, and they arrived in a week. Usually, it used to

take longer than that. We haven't experienced any form of real problem from the law or from the government.

What is the direct and major challenge for your business?

Apart from, there is health and safety, so the additional risks, the risks arise from the remanufacturing of machine on your premises. So, the health safety requirements are enormous. So, yea health and safety requirements.

The council can start charging depending on the size of your bin. So how many bins you have should depend on the. As I said a lot people have personal issues to worry about, the personal issues they care about their kids and family and not the environment unfortunately. Because that is more personal and more important from them. If they make a change, it's not gonna make much of the difference, that's the psychology isn't it. If I sort out my litre into different categories at home. It makes me feel good about myself. But it doesn't make me think that there are not any environmental issues, and it doesn't make think that it's not necessary gonna make any difference. Because you relay if anybody else doing it. It just comes to the ethics isn't it, depend how time and resources people have personally. That's why we need something as I said OK if you have 4 people in the family you can have bigger bins otherwise if only 2 people or give everybody half a size of bin, you need a big bin, you know, you have to pay, that will probably work.

I would say the problem is the governments are not entirely ethical. So, they are worried about their selection. Unfortunately, they are more concerned that if they can remain in power rather than if there is a. I can see there gonna be risk to up-step, so instead of imposing taxes as punishment they can have reward for the opposite.

Brief introduction about company's supply chain process?

I really, our field is to develop the product, cook it, pack it, it goes into the super market, in their warehouse and to their different branches and it is consumed and after that they never come back to us. We are no y liable for whatever is sold or whatever they do with it. As long we are concerned when we develop the product. If the meal is concerned, we are not looking into designing a product, umm the aim is always to make a product which can be made easily, packed easily and distributed easily that is actually the part of meal. That is, we are looking into is packaging, what about packaging that how easily it can be recycled that is looked into.

Is reusing the processed waste from manufacturing process possible in food manufacturing?

Why or why not?

It can't be, it can't be, if we have got waste you need to understand with manufacturer or cooked chilled. There need to be cooked at certain temperature and then it got to be chilled at certain temperature and it got to be packed at certain temperature. And it has got limited life. The cooked product from the day it cooked and till it is consumed it has on an average 10–12-day life. So, if the cycle they cook to chill, cook to pack has got 48 hours life. You cook something today you got 48 hours to pack it. If it is not packed in 48 hours than it is waste. Then nothing you can do to it to recycle. Look food cannot be recycled. That's it if you do not pack it in 48 hours then it is waste. With all the goodwill in the world, with all the forecast, all the customer as well as our forecast. There is always a gap between where you end up having X amount of wastage and that food wastage cannot be recycled. The only thing can happen is, you donate to the people something like that. That is not in system.

Yes, that is point of discussion of circular economy as you mentioned I can be given to needy people or use it any way possible?

One minute, if it goes to needy people, if they are not able to consume it within certain amount of time than it is a waste again. End of the day with food, you cannot lie you cannot avoid wastage. Or whatever stage you are looking at whether it is cooking stage or manufacturing stage, distribution stage or consuming stage. You are not going to say, I am targeting to nil wastage. The product cannot be developed with the idea of nil wastage. Minimise is ok, but when you going to the development stage with the idea of no wastage. We develop the product with the idea which the consumer may eat or may not eat or through away it does not. In the food wastage it very-very difficult to position until or unless, you have product which has got a long life that sort for things. Yes, you can hold it, um the business we are in, we are called a business of short shelf life. The product goes to be consumed in X number of days. It has got to packed in certain amount of time and distributed to the certain amount of time, if that does not happen, you cannot avoid that. You cannot come to zero, People can minimize it, supermarkets try to minimise it, they sell it on cheaper rates on the last day. That what it is I think, they are already there but the product cannot be conceived with zero wastage. The wastage is all circumstantial, depending on the consumer.

Which the biggest challenge for food manufactures?

Like I said, the barriers are very simple, the biggest barrier is short shelf life that is barrier that you cannot and that cannot be recycled back into the system. We cannot re-boil it, we cannot re-cook it. We cannot do anything. That is the barrier, the barrier is short life and the product raw material. Actual meal cannot be brought into the supply chain. Because of the life factor, because of the life it has got.

Can innovations or technologies help?

As I said at the supermarket level when there is only one day left. They reduce the price and try to sell it off. The consumer, if they took them but not able to consume, they can freeze and extend the life. But end of the day, what I am trying to say is, as of today there is no technology or anything, even if you extend the life from 10-20 day. And after 20 days, what? Even if it is frozen, you can freeze and hold it for one year but what happens after that. There is no technology involved in it. Yes, with apps and all you can do it but at the end it is not going to the stage that you will have nil wastage. The idea of circular economy to have nil wastage in food, will not work. It will never work. You can try to reduce it, you can try to minimize it but it will not come to a stage you can say that this product will not have waste. Whether you create apps, whether you do at super market level or we as a manufacturer give it to somebody, charities and all that yes you can minimize it from going it to the landfill rather than people consuming it but it will never be able to, what I am trying to say is, you cannot concept or design a product and no technology under which you can design the product that we will make This product and It will stay until is consumed. There is nothing like that. In food it will not happen. Whatever science is there, whatever techniques are there. As an ingredient you can you whether it is frozen peas or dehydrated peas, but all their techniques are there they have their own limitations. You can keep frozen peas for certain amount of time, you cannot keep it forever so whatever science is there. As of today, there is no science. Which will say you take a product and do whatever you want to do. At the end of the day, it will be there till you finish it, there is nothing like that. I wish I could do it and I could save a lot of money become millionaire. Kerry has a very big institution nobody is working on that and because practically it is not possible.

What are the challenges for management?

Management has got role, we have got the role, all the stakeholders has got role. We have got a role; our customers have got a role. They are two main stakeholders. They have got a role. You see nobody wants to through it who wants to through it because money is on desk. So, everybody looks into different ways to look into reducing the waste. Like I said, million-dollar question is, it is not practically possible. You will have X amount of wastage. Customer has X amount of waste and they trying to reduce it. They are two main stake holders. We are the main stakeholders. During the manufacturing, we try to minimize our wastage, so does our customer, they try to minimize the wastage. They have food controls in their depots, food controls in their stores, reduce the prices or give it to charities, all things are done. Yes, we are the main stakeholders, but it is of everybody's interest to reduce the wastage.

Any cultural related views?

Like I said people need to be socially aware. Like we donate it to people, we donate it to charities, retailers donate it to charities. That is the social impact. Consumers have to take their responsibility; people waste more food in the house than we as a retailer or manufacturer waste. They over buy, that is the social responsibility, you should only buy what you can consume.

Any hindrance factors from government side?

Government makes legislation and we have to live with it. But none the legislations are basically to reduce the wastage, but it is targeted to recycling, avoiding landfill all that kind of things but I haven't come across by any initiatives where they tell how you can reduce the wastage. There is nothing specific as of today. They can indirectly start charging for more landfill all that sort of things whereby giving the money to save money to reduce the wastage. But there are indirect excisions are there. They push you landfill charges... charges so that you don't increase the waste. But there is no what you call direct, what you call, umm regulations which tells you that you have to have so much of wastage

Can structure affect be a challenge? Why or why not?

As I said we have very highly skilled planning team, who take customer orders, see what the trends are, everything is working, try and plan production very close to that. Our customers (retailers)

have their planning team, who have very close tie with the stores, see their requirements, monitor the wastage, how they can reduce the wastage. There is proper structure what you call indirectly reducing the wastage is the planning. So, we have got very big department planning department. So does our customers have big planning department. Our planners are in touch with all the departments. Retailers' planners are in touch with all the stores as to what is selling, what is not selling, where to get that amount of wastage, then they adjust orders according to that so everybody. So, in food manufacturing, food shelf life is the main thing.

Interview: AM (Consumer- Interview duration 40 minutes)

What do you think these kinds of approaches are achievable?

Of course, it is achievable, nothing is unachievable. but again, to think to write and to implement there's a big difference so if as I mentioned before sometimes that if there is rules regulations in place for other things why can't they put rules and regulations for waste management. and I'm not talking about rules and regulations but with the implications. with the reflection, with the penalty. because in the world or in corporate world I'm not sure there are any rules introduced which will regulate the management decisions or lead them to achieve their goals from waste management. but in other industries or other let's say for example driving, if there are rules but if you break that rule then you will get the fine. yes, and that's why probably we have proper regulated traffic and all other things related to the traffic's. so, I think that kind of model will work in waste management as well. but I'm not sure if any company have introduced that kind of model or not. if the answer is yes he said it is achievable but how? That's is a big question and that is probably every individual organisation have to look into deeply and work on it then only its possible .

What type of value thinks come on the way where are the loopholes as you just mentioned that it is not a part of regulation or legislation of the government you say So what as a consumer you what you think what are the other barriers?

I think I will simplify it by just looking into my own house how do we do the waste management because if it is food related and the picture will be on a bigger scale and I'm sure there will be a lot of things to consider if you cannot compare with the household with the commercial so but yes one thing is there they have to have absolute data of everything there which is possible I think what does it mean, how much is required, what is the demand and what is the supply. and if you term and conditions of the supplier and the seller. that can be monitored closely or that can be or call if they go in harmony how much you need? how much do you have to produce? if this if I mean these things can be achieved by a data collection . if you have proper data then you can I guess achieve this goal. do you think that technology or techniques and needs to be developed? and in it should be along with the rules and regulations very tight rules and regulations exactly coming from the government to corporates like I'm sure there is a rules regulation for toxic waste

management. waste management as in what you can dump into the drain or what you can't. so, the same way the government can introduce waste management food waste management and a tight control over it but I'm sure each and every food industry who's producing the food yeah will follow it.

what do you think about the other consumer people's perception people's attitude what people's attitude is about if there are some policies come from the comment as you were saying their reaction people's perception about it would it be easy to impose anything on them or would it be easy for consumers to accept those things what you think?

for consumers I think yes because if you know how much you eat how much you need like the way you do the rationing for other things in your household then I'm sure for the food also you can do that and even the bigger companies can also keep the same model somewhere nearby. I'm not saying the exact model will be applicable. but they can do the similar things to award the wastage and then obviously it will fall the trial back towards the grower of the actual like farming and who will consider that how much do they need in the market and accordingly he will produce instead of quantity they will focus on quality yeah and probably then everyone will have a good product and healthy product.

Do you think knowledge or knowledge or expertise a play a part in it?

the waste to reduce the way to introduce that as you were saying tools and techniques about data collection and reliable data collection So what is the knowledge and especially like as a consumer we are discussing on the consumer consumption stage consumers, So what is the level of knowledge about circular economy at the moment around the people you know have you ever what is what this thing is how it is it can be achieved any consciousness from the consumer about it?

As a consumer I have seen programmes on BBC where they talk about this waste management and it simply but you can do it simply just have to have that consciousness I will say .what you buying, how much you buying, how much it how much is going what is shelf life , and can you cost really . if every individual can think it properly how much you going to eat what do you want to eat. What they can store. What they can't. on that basis they can decide and if it starts from the household. similar model can probably be implicated on the industry.

Looking finances aspect, do you think finance is a barrier?

I don't think finance is the barrier. Unless if there are targets about the profitability driven businesses there, I don't think it's like. for a simple example of you it's always it's human nature, but the on specially in the food let's say you go for the party host don't want their guests to be waiting for the food. for the catering point of view if the three are hundred guests, caterer knows how much they need, but as a host you should be responsible for order, I mean I've seen always that there would be extra food all the time. take 100 examples out of 100 examples 90 parties or the events will, will have a excess food yeah so I think this is a big deal. really, there are lots of resources, forget about the fiancé part. for the production the again supply chain for that particular product, benefits straight away green after the wastage if it is going straight to the landfill or to the drain, its waste of money that's based on everything. so if a person can think properly about how much they need? when we need? the management I will say, the food management. I think each household needs to learn that and probably I will say it should be the part of educational curriculum. where kids yeah while they are growing, they should know what the food is where it comes from what it takes to grow food and how much does it cost to go to supermarket and what you can do to avoid that kind of wastage.

Yes, that is the important thing that what you can do which has not been I think introduced at the moment in the common man?

the way you introduced finances to the kids, the way you introduce antiques I think it should be part of their growing life. where they learn that how I can reduce the food wastage because food is something which you cannot order technology cannot produce. Or the robots cannot produce yeah and looking at the future you can't see the robots on the road as your friend as your partner as your mum and dad. Human need food all the time. so, this is the basic. probably I mean this research started now, the awareness is started, now so probably it's in the capacity of every human being or every government to keep this awareness how you can keep the awareness by introducing this book, or a chapter or a subject, while kids are growing.

I would say communication I think is not being communicated in the in a way that it should be. the importance is not given that extend well government is interfering and asking educational authorities to change their subjects or what needs to be taught to the kids and I think they should

teach kids how to cook as well. I yeah properly to keep the lifestyle healthy yeah that's it thanks you

Another thing I would like to add, I was watching a video today because of Brexit There's a lot of food wastage .so I was interested to watch this video on YouTube. I said because of Brexit why there is food wastage. so, what's happening due to the Brexit there is a lot of documentation needs to be completed before any food passing from UK to European countries. and there is some there are some food times or categories which has a shelf life and because of the documentation even if you have one documentation left. the whole lot of that food is going to waste. but I'm sure if government can notice that or put into the agenda, to avoid that wastage. I think government is not serious about food wastage they should step up and they should introduce some kind of rule regulations the way they introduce it for the environment .as a ULEZ zone yeah, they're charging the fines, not fine I would say charge. charger is working people are avoiding going to central London they prefer to going for the public transport. so, I don't think any reason why govt is not stepping it up. introducing a rule, where food wastage is considered as a I mean it will lead to a penalty. that should introduce some kind of rules and regulations I think 100% confident that if they introduce this rule you will see the great decline in the food waste percentage. in each industry even in household.

What do you think is the biggest where is the biggest k loophole from consumer side?

I think where the world is going everything is run by the rules and regulations the answer is only one thing is the human behaviour. it should come within yourself, every individual living should be aware, conscious about food wastage and if they're not, then the government as a great power they can introduce rules and they can control this wastage.

AZ (Despatch Manager- Interview duration 1hr 25 minutes)

What is circular supply chain management for you?

I mean the traditional approach of the supply chain is the linear approach is quite straight forward. is it not? You got basically raw material to production signed to disposal. That is the traditional way of doing it. but as time goes on as time goes on and as environmental impact. and I think most of western world even eastern I mean whole world is waking up. we cannot sustain this , basically , my understanding to this is , I might be looking into this is quite intriguing the corporations and need act soon otherwise they will face major consequences worldwide .we have to look at the carbon footprint to avoid ozone depletion and I mean lose money in terms of waste, it's only going to work is if the whole world will hold hand together is all about the corporations hold overhand together and work as a team. otherwise here at the moment you've got some people already doing this in the world under circular supply chain. for example some classic examples are timberland , Johnson Controls the recycling batteries and famous one is Nokia other people's recycling mobile parts . this is such a wonderful thing. It's a simple thing but it requires a lot of thought and good management. it's my thinking am I right? I watch TV in my I tend to watch these kind programme what's happening to the world and I'm really keen on these things I watch the Discovery Channel sometimes yeah, I watch all these channels and I'm really intrigued by what's happening in the world people think I'm boring my kids thinks I am boring. Then I am saying this is for your future. the biggest thing sustainability requires for me three or four important things the first one is the social responsibility as a person or as a company. that is so important. and then there is environmental responsibility like we recycle food and packaging in our house every week that we should do at wider world. For me it is financial responsibility. These things go hand in hand. If you do all these 3 things together you can sustain, be responsible financially and environmentally.

I word circular itself gives you a clue, Circular, it's a circular. exactly where did you go you start for me in the end user is the consumer, but it starts from and thus the corporation, a supplier so you do design and manufacturing then you come to the retailer, the retailer then retailers pass on to the consumer. consumers consume the product in any way. weather its food or using a service and what do you with the product afterward. It should be reused, repaired, and go back to recycling section and go back into the design mode that's my understanding what the circular motion in

circular supply chain is. things like product life cycle come into it you know the impact on the environment depending on life cycles of the product it's a hesitating thing and then Xbox exactly. if I can help you in any way, please ring me and ask me.

What is your role in the company?

My role in my organisation, my Title is dispatch manager. I am part of the noon product for 17 years, I work for noon products which is part of the meals solution section of Kerry foods, which is food industry company. my job is to understand the customer orders coming into factory everyday how we can service the customer order at the least distribution cost and qualities so that's my job basically now obviously we have a team of people start from your loving husband, Planning. Jatinder will set the ball rolling in terms of the plan for production and executed by production then send the quality product into dispatch and my team's job is to hold the stock can rotate the stock review for quality and product life. and make sure the customer gets the right quantity as the right count. then it goes to their depots Sainsbury's, we service Sainsbury's and Morrison's as retailers. supply chain is when we send it from here it doesn't end there. There is another despatch team waiting in the Sainsbury's depot our vehicles to come over. they unload the product and then handle it in the supply chain to send it to the stores .so it's when it gets to the store you and I shopping every Saturday or Sunday in Sainsbury's. we are quite particular we gonna buy. Are not we? we wanted we want the best quality at the least cost. that way I look at it. my wife is even worst, she wants the best quality at least cost. I am sure you are agreeing with that and there so that's my job basically too I think and make sure order are going on time.

Sustainability in your Company?

Bearing in mind when we're dealing with a food product, so the life span of a food product is an average seven days. From we make it, and it goes to the stores its 07- or 08-days life on it. We make sure as food company we avoid food waste. if you avoid food waste, you are filling your obligation you made the product of right quantity and it's gone out. if we over produce and orders are not coming or whatever the reason is of stock holding, what do we do for the extra food I mean the way there's lots of options So what we do as a company is the classic option is not to waste the food because there are always people this community needs food as well. So, there is option to donation to charity local charities. so, it can be used. Trailing that then food waste as leave our

side and we send it to the biodegradable site so they can break the food down and make compost out away or whatever they can from that food waste. So, we are doing our bit for environment there. Also, the packaging we reuse and shrink-wrapping reuse and in the process. that can be collected and separated so that can be recycled shrink wrap we have extra or rather than jumping and general waste being sent to a shrink wrapping recycle for recycling and also the packaging so we wouldn't be looking into that and also, I would think of engineering section will look at things like environment make sure steam the boilers are efficient, polluting environment. As company will be working on things like that for me as a manager the food waste should be put to good use to avoid waste if it does go to waste it has to be broken down and reused.

What are the challenges for food manufacturing industry to bring circular supply chain management?

loophole is you have to know your capacity as a company. the manufacturing process we know how many meals we can make a week. making about 1.2 million meals a week. and we are running flat out. so, this also social responsibility of the company to look at the base model we cannot handle more than 1.1 meal. is it it's like feeling to get more orders? but sometimes more orders lead to issues. as you just point out me is the weather the weather goes hot. And store is not taking it. so my job for following week all the WIP Stock you have you cooked everything it's going to be dumped. I think the company also need to have a responsibility to understand what their working module is. when we can't accept more than 1.3 million from my lovely customers or will would love to, but we can't. because I it will cause issues in the company and other site impact slower things you know so there's also the geography of relocation where setting on a dual carriage way in West London Southall so, Jatinder knows it very well so vehicles which come in on the supply chain and this was bring the materials into us the riser packaging containers and once it cooked and despatch team will dispatch the order so you have an issue on our location we have the vehicles enter the same way and the exit as same way because we are on the dual carriageway. you that has an impact that needs to be looked at as a company should we thinking outside the box and making an exit and entrance and not the same way or find a way to fix it. or move our factory or despatch department with another Greenfield site which is more better to manage. it also affects things like way so waste, waste is collected every other day from our site.as I said if is congestion traffic congestion outside the waste of medical might not have enough time to collect their ways

and go away. while the driver doesn't come back the next day that went that way just sitting in the yard open too rodents and birds everybody you know having party with the waste sitting in the yard. you know things like that, so they are important to understand. how do you get that message across? you and I discussing this but exactly I think we have 700 people working on this site at WML. Every a person has a different grasp of knowledge of what's happening in the world, you have to break this down into three or four simple steps so that people understand. what are we talk when I say to somebody when I go away now so I'll say just talked to Mandeep and she is doing her PhD in circular supply chains . they will say huh?????.... with paper.so how do you sell that. you know it is hard bit. You can sell it by giving examples of their normal Lifecycle the parallel working in a bigger environment . people can buy into that step forward. that would be important for people to understand. We are only as good as the peoples working there and you can have the best machines in the world but the people have to be trained and understand, the elements of production, dispatch, technical, whatever field you are working in, because it affects everybody. The three also ethical bit. we have to find the right suppliers to get the raw materials in. and this the social responsibility Mandeep where does rice come from. does that come from the third world? or is it any people is there any peoples any workforce abuse. Are we paying people the right amount of money? because they've got families to sustain, if you will think about it is circular things. certain everybody yeah the people who pick the rice if they are not happy in the workplace and you don't pay them the right amount of money yeah you failed on the first step. first step.

How finance related factors affect the food manufactures to apply circular economy approach?

it's very good Question, it's very open-ended question. first of all, every corporation has a mission statement. What are your values. obviously biggest value for me is dignity of the people who work at your workplace. That is what the important part. And hand in hand goes in environmental sustainability. that's important. people have to be shown what they mean. here process is in our training you know whatever we do. but it has to go to the board level. you know so bored with the directors of this company sitting away an island somewhere. Probably they do few meetings a year. what they look at why look at the balance sheet. And how much profit we made last year. How much we going to project to make. Is it all about profit or is it the profit? Or is it about profit made in the right way. In terms or reducing waste, environment, so some time to make that work

you have to invest. yes, then you have a payback period. you have to invest for couple of years for best machinery to relook. Then you're having a capital outlay but are you back in in two years' time in less pollution to the environment. I'll give you a simple example, like in this track, we used wooden pallets. so, we put our meals in crates and sit on wooden pallets. the biggest company in the world forward on palace's a company called cheque. all over the world .and it is a massive corporation and this company Kerry foods I'm a bit disappointed with this there's two ways of bringing those pallets into our factory is what we have chip pallet and a trading pallet, it says chip pallet is a brand new pallet made in the factory. .01% like the chip. Wooden chip fall on that pallet. but this company at the moment is working on chip on the traded pallet. Traded pallet means pallets from my company once we've discarded them going to another company then to another companies it goes in a supply chain. While we are using those pallets they get degraded and wooden chip come out and it becomes substandard. substandard finally come back to us in the supply chain. You got wood falling it .and wood is foreign body. it is a chance, although I wok in the sealed meals but any wood could go in the sealed meal , We don't know . secondly picking up the wooden chips every day and putting out as a waste so that's a cost. yeah well I'm thinking for the sake of £3 or £4.00 per pallet they should they should be looking at the chip pallet instead of traded pallets. That is typical example for me. Also, things like equipment for you is like forklifts and contractor centre manual handling pump trucks. it's at the moment when using gas truck so that has his own issues. it is costly and pollutes the environment. so, we should be looking at 100% electric pump. it will not pollute the atmosphere and environment. easier to handle, you not change the gas bottle after 7-8 hours. Just charging it. like the latest technologies of batteries like Toyota cars and you know the best cars in the world, you have hybrid cars. Why can't we apply that philosophy & technology?

As you mentioned about technology, are there any technical barriers effect the implementation of circularity in food supply chain and how?

depends on the company. the company has to drive this. and who does it begin with it begins with the board of directors and the chairman, the president, general manager, senior management team then we will cascade to our teams. people have to understand this there show me road map and we work on that road map hand in hand along with workforce. we show then where we are now. Where we want to be. this is our road map. This is how we gonna

get there. everybody needs to understand people have different knowledge of grasping things. but I'm surely people will understand what's going on this world. People will not say no. let's give them dignity and respect and if you work with the people, they will come up with ideas so with the best company in the world. Yep, they don't employ the best they do employ the best engineers and scientist. but Mandeep you will be surprised some of the biggest just inventions and way to improve come from the average work employees. well, I think you understand where I'm coming from. yes. somebody is working on the production line for 20 years and we're trying to bring in multipound machine and advanced technology to get that meal across the line. somebody sitting there for 20 years comes up with a better idea. you should not person down we should explore that. and that will drop off another people and you will be surprise how people, because some people at that time they are comfortable there working on the process they go home nobody knows that process better than that person was doing it . its topic into the knowledge. Future, technology, to make it better. so, if economics is using machine with people. Design things for the betterment of workplace. Better workplace leads to better moral. Better moral leads to better and better moral leads to productivity and efficiency. should drive your waist down.

What is your view about cultural related aspects?

Company cultures important. Culture means kind of people are dealing with the traditions they have and things we need to improve forward, Culture I mean let me give you an example so this is so we work in Kerry foods, so I would say maybe 70% of our workforce is of an Asian origin in Indian background and Pakistan Bangladesh and whatever and 30% it is probably non-Indian and Irish and all that. it is Irish company. so, I will plant in Ireland is probably 99.9% Irish employees .so that's a different culture to West London. It is a same company which you have to re tune that culture to suit where your plans are. You have to take it on board. all cultures have different you know backgrounds and values, so you have to buy into that and use that to optimise your process and betterment and production yes so, the company has to do that. company has to utilise all resources of different backgrounds, set the right values and culture how we're going to go through there should be no difference to working in Ireland or Southall. That can only be set with who is leading the company. They are giving right culture to work in atmosphere. when you come to work every day and the most important thing for the person doesn't matter what your background is that you come to work with a happy face and going back to your family with a

happy face, and most importantly its health and safety you want the person to go back safely to their families. so that's the culture itself. so, you going to make sure that the people who work here, everything is done to risk assess, the work from you so make sure they are safe, safe environment will give you a better culture better working people. Who feels valued? If the people do not feel valued. They gonna go home next day they will be absent which is even worse. so that's going to cost money. absenteeism. so, it's all to do with the company has to set the standard. And the right culture, it is very important. we start from the top. It starts from the top and finishes at the bottom and there should be no difference whether you are a managing director or a cleaner. I like the Japanese style of culture and you know how they work they all wear the same uniform. they don't have on the shirts that I am the GM, I'm the yard cleaner. They have written the word Toyota. They have written Toyota the front and back. it is a massive symbol that same uniform that focus and you will feel proud to be part of that team.

it is also about interacting. So, I am sitting in Southall. Me and Jatinder. What's happening in Ireland or Scotland where the other plants are. We don't know. It should be more of people meeting. Paying visits to each other sites. And working for few days with the workforce, understanding, this is how you going to do that. that is the good way of doing it. People say that's good way of doing this, we should go back to Ireland.

Even now you don't even need to visit the company's technology are you not talking we can be talking on a video conference people can buy in to all these things and you there is a saying, "where there's a will there's a way" What you want as company and that will benefit you in the long runs so yes still I was yeah I was saying that again coming back to the circular economy it's abit of complex process and not like the linear one as very straight forward once so I think to handle handled us that thing to handle that strategy and to handle and manage that model the interaction as you were just saying it is very important you know what yeah so it should it will be happening all over the all over the companies but it will be a complex process there will be you know many other steps included in the in that normal process so I think interaction is one of the most important thing when there is a miscommunication I think that again will lead to the failure of that approach. Next aspect I would like to discuss is I think again it is as management it is again one of the most important part its regulatory and institutional or government related barriers So what do you think what are the where the government is lacking behind are the what we call current laws and

regulations are adequate to bring the circular economy approach in the in the world are not well in the country or in the industries

That's the hard question, you know you've got local government and national government as a country. So, I should from the local governments stage umm so we work in the West London and our council is Ealing council. So, it should be working, Ealing council should be working hand and hand and with all factories in the borough. So that is the part of circular standards, and they should be checking our standards and I know we have environmental officers come time to time and audit us. I think that's a good idea they have to do that. What they do they come to check waste control and add noise levels in the in the community. We are in built up area we've got flats and accommodation around one side of a factory. So, it's our responsibility also to make sure we're not too noisy as a factory which can disturb people who are living around us. So, this one thing anything council can come and audit us. If we had people well, I used to work at a company called lines Tettely company in Greenford, it used to be a coffee factory and used work there 15-20 years ago OK. So coffee manufacturing is very advanced technology and the smell is quite heavy, the coffee smell. So the environmental impact, the company was failing, this is about 20 year ago, we were fined about £90,000. Because the company was based in a residential area the smell of coffee went as far as two or three miles and people complain so much I remember Ealing council was involved, we were heavy fined and yet if you analyse that it was our ablution, it was not adequate because the pollution was coming out of the process was not being filtered to be wasted in the white way rather than that is that the coffee particles are going out of the chimney. So, we had £90,000 fine and the actual pollution tank costs over \$20,000 a classic example bound over two years would have paid back and I have no risk at all. And the government used to take lead as well emphasising fact about recycling. I know we do everything in our house we put our folding one bin and general waste in one bin.

They've got a really hit that hard with companies at massive because we only produced a little bit of waste in our house, in factories we go a lot of waste. They need to regulate it, not only regulate but become an audit company and if you don't listen to the guidelines, then you have double financial impact, So the government has big role to play.

The next thing I would look I would like to discuss about as a consumer what are your views about consumer culture

I think it's going better. I think, I think they're the consumers had a linear approach to it, go to the shop find the best deal at the least cost, bring it home, eat it and through it in the bin. I think I think people are changed now and they read the small print on the packaging. So, A, they are becoming more health conscious and people should be. For example, I work in the food industry so they need to understand what the medical ailments are, would me eating this food would affect my ailments. Umm I think some people will not care about the price of food, they see something that do. Not harm them. And also, its all about the packing as well. So, a lot of people, they don't have big houses, live in one bedroom flat. They can't dispose off the packaging. It's not easy. The another thing that really hurts me Amazon a company is a massive organization, isn't it. You order something from Amazon, like I don't know, you order a compact disc. It will come in the packaging in 5 times size of the compact disc. So at the model of this, The driver is handling the box. When I open it, it's very small, tiny cd in it. What I am gonna do with the box, either break it down, put it in the recycle bin. So, if you put the cd only in shrink wrap, all the waste is only shrunken wrap. I think, the consumer is getting really clever now. They want value for money, but they are also looking outside the box, the packaging, how to dispose of the packaging. If people have young shoo.. in the house, is it ok to dispose of it correctly.

Many years ago, when I was growing up in the country, Medicine was very easy to open. You can just unscrew the top. And children used to abuse the medicine, open and put it somewhere. Now it is one of the difficult things to unscrew it. So, it is for the safety reasons. I think the containers, which contain the medicine umm they can be broken down when it goes to waste and can be recycle that. So, ok the consumer will always have value for money in his mind. That is human nature, whether you or I, everyone thinks the same way. When we go for shopping, I buy a shirt. One shirt is £40, and another is £20. I probably will go for £20 shirt, and I buy it bring it home, my wife will wash it, after 7 washes, it probably lost colours. So, if go for £40, so probably better cotton material longer lasting, me. Wife does have to put energy to iron and wash more often for me. So, things like that the consumers are getting very fussy, how they can get the best deal. Why we shouldn't we, we work hard, you know they work hard in companies, sometimes don't pay them right standard of money. People have to look from every angle.

You should not keep people in dark, I go back to my factory now. Some people who work inside the factory, especially ladies on the packing line make rice and curry and go home. But if you look in the yards I showed them umm 5 tons of rice and curry , you made is gonna go in the bin, they

will be horrified look at the energy and hard work gone to make the food and at the end it is dumped, which is waste of material as cost, storage is cost, someone will come and pick it up a cost and then recycle the waste and putting it somewhere is again cost. So, if accept right first-time approach you will have less waste, less carbon emission. Waste is a lot of factors; waste is not just physical loss it's the financial waste as well. Waste has a figure to it and financial cost also environmental cost. This is very important.

What are the main barriers put effect on logistics stage?

I am the head of dispatch so we really, like people working with me, I never say people work under me I always say my colleagues, it's very important. people work with me; we are working together so people on the same level. So, my concern as dispatch manager is, do people know where dispatch sits in the company, two people sitting Ivory towers upstairs or board room, nowhere dispatch is. What are the constrains in dispatch, the capacity constraints, the space constrain, health and safety constrain. Maybe I as a dispatch manager should be drumming the drum more to get people involved more in it and when I did that and because the volumes are increasing day by day and then my people work with say it's not safe to work here. So, it's important myself or I encourage anybody, discuss, what the obstacles are, there could be anybody a cleaner in the chiller or supervisor, you have a right, go upstairs, tell management that I have concern here, can you come down stairs. And that manager should never say to that person book time with me, but its important its health and safety come downstairs. That person come downstairs and you it to that person what you are talking about, that manager will understand umm what cause this, what's cause dispatch to be lacking space. What can I do to make their life easy, then that person has to play his part? Whether its production or planning or raw materials. So, in my dispatch chiller I have got 8 pallets of ingredients which belong to kitchen. Kitchen don't have the space and that send it to dispatch but dispatch is finished goods environment not kitchen. So, answer to that question is, I asked that guys to remove the 8 pallets of tomato puree that belongs to buying department. Why dispatch should be holding that. And I was got smacked by the answer. It wasn't the answer I was looking for; the answer was the more we buy we get better deal. Then I said, getting a good deal is good for the business but how much. you using every day, how much the 8 pallets last. Are they going to last 6 months? There you are here is the issue you're looking at the value. You are not thinking about the people working in dispatch, the amount of space it has

occupied. Those kind of things people have to look at that and work together as team. So, for me as a dispatch manager, I am getting involved more telling people fact of the business of dispatch. I really think people don't know sometimes; people don't know the values until you raise an alarm. And one of our Kerry values is to be courageous. You have to have courage to say to somebody, I am sorry guys, the general manager or whoever you are, I am gonna close the production door, I can't manage, and we need to find the ways. Because there is a solution, if we all sit as team and say right, we need to reduce the production plan what can we do to balance out the stock on our 4 sites, I am sure will be able to do it, it's all about working together. So that's the kind of culture we should be working towards. Because everybody is under pressure, raw material is under pressure, technical, planning, production but we are all linked that's how circular chain be working together and more we interact and integrate in that chain, it makes everyone's life easier. So basically, I just need to tell, what risk going on and be positive as well and what can we do together, lots of thing you can do you need to have positive mind.

BK -Manufacturing (Operations Manager – Interview duration 48 minutes)

What is circular economy for you?

It is completely different responsibility, would be driven down how to teach management for circular supply chain. It will be completely separate. It will be driven by the environmental. So, it is marinated by the corporate strategy.

How do you work with this business model related to suitability?

You need to be aware that the I am pretty down in the food chain in my company. It's a different manufacturing sector, I am dealing with not with the chilled manufacturing so the waste environmental which comes from basically from the material, out of spec products or could be over production or under production, utilisation of electricity, could be miscellaneous resources, even when the lines are down or..... It also accounts to environmental wastage unfortunately. Again, a machine, we can't switch them off. The recycling, though it is recycling you still utilize additional energy and there will still be a waste. Apart from that, the things you put in landfill which you cannot be refilled. Those are tangible you can't save it. Fortunately, we have our own electricity turbines and things are refined there and the electricity is produced actually put a wide saving to the grid back to the community, actually sell them off. That part is bit Tricky, it's not that open but yeah, we do a lot of saving energy on that side of environment. Reduction of water pressure, reduction of water usage onsite installation of smart taps, smart nozzles you know, which should have Effect instead of turning off. Looking into it. Obviously, every part is doing that. And we have challenges on that because it is very old site 140 years old there were vast, massive footprints I reach. Yeah, we have challenges around it. Something is out of date and some things which cannot be replaced. If someone invent something.

Is Circular economy achievable?

It is the very spear target yea it should be a spear target; I wouldn't say it is achievable in the current environment but may be in the future if the right technology, right invention, a new process, the future looks good but the zero waste an aspiration to it. Specially in food manufacturing we always have processed waste until we start inventing something that production of bi-products and start utilising, but you always have processed lots.

Do you think lack of techniques is a barrier?

Technology is derived by the policy; it is not the technology completely by itself. So, it's not just the technology it is the feasibility and the terms on it and is it feasible. I mean you have but nobody hears that to mitigate supply chain issue. There is Jail , there is WMP, there are plenty of sources to deal with the supply chain issues. But ... cannot be determined better. Unfortunately, people drive the transportation vehicle, and you know there are delays and mis haps that are not avoidable. Simply is, there is streamline definitely, I will be very blunt online, you be looking yourself redundant. So, it is not as simple as that so it not going to happen in that way. I think technology alone is not the answer, its company's policy, it is corporate goals also combined with the country we are staying in, so country's policy. It's a wide spectrum what have asked.

What are your views about finance aspect to bring circular economy in force?

Financially it is very painful, but you do your corporate social responsibility, you have to show. But yea government can facilitate by giving a certain percentage of rebate on the revenue tax and then it can be mitigated. But then the investment needs to be there. Confirmation part has always been failure in every country or the push from the government or any other infrastructure. It has been very harsh on anyone, and it is Ambridge from any country has an issue. Obviously, we can't get rid of packaging, it is everywhere, that is the harsh fact of life.

Technology is there but there wouldn't be any buyer similarly then you. Similarly, you know that there is technology there, the technique needs to be invested more in hydrogen cell technology, it is there. But you want investment to form the petroleum sector so it's quite adiated one.

As you talk talked about buyers, in what other ways finance affect the food manufacturers to accept circular approach?

I will be straight forward; every business is there to make the money. If you are making substantial money, then you can afford to do this. But if you hand to mouth this is the last thing on anybody's mind. So, it depends, how well the company does. What is the strategy. If you are talking about the small-scale company which makes the massive damages are not that financially capable. Hence the government guards.

When you invest in the marketing, you not gone do all online, you gone do pamphlets, seminars, it creates wate again. So, it's not going to get away.

Sorry I am bit harsh on this one, but I am thinking in the way I have been trained. You think it but you not going to achieve it. Because it is not practically feasible. Any company would not plan for failure. Every company has some set of objectives, smart objective. So as objective is not smart there is no point having something it not, they are going to fail, and zero aspiration is one of these so why not they will do which is achievable and work on it.

For example, coca cola, they used to do 3 litre of coke cola and they have brought it down to 1.5 litre. What they have done about the energy consumption.

What are your views about company management?

Of course, without this nothing going turned around people are not going avoid, they will start holding people accountable. We must mentor them, there should be clear guidance and action plan, the consequences, and the negative impacts of it. For example, the company I used to work before, I reduced Waste in a year. All I did was to put the money we are losing and Dump shire and showing them that this is the amount we are throwing a week. They asked not to escalate people's thought process. The trick is, how to break it down to the grass root level, perfectos. If you can't break it down simply because it has not been broken down for you simply, you are heading for failure. If you are not clear about your targets, you don't have clarity, you are fighting for something you have no idea about.

So that is another reason for failure and lack of knowledge. And lack of knowledge how to implement it.

How consumers' perception and attitude and buying behaviour affect to bring the circular economy model?

If the consumer expects his product should be of beautiful packing, thick packaging, or small packaging whatever it is. You cannot get away from that. So, I think we should be a model for the things you present now. I mean just think about vegetables like cucumber or carrot, you will not buy it. Subconsciously you think it is bad. But it nothing to do with it. So, people are focussed on how it looks. Unfortunately, that is how it has been marketed. Or green capsicum having yellowish thing it is not bad, it is its natural process, but it is counted as waste. So, if you use this concept to any other vegetable or eatable or consumable thing you will probably get the link of it. That is the basic funda of it.

Awareness is still lacking. But if you think about country like India, people are aware about it and that is great pleasure to do but that I was depicted. It is a myth that western countries have more buying power. Asia or Europe has more buying power. If you see in UK 3 out of 5 spenders are Chinese.

Are there structural barriers?

I have zero knowledge about this, I am sitting on the position of authority. I am a stakeholder. What you expect me to do about it because I have no knowledge about it. If somebody ask me, come tomorrow onwards you have become CEO of the company with no understanding about finance. I will be taking financial decisions; how would it go. This is related to Circular supply chain. Hence the management structure is very important. If it is not set up right and no clarity of hierarchy then it's their doom. I think it's not only CSCM its basic of management. The corporate goals in America are completely different than the goals in UK. Individual goals will be streamlined with the corporate goals. If the government is more stringent or its well enough or its bellow, example of UK and America can't be wrong than that, the targets of each other. Luckily, some inter religion blocks who.....wash put another thing in packet which is compliance for both the countries. If you think individually no it doesn't.

How law and regulations of a country is an important part? And how government can help to make it happen?

Government got their part. If you think about corporate social responsibility, the policies are wrong, has been set up for the failure. I can add bit of human rights up to CO2 emission, right up

to your make and right up to your loss and profit balance. Its government policies, needs to bring down to work rather than spoken about. Like current ambition is to bring carbon emission by checking down diesel and all. That process can be from the centre and could be affecting all of us massively through the economy, but I don't think it has brought forward to about it by educating all. What about the self-less vehicles currently running on the road, you not going to scrap that? It is a bit of deathly topic right now If government want to grab, give them a grant. Now you see Policy. Are they good enough, is there any 0-interest loan policy? As I said to you earlier, 70 percent oral skills 30 percent multinational have taken 80 percent business. Out of 20 percent 70 percent man force is doing more difficult one to capture or implementation. If you give it to big multi nationals, they will implement it. But if I am business and my turnover is less than 5 million, I will be doing mathematics to survive. Every business is here to make money, if there is not enough money, they are not going to take it. But yea there is another way of enforcing it, whether it is right or wrong it's a topic of debate. You have set target to achieve it, you must take some drastic decision. Sorry I have been mindful of the time, but Boris J said I have plan to do country 0 emit in next 10 years. How many times you heard his road map, have you ever seen the road map to achieve it. So now link back what I said that there should a clarity about what you going to implement and at stage. So, I don't think they are committed to do that so how you going to achieve it, talking there? I think, M is basic, man machine method, money, and mentality. I think, need to work on that one

BR (Manufacturing Manager- Interview duration 38 minutes)

As per your perception what is circular economy is?

I think based on what's happening in sort of economy at the moment anyway so in terms of how you know globally things are being basically prescribed as how what should be taken you know in terms of what is ethically correct and what is the corporate social responsibility of what we should be basically including in our normal businesses I think nowadays there's a pressure on the businesses to basically go in the right direction to incorporate all of these things and especially with things coming up such as B Corps you know so companies are basically these are there telling are certified but we should be companies should be more sustainable there should be more I think there is a lot of pressure on the business kind of grow moderation now a lot of people have been made aware consumers are being made aware so even consumers I think that turn is also gonna possible they want to buy products which are more basically sustainable which are more you know better for the environment which are more better for the future so I think there is a lot of pressure this is nowadays especially to go and stop being people sustainable start reusing their sources.

Could you briefly explain supply chain process of your company?

So for us well how are things have changed from where we were so in the past so basically for example so we obviously deal with ready meals so we produce sort of chilled meals as brands fall supermarkets such as Sainsbury's and other supermarkets now with this so they would come they would tell us this is the brief and pretty wood which is you know product development would take yeah brief they would develop products based on what is your requirement yeah depending on what the trends are consumers want their designed those products and then you would basically go for the trial phase and then and then it would go down to last manufacturing it and then going into the consumer cycle OK through those phases you know we have worked for 10 years so similar changes here so in terms of even based on trends people want to buy it I've seen people basically going from even if you just about food trends here but it's gone from you know sort of

curry's to healthier things where they would like that more salads and yeah and stuff at the food yeah and with this new plastic sort of reduction thing so we've gone from having sleep it's non-recyclable to natural see pets which are reused plastic yeah so consumers because in the past they wanted you know their requirement was different and now we see the requirement is changed so now they want a lot more fan so that's where we are and I think it's going through system is also that I've seen so far in terms of food waste any business would obviously have a lot of waste yeah that gets incorporated fruiteries has been there ever since the British started now this food waste that gets collected so we have different streams of how waste is collected so you have different standards or what can be recycled what can't be recycled what is classified as true food waste is collected separately he goes on to these farms using basically animal farms square 3 which is converted into feet yeah plastic sandwich stuff now again we never used to wish you just basically categorise them as general waste yeah plastics films papers and all stuff but now we start have a recycle stream being brought in as well in the business so things are getting recycled through the Cardboard baler cardboards in terms of ready meals finished products finished products go through the system and at the end if you know we don't need to requirement or suppliers or you know the out of life but they're not within spec then they go to the charity's acting OK so we have a lot of charities and we supplied to basically we seldom too employees for cheaper so again to reduce waste are there the moment in terms of sourcing I'm not sure how much I know this but in terms of sourcing ingredients again consumers who want us to source ingredients from sustainable sources so i remember i think prawns and start stay again come from sources which are sustainable which do not harm the environment, sources such as wild life etc.

Do you have sustainability targets in your company?

Every year we get set KPIs every Department has run KPIs on how much waste that we should be basically producing in terms of what are we doing to reduce food waste when we doing to reduce our line waste so we get given targets and then we get given project base or water trends are and how much would you reduce it.

Bringing circularity in food manufacturing company, how easy and difficult task it is?

If I see food manufacturing, now based on other industries obviously people want food to be in a daily city right everyone wants to cheap and people basically want to day will go and buy food

you can't you can stop by includes you can start buying you know shoes stop buying food basic necessity that regards you know through this always required and based on that as a second you know backfill traders people expect for it to be very keeping excess. No one wants to location yeah 100 pounds to be easily accessible you want food to be cheap and yeah you will you know really available and that's what the aims of the supermarkets are yeah supermarkets are not aiming for food to be you know basically Michelin star high priced go by the that is our target audience for that we need to produce it as cheap as possible need to give it to the best potential price to customers which are supermarkets and so that that is the biggest barrier crazy always trying to be sustainable and trying to basically make sure that we get the right pets in or the filming is not always the cheapest option available recycling organic these things are expensive, that is the biggest barrier our company have.

How and what techniques can be helpful to adopt the circular supply chain management?

In the past, I can't say for search we used to do it where we used to have this product called Katti Kebab, think about basically what it was it was you know taking me to get cooked and whatever chicken that we can't use to pack in the meals we shred them and we use the same chicken to produce a second component or product yeah that was whole idea behind it and there are other companies outside who do same so I think your sausages or whatever this scrap meat to take better than make something else there meatballs out of it. There are ways, there are techniques. People have to be creative, think out of box. How we can reduce the waste & different ways to deal with.

Is finance a challenge for companies?

Every industry wants to make money too in terms of what is 2 customers were going to charge this from the concert is going to be yeah so in terms of that like I said so food you know we deal with pence's you know it's a power underpants or whatever it is so you are getting massive amounts of milk so you're possibly profit again is in pence's not pounds .Based really do want to basically make as much revenue as possible to think that that is involved but like I said you know nowadays there are more social pressures coming in from outside in terms of the global awareness consumer awareness which basically forces is have to stay in the market after seeing the competition yeah they have to stop thinking you know more about corporate social responsibility but these things yeah is coming in but then again as you mentioned I think it depends on what the organisation

what the strategy is strategies whether to basically follow the same route and basically you know be more sustainable and be more economic stable & be more in control possible them and they will do that.

What role the management play?

I think it is just basic company strategy , if the leaders of company, CEO - where they have certain goal and want to grow and development and this is what they would implement you will get rolled down from the business, there is no stopping at this is what the company you know E poses with company messages that's what they will follow to come from the computer ship which I don't think it's there 100% in all of these food manufacturing industries yet but it's on way, hopefully in positive way.

And what are the barriers from consumer side? And how they affect bring these changes in the company?

I think looking at the trends now & based on what people are aware of, I don't think it is the case. Again, for me the barrier would be cost, right? Consumer wants it to be sustainable, they want to be everything, but they won't be willing to go over the price. For eg. I have family, I want to buy meal for my family, I want to make sure it is Organic. But Organic is expensive whereas you have option to get cheaper food, so I won't be able to afford it and go for it. This is what managements are making decision on based. But looking from trend is been up towards what people wants. I think the Gov. is also guiding towards the direction, Gov. is basically putting all these rules & restrictions to basically like for plastic bags. Like before it was free but now you have to pay for 5p per bag by this people are using you're their own bags & plastic bags has been reduced. If Government put some efforts towards organic & sustainable – it will be cheaper to buy organic, then consumer trend will be higher.

As you mentioned about government, what role the government play for getting circular economy in place?

Definitely, I think that is the key. You know there are rules & regulations, legislations, that will play huge impact like for e.g., Giving businesses grant or giving business somethings like saying re use your waste, to be inventive. Basically, you are not producing waste & landfills. I think

business will also want to be responsible for everything they produce. Similarly with consumer, you know, like for e.g. If they make organic cheaper, or all these things make cheaper & recycled product cheaper. People want to go and buy those goods instead of basically spending money on others. It is not expensive and good for environment at the same time.

Do you think current laws and regulations are inadequate to bring these types of changes in the food industry?

I think so, yes. A lot more can be done, a lot more can be put in place to basically to expose this a lot sooner, quicker. Saying that like I said I was here too past 10 years, 5 of those years we have been using unrecycled plastic. Obviously, we have progressed towards using natural C-PET, so recycled plastic. Things like these you can do, may be not like, in the quicker way you think you want to change, similar sort of things, you know, you see those in documentaries about in danger species, fishes and all those things causing harms. Business have been demanded; customers are demanding to eco-friendly farming.

What is your view about organisations structure, why or why not? Do you think applying circular economy would be a complex process?

I think, in any organisations, structure plays big part, all contributes towards what you are converting and what to. Again, as you think out of box, as you mentioned earlier, you have the key & you have right way of marketing through, then yes, the product will be successful. If you don't market right, it through to right consumers, you don't market it to whoever it will be sold to & not generating enough revenue to sustain yourselves then it will not be successful. everything contributes.

Are there any other changes food manufactures can face to bring this circular economy in the companies?

As far as I feel, no, I think it is government, consumers trends and business wanting to stay in competition, this is the trend and business have to compete. I think it is what needs to change, people's mindset.

DE (Supply Chain Head Interview duration 57 minutes)

What is your job role in the organisation?

I work as a manufacturing manager and my job is curtaining packaging. So, packaging basically pack the meals and cooked components comes to us and we portion them in container, and it will go to curtaining which is basically the sleeves them and despatch them.

Ok, so what you think are the potentials to bring circularity during the manufacturing process?

I think, as I mentioned before, we use to have products where we use to basically used the shreds from another, we have stopped using them, I think basically NPD have developed where we can use those products. Apart from that, at the moment in terms of manufacturing & our waste, I don't think, we have been given basic components to us to produce . Whatever food waste, we generate goes into animal farms, so we do recycle in that dept where plastics are kept separate and you know the containers are kept separate & food waste is kept separate. That's the stuff we do & any of ready meals it goes to charity.

From the aspects discussed earlier, which are biggest hindrance for food manufactures?

I think it is more to do with innovation from my department, like I said, you know we need more development, need product research – how we can stop the waste. Obviously, we have to make things & maintain food safety, that's the key. Like I said it is innovation, people need to think out of box, different ideas.

Are there indirect barriers which prevent to bring sustainability during manufacturing processes? At the moment, I don't see it as barrier but like I said we had issues, basically we had legal requirement of these things to be changes, plastics. I think that what have caused us to change the packaging. I don't think there is anything else.

Would you like to suggest any drivers which can help the food industries or countries I would say to accept circular economy in food supply chain process?

No, I think people nowadays, from including schools or how we educate our kids in developed countries like ours requirement is on how we are going to sustain and sustainable farming. Some countries, unsustainable farming is there, that's what they will go for. I will depend on how we educate ourselves and how we going to teach people around us & bring up the culture.

In your organisation do they have any sustainability or waste management goals which are given to the staff by the management?

There are, there is but again these waste management thing link to their sale, to the profit if you have £100.00 of sale you can waste 1.5 something like that but this is obviously it helps. Because we recycle things and we for example a damaged product we try to sell it on the half price and something like food we find out that its gonna get out of date we sell it on discounted price rather than putting into the waste because when we put into the waste that costs company involve they have to carry it back to the warehouse do something to get rid of the product rather, its gonna generate cost to the company, even if we give it for 10percent price or even we give it free to the customer that will be more beneficial for the company because there gonna be transportation cost and going to be carbon footprints again, then they have to recycle it, reuse it, they will have to pay for that. So there is another nothing is, all the cardboard thing which comes in which the product comes, anybody can collect it from us. Anyone like moving house or something they can take it. Because Nowadays Amazon there are a lot of small business today, they are working from home, what they do is they take it from us. They take their car; they take as much as they need and for us its beneficial. We don't have to recycle it, so they use it. In my previous organization, what they have done is, they have contracts with local food banks, they give it to food banks, they give it charities rather than wasting it, we used to give it the charity. For example, at Easter at the end of the food we couldn't sell we donate it charity. So, they can play with it. So, something like that.

How technology can be a important aspect to bring circular economy approach?

How it affects is, it's all about data. All the companies collect data if they don't know what they're wasting, they cannot make policies to control it. So, they will not what are the products going out

of date. For example, my hand tells me which products are going out of date next three months. So this gives me an indication that which products I shall get rid of. Every morning I get notification that certain 50 products get out of date in 30 days, so I go and check them. so, I will go and make the insert technology visual checking it give me more reliable data.

What can be the barriers?

The biggest barrier I would say is people are not ready to accept the change until they get educated. Like for example, customers become habitual of products, they been using for long. It is difficult to make their mind to change the taste and preference. Like working here, I have seen British people prefer British food products. They patriot plus they have set their taste.

It is complex because no one knows about it. It should start from top level making strategies and having proper way of communicating through the employees and customers.

What is your understanding about Circular supply chain management?

I had never heard term circular supply chain before, so I had to do a little bit of look up about it. I understand the principle, but it has never been referred to me before as circular supply chain.

So, my previous business, which was a bakery business, there were a number of things we did following this principle. So, for example when we were manufacturing, there was huge amount of trim that will come from the process which was end work for the next batch. Which was theoretically constantly using your rework so you are manufacturing waste, it is half on the floor or there was contamination, which would not be used. Anything that wasn't used because umm of shelf-life implications we send it to pig feed. So, it wouldn't ever gone in the bin. Umm we had, umm the packaging we used, the containers they came in as or any waste was sent to recycling. Umm and We looked, we actually didn't look whether or not it would be a better option, the things we couldn't save because there are 2 parts for the business and there was muffin business and. Looking whether we can't rework, once the muffin kind of destroyed by machine or whatever you can't grinder that up and put it back that mix, We used looked at whether anaerobic digest to help any other of our site would be better to use product rather than sending that to animal feed. It's like same the long way.

So, few things stucked me, the traceability and shelf-life. Specially looking and at mix kind of, so we take we sent the products out. If you are making a Thai red curry for example. And gets to

Sainsbury's and Sainsburys sold whatever they can and discount the rest with . amount with the acceptance, to be able to strip it back. you can't give for animal feed because there is meat in it. You can't feed meat to animals. What can you actually do to it. You got sauce, you rice you got veg and a protein in that. I can't see how that could be reworked anywhere. The only thing I can think of is if the fat content was higher that it could be used in Anaerobic Digestion plant to provide umm power that particular retail store for example. That depends on the amount off the product to put something ion that you would be producing a significant amount, I have no idea what the retail store wastage looks like. That may be Elie could help with it. That was to go back, reused by the manufacturer by another manufacturer the shelf life quite significant. So, there is reason those food have umm um a use by date or best before, which means the product is better to use before that otherwise there is potential food safety implications that you have to consume it and that's because that contain those products, may contain bacteria that can be potentially harmful. So, I don't know, with short shelf life product, how that would work. I totally see with something like bread waste or Pasta waste. That's not . how would it work. Almost single ingredient or very an easy in terms of umm traceability. When you get into the term short shelf life into protein you would have to be able to prove. Like that particular product came from the Noon product for example where Noon products got the chicken from, the rice and the spices come from. Because there is food safety element to it. So, without technology that could, I don't think that can used from human consumption unless that is vegetarian that can be used for animal feed.

So, we had a little bit governance, on the Spurway site where I am currently sat now, used to deliver their own product to the Sainsbury's Green ford, which is latterly. It's one minute's drive and they will deliver the products that were manufactured may be the day before and they will deliver it directly to that depot whereas previously , what would had happened , products were being collected from the Spurway come all the way up on M1 to crick, and come back down to Greenford depot and that worked and there is certainly, when people are planning ,transport, the logistics provide us that use for planning transport there are a number of things that we look at . To look what is the shortest route of depot. In a lot of instances from the financial sense to also to align of diesel expense it worked, unless you are producing the whole rage and you have volumes for that. So, for example if we are in London. So, there are a number of Sainsbury's depot which are sat around London. We got 10n sites, Waltham point, we got Saint Albert, and all are fairly manageable within th reach of London. The issue is on someday, you will be sending out a big

vehicle, 26 pallet vehicle, to deliver 7 pallets. So, unless you got competitions on local area, with local manufacturers it becomes a naturally to an extent, why we are sending the vehicle with 7 pallets on. Is that environmentally good?

I suppose it's the similar kind of model that umm you spoke about that some of the Co-Op and Waitrose stores are using. Where you can order from them with an hour of your order you get your delivery, and the Co-op is doing it by bicycle. So, the people on the bicycle who are delivering that groceries, I think Co-op its within 2 hours of booking it. Not only in certain and I think put it help the people who, found convenience, but lots of people are also bit lazy and don't want to go to the shop. But there will be other people who need that kind of service, so they are able get their deliveries very quick.Uber eats and umm Deliveroo and generally mainly Uber I think, who have dock kitchens whether they manufacture, you think you are placing the order and its coming from the local store, NO. they are ,manufacturing in their kitchen product for the different brands, that you are aware of and Nando's, Wagamama's from that dock kitchen and they are sending it all out from there as a way of kind of centralising and being able to deliver it this on shorts places, they can do this because it's not a week shop. Their situation is based on their locality so they can make that money, but we were to do this try and to get various depots around those short period of time. Umm that to be able to manufacture get out with short, with the maximum of our shelf life, first need fixed order to do that and I think the retailers would like that at all. Because then they have waste potential on their side. Because just because I have eaten its consumers ethical thing but there are lots of people who consume same thing every week, week in week out, their shopping bag never change. There might be some treats on Christmas and birthdays in reality, their shopping baskets stays same. The other people who are inventive for like to eat something differently every day. It's very difficult to predict what their shopping basket will look like. That is why we have such issues with forecasts and order variations in short shelf life. In longer shelf-life products, I don't see why they wouldn't be more work upon.

I think its product dependence, I think there is probably, if you do not look at the total circular supply chain as end-to-end piece from kind of umm conception to consumers. I think you could probably within certain stage of food industry. You can probably this sounds so stupid sorry. You can have small circles in different area so for example the manufacturing piece could be tightened up significantly. I was saying a number of foods produces whether to product to reused, used or he waste is used for rather than landfill.

Then you got the supermarket piece, what are waste, what are the recycling etc more what they are doing with that and the products that have gone off even not utilized them, themselves, could they go to central location. Where composited or stripped off or its used. But few then consumer at home that uses that product, so many people do not buy wisely, effectively, may be our jobs as umm retailers and food manufactures to look it, like portion and pack size that we are doing right things. A kilo of carrots, it's really cheapy but the people actually want 500 grams because other 500 grams gonna go to the bin, Is that the right thing to do. So do we need to make the conscious effort that might increase cost because of the packing. But its right thing to do to avoid the waste. So, the other thing is cross functional uses as well, I think if the manufactures work close together in forums, than one manufactures waste might be used for another manufactures I don't think it's always necessarily explored. So, for example I don't know, probably with milk, milk needs to be sold within 10 days life to retail may be, could be sold with days life to a yogurt manufactures, because its secondary process that so then the initial process is never wasted, or waste is reduced because its has been sold for the secondary process. There isn't any primary function but can be utilised by somebody else umm.

I mean it's interesting isn't it because if you think about the development in packaging sustainability in last few years that come in leaps and bounds. The recyclability of packaging has come in leaps and bounds and Noon (Kerry) is a first business that gone for recyclable trays so that was first in the market, so before that there were black trays were not recycled because it was not taken by the recycling centre. But still, we are relying on people to recycle and there are plenty of people who do not recycle. And I don't know there needs to be some kind of government directive that umm the forcing people in that way of working, I mean there are plenty of people who are recycling say wash I don't wash to put them in the bin.....it's too much hustle. But there are plenty of people, the ethical recyclers if it has been crystal clear and if you think about general waste collections has reduced. If you don't recycle then you bon overflows and there are people who pay absolutely no attention to it, so there need to be some kind of regulation or law for recycling.

Are there any technical related challenges?

For short- shelf-life products, definitely shelf-life spoil it, umm traceability systems that one producer can use multi-component products and be assured that supply chain behind that guarantee the food safety in that proper welfare standards etc, that's definitely a barrier.

And another part is, its bit odd one, probably need to think about it more as well, one of the things is just manufacturing things with waste, where waste is just waste and autumnally you need to just strive to reduce waste. It's not consistence or continues umm you can't just assume there, because people are making that waste and trying very hardest to reduce the amount of waste they have. If you design a process or product that was based on cutting a certain amount of waste, when give you the output when applied it's not guarantee that would be difficult. So let play a part or lets you could source out the waste from multiple different location which you could that if used in food products would be difficult because of labelling and legislation reason you can't just switch from one thing to another without having a specification or ingredient information index and nutrition value nd bla bla bla. Where that would be difficult, unless you could use the waste into further product that is unused. I think that would be hammered.

With longer shelf-life products umm flour for example, if you had flour as bioproduct that probably be a waste product within side book. If you had a biproduct that was made by multiple manufactures that saying constitute things and if it is not coming from one supplier, its coming from another that might work as per the supply chain would be the waste factor uncles its going for uses that will not be a part of human consumption, so that could be used for a field or animals feed or other purposes. For example, my daughter made a dress put of plastic, it does feel like its made of plastic its very beautiful dress. But plastic has been used to make that dress and its totally a recycled dress. umm unless you could do something like that. Unless there is some kind of science that get things accepted over food safety implications that come with it that gated and it became a based product that come from. I can't see how that would work in short shelf-life environment.

What is the finance related barriers?

There is technology required and technology need investment that becomes a barrier. It effectively umm lows value products that could be produced from it. That will cost of manufacture outweigh

that cost will be generated by use or needs to be subsidised that may work, and the government need to think about to reduce the food waste.

And you quite rightly pointed out investment, if things need investment, it needs return, if that return is low then it becomes difficult. even if it is for very very very good cause. That becomes a pilot.

Are there any challenges related to management?

There would be management barriers, there would financial barriers and people need seeing the asset that will be required is worth the umm worth the output book. Every business that deals with retailers business has got the sustainability plans in order to stick on that. So major will get the sustainability plan so definitely a big.... agenda and while they shouldn't be I don't think they would be, until the technology is approved or sources are approved that would be difficult in line with business. I don't think, anybody is willing, the boards and companies etc to join the system the sustainability fight. I think that needs to be sent to them by either ... of loss making to profit making.

Any barriers from cultural side?

Yes definitely, I think it take big plans, probably make it for inline either that or to people the requirement of the people those companies supply so for example a retailer turn around and say 90 percent of your waste, your food waste is used for the purposes for X Y or Z. Then there will be real drive to make that happen, may be not achieve it but to make it happen in till in the pass way in the 5 years planning process. So, its bit like whole recycling thing. Every business recycles initially or recycle until the retailers and government give 0 landfill target to put in sustainability agenda and so share, they are doing the right thing and is complained by law and law plays an important part in it. If law come and say if you are from X Y or Z category. You need to do than they got to do it.

Awareness is the key point; people are not as aware as they should be and that is because we don't message them hard enough. I mean umm if you think about it you go to YouTube or Facebook, several years ago, there were a number of television program that shows the conditions in which chicken eggs were produced. So the condition in which the chicken eggs was produced, they were basically dark..., the cages, chicken poo everywhere, gel chicken on their eye an hazards and it

shocked a common people, because in their heads they thought it comes from the farm ,picked on the ground and they are having a lovely life and the eggs are collected and I don't think people understand totally that industrial methods we use to take those eggs. Now if you go into a supermarket there is a clear sign on it, that whether that chicken is from free range or barn chicken or caged and if you look at the numbers on all the types, there has been a massive swing towards free range. Where previously, it was other way round there was a tiny amount of, this is pigs farm chicken in your local store and that how bringing the awareness in the population, The facts is Helmond's and etc all moved, how long would that be may be 10 years ago 11 years ago to start free range in their products, lots of free range eggs, onion in their products, Waitrose free rage eggs onions on their products. That was massive shift and that came with the awareness. Activist and television programs came and started talking like did you know this is the way your eggs come from. People should be aware what is going into their bodies and then they can make their decision. Awareness plays a key factor, if people are more aware as a consequence as what they did then everybody will make different decisions. So, its education piece and I don't know, when I was in school, I didn't know anything about composite, nothing about composting. And my grand dad had a composite heath. But my daughter in year 4, they did their whole term about composting, how to make compost and why you make compost, what is compost for, compost will heal the world that's what she said. You need to take all your food blab la bla. And she will tell you about it, which is completely factually right, but you need start with education making the people aware of the consequences and that is how it will work. They did a junk bottling project, where they build with recyclable material. On the book day last, pupil was asked to read a particular book on recycling and use quotes from that book, when thinking about their own consumes, book cycle, explain everybody the importance of recycling, so almost forming hard core, if you are performing a part, if not then you should do because you take a child, message them, explain them that its right thing to do.

How structure can be a barrier?

Ummm, I think it needs to be as easy as possible, and when it's difficult, then there should be directives to do so. So may be the engagement is not necessarily there something requires a complex supply chain from another plant together to your supply chain is not stable, then stat would cause the problem. Unless it's coming from the top, it will not work so needs to part of

company's agenda, it needs to be the part of their policy and the mission statement otherwise there will be no group led activities. Somebody from factories floor could not start revolution, it has to be it has to be started from management with all colleague's work.

Are there any challenges from government side?

Targets, the government needs to set targets for this and conduct ... as their own. There might already be sustainability targets, but it needs to be tightened up on all areas not just fields or resources, they need to look food as resource as well.

EGD (Planning Manager – Interview duration 50 minutes)

What is circular economy to you.

So important right now. Current food wastage in tons.

I think to be honest with you over the last 30. Aaaa. no. maybe last 10 years 15 years and probably for next 10 years to 15 years it all phrase though. I think my dad is 70 now he may be 50, may be 30, may be 20, 25 years ago he was working with powering vehicle with natural gas instead of petrol and he works in British gas, I mean it was very very new. People didn't really care about environment back then, only green piece since about then we are kind of going into a journey where lots of peoples are waking up like if you have children and children's children, then you have to think that you have to do something today to change the economy, to change the environment. so I think it is interesting is I where an interesting point now so that actually there is a sustainability steering group in Kerry and I'm lucky enough to be honest and where we were talking about I guess how we can make a business model to say how can we save money though we need to we need to do that to make sustainable in the future , logically and economically as well, for the people who work for us , to support their families. so, I think it's kind of I think you lead it to the business model and then it becomes the environment Strategy.

Is it achievable in today's scenario in the organisations?

I think it's very achievable I think we probably standing on the tip of iceberg and I think the right things but it's not the number one priority and I think I think it got you to the people on the steering group and the people that worked it now but every everyone today it is their responsibility to put it into teacher generation it's a business model so that it becomes something that is something that just part of the standard operating process is not something that something is different and something is new.

Would you please briefly explain the supply chain management process of your company
so I would say probably the only thing that we do that would be baby circular is what comes back call so one of our site Dean way they use their delivery vehicle to deliver Waitrose, Waitrose lorry is gone from the Depot to Waitrose in Southall or Waitrose in Ealing and they empty all the stuff at the store then on the way back it will pick up pick up the Curry and stuff we made it back to the Depot again instead of bringing empty vehicles back and coming back out it that's cheaper for us
The thing is that it more environmentally conscious . says yeah yeah I don't know if we do that at

WML because my brain is only so big and I don't know but I think dawn will probably has told you and I think what we've got we've got an opportunity at WML that we've got the warehouse and there's always a queue of lorries outside get into the warehouse , Massive opportunity there to stop the vehicle cleaning up their engines running having emissions make . we can make it bit smarter like are the lorries full and at the moment we don't have to structure a place to do that then I think what we've got act at noon is opportunities we don't have good process is something but that yeah

and what are the main factors you think comes on the way to apply this kind of revolutionary approaches in the businesses looking at food manufacturing company So what do you think what your views are can you just explain the question again yeah I mean what are the challenges come on the way to apply these kind of revolutionary approaches in the food manufacturing company OK so

I think a lot of it will be around priorities so as I'm sure you have seen from Jatinder, as there is no time to do anything .you are coming anything right and you are thinking I'll do this today. When you will turn on your computer and you have 5 emails that reeving your day there yeah because they need your attention now. before you know it, its Friday and you haven't done what you wanted and then it's January then it's march so I I think to be honest with you I think the biggest the biggest challenge in time I think people want to do it but there's always another priority and that's why I think you need and you always talk about what your Boss is talking about you know what kpi yeah , Labour cost , you know number of people, things like that, I think when we will be talking about how we can be more circular, how can we use recycle, you lead by example and then everyone follows yeah I think the bigger the biggest challenge is that the leadership team yeah I understood group Bolton but yeah really just come down to time and maybe understanding and maybe it's around not having not really understanding exactly what you can do things like turning your monitor off at night and things that you that are more environmental than circular you know that I've been asked I am working on the waste project at the moment probably from a year and I still don't know from where the waste is coming from . okay I still don't know haven't got time I still don't know yeah that what is driving that waste so I know now that we can convert it to charity. which we can give it to hungry mouth instead of throwing it away, so I guess that's

probably the most circular we got it's giving us food waste charity it doesn't it doesn't go to waste is actually used by people that need it.

Do you think there are technical barriers? What are they? And how they affect circular supply chain management's application?

I think so yeah especially in food manufacturing its very people orientated we need people, and people make mistakes. People are human I think there's an element of you don't want to make them redundant from machines. But we are not like Lego for Example they are manufacturing 24 hours a day 7 days a week and they don't have much waste because they are just making bricks and it's a robot making it yeah I think food manufacturers Hard also nice so Lego I keep using Lego as example as Lego, because Lego is a brick company, they can make red brick yeah. And if you will not use that brick for three years, still it will be red brick. We have to be so far ahead with our orders before they come through you know you could end up with so much rice that you don't need it, you don't have orders for that. You have to play a gamble is like you are in casino, you have to play gamble with how the orders were coming and obviously you can give it to charity. But still it is cost to the business because you paid for the ingredients you paid for to cook it and paid fo to pack it and you are not getting anything for it. I think food manufacturing is the hardest, because you got a time limit on what you do , you have to make this decision now. Because of you wait for two days food will run out of life and no one can eat it.

I think we probably do a lot of that from machinery point of view. we recommission machines but the trouble is once we recommission it goes wrong. The initial manufacturer will say I can't fix it because you changed it and we don't have the capabilities. We kind of find ourselves now in a point where we recommission things 5 years ago, they are going wrong now and no one can help us. Or we have to ship something else from Belgium because there is nothing in the UK. We are trying to be circular and not making machine redundant then we have to pay carbon emission..... to get something over from Belgium. I think the biggest thing is short fi.... s rather than long term kind of it I think this sort of project thinking you need to be long term you are making it different this year you may not be making different next year. We need to do this this year than in the 5 years and 10 years' time to be bit more circular. I think at the moment its very much hearing now what is happening today.

How economic and finance part of the business affect the application of circular supply chain management?

I think there is massive financial opportunities, definitely, I think I just answer this question just there, so think what you need is the confident and you need to be brave that I need 5 years I need 10 years, and this is my strategy for that for next 10 years. It may not make improvement this year or next year, but in year 05 you will start to see the benefits. I think need to take a step back or few steps back to really look at what do we do, why do we have lorries Ki..ing at the warehouse, Where are based commercial vehicle , can we sort these vehicles out. You know all of these things, we are so here in now, quick we run out rice , let's get rice in no realizing that we can put on another vehicles, I think the for that is businesses working together. May be competing businesses working together like sharing lorries, things like that, I think the financial impact of that taking massive that you are mor efficient , you are probably cutting down on lorries , on deliveries, things like that.

What are the management related barriers?

I think it is probably pressure, everyone put pressure, especially now it is financial pressure. And no one is brave enough to say I need to take some time to work on this and in 5 years' time it will be better an also like I said earlier people do what their management is talking about. Until the management and leadership team and Kerry business leadership team is really talking about circular supply chain, Circular economy then it is something peoples want to do. They just don't have the skills or the time or mainly the know that how to do it. how to work out this own what it would look like how it needs to be. It has to come from the top.

What is the role of company culture?

Definitely. I think company culture is an interesting thing. Like what they write down on their websites and what happens. And I think sometimes it's very different, sometimes. so, think its again comes down to leadership if you will think about company like Kerry is so big, you could be working in the factory in Malaysia, to you could be working in Bangkok, or you could be working in Southall. U know the Kerry value is still the same. When you will google on the website. Obviously it's down to general managers behaving, how is the ops directors, shift managers are behaving, all of that .

I think it's very much kind of, its two things one is what is company saying on the website and everything else and most importantly 77% of actually happening. and it will come down to leaders. is it not? if the leaders at the site are living and breathing the value of being more circular using what you don't need and finding the ways of recycling things then everyone else will do it. Sometimes the best idea is come from the peoples working on the lines or doing the admin but until they agree on the switch things or something like that no one even knows what the idea is there.

How are what is the effect of consumer side of culture?

What do you mean by culture the peoples who are eating meals?

I think interestingly consumers certain the company I work for more focused on circular using circular resources I think it's if man that shows about environmental piece and what they doing to using potential waste things like that and they are doing slightly better certainly doing better what they were before Covid, and the companies were called out as being wasteful and caring about the bigger environmental picture and potential covid has impact on this. Consumer has changed their behaviour and they get what they can online or quickly they go to grocery store and buy first thing they see if they want it rather than spend some time really thinking about. However, Definitely its going to the consumer, its almost I saying about the leadership for example. I always think the other thing consumer will put the pressure on the leaders and the leaders will follow. I think consumer probably play the biggest part Because you have all the categories development Looking at consumer trend, if you think about the money and move towards plant-based diet. Obviously, it's not the same but its similar kind of grounding I think I think almost. I think the thing we go first is the consumer waiting with the pound and the leadership team will follow then it will be a kind of chain effective that. Consumer is a key yea yea yea I think so I think so. Unfortunately, it should be the leaders want to do it. But in the meantime, the focus must be to keep the business running.

What are the structural barriers and how they affect this transition?

Yea the biggest impact is having a structure that will focus on circular approach or sustainability or something like that. The business that will do well will have sorry I said I in the sustainability stirring group, but I don't have time to focus on that you know what is like. You know the hours Jatinder works. It snice being on it built there is no time to implement. If you have structure in place that has a sustainability director and then each each-each business area R&D supply chain

manufacturing commercial had a sustainability lead that is obviously then way of business showing its really important because there are investing on the people also spending 37.5 hours a week or 60 hours or however many hours working with people on that we have a transformation team. So, they are working in looking at project ideas cosyng out things like that. ITs almost be like that so I think structure is the key for looking potential of circular opportunities.

How can government help food industries to bring this change?

We are having being a cynical here. I think government probably pay the biggest part offering businesses incentive so be more circular specially if it financial incentive. Then business have got a written document to put a structure in place so yea the financial benefit from the government to reduce something like carbon emission or you will be taxed of you don't do. I think it comes from the top and absolutely and obviously we have environmental minister forever but I its more about legislation can government, The government can ladder on the businesses. Business they are doing the main talking rather than Boris J doing the press conference on circular economy. People are bearing the views of him. I don't think that will change anyone's opinion. I think lagging and taxes will definitely work.

Are current laws in the favour of circular economy?

They are inadequate because I haven't seen anything revolutionary yet. So yea definitely. They definitely need quite revolutionary change in the way people behave, businesspeople everything. At the moment we just don't have that. And I mean you got things, the congestion charge, drive zones, if you really got old car. We don't want that but that's not really government is making to stand for something different. I think government should be doing something revolutionary for that. I don't think government will do or share data on that. The food manufacturers are almost 50 percent of emission, and these are the worst manufactures by cubic, I don't know what the measure is. As we were saying about the consumers, and they can tell the criteria. If want a Pepsi or Coke and I know Pepsi is so much worse than coke and it might make me to think that have coke is best or you know umm then you can have firm decision from two similar products to choose, ... I am gonna boycott that company and I will just but from here and that where leaders start... so here the government, I think the leadership has to come through. So, the government cam very easily

change something even without move taxes or something like that on the businesses just to show the numbers.

What are the challenges for manufacturing stage and how it effects?

So, we get, have forecast from the customer and then at some point all the orders are finalised. Like say this is my forecast, this is actually wanted, I want you to deliver it on X day so I am Sainsbury's and is Thursday, this morning they call us and say they want Saturday depot. We have to start loading that tomorrow so we have then had to start consumer Monday or Tuesday, we will look at the forecast and will have to start cook on Monday. And its gamble you know, we are playing a gamble like casino on someone else's money. Ok we will say we will cook this much and it's all going into the chiller. And next day we will say alright we got this much on the chiller looking at the forecast of Saturday lets pack this much and on Thursday we will say alright, this what is the order, and this is what we have got. and anything over then we have to say what is the use by day, can it go to the next day depot, can we ask the customers to increase the order or do we have to give it charity. The biggest thing that is impacting us the reliability of the customer and their forecast and order window and we used to have to get the orders today and out loading it tonight for Sainsbury's so for us which much harder to control and recently we change the order window I think, the biggest impact we have the longer order window. So only we will be cooking thing according to the final order. I don't know if it answers your question or not.

What is potential for circularity during manufacturing stage of supply chain?

Probably the easiest way, easiest thing to implement the circular economy. Purely it's going to the order cycle window and trying to use Sainsbury's and keep using Sainsbury's as an example am trying to ask Sainsbury's its Thursday today, isn't it? So, hang on a minute, one-two-three- four yea on Sunday, which means I could get the order this morning and cook it then pack it knowing that I have got the orders and definitely I will cook what they want. The waste will come from the batch sizes like and that is not in our hands that we can do something about, and this is something that going back to investment. If the factory windmill lane factory was built for big, long runs on Chicken tikka masala or chicken korma for Sainsburys and over the years we started 140 SKUs and some of them are not of long run. Maybe we need to invest brat pan or smaller kettles that is in our hand. So, it can take the risk and it becomes the internal risk. The biggest opportunity for

manufacturing process is lead time window when the customer tells you what they want, and we haven't cooked at yet and you're cooking only that you know what they want.

To bring the circular economy transition, what is major challenges for your department? and how?

Again, it's the customer's orders, if they drop, or if they increase, we already started cooking them, then we need to do something with it. It's just customers and what agreement we have on life. For example, noodle, we have to cook today and have to use today and if we don't use it today, it will go to the bin. Otherwise, they will get slimy. Technology you know that sort of things, you are then in the circular environment you want to keep using them, but you can't and I think food safety as well. And it comes down to food safety, which is most important think, but it is barrier as well. What policies would you suggest?

Longer lead time on the products and more flexible food safety window, ability to adopt batch sizes easier.

Anything else you would like to add?

I guess umm hygiene window is the barrier, it comes down to food safety again. You have to run it but it's a barrier over a time when you have to keep going, that you have already cooked something, and you have to pack it but you can't. You need to stop production because hygiene needs to come and clean. Because if you know, you can't pack it tomorrow, because food safety risk than this is something, then you cannot be circular. Not that you want to do something differently but it's a barrier.

HM (Head of international supply chain and Logistics- Interview duration 48 minutes)

What is your understanding about Circular supply chain management?

I think businesses are evolving, I think it's gone through a bit of a curve. Somewhere like Marks and Spencer's we kind of kicked off and were quite industry leading in the kind of plan A which I'm sure you heard off corporate and social responsibility and you know sort of 10 years ago you know and I think we were quite leading the way then others but I don't think customers necessarily knew what that was I don't think it necessarily transposed to customers understanding that I think it was great in industry and I think we were leading edge and I think it was great call-back. You know customer looking at those bananas looking to buy them or looking at those mushrooms and the pack, then this actually you know made from recycled. I don't think it ever at all we can do a good enough job to really move that into end tell the customer storey of maybe why that might decide to be more expensive and that's how I think it kind of lost its commerciality. We are not going get businesses to really buy into this. It also must be a kind of Profit lens with to it. Because you know you have to make strictly note in the current climate that our margins are so small in the food industry in particular. You have to have a commercial advantage for doing anything. I am sure you can just do things because they're nice to do. Nothing wrong, but there are ethical and moral threats there obviously. But it has to be commercial.

So yes, kind of 10 years ago, I think other retailers I think of caught up and I think actually M&S is probably behind now a little bit you know we were late in the plastic situation you know there's a lot more people on the front foot although I'd say we did pretty well plastic bags. So I think it's kind of evolving there's a lot more now customers are not a lot more focused on it. However, everybody looks Primark don't they you they. Customers say they like it, they want ethical, they want to be sustainable they want all pairs of denim to recreate but they also want to bargain. I think this answer the question, I think it's as a business we have to be able to see commercial worse and I think we have to be able to measure it. That has been also quite a challenge in the past when we're trying to set some of our internal kind of targets on these things the obvious one's waste to landfill which is which is not common target but again how do we're looking at you know how you see Co2 emissions. Well, actually how do you measurable.

What do you think is it achievable?

Zero waste, OK I don't think because there is no movement if they zero. I don't think you are going to get zero but I'm not sure. I think there are probably certain supply chains you might I think you've probably can play with certain product types. Those products that I think you can get to it we have to be able to get to 0 food waste yeah that that should be we absolutely and we have a moral obligation to that not just.... Something like food waste food I think you must be able to know whether that's going to charity as an exit and not to landfill we have to be able to do everything. Are going to cut plastic out completely no but again was a type of plastic to be able to recycle. Clothing is a big one as well I mean it's your area that you're looking at. But at the moment we are trying a lot that how we do with clothes and people just throw close away. That's people 's the mentality towards clothes is, I wear it for a season and throw it.

What sustainability and waste management goals you have in your company?

As we talked about plan A few years ago, we just kind of be energised this year. We have got very big targets; we've got very clear targets to zero waste to landfill. So yes, and we must report that to board level. So, yes, it's quite a key and that's not just one, about carbon emissions as well, is another big one. We also have got airfreight because we have international supply chain as well. It is a big factor in international supply chains.

What extent you think application of circular economy model in the supply chain can help to reach towards 0 waste vision and to achieve sustainability goals?

I can only talk from a retailer's perspective.so I can't really talk from a manufacturing or supplier side. From retailers' point of view, we've gone through a very difficult time in the last year of demand clarity, not having the accurate demand in certain times on products is quite a challenge. So, I think there's about how we get the right systems in place within supply chains not right demands but to try and accurate demand forecasting which then gives you a fighting chance actually then be able to manage waste. then there's the process and policies around what you do when you have that waste. But we look at it from M&S point of view now. From those who looking from ethical angles, very much involved in commercial angle. But I think in..... changing from the last year people haven't got food. They need the food banks now iits just grown phenomenally. This shows that the product you were able to have gone back in the day. It was seen as a embarrassing thing go to a food bank. They just went around but now there's a lot more outlets

that retailers can set up with that local charities, local establishments to be able to clear that and began give it. So, whether they can clear it so it doesn't go to waste, but I don't know but they've got a better chance when they give it away for free we have.

What you think are the hindrance factors which comes on the way to apply the circular approach in the retail retailing industry?

I think the lack of flexibility and agility to be able to react, so I think you need supply chains that is necessarily quite established and being able to kind of adapt and be flexible to react is probably quite a crucial but let's be honest that's a requirement going forward with everything going on anyway now exposed supply chains in lots of ways not just around circular supply chain. So, I think this definitely fingers around flexibility I think it comes back to my point at the start which is around you are going to get costs you make sure it stacks up from a profitability point of view rather than. Because if it doesn't then I don't think you're ever going make it work.

What are your views about technology?

I don't know for retailer because I supposed to have on the systems took obviously demands correctly at the right at the back end there isn't really much, we can do from a system. Because but you have ordered the wrong amount and it sat in stores other than I'm not sure what systems other than creating a better demand put the right amount of stock on the shelf in the first place other than that I'm not I'm not sure. I suppose you could have some technology around people having visibility, But I think, it's really difficult, having been the person who works in store when you're putting in the yellow tickets on what you don't want is people waiting instead of buying full price then you don't actually buy. Like on Christmas when the stores are closed for a few days, so on Christmas eve like at half an hour before you get so many people coming in. So yes, that kind of app but with the app you really need to have the right motivation because it's a business and you don't want the business to be taken away from full price to sales.

Are there finance related barriers?

Giving the example of Primark that everyone wants to be ethical until they see the price. So here the challenge, how the businesses is or how the businesses turn this into PR and selling point. That is business have to do and will be rather than they kind of do it because they put pressure on to do

it corporate social responsibility challenges. The best company can do will be, how they how is it a unique selling point. I worked in a lot more clothing and the food side but someone like Toms that Toms is a shoe company, every time you buy a Tom shoe, they a pair of shoes to a child in need. So, it quite a big marketing tease required for circular Supply Chain. As I used the example of marketing technique which pushes the corporate social responsibility. Its about how you sell that to a customer. In an easy way, someone walking around the store or different messages

How management play a part to accept the circular supply chain management in retailing companies?

I think the way people get managed about the way they measured on. I think, if you don't set someone an objective on this or KPI, it will not work. You can only manage something you can measure. So, for me, as management you have to set it as an objective that's just important as you cost related objective or your service metrics anything like that. It should be coming from the top. You have to have your boards directors, in your senior leaders have to have these objectives as well. It can't be just like four tiers of management has the objectives and the board doesn't have it's the CEO doesn't have an objective that's true.

Is company role important to accept circular supply chain management model in retailing side?

Company's culture has massive role of that's what that's what makes the company in to. That's what stands companies apart is ultimately their culture isn't. When everybody is selling the same thing so there's only a few things that are sold apart and that's the unique selling point of the brand and what that brand stands for and the people said that brand stands for what they stand for and again as the culture of the people being a lot more aware they want to have brands that are more socially acceptable, don't they? And setting that culture can't be done overnight it takes time create a culture. The same point on the management side it has to be just someone decides today and we going to be ethical company.

You have to live and breathe it every day, you can't just write on a form and say that's our core values everybody. Everyone has to live and breathe it, because of which It takes time. Some of the new starter companies they have great opportunities cause their stocking up and therefore they can

establish in a new way of working. A very old well companies, a 120 years old company has legacy culture they have to recognise and move it the time and that takes a bit longer maybe.

what cultural factor do you think come on the way to accept circular economy model for an organisation

I think it's that cultural mix crucial and the direct of cultural diversity. Let's make it portable for the any organisation to do with anything not just the supply chain. I think so values and have to be established throughout and the diversity of cultures across it, part of that.

What would you like say about consumer side of culture?

I think people can't afford, have a conscience. I think everybody wants to do the right thing, but you haven't got a job you've got three kids, you got mortgage to pay. You have to look for you to be able to have that choice. So, let's the retailers or the supply chains make it the same price which is a big-big question for yeah if you can't make it the same price you're always going to come behind. Obviously, a lot of people who can but people who cannot be able to choose in the current climate in the current challenges as we are going towards biggest recession we've ever had probably.

What is the role of organisation structure?

I think it leads back to the management question which is I think you have to have a structure that shows the importance of that area so if try and say, this is our biggest objective and this is our KPI on it and then put no resource to it so its not going to be delivered. Structures needs to be an appropriate resource attributed to it. The widely depending on how organisations are set up a lot of supply chains are kind of integrated supply chains. So you end up having different departments may be looking after different things so somehow you've got to just again just certain supply chain but how do you integrate, buyer might decide what's the right thing to do can stream any action you've got to consider the whole end to end in the way it's structured but that's difficult when all designs necessarily put in silos little bit.

Is there any barrier from government side?

I think this probably two things that spooked like straight away, I think, how the government help organisations to achieve it. Whether are funding, grants. Because investment being a barrier because it might not get right return on the investments, to get cheap loans to be able to invest. That will help. So, I think grants and then what points they make for all companies hit To the regulations. what point you regulatory to keep things consistent. The problem is, we don't want to put this a business deal. So you kind both at the same time, .. plan to say ok there is food bank on edge or there is warning or support to be able to do that it's going to be difficult. A little bit like electric cars, its ten years away but they are very clear, they are forcing a change. So, I think it's a fine balance and at some point, it's important to enforce the change.

Are current rules and regulations, inadequate to bring circularity in the UK food industry?

I don't know, I know about the plastic bags, the one we are charging apart from that funding and all I don't know.

What can be the measures to ensure the sustainability?

We do mark downs the products, in our company, we do it as policy we do it certain times depending on how much we have got. you might mark it down in the morning if you got a lot and then later you do several mark downs certain time like sometime will be 10%, 20 %, 50% depending on how much you got. So that is mark down piece. Then once the stores close, we move which is going out of life and that is delivered or collected by local charities or food banks. We also have process in our depots as well so not just in stores, so if any problem in depot them we also have processes and set up, so that's how it goes. So even if we got food waste, it wouldn't go to landfill, it will be going for generating fuel.

The food which can't be eaten or not edible for example it smashed that is of recycling companies but that's quite small amount but the most goes to charities and food banks.

It's in place so, we put it in place so while in terms of those process, in one stage you want to celebrate that it goes to charities but with your commercial side, you don't want to celebrate because that's loss of profit, so I don't think there is huge amount of barriers. It's quite frustrating sometimes to cancel things to out of life but we can do is provide the charities, but they don't to use it, it's up to them. We have loads to wate, but it does no go landfill.

JSS (Consumer- Interview duration 55 minutes)

So, to start with, are you aware of this term? Circular economy or circular supply chain management? Word about like secular things.

I heard his word circular supply chain. Not like too much technically, but overall, I have kind of rough idea about the circular things, so can you explain me a bit more about what word actually want to achieve?

How would you explain circular economy or circular supply chain management? What it is?

Yeah, so from this one actually on top of my head I would say what I got from your brief introduction about circular economy. So, the thing is basically. More maybe now commercial and talking about commercial thing. That's what the topic of research. And that's why it's more commercial thing but actually feel see, nature created the food in that way so it's circular. even A like for example any apple, any Banana I am just taking a hypothetical example. So, nature created in that way, so just go million years back when humans were not human or all the animals they were living in the jungles and All in all. Nature created in that way, like if They like someone will eat it on the life span, then it's fine, otherwise the same apple same banana out any fruit, any vegetable or whatever is eatable good are, it will drop down. It will automatically decompose in that way, and it will disappear. So, this is, this is what the circular. already created by nature. and in this way, our turn thinking is nature even didn't think about the waste and all, he just overall created these things and waste whatever the waste he didn't think like we can do that One this one, so it will be automatically circular. This is what is created by Nature, I would say. But now actually the thing things are commercial like. Commercially we are growing fruits on a specific place. It's not natural, so we are seeding and what would you say. You will water them. Yeah, of course these are more commercial, so we are we are. We are kind of playing with the nature, not playing in the double course work, but a kind of. It's we are that selfish. We're creating that thing and we're selling them and It's not natural anymore. I would say. So now the things are. Commercial and commercial things are not like designed in in like proper way. How nature created. so that's why you need to do this research. I would say otherwise. We don't need to and. When we add so the thing is yes. So of course, when we are commercial, and we need to live with these things and of course. we

need to think about. About the waste thing about the circular, how we can make it happen? What I'm thinking on top of my head is Just simply see the process of nature, how nature created and just align all the things with the nature. Very simple way. exactly so for example. These fruits and all, if it's coming from that particular idea, naturally it's growing is coming too. And The thing is, all the time we are thinking about our comforts, so we're rather than going somewhere, where specifically, for example. You can talk about India, because I am from India. I know more about the India so. More bananas are in the middle part of India. So, if you go there and will buy and this is this is what the beauty of nature was. So, it will go there by their state way they will transport that part from there to here and they will freeze it. They will keep. Them in the chillers, to like to extend the life, artificial life, I would say. Again, playing with nature. So, I think if I I know it's very blunt statement. aaaaa We shouldn't do that. We should like save the nature so where the speciality of that nature created in that way, so it will be there only the bananas will be there. So, we should go there, and we should enjoy bananas there only rather than bringing here it's other way round as well. So, we in this busy life you don't have time particularly to go there and in this way, we will not be able to enjoy. Yeah. That part but. This is, this is how I think. It will be automatically. It will be that area will be.

What are the challenges to circularity in food supply chains?

Okay, so now we are living in the world where we are working according to the systems. So, systems are like created now, which is controlled by government and obviously government is creating the systems for all of these circular things and these kinds of things. So, I think although it's already started up to some extent, by Govt like. I'm living in UK. Food waste is going into different bin so that food waste they are taking it, and opts going into Their recycling and upcycling centre, like they're making some bio or something that I don't have, like exact knowledge about. Yeah, but they're making something from that, so they're kind of these kind of initiatives are already taken, but I think only are we are designing now in that way. So, because the population of world is you can go is increasing day by day. So now the only way to control which is I would say I'll be agree. The only the system. So, system will work. for example. we are driving a car on the road. If there is a red light, then we have to stop. If there's a green light, then we have to go to. Our brain is now designed in that way. so anything, is controlled by the government so well go it will make the systems like. First of all, then then only it will be possible, but at the moment. It's

it's. Companies like as I said, like it's all commercial now. Everything is starting and directly linked with finance directly linked with these things, your graphs, your budgets, everything is now controlled by electronics. I would say or by government and data and these kinds of things. But only thing will work is moment systems. To do this approach. This is small scale if you're talking about the home things home, food waste or biggest in the food industry. But I'm thinking is this is not much scope of upcycling thing. there is there is like we can use some fruits, vegetables, shell and we can use like we can dry them out and we can make something out of that, but this is very small area of recycling and which nature created like in circular. Yes, that is, but I think only government can control it. From my point of view.

What the challenges from government side you think are the current systems and laws and regulations? Are they adequate to achieve this sort of approaches?

See now actually. We are entering into these kinds of things. OK, the country, like those countries which are not that developed for example India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Asian countries which are not that much developed yet. And still on development stage. They are. very circular, I would say they are ahead. Then the developed countries. So, developed countries people are that, although there are more resources to enjoy their lives and their lifestyle. But because of different reasons, I would say because there is poverty, so they don't have that much money. Because if even if I'm just pick up the example of two countries. compared to countries India and UK, for example right so in UK? Everyone is self-dependent and earning a good amount of money to live a good life. If he or she is working minimum hours. he got a good life. He can buy food. He can pay his or her expenses an all expenses. They can bear right. And sometimes even. I need only one kg of something and two KG on offer or something. It's promoted by co. and I'm taking two days. I'll do another kg which I bought extra is going in bin state way. But still we are buying it and I people sometimes not bother.it is just one pound so don't worry about that. Yeah, so at one side is positive because I can I can bear my expenses and I'm living good life but on the other side flipside of the coin I would say I'm wasting, I do not value of that that one pound. Exactly, so the country, like the other side. If you see India, they are struggling for their basics .so they know the value of single rupee. So, when you will, you will try to buy even two cagey in place of one. You will try your 150% to use that another, because otherwise it will. It can affect massively on your budget

whatever you were trying to do. of course, one or two day you can do, but not regularly. because they necessity and basic needs. Oh, when we're thinking about these kinds of things then Oh then the system systems are on step 2. First this is awareness and how important it is like to first of all to save the food. rather than going into waste things. but if it is going into waste things what else we can do. To save it. can we feed to the hungry mouth? What is the option. For example, if something is here at my home. And I know it's getting expire. What can I do for that? I mean I want to save them. I know there are 5 meals siting in my refrigerator. I can use 3 out of them and 2 it will get expire tomorrow .so from Govt side. I want to save them. How can I feed it? Because The thing is I can feed someone here I can call anyone, and I have spare one can buy but people will not ready to give is there are lots of frauds are going on and they can mix something and it can be poison or something and from Govt side how can we assess the quality? Yes, it's good. Or how can I save it? It's very small example although, but if you will see on the bigger scale and like about the industrial waste industry but home domestic. I want to save it when we're like we keep it circular. I don't first of all should not go to the completely landfill, but extra we can do so. This is again 1 barrier. I would say I want to save it, but I cannot. I have to dump it at the end of the day because if there's food end safety, there are some other like. If someone will take it, it can be poisoned and I at home I cannot access. The quality is good or bad tomorrow, right? So, this is this is 1 barrier from the domestic side different affecting the commercial again? And they're actually some. We are using. I think technology in these days and commercial waste. I have seen one app is called Too good to go. And it can be more as well, but I'm using this frequently. I'm using that app and the commercial that small restaurants. And these all-food manufacturing companies on this scale. So, they are selling whatever the left things are on cheaper price. Rather than straight way going into the bin. Because that control is there, because they know the quality is getting expired is still good because they're selling it, and all government controls are there. because that's commercial part so. Yeah, they're trying their best to do, but again, it's when we're two commercial and we forget about ethics and these kinds of things. So then at. Restaurants as well. We sometime restaurant owners are not thinking about that. Things like we should feed to hungry mouth. If there is no sales and someone not turned up in their restaurants in that next it will go in bin because it's a food nature, bacteria. And again, we have to dump it. so, these barriers. Yeah, these are. These are on top of my head. These two three things like. I would say.

As you talk talked about, technology can help it in it and there are not enough techniques like how we can use them and how we can assess them health and safety things exactly. It is a big, big barrier. Big challenge if we want to, you know, apply these sorts of changes in and. Ah, another thing I would like to discuss about the. Management, what do you think? Um, if the circular economy thing, I think it's. If do you think it's a complex process? If we want to implement in the in this country, for example, we should. We would be including. Up a common person to a big industry. So, thinking about all the all this department solve the stages and then scrutinising on all the small things do you think is a complex process? If yes. Then how any thing which can drive it? Effectively.

And yeah, so when you say complex, I would say yes, it is. It is complex. One because it's very initial stage, now we started thinking about these kinds of things. One thing I will link back to my previous statement when the things are very easily available. You lose the value, yeah? With units is food is money. If anything like if it's very easily available, then you will. You will not value them. although our superstores our companies everyone is thinking the best way. Structure wise I don't know very technically how and what it can be. It is just roughly, as a consumer I would say. The More engagement. More awareness. And on top of that, very important control. And they should be like. If we can see domestic wise. Like energy. So, we can see which household is using energy up to what level, its green is red, like categories. Exactly, so this home how House number one, XY ZED is using this much amount. Is this read this much is so this is called a kind of control and then actually government can control in that way, so this household food waste is this much this many kg at the moment they are just collecting. Whatever it is, there no control. And there can be like. A household who, like as I said, don't value the food and they're dumping allot allot every day and then government can control because if they're collecting waste from that particular home. Let's say let's 500 kg per month or six months? So, then Govt should ask a question. So why? Why are we wasting that much of food?

Is that even if they can be some like some genuine reason? But of course, but sometimes it's just the behaviour. So why? Why so these kinds of controls. This is not straight forward and easy. This is complex exactly. is your question being, complexity, But when we are thing and brain storming then these kind of things will come up. Its more about more control, because I am working in

corporate world. My brain is designed to see all charts. That is the solution I am thinking on top of my head.

This all the way complexes. Start from people. Start from. If you start from the industries organisation organisations. everywhere it's. It's a very complex in especially in food Industries. Because the life of food is limited, it's like. Nature created in that way, so there is a limited life. and to control these things. It is very hard and involved costs state way. cost for households, costs for government cost for industries. So, I got chance to visit a factory. Uh, they were making snacks. like they are still based in UK. So, what I have seen there is they were making some snacks. It was battered they were using flour, they were using potato starch, breadcrumbs, And two make like few Kgs of that particular product, they were wasting almost similar amount of that flour or better or whatever was required. And that breadcrumbs can be reused for something else. to recycle, not recycle, upcycle. What would you call it? that way so that breadcrumb.it is nothing wrong with it. it is just battered and that is good quality. It's in life, everything is there. But then what i was thinking with my small brain you need to keep it somewhere, in different bin. For that we need space. To keep it alive to use next time we need to keep it on required temperature. I am talking about one product, and they are producing almost 80 to 90 products. To control 80-90 products, they need 80-90- different bins. And all businesses are thinking in that way ok so how much worth of cost that part is. It will cost 10 pounds. How much cost will be to store it and to keep it for next use it will be 11 pounds. Ok then let's dump it. it can be reused. but cost involved everywhere. on bigger scale if any brilliant idea come up then we can. But this kind of process is I would say it's very complex and very complex to control for everyone or households, for commercial industry? Everyone, everyone else it is that complex, but It's doable. I will say at one point it's not like impossible if we will start thinking as you're. You're the first one I've seen like doing this kind of research and now. I would say I'm start. I've started thinking about these kinds of things, which I have never thought about. I'm looking at the waste thing, but I'm so I'm thinking in that one or two minute when I'm going home, I forget. Actually, I'm busy with my life, but when you will talk about these things every day and that will be part of your life, yeah. We will come up with new ideas, which Albert complex, but it's still doable.

Continue that example of breadcrumbs, for example. Add we used that breadcrumb. It is about control again. Let's continue the same example breadcrumbs. If I have reused those breadcrumbs

in the same industry, for example. It is nowhere mentioned like. That product is product ABC, right that produced 7:00 o'clock in the morning with the breadcrumb. And in place of dumping that breadcrumb, they reproduce the same product in the PM in somewhere for 5:00 o'clock in the PM by using the same breadcrumb. It's nowhere written, and it's nowhere recorded that we cannot reuse, or we cannot use that like. OK, so whatever is. Written on like the nutrition along with that one. If its risk assessed. And there's no, there's no risk to reuse that product. I will believe that. exactly still unbelieving it. I don't know how they're making a I don't know the process. I don't know the product I'm eating today is cooked in which oil. maybe they have cooked some allergen product in the same oil or meat product and I'm vegetarian. I don't know, but whatever is written there, I am believing that. yeah, exactly so that that is government responsibility or the different bodies who are assessing and auditing these food manufacturing companies to checking their quality, their processes, and the system. This is their responsibility, and this is how I think the system will work. Otherwise, I cannot go back to the industry to check each and every meal exact coming from. So, it is their responsibility. So i would say no. it's not affecting me. as long as its risk assessed by them, as long as it's written on the sleeve or the packet of that product it's safe to eat. It's not affecting nutrition value any of health .then i don't mind. If it is reused. they know better than us. If something for example some gases. They are telling us its wrong for us. Then we are taking care. Like keep away from kids etc. so if it is risk assessed, I don't mind. I'll be happy yeah food, if you show them the mirror. I think the effect will be different.

If you don't do it, that's going to be yes already. There is awareness. Awareness is coming, but it should be more precisely yeah, and as you said that yes, if it is risk assessed if. The top people they are telling us whether the industry is, whether is the comment and as we have like many departments. Many Ministers, department SIFF. if thinking about circular economy if there is a special minister about it yeah and the whole body is there and I think it, can you're right?

See, first it should be on bigger scale, bigger scale means everyone should know the name circular. Everyone should be aware. Special events, special recognition. As i said, like. If. Let's just pick up the example of electricity. Like before someone is green all the time and using that electricity efficiently and effectively. Then there should be some rewards from the government, like some concession in text. if you are wasting less food you will get. Concession for tax, because this is all

about playing with your mind, right playing with people's minds. Yeah, yeah. So, when anything I'm I would say I'm talking about myself first, anything related to finance., I'm that'll be my first priority, so if like we will get some benefit from government like you will get 0.5% or 1% of this text yeah from this tax or you don't need to pay this tax or reward in that way. People will take initiatives. Yeah, yeah. If. Government. Can put some fines kind of things as well, although it is negative approach, but sometimes we have to adopt it to control. Like traffic, if someone is not following the traffic rules here, he/she is getting tickets. And this is all their controlling their speeds. This is how that system will work. So, if kind of finds as well. And. Motivating the I think ideas and industries exactly. This world is not lack of technology. People have ideas, but sometime in those ideas you know stay behind because there is a lack of money. Yeah, so these sort of things and promote. I would say nature. Nature natural things. It's all commercial and we're thinking we are providing food on your doorstep. And all of your we're taking care of all of your comfort. Yes, it is good. It feels good at one point, but it's affecting somewhere. I'm working in corporate world. like I don't have time to do anything. For my health, my physical health I I have to go to the gym, and I don't have time to go to gym. All the time and I'm thinking my car is helping me and saving my time and is conducting but it's affecting my health, not doing any physical activity. I'm doing sometime once in a week, but that's not enough. We're not designed. I mean nature doesn't design in that way. So, keep close to nature. And whenever you are doing anything, whenever you're developing any product, whenever you are, you are implementing any change anything which is drastically easy for for humans, and there is. They're getting very comfortable with that, but think about these things as well, like process of nature we are doing about circular things. Like it, it should be part of everything like now yeah, if you have to open the restaurant, Government needs to check Is there any sufficient parking available for that? So, this is their task. This is in their checklist, yes, . it should be part of their checklist. Yeah, all the time, yeah? So that that can be another control for the industry, like there are lots of other ways, but I think we should. We should talk more about these things, but definitely I would say it's very good topic and I will start thinking about these things now.

MC (Senior National Accounts Manager – Interview duration 35 minutes)

Your role in the company?

I have been working with Kerry for 3 years and I manage umm Sainsbury's account so which account about 70 million pounds. I lead the total customer interface. Everything to do with the customers is led by myself. I work with prosperous things I work with process development; I work with process category, I work across the bad-track. My all-role target is to basically to hit my prox sales and profit numbers. Um yea KPIs full hits my profit portfolio numbers.

What is circular supply chain management for you?

It is combination of all environments, economics, sustainability as well as business aspect, its definitely to get the sustainability to cover the top sort of tier, however it's unique, I give you an example as my customer is Sainsbury's and Sainsbury's have ... target to get net zero carbon emission by 2040. So therefore, if you are not working towards reducing the plastic, increasing sustainability you would not have permission to trade So for example yesterday we had quarterly business review, so there were 5 points on the agenda where those points were for sustainability. Absolutely, It is a key for my customer, Out of 90 minutes meeting about 30 percent we were discussing about sustainability. There are various ways that retailer is discuss it and so for example we were discussing the trays we supply the food, we were actually discussing we could use smaller trays. Therefore ware 2 way we are doing. if we reduce the size by 20 mm straightway, we will be using less plastic, we will also then need smaller to pack them and therefore we could fit more boxes in the truck. Thereby using less trucks. So such small changes by reducing 20 mm. It will have such a small effect on sustainability. I guess we are looking at circular management although I am rather in the sales business part in the organization. That is the thing makes massive impact on my sales. Because Sainsbury sees the reduction to reduce the coat as well by using less trucks by using packing and obviously, we are spending less money as well and making the product cheaper.

Are there any challenges to accept circular approach?

I guess for myself it doesn't necessarily know what is possible. That's not something I have been trained or probably I should know. The big barrier from my understanding is what is possible or what not possible. So actually, training of circular supply chain ma will be valuable.

I think definitely good business practice so not only it's the right thing to do economy sorry environment world's sustainability point of view. It is actually a good business practice which I did not realise. I have been out in commercial world for 3 years part of this job. And see here it's one the top 5 things of my customer's agenda. Its thinkable in next 5 years. I guess it very much important for customers front of my commercial world now thinking about the circular supply chain management.

Are there any management related barriers?

It is the culprit. One of them would be it takes a lot of time so I would have the results available. So, at the moment, I know what I am saying is important for Sainsburys, but I would really help If I haven't got the time to manage it. Can add on results are definitely one thing upscaling going back to the training, Fortunately, I have work somebody who has worked for 20 years in the company knows about a lot about packaging and how we can reduce packaging. And I don't. If he wasn't around and guide me this could be the missed opportunity. So that sort of answer you were looking for.

What are your views about cultural aspect in the companies to apply circular economy change?

I think it comes very much from the top. Kerry as a company have it a net zero by, I think 2030, umm without that kind of culture if my company did not care about sustainability I would have no support working on these projects I think. Having a support from this company, if my manager comes back to me that he does not care about sustainability then actually I will be only thinking about sales number.

What do you think about consumer culture, are there hindrance factors related to consumers?

It is becoming more and more important. I guess in particularly young generation have been brought up. We been talking about the sustainability environmental issues for 30-40 years now.

For younger generation its natural they want to know about what you are doing for less impact on about environment. As consumers, they want Kerry as a company believe to protect the environment and believe in not wasting and not producing waste.

Structure is imp because I need support to do this thing. Like I say if I don't necessarily have the time or the knowledge. Without the company structure behind me and having experts in these areas I would not have plans to do that. Structure is vital. So, for example I have to be a ...do you know the phrase Jack-able phrase. I have to understand a little bit about 100s of areas. But I don't have the specialist knowledge to work further and deeper in the supply chain. I will facilitate the conversation, but I would need an expert which the structure would provide and actually to implement anything.

Does government play a part?

They do play part. I don't think gov is doing enough towards sustainability. Definitely, they could penalise unsustainable companies and they could reward sustainable companies. And I don't think they are doing enough. They need to make much more sustainable policies on governmental level.

What are the possibilities to implement circular supply chain management approach?

I guess all of the things like orderings so ensure they are ordering right amount of the products not wasting it So If they know they are selling 100 a day order 500 /100 a day. also, there is other things in working in conjunction with like for example if they know so ... If I give you an example like we are working on sustainable non-plastic packaging. But actually it is going to be quite bit more expansive but retailer is going to support it as they know with is right thing to do. That's what their customers want. So that's how the retailer will support it.

As an intermediary between manufacture and retailers what challenges you face?

One thing will help us if they give us longer lead time on orders. At the moment we order on Monday to deliver it on Wednesday. One of the things that does is we are literally we produce the products before even they ordered it. If they give us longer lead time than we can just cook it on time because that will reduce the waste. It would also enable us to plan the vehicle utilization

better. So longer lead time will really help us in reducing waste and utilisation our sort of fleet of vehicles.

Which factor directly affect your role for circular economy?

The biggest barriers are structure. Now, I don't have time, I would like to dedicate to sustainability personally. So, structure is a biggest barrier.

MP (Business Development Manager – 58 minutes)

Can you please give a brief introduction about your company?

Biogen is a company so been kind of active UK since about 2007-2008. So, we started as just a single AD taken in food waste and recycling it for green energy. Basically, for the first couple of years we were building so we have 7 of our plants and a couple of years ago I think it was 2017 we've purchased by a company called and Carla partners basically their pensions investors so they have we like their kind of parable digestion fraction of their kind of investment portfolio they also they also have investments in kind of wind solar so lots of different kind of green infrastructures which they invest in. From there we've been gone round and basically bull size across the UK. So now we have 14 AD plants. And we have been recycling about 350000 tons food waste annually. We also have section of business called composting, so we also have 4 composting sites, which has taken in a green waste in garden and that sort of things. In terms of the customers, we deal with then obviously we deal with food manufacturing, food retailers, food distribution companies, local authorities are taking in the household food waste. Then Obviously we are taking three grounds which is hospitality, you know like restaurants and things like that so they're kind of the four main sectors, where we would source waste from. Basically, we go around or see these customers and we find solutions for their food waste whether you know whether it's implementing like what we've done at noon with the doe lab system the sites have the go labs it's collected and then we take it back to the site and we process to it that way Basically, we put trailers on site or skips. We just want to provide the right solution for the customer. I just got to making sure that we can provide cut the levels of customer service that they're looking for.

I guess kind of any barriers blockers that we see I mean certainly over the past year one of the issues we've seen is obviously not being able to go around sites kind of not able go around the sites because of Covid- 19. So, we have kind of gap what we do in terms of a lot with Team. We have obviously done the video conferencing and basically getting Of the material or the sites so yes, we haven't been able to do remotely. In terms of issues or barriers in most of the food companies now will recycle their food waste. obviously, it isn't a separate food waste kind of collection from the site it's going in the general waste and then once you take out the food from your general waste you know you're decreasing your costs massively there because food is

probably the heaviest thing you could put into general waste. Rights of landfill and things like that it could be a real kind of cost benefit to the business just by separating out the food waste.

What is circular supply chain management? Is it a business model, environmental strategy, or sustainability strategy?

I would probably say it's a bit of a combination of all of them. Obviously, we benefit the business in terms of, we offer the cost saving, it's the green way of disposing the waste, it gives them a bit of CSR in the terms of saying look, what we do with it. They not going to be contributing towards, unnecessary emissions of greenhouse gases. We collect them ... when it was the case that it was going to the landfill, it will be taken to landfill site and we will be releasing methane in the atmosphere which will obviously. the greenhouse gasses. With this process, you know, we are benefiting the environment because we must not methane which will otherwise just be wasted it into a process and then we capture the methane and put it back into the national grid to produce green energy. That's one part of kind of circular economy. Additionally, we also advise the customers you are sending the food kind of full circle because its start most of its going to be starting to our farms and basically the biproduct of our process is a digestate or biofertilizer. So, that will obviously then be put back onto the local ground around, where the areas we service. And its s going full circle, like it's gone back onto the land and it's going to help to grow further crops which will then eventually turn into food and then if any of that, so it is then wasted yeah come background.

Looking at the current scenario, is it achievable?

In terms of kind of food so you know I'll recycling rate is about the kind of 95% mark. so basically, with a lot of customers that we do deal with there will be a kind of an element of packaging within some of that place because we are taking it from retailers' people that. Obviously it's not a practical approach or somebody to be their kind of emptying out packets of stuff and sending. To the front end of a process, we have a D-packaging machine which basically kind of threats the material up since the packaging will be out and then we will be left with the organic matter which is then taken stank. So, from zero to waste customers, we will send that to energy from waste and there we have 100 percent recycling rate because nothing is going to landfill.

We have environmental policy and things like that in place, I don't think it is confined in numbers or targets and things like that. We always try to do or make sure that we always try to do right or ... dispose really. We are very game in the terms of processes, producing a lot a lot of energy, which is fitted back into the national grid. I am not 100 % sure that if there any quantifiable numbers which has been put on these things. But your big part of our visions and values be trusted, be bold and those kinds of things. It is doing right thing and making our customers to put right things on place practically as well

What we call household waste is as well so how is it possible to after the you know example consumption stage off their products is it viable

I think it's good to have a target to go towards in terms of trying to get to zero waste what we find you know with these local authorities that are tipping a lot of you know a lot of households still don't recycle their food waste whether it's a case of you know they decide they don't want to and they rather put it in the normal bin or people have logistical issues in the terms of like high rise flats and things like the. So, I think it reasonable to try towards that. But the practical side of this is, like things like buying the ... sort of stuff, people are just lazy and not thinking about bit of sorting the bins, so I think, that going to be bit of issue. So, awareness should be there, so we start awareness process we might start getting 100% mark. I hope, it's going to be generation progress, a lot more awareness is there now, especially things like social media, Netflix and all kind of stuff are starting to focus on approaching the subject.

The awareness and hopefully everybody kind of takes unbolted and that's something that we all need to work well together on really

Are there any technology related barriers or challenges?

we've been in the market since about column to 2005 2006 mark when business kind of a this, was just an idea to begin with and then we went out and started building sites and so all of our sites are kind of tailored to kind of what we call the 'Biogen Way' so basically you know all of these sites you know we can take a guide for once I'm putting another site he will know exactly how they work it so you know we offer in terms of so especially with kind of customers one of our big selling points is you know we never going to turn waste away because we've got issues on site we were multi-site so you know what I scenario we can just pick away stuff move it elsewhere. I think

the main a part for us is it's all kind of our own technology, we are using, we understand it very well. we've been doing it from a very-very long time. We know various kinds of food wastes, we know that that the mix of food waste that we need to get, and we've got a lot of experienced people in the business working from beginning and that becomes part of the business, been working for long time. Just making sure that from employer to all the employees driving towards the same kind of goals. Biogen been the most successful AD business around there. We frequently get the customers move away because of the price and then you know the service just doesn't follow so then they come back and say could you go back and help us out but I think the customer service plays a massive part lots of people are looking at costs with pinch and bit to save and that obviously that is push gate fees down in terms of what we are going to charge for the service but Biogen has composition we've got you know plenty of good long standing customer relationships there.

What are the economic and finance related barriers come on the way for accepting a circular approach for businesses?

I guess in terms of financial it would that will be for the customers that we are approaching you know is that the economic factors they will be looking to be honest. I think there's very minimal in terms of that, it would specially start and upper we work with a network of all year, so you know in terms of trailers skips we rarely charge for that. Unless there a lot longer than you know the alternative disposals which could either be you know sending it for incineration or landfill and so I don't really think you know in terms of kind of separate food waste it's a no brainer really because you know it's quite heavy part of their phones which is cool too but the Wolf content which is you know it's it's a lot of weight yeah so I don't really think there is many kind of economic barriers in the way I think the most barriers that you would be gonna come across is you know humans at the end of the day it could just be you know some people just see a Skipton just thought in there so you know it's getting buy in from you know that the customer and you know kind of the map thing that put in place really.

Do you think management becomes a barrier to bring the circular approach in food supply chain or specifically from recycling point of view?

No, I wouldn't say so. Sometimes that could be slightly funny about it but at the end of the day, a lot of companies I say you know probably most food manufacturers or people like that are already separating out the food waste so we do not really see management issue as at the end of the day that they will be asked to keep the cost down.

What role the cultural factors play?

Culture is a big factor in there, you come across the company like Noon, they know the right thing to do with the food waste and the material we are seeking from them we get in the good clean quality, I think it comes from the managers are supervising the guys who are filling the bins outside, I think it is very important. Certainly, we see a lot of people wanting to do the right things because you now, at the end of the it gets out massive food manufacturers .. everything to the landfill. The back press of that business probably generates for that business probably quite high. So I think they ..to know, if this is not the case the person and the management is not passionate about doing the right thing so there is benefit for doing just been seen doing the right thing.

And what are views about customer culture?

As I said earlier, certainly there is big buyer from the people to buy more sustainable products. Obviously, the more focus is on plastic, the containers which the food comes in and there is a bit of balance between... When you go for shopping, you buy your food, you want it should be in the good state, not bruised, damaged anything like that there is bit of balance between packaging in the right material. When it transported, Its still in a good state because we will .. you do care about the quality, don't you? So it's kind to making right balance from packing, transported in a right way, then also making sure that it is kept fresh for as long as possible, because otherwise it will Place and more likely to be wasted then.

But then also in terms of kind of consumer, everybody's a lot more aware of conifer plastics in terms of you know how easy is it to recycle? Can we just chuck it? There's definitely a lot more awareness. You almost want to go for 2 minimal packaging otherwise that sings on affect. The amount of food that is going to be wasted and because it's not transported as well,

Is structure of organisation a challenge? Or can there be structural related barriers?

I guess in terms of the structure every business is different in terms of kind of people. It depends, in terms of making the decisions really in terms of what's happening the way so. You know direct

to board level, those kinds of things. It would be more SAC about team managers. I guess the closer to the other people that are actually gonna put in the bins is probably you probably gonna get better buying and then you know if it's you know a company director. So it also comes in playing in terms of ,it depends on the size of the business. It could be the case you know, it's just a small family run business, in which case you would be speaking to director. Is it going to be easy to implement? Where, it's a big organisation, and it's going to be kind of 1 bloke. That's going to be tasked with right wasted under you. He is going go out and in the best deals for it. So, I structure will kind of glad of factor in the kind of, I think you know the buyer would normally be absolutely fine in terms of you know whether it's a director or manager. It's just a case of, you know these people being in place and you know having the buying in from everybody. So, I guess now it does also come down to kind of personal in terms of you know who's in charge of doing what kind of thing. You know, in terms of making sure that the right solution is put in place that helps with the buying. You know if it's if it's a complicated process in terms of you know, and it makes their job a bit harder to do something in terms of both in the food. You might not then get applying because it might be the guys are on the floor to say, if doing this, Costs couple of saving a couple of minutes so you know it's making sure that the right kind of processes are in place for the site to be doing the right thing. you know it's easy for the guys just to quickly do it into making it as easy as possible for you otherwise you might not get those buyers.

What is the role of government so far to help the industries to accept circularity?

In the terms of government and legislation by 2023 it is mandatory for the food coming from household have to have food recyclable and collection as an option. So that will be increasing tonnage on to the food waste and then another the food place or into kind of the anaerobic digestion market by 2023. Every local authority has to offer a separate food waste collection. So that will bring a lot of tiny genes to the market but so basically at the moment that is something that Wales and Scotland already do. This is insert kind of trickle down into businesses as well. So, in Scott any business that is creating you know more than a couple of kilogrammes of food waste a week in Scotland, Wales has to have a separate food waste collection. I think that's something that start you know that's very much been laid by you know government of these places so it will be coming to England by 2023, once the household local gate in. A lots of councils probably role that out to the local business as well to fill up the vehicles as much as they can. I think it plays a big part in,

it could be case job lots, it could be a fish and chips shop on the road, it does not throw huge amount on the road , but it is easier to chuck in the general waste. It's the government at the end of the day, so for example if you are producing may over 20 kg waste a week, you need separate that out, it durable with just a small bin. So that will play a massive part, in terms of smaller businesses.

Is current law adequate for bringing circular economy in the industries?

I don't think there is really anything in place which tells people what they can and can't do with the circular economy of things in terms of, making waste to be sent to the right place. If the business wants it to just go to the landfill, that's want they want to do. It's expensive. So, they can implement it like, put the landfill prices up, or landfill tax or stuff like that. That would push tonnage to the more sustainable ways of disposal. The things should be in place like legally you have to do this. There are always going to be some people, who will do the things which are easier, putting everything in one bin. They can sit with the waste management companies, they can go and show them, what the right things they will be doing, and the process should lay by us well.

In terms of the legislation, which are currently out now you have to make sure that a business has to make sure you're getting your rid of you are getting rid of waste in the right ways. You know you're not just giving it to somebody and then you know just there chuck it anyway. There are things in place to stop that, but there isn't anything in place to say you know you have to do the right thing with it. You have to send it to somebody with a licenced waste carrier and it's going somewhere with an environmental permit. So yeah, I guess if there's a bit more guidance whether there's just legislation like we just said they say, right any business that produces X amount of food waste, you have to recycle it. That will probably come, sometime a bit further down in line after 2023.

What is the contribution from the recycling stage only?

From the circular economy the main section it would cover environment side. We take the food waste, which would be releasing methane into the ozone layer. We are removing that in terms of within caption and making it a useful commodity, so it's them being fed back in engine which is fed from methane. And that then feeds back into the National Grid providing yeah electricity at the site. it's solely, the environment factor we are covering.

What can be the motivational factors for every recycling organisation or to apply the circular economy practises?

When AD was a new technology, the government used to provide subsidies for, basically they used to incentivise the for the business which go forward in it. So basically, what they are is all of the site that tied into terms called feed-a terrace which basically you get additional amount of money from the government for every kilowatt of electricity which is fed back into the National Grid. So, all of these sites which were built between that period when they were offering these is locked into those long-term agreements, but those sorts of incentives were removed a couple of years ago now, which then doesn't make it financially viable to build a AD plant.

So, I can only comment from an AD point of view of you because that's the only industry that I I've ever worked in, really. There was an incentive to build 1, without that incentive, it doesn't make financial sense to build an AD plant but saying that you know with the local authority or going to start collecting the food waste from the 2023 that will see bring, you know, a large proportion of tonnage into the market which they are potentially isn't going to be capacity for. So obviously the government is then, will need to introduce something like this. But if there's no way it's take it, or there's not sufficient space to be able accommodate all of it. What do you do with it then? So, I would assume you know, once they start to, you know rolled out, will they then say right? We need more AD plants. People can then start to go out and look at once again because it stacks up financially.

NB (Operations Project Manager – Interview duration 1 hr 10 minutes)

What are views about circular economy?

I think it is good introduction, I mean you are working on it. I think the people will benefit from it. As research goes out, people are talking more and more about, no doubt about that one. Yes, it is continuance improvement we are working on it trying and improve the efficiency. But then again as you said it's not one way it is two ways, and we are working with retailers but then again that is where the problem but never stops nowhere. I was going through, I mean there is some information on our website, I was looking in that – they are saying to focus around 63% waste and 37% waste is post-consumer even if we just contribute towards 37% that's more than enough but that is not entirely with the manufacturer, there are so many factors in it, I mean it starts right from the day the day we actually get the brief from the customer that this is what they want and of course you know that then they want to save money give, they will never give you the true figures. If the figures are inflated right from the beginning, just to save money & cheaper prices.

The price for 100 articles will be different to for 1 product. It will depend upon productive of course the price will be different if you obviously so that is there, I think the majority of this issue lies.

People who are in manufacturing they should take the initiative, talk about our company we generate food waste of course, majority of the time it is unavoidable. We do try wherever we can but there is much process involved. Again, we got oil waste. We are going it to companies who produced biodiesel out of it. 10- 12 % of our energy is renewable. We are contributing towards that. It is twofold government of course – they should give some incentive to do the industry as.

What is circular supply chain management to you?

I mean so far as, us as company as concern we are looking only at, I mean we are looking at the environment of course the marketplace workplace and centre community side off as well not only sustainability part. We are working towards it if I give you some numbers the numbers we discussed last year on our sustainability programme and our volume grew by almost 25% in the last five years at the same time we met our target of 20-22% of carbon reduction so that is what our target was and then of course so far as food based this concern are target is to reach 2 billion people so that it will gives added benefit of whatever surplus food we go the can actually get that

consumed and then at the same time the plan is to reduce intensity by about 15% and go with renewable energy 100% by 2025 and the landfill waste successful so far food waste is concerned, landfill waste to be halved by 2030 add these are the initiatives which we which we are working towards as supply chain emission operational admissions is 33% that is in line with the best climate accord objectives so that's what we're working towards and the good thing which I like personally like most is that our company actually decided on the group actually decided to plant 26,000 trees every year that is one per employee per year for next 10 years. I mean we are working the three countries and that's what the programme is so that will help a lot you know so this environment this concern, so these are single core safety equipment everything is covered in that. It is not only growing the business or growing the volume and not thinking about everything and anything else and we're working on the packaging at the same time, we have target to reduce plastic, Virgin plastic usage should be reduced young 25% reduction we are working on 10 to 15% for these coming years, Plastic waste - we want that to be reduced by 100% before 2050 so these are what we got as an objective for us at least as company.

We are working on packaging; it is very new concept. It is fully biodegradable. We are doing the trial. We are working with company with manufacture itself. We may be first in UK to introduce to the market in read meal sector. We are working very closely with those suppliers and manufacturer is based in Ireland and there is another based in US fairly new though they are not new to packaging industry, but they are very new to this idea. I mean it is so expensive at the moment but understandable because they are investing in new technology everything is going to be new for them and they don't know how the market is going to behave yeah it is expensive, but somebody has to bite the bullet to start with. The good thing is our retailers Waitrose, Morrison, Sainsbury's to a degree, they do want to work on plastic reduction as well. We have done lots of work in the recent years by reducing the plastic introducing recyclable plastic as well. But yes, there is a lot to do.

What are your views about technology? What role the technology play to bring these types of revolutionary changes? Would there be any technological barriers for companies?

It is financial more than technology, in my opinion I don't think his world lacks technology now if you know where there are so many new innovations, but it is the funding. These are the things I

think that that hinders these things most normal company. We are working energy efficient equipment's, our cooking vessels are actually steam and based on steam not on electric or otherwise gas .

There is only boiler that works and then they produce the steam and whole of our food is cooked on steam rather than an electric or otherwise on gas. Yes I mean we have all those things technology is there but it is who can actually invest in that technology and then keeping up with it is another challenge I mean if you have invested in something which is which is new to the business new to world now , in the year to come that's Gonna be old they will be something new on fast pace.

Do you think there are management barriers, to the circular supply chain to be implemented?

As I mentioned, our company have objectives in next 5 years are already set. That's what we have start working towards it from beginning of January onward. May be companies who are not thinking looking ahead and still want to work on the traditional way the way they have worked yeah I mean the world is changing so people do change and if they're not changing so that they will be left collecting what happened to Nokia yeah you know still did not next they were right on the top and then they vanish yeah that's true if his people are not in a going with the changing word at the same pace obviously the pace is another issue I don't think anybody or everybody can go with the best pace , world is changing yes maybe but not our management so far our management is concerned we are looking towards it based on those objectives . We have our KPI's for those objectives.

Yes true, finance is one the biggest.

Sometimes it is the technology and taste. That is that probably is dangerous at the barrier as well now if you're working on a on a specific cuisine and you must have certain flavours in it and then you can only get it if you cook it in a traditional way so that may probably push us back & stay with those methods. We did use in the past it was one of the Australian company and those who were working with is very good very good technology and you can save lot of water and lot of

energy but it is completely different system altogether. They were working with Fire expression systems and they're saying that with a bucket of water they can set the fire off in a hall like 25 X 25 sq meter. I mean so much is available at the moment word but then again when we trial with our product, it didn't work for us okay you lose all that taste from the product, it is so rigorous from stirring prospect, you lose everything in terms of taste.

Technology is not good for cooking food but we get looking at you know say will save us a lot of the same water so we may probably achieve our targets well before. Yes, I mean you have to have that I think the small manufacturers are so probably not that lucky so businesses and there they're working with the small farms and they're not getting to know as much as we probably get companies is worldwide and get to know more.

As we talked about consumer side culture, what are your views about company or organisation side of culture?

It is not entirely on manufacturers, yes manufacturers have responsibilities toward their employees & towards the consumers as well, but retailers should play their part.

I will give an example, so we are doing food for M & S which is on high end, and we do for Aldi those who are discounted so far ingredients are concerned we are not compromising on quality use you know obviously it's not the same quantity. I mean if Aldi wants us to produce, we will produce more water, then compared to coconut milk or cream or anything else from M & S.

But it M & S to tell their customer you know so why they or the end user products are expensive why their products are expensive. I mean we do declare nutritional values as per Govt. legislation. The information is there at the back of box but how many people go and reads it. If the retailers are fully engaged and their customers are aware that you also is there buying something for a Pound rather than £0.50 at ALDI is the difference but they're getting other getting for the value for money yeah fine if not then they will probably say no not by this all probably we will say – I will not buy this, I will buy it from discounter and then without knowing taste , without knowing the best without knowing the fact that voice is expensive that is the problem yeah awareness is a key.

As I mentioned in the beginning, when we are developing the products of course be able to help that and then it is going sell well on the basis of that we're going to put the demand to ask likes yeah and then that goes all the way to the farms or where it gets produced.

If it's not aligned is new product this is just imaginary numbers we work with but just to keep the customer happy we have buy those things and some of them have short shelf lives among longer shelf life so now you know some go to challenge on the as well so you can't buy in Kilos, you have to have Ton in here bringing it from wherever and those things get stuck so those challenges are there.

Can you shed a light on government side?

I mean food safety is around & it is fine. And if there is any legislation, we all need to follow it. It should not be to encouraging waste.

The government should work with all those technologies. They should encourage it for their own manufacturing. We are not lacking on talent. Somebody sent me the article , not sure whether it was on Facebook I mean somebody send it , okay everybody is just picking up the plastic and working recycling the plastic but then all these the bags of chips , there is silver lining inside because nobody is recycling that but there is a group of people in India who are actually collecting only that and there they are shredding it and from that shred their preparing so many beautiful things even the vanity bags with it is fully Hand crafted and then of course it's bit expensive and again the order of their utilising that.

It is not surprising, when you see the Rock Garden of Chandigarh, India. It is one of oldest example of upcycling. I did my Graduation from Punjab University, there was one young lad, he was senior to us. We saw him driving electric car in those days, I am talking 85-86 year. The Electric car was made by himself using shells whatever he had. But he didn't get no encouragement, nobody actually scored him not even the University imagine that you know 1984 -85 if you need develops something which was capable of taking four- five people are you know, and he I have seen it I'm not saying that heard from someone but I've seen it. The Govt. take an initiative & encourage people but if is not available to people then not everyone is lucky, funds or finance is available to them.

We used to have Soda factory in our town, and they use to serve the people fresh soda. If you need 24 bottles of sodas, they use to produce them there and then, not like stocking them. They had big machine at the back instantly. It was very very local to us, not going any fun far . I have seen people returning those empty bottles back and getting refilled.

I mean here living in developed countries, living local. Theses recycle bins were not available years ago, everything was landfill.

Are there any structural barriers?

When they say about structural – it depends how you are on your information technology.

We are not living in the world where getting the information is difficult, like last person was not even aware what first person is doing. As I said – we had this conference last year. We took session, one was for Europe, and one was for USA. I can understand some people may probably be not aware but hierarchy in each and every organisation should, they were engaged so they were invited. If for whatever the reason they were not there and they missed that is still available so they can take, ask for it. Yes of course it is a challenge hierarchy is structure is so long to change is so long and then the lot you know so and the messages getting lost in cancellations and then of course it is a challenge but the information technology available and all having wrought from home and the small industries again if they can't invest on that sort of structure turn of courses is difficult as well. This pandemic is set back to many industries, a lot could have been done. Because of this image probably be hindered all these months but I mean of course yes, I agree that yes fine it is a challenge.

I mean especially in our case in the food industry I think it is recycled, composed and the recovery of all those extracts whatever you can extract from refuse in terms of material or energy that is the most common I think should be for our industry working towards it yeah so well. Whatever consumer habits are, industrialist have to invest for that as well, so you make sure the people are engaged, people are aware and you know the last drop is used. Especially, Ok fine people are people are going after these deals and all those things I mean how much you waste that creates. I have seen people they just put this on promotion by one get one free & they can get 2 pizzas. There is only one person or two people just eating outside they only eat one and second one is dumped; they just bin it. So why to work on the deal, why can't they give discount. It saves their gas,

electricity, save on dough whatever, that all can be saved. Of course, it is the people are in business are responsible for those things.

Up to certain extent yes but manufacturing is fully dependent. We are end users to threaten on so many things, our manufacturing is total dependent on farming & on harvesting. I mean we are buying rice, salt, and other ingredients.

Yes challenges are there, we can work towards it but then again is not, I mean we can invest on technology we can make a balance so we can align our demand planning but again this is very difficult to say okay fine you need hundred articles and local produce 100, the waste is always there I would say yes I mean not that it is nothing we can do, there are so many things we can do but it is totally dependent so we had to work with we have to just make sure our customers satisfied before we supplying from all the way from their demand to service level. Service level we are providing, products reaching them. But certainly there are so many things, we are working towards like packaging, we have got our plastic reduction target in mind so that we have got food waste reduction in our mind, so we want to halves it by the years to come. There are challenges towards fresh food.

Food of course, I will give an example, what we use to have in the past, obviously it was stopped. Not sure whether the government stopped it or what happen to it, all that food whatever we had as surplus, we use to give it to piggery farms & you know there is no waste if the food gets baked.

We used to fill the drum with all that chicken, rice and these farmers use to come to us and then we use to give them that. They were happy, we are not charging them anything. They were coming and collecting at their own expense. There were hardly any waste in those days & that is where those government legislation & food safety came into. I don't think it was to do with quality or food safety.

We do the same thing in our homes as well. if you got something which was prepared yesterday, heat it and you eat it. But again, the code of practices we have from our customers, we can only keep that certain amount of time like 24 or 36hours, after that it is waste. Of course we are working on forecast and we are working on estimating figures, we have to produce & we have to supply them and then it you are producing that keeping in mind for the safe side, lets produce 100kilos instead of 98kilos and they orders 80 kilos, in wasting 20 kilos. If that is what they allow us, you have got that either you produce it with less shelf life and supply to local areas. You know we have many depots, hubs around London which can be reached in no time rather reaching Scotland. So,

we can supply them one day less shelf life. So that can be saved. Or code of practices says ok you can reheat and full shelf life is applicable but again that where legislation, code of practices , these retailer's practices comes in. So much technical aspects are around, it's nothing wrong in the food. It is safe, kept in controlled environment, if you just eliminate all those micro loads in it by reheating it and serving it to customers but we can't.

That what I said – manufacturing is dependent.

We have introduced so many new things, technically new things because of Europe. EU legislations are completely different to here. If you compare our legislation with USA's – I mean they are so relaxed. They are safe as well; I am not saying their foods are not safe. They are technically biz are not strict as compared to us. Taking example of dairy food, India can supply dairy food to USA not to UK. No one wants to play with people's life, it is food at the end of the day.

NR (R&D Packaging Lead – Interview duration 47 minutes)

What is your role in the company?

I look after the front-end packaging innovation and packaging sustainability. That is the development of infrastructure or sustainability systems that will allow us to be sustainable as much as possible we can and reach in the consumer goods area in that respect, that's what my role is.

What is circular supply chain management for you?

I will take is an economy strategy, obviously where few manufacturers, one of the large manufacturers in the UK, are taking it massive seriously. As I joined the company about five years ago, and we are working ever since and trying to climb all three of those things that you mentioned. It has been fully adopted by the leadership team in terms of something that we need to address. Start the wider business is implemented, a programme called there 'Beyond the Horizon' and which is a total sustainability strategy. However, within foods, whereby we put products in the front of consumer, we have developed Strategy. But it is imbedded totally within the business now. It is regarded as one of the key success points in the futuregoing forward now. It is built into the environmental strategy; it is built into the sustainability strategy it's done from an environmental perspective. So that way that it has been brought out around genuinely doing the right thing rather than performing any sort of greenwashing type activities whereby we trick the consumer level. I think all the work that we do is based in science based and data their spacing Wi-Fi analysis. This is based on trying to fundamentally find out what is the best packaging solution for example, we put in the market to reduce the impact as much as possibly we can.

Do you think circular economy is achievable in food industry?

Within certain application, it will certainly be achievable. From packaging perspective, creating a circular economy, probably one of the biggest We have for next five years. Addressing back, we try to create an infrastructure, were packaging we use get recycled, get recovered back to the packaging manufacturers and used back in packaging again. Where joining up with a foreign imminent space called the IGP, whereby all of the leading some companies across the world are going to try and tackle how we can create a circular economy for packaging consumption from the packaging perspective I think that there is a lot of effort behind it now. Potentially, there is a future

for it, any companies are working on it. when you look at products and food might still in linear but yes, from packaging perspective it is effective, yes.

Do you think there are challenges come on the way to apply circular approach in the food supply chains?

Yeah, there's money, and I think the biggest one at the moment that exists is around clarification of one of these is actually what we are trying to achieve. At the moment all the big business are on the way to work on their own agenda trying to make sure they are appearing to be, green as possible to consumers. Now actually doing what is genuinely. Like for example, I've just completed a study of plastic trays that we use. The board tray and actually a plastic tray comes out on top on 17 environmental and circular economy matrices. From all 17 matrix, it comes out on top, but we still got a perception the consumers hold plastic bags and board is right. That is my job and understanding is covered best thing we possibly do is to create circular economy services we use. But we are reusing it not using the virgin material. But that is not understood on the consumer level. So, first one will be using, digging the action challenges around consumers not understanding the implications or specific material or the implications of certain And, on the same time they are very passionate or angry about certain things. It might not necessarily be grounded in the fact or science but it's difficult to. It's an education piece which is really hard, and then the third piece which is challenges around the infrastructure does not exist at the moment. So, Yeah, when we put your stuff back in the bin away, its certain percentage of it is probably going to get recycled for those that drive. or people put wrong stuff in, or they don't know what to put in or they haven't put it in the recycling bin. All these things try to get the material back to supply manufacturers, I mean to the packaging those are the few barriers, I think.

What is technical part? Can there be technical barriers?

Closer start one of the great things about this movement is about a lot of people care a lot of people care about it putting energy behind start-ups. trying to create solutions that can improve circularity and environmental impact. I think Elon Musk as recently announced that he is putting 1,000,000 pounds in next 10 years to up solutions for circular, so there's a lot of support throughout the world, and people are trying to crack it. Technologies that might be didn't necessarily clear in my mind just yet, but I think they were on the brink of finding out what they could think.

Are finance related barriers? What? and how they affect the food manufacturers?

In reality, the intention now is that more sustainable solution sometimes can be more expensive. and that is simply a supply and demand issues. What we are trying to do with the retailers, we were working on a project for the moment, we were trying to push and promote over really sustainable packing solutions, but it can't be the 100% un-costed. The reason to be un-costed is no one is buying it right now, there is very little scale on it. We buy 300 million ready meal trays over here but we have already this volume shift this in new technology overnight that cost dropped in .. and then it came cost-effective but area and financially the factor is it takes 2-3 years to become cost effective. The cost of unsustainable solution continues to become cheaper because of materials etc. So, it's about taking a longer-term view and that's difficult when companies have targets based financial targets to meet without it. Yeah. Rather than you start taking as 12 months

But on the other side of the coin, what we have seen is that actually there's a lot of purchase intent at the consumer level when you can demonstrate on the pack, why thing you you're making is really good for the environment, now it has got recycled material, sustainable material make motion plastic .If you market it real well, it really does grab the attention On the congress side, if you do get the idea. Unilever or Protector and Gamble put on certain products like shampoo products they put brilliant branding on it like it has got recycled content and obviously grab the purchasing intent

Next aspect is management side, what do think about management related barriers?

Okay, yeah, I consider the way in your definition and management same as infrastructure so for these processes' infrastructure does not exist as of now, we are working with the company. I mean, I mean they are packaging manufacturers but they are also opening a recycling centre here in the UK so the packaging they put on the market then because they have to buy Virgin materials so they can either buy Virgin material and try to recover it according to recycling and they are creating a structure themselves to get out that material because it comes more economically viable as well as more sustainable. So, once we start getting companies like that, taking with decision to invest in the management and the infrastructure though to support these sorts of systems, it will start growing then. There are ample of examples of that happening, but still need more and more.

Is companies' existing culture a barrier?

Yeah, it is. because you can't start to educate consumers and people that are buying a product before you educate everyone within you. I can only look on the example of own business that I am working here there's support from the senior team in terms of trying to get that education peace out. I did a presentation yesterday with 11 number senior people talking about that exactly talking that sort of stuff. And it was creating that culture whereby an everyone in Kerry Foods this year for the first time ever I've got a sustainability goal in their targets for the year. So, when you create situations like that where everyone in the business. I'll get their targets around trying to improve technical infrastructure with in it. That actually does drive to create that kind of I think it is happening in Kerry Foods and everywhere else as well that the culture within it is very important.

Do you think business competition put a negative impact to accept circularity in food supply chains?

Yeah, I think I do think they are on. And again, I am going to link back at Kerry Foods I am trying to understand what all our competitors are doing, not only the food manufacturers but what globally businesses are doing, in the terms of creating circular economy, creating sustainability infrastructures. So we are trying to look into the market and understand to push the into the market countries and on the top of that we are the only company who makes. We make and products and sell to the supermarket or all other companies sell to the supermarket but one of our most important point trying to improve in the supermarket that we have sustainability agenda. Which kiosk products. Competition is really driving innovation.

Are there any structural barriers?

I think historically very much in. is barrier because looking at fore-hand functions most important function of any business is sales that part of business that drives on the money and make the money. They inspired by the margins and volumes one things. Margins are. cooperating more expensive solutions, that it's not gonna cost more. Historically, it would have been a barrier. So, I have been working in the packaging innovation for 15 years or more and in that time early in last 4 year when we have really-really interested in circular economy and sustainability. Before that because

consumers did care business did care... didn't care/ What has changed now is consumer's pressure, structures of the business have changed not. Again, looking at the Kerry

We have hired ...people in sustainability and he has team under him working on the global ... of sustainability, we have functional head of sustainability we got sites head on sustainability, we have sustainability team at Noon site now. The team ... drive that sort of things in industry and in the Noon the structure is improving.

What is your perception of government law and legislation?

Yeah, very much. If you look at the example 10 year ago Spain had ... recycling rate in all of the developed world. Legislation after legislation was changed to address that and they brought in taxes, and they brought in regulations, and they brought in infrastructure and recycling capabilities and put money into it. Glad the money that was coming from the charges and the season regulations and that is one of the best circular economies at the moment. So, if you rely on this course that will meet the competition will drive it might happen eventually over the years. But it really needs government incentives behind it to make it genuinely happen out sometime and And the problem within UK is. We are in Brexit from last 5 years, Brexit and then the covid so going back and back and nothing has really changed, Now requires a change into it.

Yeah, do you think if you consider UK law are the inadequate?

Yeah, I think they are so. So, we work with Rap and Deborah and number of different NGOs and government bodies, and family are they are doing it but it just comes back to the fact that they've just been to distract, increase, the focus is diverse. And the first thing that they're looking to do is the tax coming in next year for products that you put on the market that don't have 30% recycle content on it. So, they are trying to make people more use more recycled content and if don't you gonna to get charged for that charged. That's the beginning of the journey that comes in. When you realise, government side is taking up but again it's just the beginning

That's a good question I don't know I suppose. The first day around is increasing the recycle content, I take here, I take here, which is the perfect example. Deposit return scheme, where you buy a bottle of coke, instead of paying £1, you will £1.10 and when you bring the bottle back, you will get the 10 pence back. That is happening across the number of Europe in a number of different countries that creates instantly circular economy.

Similarly, the example of poly bags consumers mind, it's only a small barrier, its only 10p or whatever but it changed consumer's behaviour. These sorts of big initiative can happen and they can only happen at a government level. That would never have worked if just Sainsbury's would have started to do that. Across the board so you can only do it across the board if it is forced by the government. And if there is an environment minister for example, there should be environmental sustainability minister who makes to drive these sorts of things this.

What are biggest challenges for food industry in relation to bring circular economy approach and how?

Yes, the biggest one, we are on that actually is convenience. As soon as you make something difficult for someone, they vast majority of people in this country we get out, unfortunately they actually don't care, so if you put a barrier in front of someone.

Like our ready meal trays, we put into the bag, we have to rinse it, when we put into the recycling otherwise, they contamination. But certain people just them in the bin straight away. No can be bothered to do that, if you put a barrier in front of me, I am not intervening more if it taken up I can be levelled. As soon as you do that irrespective of people who say, they will show but generally the vast majority of people are lazy, and they don't care. If you put a barrier in front of someone you can.... happening and anything like that.

I just think probably, manufacturer, we are manufacturing a lot of ways and are manufacturing for a number of years like that. we I started bringing new material is more complex required procedure that additional sort of complexity can be sort of barrier at the production level.

Another barrier is, procurement the buying teams so their targets are keeping the customers... as much as we can and their targets are maintaining relationships with the existing suppliers and my job is quite opposite, my job is to bring more expensive and different suppliers that's kind of a barrier that they trying to go right opposite to where I am going .

Another barriers might be internal education so if the people within the business trying to understand the implication and why we doing something specific and they can get ... because they don't. want change because they don't consider it as benefit.

And also, another one barrier is Within u this market so in our business we are putting on the label which is dictated by the retailers so they have their own objectives sometime that will be very much disagree with it btu when ... manufacturers we have to do what they say even if I know.

What we initially thinks the best way to do it is we gonna find out, working with wider firms, wider community, through the ... through the councils, sustainable businesses, that includes recycling contractors

I am working in collaboration across the different kitchen businesses, rather than working isolate because that is how we drivable make changes. We need to bring . in the market that will be better put shift in the whole industry or to create he whole system like coffee cups or whatever it is may be, the way to tackle it may be through collaboration.

PG (Retailing manager Interview duration 1 hr 25 minutes)

What is your understanding about circular supply chain management?

I would say it is very good business model. If implemented properly, it can be a very good business model. Because you're tackling 2 problems at the same time. Because of which it is good for us. It's a good business model.

what sustainability and waste management goals you have in your company?

We have a constant strategy of think and shrink in our company. So, where we try implement or we try to reduce waste as much as we can on the grow. Okay, not like there's no particular Department or a particular process to be followed. It's like if you're walking around in the shop and you see that a customer picked up some frozen item and left it in the crisps isle or a grocery isle. you happened to walk past you pick it up. You pick that product from that and place it in the fridge or in the freezer immediately. Because, you know there is 20 minutes change for any product and frozen products if it is more than 20 minutes. It has to be wasted. if you happen to you pass by and see something that belongs to the frozen isle and when you pick it up and you see that it has been more than you put it in the bin or less than 20 minutes than you put it on the right place. That's not only for the product, also, if you're working in admin department when you're leaving. Make sure, put your computer on sleep mode, you Turn off the light, the heaters are turned off. So, these bits and pieces help. We need to implement that. And it's also on like it's not only limited to those energies and product is also on staff as well, if it's just one guy working in some other Department, that means actually needs two people, and there's another guy that sitting idle. We are supposed to go and help our staff. That area so that the work is like you finish the job in like in 15 minutes instead of half an hour and you knew you then got another stuff that you can utilise somewhere else. Maybe in checkout any car park. That's how we Create.

Thinking about sustainability or circular economy? Have you got some sort of unit targets related to sustainability or any goals in your department?

Morrison's working checkout go Department. We are also being informed by the management that we need to promote our food bank, the management team keeps on reminding us to ask

customers to make as many donations as they can, and the donations are not just limited to the product to buying products from Morison's. If you want to donate something extra in your house that they not using anymore, they can contact the head office and they can donate.

And as I'm talking about circular economy specifically, it focused on zero waste vision. So do you think it is approachable? Or achievable?

As an environment friendly person, I would want it to be achievable. How much how much ever I want it, but right now I don't think it is possible immediately. Because the companies do not have enough resources, they don't have a clear vision as of now. Where they want to go with that? So yes, they are trying to reduce the waste as much as much as they can. But there's a lot of barriers to it. Because of which I don't think it is achievable unless and until certain steps are taken. working with this company for last six years and I've been working in customer service Department like checkouts and customer service. I am a supervisor now why I started as a customer system, so I've been working with the customer Service Department for a long time. There's like there's no quibble guarantee there is like people if they, if they go home and they eat something they don't like it, even if they don't like it, they bring it back and they bring it back. The company returns their money, so there's no. There's no harm in that. Yes, it's a good service. Good customer service. Yeah, turn the money, yeah. But even full item. I have seen people coming back with half eaten piles. I've seen half of Chicken bringing back. Now it is common sense. Obviously as a retailer I'm not going to put that half-eaten pie on my isle. Because there are food health and safety standards, Yeah, yeah. I'm obviously going to waste it. Even though that individual is not wasting it directly. I am as retailer, wasting on his behalf. Ideally, if he has opened the packet, he shouldn't be bringing it back. some steps need to be taken from the company that OK, you don't take the food back to give them coupons. Right now, what is happening in my in my store. I've even seen in other stores, especially in the UK. Once a customer doesn't like it, he definitely going to bring that back even if its half-eaten bread. Half eating pizza half eaten bread- chicken. Yes, I've seen that and have loads and loads of waste every day. I see those things happening in my store and I tried to argue with my manager, but the company knows it. if the companies want to reduce their waste, they need to stop these things. Even right now, in the pandemic situation, I have people by product. I have seen customers returning the products. If they have not open that, it's fine, bring it back and give the money back. But the products on the reduced that going to go off today. People on the

next day, bring back as well. People need to change this mentality. People know that the retailers are going to give my money back. These trying to save their money. But at the end they are wasting these things as well. I believe, there are whole trade standard involved in it, government involved in it and then the retailers. If they all come together and say that we need to do something. If as retailer I say I am not going to take this back and customer will go the trader and say this retailer has not taken my product back. At the end and one was going to lose my licence if I'm trying to change the planet, I'm losing my licence and so why? Why me as retailers will do something like that. So here, there have to have some kind of protection for the retailers as well. If they want the retailer to reduce their waste. There needs to be some kind of protection for us. If there are things happening like half of how he can return half eaten pie. I have had half a carton of milk. I had it, it was good but had gone back and just because the expiry date is still valid. Me as a retailer and supposed to give them the refund. Obviously, I'm going to waste that milk. We have that facility to check the reasons and all. But our company law says first you give the money to the customer. Once you give the money back to the customer, our staff is not going to be bothered sending that carton of milk back to the head office and test it. There are lots of costs involved in transporting that much of product. There are 6 forms I need to fill just to send that that pint of milk back to the head office. No, I'm not going to do that. The staff do not have time, This thing would work if the customer has a problem ,the customer should send back milk to Morrison's head office. Then, the company will actually know how much damage is done, was the damage, and was the problem, and there will be definitely a reduction in the waste because they have their easy facilities because the competition just give it to the staff and start will do it for you there. They can't be bothered.

What other barriers you think come on the way? What other things you think does the technology play any part?

The competition is one of the biggest. I would say the competition between the retailers. The biggest barriers in reducing any kind of waste like you have a giant like Amazon entering. So Because Amazon is entering retail sector, an Amazon is a big company, and these retailer like Asda, Morrison's or Tesco, although there big, but they're not big enough like Amazon, Amazon. Yeah, at the moment. Only the only. The only way they can fight Amazon is by latterly by becoming flexible. If there 100% flexible now they have to be 200 percent flexible with the customer in order to compete with Amazon even you shop online, add shop on Amazon as well. there are no questions asked over there. If you don't like it, get the money back. If you don't want

it, you can just send it back even your shipping is free. So, in order to fight Amazon the retailers re definitely going to be more than what they right now .If they are going to be more flexible which means food waste is going to be more , increasing wastage. Like right now, Morrison's at have a tie up with amazon and Morrison's have tie up with Deliveroo as well. And the amount of orders on Amazon and Deliveroo, there hasI n certain stores, there's a separate Department completely Amazon staff is only picking up the stuff for Amazon on the shop floor. So, and then there's another staff for Deliveroo that keeps on picking stuff for Deliveroo and then the third staff pick up the stuff for Morrison for online delivery. The shelves are empty, are people actually consuming so much stuff? Onion, coriander, lemons, Will not last more than a week, Let's see 15 days. The number of fresh products that people keep on ordering from Amazon, whatever they can. It is huge, it is a lot. So, if the company, I don't know where they are going. The competition, I feel that the competition is one of the biggest barriers. For this waste. Companies do the talk about carbon footprint and all these thing, but to be honest nobody is working towards it. I mean they are, but whatever they're doing is not enough.

What are your views about companies' management it?

These things, they come top to bottom, that is a big problem. Because the people actually sitting in head office don't know what goes on in the shop. They need to come on the shop floor and I think everything in decision, should be tailor made according to that shop or that warehouse t that organisation and not universal. You can't say one size fits all. Not certainly, not in these days and age. Because during the lockdown, if I don't, If you notice there was a lockdown. Yes, there was a nationwide lockdown. Full weekend as well open and people were allowed to go in the shops and buy certain whatever things what happened is. But during the lockdown, I used to have 200 and 300 people waiting outside my shop, just to get in. There was no use on that lockdown. We were told that the number of people we can have in our shop because my shop is a big one, they said the maximum people need their 200 people you can have. But 200, how? Not just only one person from one house was not coming, the entire family was coming. Yes, 200 people but those 200 people never came alone. They came with their kids, their mother, the fathers. Because of this, there's a lot of people, So I believe that the company should have left it to the store manager to decide what should be done in store. Like one person in one out like that. You say 10 people together, then people together then people out. I feel that similarly if you are implementing some

kind of waste policy for your company you should analyse the amount of waste at certain or particular store is generating. Depending on that there should sub-divided policy to reduce the waste they are producing. For the simple reason, there might be a bit the amount of waste in that store must be high because they don't have staff. There are not enough people to manage, to put the things back that were left by the customer. You see people, they pick up whatever they see. When they come on the till, they leave half of the shopping bag. That shopping has product that has been taken out from the fridge, maybe two and maybe an hour ago. So, by the time you reach this, its's waste. So, you see it as a floor manager I would have had enough stuff. I would immediately take that product and put it in the fridge. That way you reduce waste, the company doesn't lose money. Everybody is happy. So, I think that they should be tailor made policies especially regarding certain things for the stores not top to bottom, I, I believe it's kind of outdated right now. Because we are not living in a normal world anymore.

What is your perception economic and finance related barriers come on the way to accepting the circular approach?

I think people who keep on keep track of these, you know, return policies, it is general perception that most of the times the people who don't earn enough do all these. To be frank, It's not just those kind of people, there are people from well to do families, even they take good advantage of these kind of policies. Its again the government can give subsidies to the to the companies for reducing their waste companies, some kind of incentives. Like some fruits and vegetable can be used as a manoeuvre by farmers. You don't need artificial fertilisers all the time. You can use this as manoeuvres for the fertilizers. So if the company give wasted food back to the farmers and depending on how much they doing, the government can actually give some kind of incentives to the to both the farmers for taking it and the companies, retailers for giving them. That would you know motivate companies to do these things and they are a lot of food that can be used as fertilizers. Not only fertilizers, but there are also a lot of products that can be used as substitute to lot of things. Nowadays, I see a lot of bamboo containers in my shop people use bamboo product instead of plastic, so Bamboo is a product, it can be reused again and again. the biggest barrier in those products is the price. So, the government can pic it from over here. And they can subsidise these products. So that the cost of these products goes low. People are motivated to use that not just the people who come from a poor background but the people from good economic background, can

also be motivated. Even these products break, there is no harm. And like, when they taking a waste like for recycle, we have different bins for recycle maybe a separate bin can be made for these products. So, they straight away go to be recycled and not get mixed up in the normal recycle bin. So, companies can be some kind of incentivised, or the government can introduce some kind of subsidies for companies to use the sustainable products in their manufacturing more. So, because you see, when we think about sustainability, we straight away think about retailer's role. But what is the government doing to motivate those retailers, they need some kind of motivation from the government as well. What is the government doing for them? I don't think they're doing anything as far as I know. For example, government in India is providing a lot of subsidies on electric cars. because of that There is a boom in India in manufacturers to go an electric so they are motivated. So, they are motivate although the infrastructure in India is not doesn't support enough electric cars right now, but there is a motivation. That is why a giant like Tesla is planning to move in India. So, you know they are, they are. They are motivating both the manufacturers and consumers go for electric by giving them subsidies. Depending on the cost of your car the government is subsidising the car, so the price goes low. So maybe something like that can be done in food sector or in retail sector to safe.

Does organisation's structure play an important part to bring circular approach in the supply chain, in the retailer organisations?

Right now, there is bias to directly contacting the producers or the suppliers on behalf of the organisation and then depending on it. We can actually think about it as the feedback that goes from the retail store to head office is then conveyed by the head office to the supply chain. Then supplier go looking for good looking for the product accordingly and based on that and the kind of products they get from there, they send back to the stores. Start, I believe that the organisation can make a kind of separate division within those buyers, whose job will be just to hunt for the innovative producers. Who are actually doing something different than other producers and they can get the samples badge on those producers and place it in some of their stores to see how a these products are hitting the market? Is there enough demand that is being cultivated rather than just the consumer giving the feedback to the retailer and then retailer pushing it forward? Retailers themselves can actually have a division within their organisation structure that these are some products that are quite innovative and quite different, are environment friendly and they hit our

target of reducing the waste. They also help us in reaching lap. I would say a little bit of proactiveness on the part of retailers within their supply chain. I think that a little bit of change in their structure, in the way they functioning because they have been functioning for a very long time. So, I think in order to change something like Amazon has it. Amazon doesn't go anywhere they've opened a platform for everybody. As retailer as you as a retailer or me as a retailer can register myself as a manufacturer, I can register myself on Amazon's on platform and sell my goods. Similarly, the retailers can expand their horizon, have a separate division that can just go hunting for these kinds of different small retailers or manufacturers who are doing something new and can provide the platform in their shop. Maybe we can have a separate isle. We have a big isle for cereals and so why can't we have a small isle for sustainable products, environment friendly products can be show cased there. So, I think help the environment help small retailer and small manufacturers who may be who will earn some extra money. And if the product is good itself, obviously the supply and demand can be increased or whatever you know the normal range? Will get something new, don't know. These things can help us.

Do you think companies' culture can be a barrier to the organisation bringing this circular economy?

As you know change is always met with the negativity first. In the beginning no everyone will reacts to the change in same way. Because these things have been running for a long time, and then there's so much step in their own way that will that company or any organisation has to freaking according to that culture. The company doesn't say individual needs has to change the according to the company's culture. So obviously when these are things have been running for a long time. They are barriers, but then it again comes to the company's management. How much they want to change. what do you want to change? They will definitely change it. Like right now, plastic bags or the bag for life that they are selling. When I started with my company, those bags were of 10p. From 10p, they decided to increase the price of those bags to 20p, and they completely chuck 5 Pence bag that they were selling, which used to be free when I joined the company. So, from free to they went to 20 Pence and decided to ditch that. Yes, good move, but on the same time they increased the 10p bag to 20p and then 30 pence and right now I'm selling those bags at 50 Pence The same bag, same quality, everything same. If a company can decide they want to sell the bag that they actually used to sell for 10 pence to 50 pence. Then, the Company can definitely

become autocratic and actually pay for good, so it's just about the perspective and how much you want to change and what you want to change. Since I'm working with this company, I have seen a lot of changes in them. It's not just this company, the entire retail sector. Although I don't know much about other companies like Tesco and all but yes, the free plastic bags they used to give for the meat. They stop doing it, there are lot of changes. As I said 'Think-Shrink' is a kind of a motto of our company. So, the staff are constantly reminded they need to think about saving more than what we have. And even the top management is always on a on a constant round across the shop. So, as a duty manager, they're supposed to be collecting all the goods time to time. So, there's quite a lot of things, yes, but I've seen somewhere or the other. Shortage of staff is also one of the biggest barriers that for the the management in the stores. this is quite a big problem because of not having enough staff, they can't do any extra things. I wouldn't say extra they call it extra, but I wouldn't say extra. So they just getting the deliveries in store and emptying the lorries, they're not able to manage the waste to be wasted because they don't have enough staff. If retail companies are keen on cutting down on waste. They will have to invest extra in staff. In order to improve their performance. At least for a while and improve and see how much staff you actually need, in order to get everything done, So that maybe you know things can be done in a better way in usual.

What is role of consumer side culture, in the food industry.

The consumers actually have a huge role to play in this. They have to be taught in way so that message can go to them that they need to change. Because some consumers over here are horrible. They are very pampered, and they have been very spoiled for choices. If they don't like something they will change. I think this is good as consumer right , yes it is good. There has to be some kind of close measures to it and has to be some kind of treatment to it that they can't just be throwing food away because they don't like it. Because I'm sure you are aware, UK is one of countries where food waste is the most. So, I fell that the consumers here need to get this message. They can't just eat so much of food because they just buy whatever they see, even if they don't need it. I have people in my shop who come every week in my shop, and they buy the same things again and again in bulk quantities. I don't know what they do, I don't know. Do they actually consume that much, no? Just buy it because it's because it's on offer because it's free. I would like to add here, buying power as well. In some western countries have more buying power than so called Third World Countries, the people in those countries don't have that much buying power. But the people

here have it and they are misusing their buying power. If they think retailers are exploiting. Retailers need to stop giving unnecessary refunds. They need to start regulating. And It's not going to be one store or one retailer or one branch, it has to be across the world. Where they say we going to stop doing this. We are stop giving free discounts, free coupons, to the people who are refunding things. If you buy you it, you buy it, you don't like it, that's not my problem. Consumer has to be educated by the retailers. No one else can do that. Government can't go knocking on every single door at ask, oh stop buying unnecessary food, No. The retailers have to take this step but yes, what government can do is to back the retailers. The government needs to back to retailers. Because. It's painful to see so much of food wasted every day in the store. So much of goods wasted. I'm sure you see those kinds of people who walk on the high streets with labels on their clothes because they are going wear it for one party or a party or two. And they're going to go back and say they did not like it. Because obviously they know they will get the money back and no questions are asked. But retailers are not going to put those clothes back on store on their shelves, because obviously they've been worn. Everybody knows that it's an open secret. So, companies need to stop doing that.

How can the technology be a challenge or driver?

We can use it to our benefit, the scan and go. We can go beyond that, take a step further. Like the consumers can just do it from home instead of scanning products physically. And, just pick up the products in the basket. We can have a drive through kind of thing. Like McDonald's have it. The shopping will be packed into the shop, there will be a collection window. You can pick up your basket and go home rather driving around in the shop and taking product that we don't need and then leaving the fridge product in a grocery isle. There was a lot of progress going on in that direction, but all of a sudden because of this pandemic, it just stopped everything just stopped. So, I feel that they can only work on that. It will be good for the both the companies and the consumers, because that way the amount of waste will be next to zero. And the staff inside your store can just focus on picking the stuff and packing it and just putting in the car rather than getting stressed all the time. If you see there is a lot of stress involved this job. because the people are not always helpful towards the staff, they don't talk to the staff very nicely all the time. So, it will reduce the mental stress as well for the staff. They can turn the entire shop into a warehouse. Just Park the cars in the bay, pick and go.

Any other thing you would like to discuss?

I said earlier that its more towards the consumers. If the consumers demand retailers have to do it. It comes down to the consumers what they want? It's understandable that you know we are focusing more on personalised retailers to do this to do that. Actually, I feel it actually is vice versa. If the consumer demands, the retailer has to provide it. If the consumer is not demanding it, the retailers think that it's still not the time for it. We all know that change is coming. Yes, it is coming. The focus is shifting towards all these things but I have seen that if consumers start saying that we don't want plastic. I tell you when we stopped giving people those plastic bags for their meat. There were fights, there were people abusing my staff because the staff would not give them the plastic bag for free. And they will say, Oh no. How can I pack? How can I carry my meat? And because I was, I was new to the country and industry back then and I was like. What are you talking about? I've never seen people carrying their meat separately. I mean, if its covered by butcher in pharmacol container and wrapped with cling film, got a label and everything but the consumers, the customers were clearly fighting with my staff. I was like what is he on about? So, even though or store has implemented it because there were a lot of complaints, they had to re-introduce those plastic bags, small plastic bags again, all just for the meat. So, you see we always blame the retailer, agree, but it is actually the consumer, the customer. Customer is God. If the customer doesn't ask for it, they are not going to get it. The people need to be aware about it. How are they going to get aware about it? Maybe government can run the campaigns. Like the polios and all that. Like they are right now they are running for Covid-19 and all that. Why not do for the environment. I mean they have it but they all silent, they are not as open. If there's a World Cup tomorrow here, they'll be running another campaign for God knows for how many days. If there is football league, they will be running for months and months. So, they are wasting so much money in those campaigns, why not here? Maybe they can do it in their movies, you know, because the movies have a big soft power, they can do that. But it's a problem that because the consumers are not asking for it. No one is actually serious about it. If the consumer start asking for it? Everyone will be serious about it and they will actually do something about it because right now I the least bothered are the customers. There is small difference of 23p in the milk we sell, is the same milk no difference, one is 23p extra for farmers. Let's see if human cost £1.10. This, 'for farmers' milk will cost you £1.33p. They both are placed next to each other. One says plain 'milk' and the other say and 'for

farmers. It happens 'N' number of times because they are kept next to each other in identical containers. People take that by mistake, and they bring it to the checkout and when they see the same amount of milk says 1.10p over there, is charged for 1.33p. They don't want to pay 23 Pence extra. And they simply say, oh I don't want it. Now, the problem with that is there is no harm in leaving this back. Obviously, you look after your money, that's fine, but She or he has come in the shop at the first thing they picked up in the milk, they are coming around the shop for let's say 45 minutes at least. In that 45 minute, the chain of 20 minutes is broken. The product cannot go back on the shelf because it's gone off. To be honest, I have never seen milk going bad within 20 minutes. I've never seen it. But the government say more than 20 minutes can't go back on the shelf. So what my staff going to do is, my staff is going to pick it up, put it in the waste, in the chiller waste. So, that's for 23p the whole 4 pints of milk gets wasted. It happens 'N' number of times, I can't even count it. Every 4th customer does that mistake. So, now if I'm on my shift, what I would say just change the price and give it for 1.10p instead of wasting that milk. If it was down to me, I would do that. I wouldn't waste the milk because the farmer doesn't get 23p extra, but that milk is not wasted. There's a lot of factors in this thing. People, when they're picking up the product, they don't read about it. They are so used to of going a particular shop every day. It's kind of like a routine. You know that these things are going to be kept here, the milk is going to be here, breads are going to be here so they just follow the route and just them up. But sometimes read it, sometimes not. If they read it, they not going to pick it up, obviously. Most of the time they don't read about it what it says. I have a customer, who's been coming in the shop for like 6 years, one day she picked up by mistake. She was like have the prices gone up? I said, No, this is the milk for farmers and she said what do you mean? the farmers going drink this milk now. I said no, every time you buy this milk 23p that we charge you extra, go back to the farmers straightway. She said, I'm so sorry I can't be bothered about the farmers, I've got my own kids to look after. She can't see her going to do that. So, what happened is, doesn't matter if she cares about the farmer or not, but that milk is wasted now. She thinks she can't give 23p extra to the farmers, but no one got anything the milk is wasted. So, way or another Morrison's is doing a mistake with that thing. Straightway, like you know you keep one flat price and why not just give the money direct into that farmer without advertising it. Because they want to advertise it, there's so much of wastage, just for their advertisement. Consumerism, yes, it is good, but it has problems as well. Maybe

consumers are not ready for it. Or maybe they're ready, but they just can't be bothered. Yes, because they have family to feed as well.

PJ (Demand Planner- Interview duration 1hr)

What is your role in the company?

I am a demand planner for four of our sites and that is for short-, mid- and long-term demand planning and I have been with this company for 11 years and on this role for 9 years.

What is Circular supply Chain management to you?

So, yea it is a sustainability strategy within the business also it has grown up as vision about the broader business. It is something we get regular updates as well in the term of approach but as our section of that business will be, um one the biggest challenges around that how we are umm. so, we make on-label products as you know so we are answerable to the retailers. And waste and availability are keys to the retailers as we are holding to them, they get to be . to us currently. We do work collaborate with them, we answer to them and wate at retail level certainly have higher value or measured at higher value. Then is supply, we do work together to minimise the retailer waste and supply waste as well, but it is also currently, inherit in manufacturer and supply chain and retail. For manufacturer obviously the waste is inherited in batch sizes. With this constant risk, from the manufacturing side, we never gonna get support from retailer from that perspective, not in the current world, or certainly not. How they will support us without our pushing supply chains. We produce according to our efficiencies and they take what available on agreed week or whatever. The of our product is also big part of manufacturer, at supply chain and level and obviously more so the life of our ingredients. So at the raw material stag there is not a lot to play with and it is a risk on the supply chain level as well. As an example, the Brexit is putting a pressure on life of chicken. It is coming in from Europe so currently we receive a day less what we normally have and certainty taking a day less of factory life of material. So then umm. supply chain obviously, it's more to do with damage. Beyond material at site and retailer as well its its inability to sell a short life product. As you can see with the pressure on each stage it is very hard to see how we can eliminate it. But also, it does produce the argument, why should we work together in order to try.

Is application of circular supply chain possible in food industries?

Unfortunately, In terms of plastic wastage, umm that's the only I think um part of that supply chain so what is left us, the only thing that could be recycled with the current technology um, would be

plastics and I would say there are technical reasons why we could not pick it up because at the stage plastic .. to change it, so I don't know if we can use it, but it possibly could be recycled and hopefully by the retailers I don't know. In terms of food which has so many restrictions on that to do anything with this. However, retail have there on solutions on sustainability and reduction of food waste. Which I hope involve using that for farms but in .. packing to our supply chain.

How do you work with the business model related to supply chain?

I don't personally, Umm My role in the business is basically and I am you know what my role generates part of the non-sustainability. The aim of my role is to reduce it but its umm but the pressure from within the market. I mean this last year has been incredibly difficult to get the accuracy which we like to have it. Accuracy um accuracy in terms of planning is probably the greatest measure in terms of waste reduction and efficiency to umm to the carbon reduction. So I personally do not involved in any project related to sustainability not to save it , one way or another to food target.

What part technology play to bring circular economy transition?

So um. it's an interesting question because the technology does exist to potentially improve this and that would be either through pasteurisation or another similar method umm for extending the life of products, reducing bacteria. Umm there has been I mean we produce the.. meals in the past unfortunately its determinantal to the fresh qualities of the product and it's not popular in highly-highly competitive market. I would also add If we were successful in creating fresh nutrition meals umm via pasteurisation or retort which was palatable um and good on the eye or accepted by change by the time actually all of that change wouldn't go first and foremost go in the change of sustainability with the profit, partly go with waste reduction and all but I think profit would prevent it for ever reaching sustainability goals. And that's right, the way across the supply chain starting at retail, I think.

And what do you think, if there is any business with who want to invest in the? In in a new chain, or maybe your business, they start thinking about investing in a new chain of. Often and only about the circular products. Do you think I would that stretch strategy be viable, or would there be any economic or financial barriers there?

I think they would in time, but not currently. Now we are seeing changing market forces and certainly in the last two years if we take code out of the equation. Yeah, there's been a definite sustained trend towards more environmentally friendly ways of eating. And that's coming from a younger demographic, so fish vegan in particular. Really big increase which is hard to miss in the supermarkets. People have turned their back on that a little and and healthy foods during COVID, but I think that's understandable and more source biological then than anything else. Yeah, so I think as as that as that demographic matures. And another generation grows up beneath them, and I think there will be more and more hunger, more appetite for sustainability within the food supply chain, and to know that what you're eating is good for the world, but at present, probably not..

What part finance an economic? Playing that I understood yes, the trends are changing nowadays as you explained very well. The with example of vegan products. How economic and financial type of challenges affect an organisation or a business to to take the risk to invest in these sustainable types of products?

Yeah, that's a really important question. But I think he almost certainly unless there are government packages to support that I think the risk would be too great for foreseeable future. knowing that we're going into a whole new economic landscape as we come out of COVID, it's only going to get harder. Umm So it really does depend that change in consumer behaviour and I think put the retailers to promote it and encourage it and get behind it and appetise behind it. So um.. I wouldn't say that it can't be done but finance side would be a real struggle to have that happen.

What is your view about management?

Umm I think pressures on the management probably make somebody less the priority even that's unfair. Our company within it holds a lot of entrepreneurs a lot of visionaries. This is the nature of the way how the business has grown is to check those people and there is lot of people go passionate about this subject. I think it's just, it's the pressure on us an industry um probably making it harder. Um That would be seen through management but it's not the management itself. I think we have taken risk; we have started taken risk in order to do that it an overarching vision and policy more and more policy rather than vision within the bigger company. So, it will only be promoted more and more.

What is perception about cultural aspect?

Um yes, although I think, the positive culture that I see in my business is shared most of the businesses as the realisation of the sustainability come to reality. Its um less probably less mature businesses start-up projects those are first 5-10 years, it's probably the lesser priority for them. As they grown as they sell the business the businesses on, they will also take this culture. I see discussion across the industry, so I don't think its difficulty for our company.

Would you like to add something about Consumer Culture?

Apparently, because that's obviously um That's where the product hands up, that's where the demand actually comes from. That's why it's not for the industry, it's the global problem, It's not for the world to wait for the consumer to want it. We have to make then catch up fast. So, the industry not to push the consumer but to argue the benefits.

Do you think there is lack of awareness in the consumer?

So, yea, constant review is the must to achieve it. Um I do think, it doesn't necessarily follow the having that regular review would help to make it any quicker. It's just we have to be, we have to be ready to take on the any stage of sustainability have the earliest opportunity. And we have to push for that to happen sooner. I also think there are a lot of external factors which are going to make it harder, certainly. Not to say all people delay it but it will. But it will we push hardener.

Would like to add something from structure side?

Umm Structure includes reporting and reporting means having target around. So, I agree, it is important, provided the targets are shared, the correct targets are shared across your business. Um I don't think its deciding the factors which would enforce the change. Um yes, yes, the structure which encourages us to meet the right goals. It's important its hard, it's hard to picture. But most business structures in these days are lean and that's required to be so and That means you are reporting up to less people and less noise to reporting structure which means more clarity on your targets.

Does the government or institution of a country help to make the circular economy a successful transition?

Yes 100 percent. Um, and I think it obvious, what sort of government we require to make it priority. Umm, there is swing on the wrong direction at the moment. There needs to be positive political side of it, but yea government is one hundred percent needs to be by example of it yea.

How current laws and regulations are affecting the economies or industries to adopt circularity transition?

Yea, am not, am not. Umm, from the government side of it there is a lot of focus on. If we take a very broad view, looking at decades rather than months weeks years whatever. So, if we look at decades there has been a real focus in recent decade about the safety and more and more about food safety. Umm the rules we are bound to probably do make it harder for us to reach those goals currently. So, but yes, there is the room for change, but we should not take eye of from the safety either.

Is there any financial support from the government to support circular economy?

Umm..., given the size of the problem, I am not sure, am not sure it sounds feasible. Looking at the size of incentives to encourage businesses, once you put down it to national level, umm, if you are talking about, for example tax deduction, umm it would be enormous and determinantal to the country. Because of the size of the industry. But yes, it is a great idea possibly a little idealistic. Difficult problem isn't it. Because you actually, arguing at the end it favours for capitalist businesses, which makes money out of the public purse and that's very hard shell.

What is your role in the company?

It kind of covers several area. So, my plan here is currently 12 months ahead, within the couple of months now that would be expanded to 18 months. So we have constant ... for 18 months future forecast. It is difficult in fast moving consumer goods world and it enable us to get our best view where we will be in that time and that means we can plan our factories um to spend cash available in right area that is about efficiency umm to work on, currently we are bringing automation to our sites. It enables to do these things by looking at the information available in multiple ways currently 12 months. Umm we are looking at to buying those materials typically time rage from 3

days to 12 weeks um, um some are beyond that because you know it's a global supply chain we go from all from the world. Obviously, part of that, we are trying to reduce the footprints to innovation as well. Umm., so with demand plan we see those sorts of things. And then we get next weeks for manufacturing site to look for their immediate capacity up to 12 weeks ahead. Umm. and planning the volumes for the next two weeks or beyond that two week three weeks four weeks and then the immediate of 1 week 10 days, 2 weeks depending on which account we are looking at. They will reduce the estimate which shouldn't be available by the day from the retailers and then we check and match up on the weekly level. If you see there are a lot of different ways to play around with the numbers to work on theoretical solutions to improve the efficiency.

What is the potential to apply circular approach in your role?

Circularity in the terms of bringing the goods back into um to supply chain, once they have gone through the retailer. Umm, if there is a viable route for that um which is a back into our supply chain then yes. Because then we will obviously see the demand which eventually will become the part of. So, we obviously need the plan falling to back in um parallel to what we are planning to manufacture from top of that. So, yea, at the moment plastic is which would be the part of them.

Which barriers affect the demand planner and how?

I think primarily that has to be around retailer's um we as say we work out currently 12 months sent to be the 18 months. However, when you look at the retailer's model and the interest from retailer um they want to make sure they are hitting the target annualising, reacting to market trends umm or responding the retailers market because its competitive market. So it is very difficult for us to encourage them to narrow down the plan and as far as we would like so yea I have magic worn today that will be to, probably the first way would be to get the retailer aligned to turn from 12 to 18 months planning but given the reason behind it, but it is a big ask and difficult thing to achieve. So, we have found ways of getting closer to it rather than achieving it. So that's retail, that just, so Covid is exaptational and there is massive impact in terms of our ability to um plan long term. So that's obviously otherwise we would have been put exit. So what else, these are I would call up as top challenges. It constant change consumer behind it even. It changes faster than I have seen faster than last 2-3 years. Change faster than 5-6 years I have seen, I think.

Do you think consumer perception is a hindrance factor?

Umm I think, thinking myself as the consumer, I understand the problem. I understand what we need to do to change. However, I spend a lot of money in the Waitrose because I know it is the best quality. So, it's obvious where, where personally my approach is, I think um, I would say there is difference between educated and less educated people around the world within any country, you get different responses and certainly economic difference as well but on the whole the responses will be negative in the current climate. I would to say without the right message, consistent message and I think this start with the government and from the right bodies umm., it's gonna be very hard to convince people to change until change is the only option.

What can be the Driving forces?

Umm., I think if we talking about circular supply chain here., there has to be umm an upside for the consumer to ask in the reduction in the price, technology has to be sustainable first and technology has to cheap umm which I dare to begin with its not going to be . but this is part on it it's the technology, it's the way of things, its worth starts out cheap um providing there is cost incentive then I think it could grow, However it also comes with umm it will overshadow if set to be cheap, giving your family cheap recycled food umm I can see there is negativity surrounding it in the world of social media currently. I wouldn't be healthy if compensation There is another difficult one to get ride but I think it has to cheaper but obviously not cheap as you wouldn't be giving your family bad food. If you are making recycle food as option for poorer people obviously speaking as socialist for self in this country.

PK (Operations Manager- 1 hr8 minutes)

Is circular supply chain management a business, environmental or sustainability strategy?

I would say it is mixture of all, because it will improve of all three sectors. umm at the moment food sector is much more working on the commercial aspect as well as on the end-user demands. So, their focus is not at the moment on the waste management, end-user waste management I would say. Umm the manufacturing stage yes, manufacturers are considering minimising the waste or whatever waste we generate, how we can recycle it. But reusing consumer waste and utilizing that stage has not started yet. Secondly, the retailer side because they are more focussed on to the sales and store management. Like the excess stock they are trying to sell it on lower prices. They are not focussed on to utilising that somehow into the same chain of consumption. These sectors still not considering the level as businesses are seeing the pay back. Business is just in to the making money and they look into the waste that how they can reduce but not on how to utilise it in effective way. The focus is not there, or the ways are not there. If I give you an example of our retailer, we are bond to their standard recipes and containers. So, we cannot sell them too somewhere else. We can give them to charities, but we will have to remove the labels. So, that's it is there is not any upcycling stage. Just instead of sending it to the landfill, we are just using it for good causes but there are not kind of any controlled and effective measures for it. It is just an additional activity been added but it is not any controlled or managed activity. It is not the part of the strategy of the business. Only the over flowed products which are good to use are sent to charities, but we have a lot of other processed waste and that is not considered into generating other consumer products. Surely people are thinking about it that food waste is the massive issue but not at that scale where start putting them into effective activities or essential activities.

Is it achievable in food industry?

It is of course achievable up to certain level, it might not be one hundred percent, might be 70 or 80 percent. So slowly we will have to jointly work around, how can we at least improve on somewhere or .. somewhere, start from somewhere, start from 30 percent 40 percent and slowly people will learn from that and when see the business is always revolving around money, when people will see that from that activity the money is generated or money is saved then they will focussed on it. Its all-money driven world.

See If I would say, our process waste we do our processes but when we develop any product, we focuses on utilising 100 percent ingredients means no waste so as waste is coming because of irregularities or some errors into the process. But that circularity waste management I would say still not exist. The reason is, it has not been considered that we will waste anything. When develop the product we do not consider the waste. We are meant to utilise whatever is there in process. If we make is sauce, we will use 100 percent, why to waste but that waste is generated over the period because cycle or the pattern or the demand and supply is miss-matched so umm like if we are getting customers order this morning, some of the orders we will have to supply tonight means we have to dispatch tonight and some we will have to dispatch by tomorrow so by that short period we cannot do everything because we have to order the ingredients and for ingredients suppliers have their own lead time. And then we have to cook that pack that label that and then load and send to the depot. The whole process is aligned in the way that there will be zero process waste. No one going to say that there will be wastage, they are expecting that nothing should be wasted. So that's where the circular supply chain management is not into that kind of open strategy.

Are there any technical challenges for manufactures?

There are few barriers we can considered, one of them is our chilled manufacturing mainly processing the natural ingredients those have short shelf life. So, because of short shelf life, it is a limitation to use that stock and product we produce are also based on those short supply ingredients and production their life is limited. It is not kept by the time there are sold out, but they are kept on the basis of shelf life. So, time factor is there, not selling factor. So, if we keep same product in the freezer like you see on the product sleeve that you can utilize that product for even month of you freeze it but as chilled it has only 7 days life. So, technique or technology, if can help in that thing that we can get the product life increased and affecting taste and texture. Because end consumer needs the product for human consumption and that there has been taste, texture and likeness of the product. But yes, it ends result is nutrition value so legally and ethically that required. So, the food I mainly taste, texture and likeness. So, the food we are making we should consider if it attracting the end user So if those umm kind of ingredients increasing the shelf life and not affecting the taste, texture or colour or eye appeal of the customer, I think this help massively in this industry. we have the wate in our side because of the order fluctuation, order go

up and down and our products we cannot send against the orders or stores. They are unable to sell the products within that shelf life. So, these are the few factors in food manufacturing. And the food products are very sensitive So has to be 100 percent quality standards like it is not like cloths or etc that it can be sold even if there is little defect. So, food means 100 percent quality standards which means waste if it is not there because we can't rectify it. And we can't use it for any other process of manufacturing, it will go for the recycling only So like in industry, we are recycling every small content of waste, so we send it for animal food. So, our recycler takes, clean and use for animal feed.

What are finance and economic related challenges?

See finance, obviously it is paid by end consumer but if we have the other ways for reducing the waste that can be umm reduce the cost for end consumer and they will have more supply of the products. Overall cost will be reduced and financially people, public would be benefited but because any business, they are making money by selling the products and they have to pay back their bills and expenses, so the pot is the same from money is coming. So, revenue is generated by only one activity that is by selling the products. So, of all activities, increasing the cost of that product So if we have more waste, our product will become more expensive. So that has impact on everyone. And If I say environmentally that there is still much food stuff goes to the landfill Like if we have produced our packs so the plastic, some part will go to the landfill even we are trying our best for recycling but that's not gonna go 100 percent. So, whatever is wasted is affecting the environment. So overall I would say there is impact everywhere. So that is why companies are thinking of reducing the waste but along with making the standards product. But if something still going to waste during processing, we should think to reuse or that or how to upcycle that. That part is missing.

Any management related factors affect the food manufactures to bring the sustainability?

See, we are the management, and our job is to reduce or eliminate the barriers so it could be some management but most of the management is always focussed on to, there are no barriers or to improve profitability and better production. And even somehow, if somebody does not like that not focussed on to that particular factor umm, I would say company somehow should be able to mould the all to get the job done but the main barriers for the management in food industry is to

what options and what techniques are available to upcycle or to reuse that product. Because I do not know for example if the chicken is outdated, what can I do with that. Because officially, we can't do anything with it, we cannot sell it to the customer, we cannot give it to retailer or street food makers or anybody, we cannot do anything because it is outdated. But sometime in India, I have seen people storing the onions for years. They have their own crops and save the rice, grain and there is no use by date on it. So why we need use by date on everything. I think, there is a consideration if the umm management driven excess into that and at the moment, food safety laws and legality does not allow that so those are the barriers. Like chicken if we are storing it in particular type of storage and there is no loss to the product or standard why we cannot use it. So, there should be some human interference human decision making should involve in it. Not going by hook where the technical people only go by hook like oh, I can only allow this much. It is not wrong, business asking them to go by that clause they can't alter. But there should be alteration into that assessment assess it, what's wrong with it, if they find there is nothing wrong, why we can't use it, might be it required little bit improvement like instead of using it for 10 days it can only be used for 8 days but still it could be utilise for some stage of for some life. So, these barriers are in built because of the legality or regulations and human consideration has been reduced. So, there are like I give example we use curry leave buy from local market cost us £1.35 for 50-60 leaves. We bring that and put into the freezer and whenever she needs it she use it but here in the industry, we have only cook+2 days life for after frying we can only use for 2 days only. There is nothing wrong in it. It is very straight forward product it has no harm even if we keep it for 2 months outside. It is such an expensive product. So, these all the policy hooks we have to follow. So, management is easy to mould, any changes come, management can easily be moved. I don't think management is barriers. Management is not self-driver they are driven by the business requirement, by the business operating model. So, I am told that we will not waste any product and you use it anyhow, I will have to follow that. I think not the management but the legal and set standards, rules and clauses been added over the years. If I would be stopping anything my boss would be monitoring me and then something is not done correctly, they will not tolerate me. They will replace me, so management is not the big issue. Bigg issue is all scenario when become the routine life and people start going by that like you cannot do this you can only do this.

What are the cultural factors?

See beginning of anything is always difficult. But umm something new comes up we tend to go with that and sometimes we have no choice. like the covid vaccine people will have to have it. No one would have thought about it. So, it is mostly driven by senior management whatever they want and how they want their operational model has to be. Umm with food industry the main concern is still condition and nature of the product and rules and regulations around it. Because whatever we receive on our site everything has its own life. We have to consume them within that life cycle and at the sometimes it has to be sold out within same time span. I can't go beyond that life. And the process mostly customer asking us to produce a product like match one product like as it is sold somewhere else and they

Want to replicate the same products. Because they do not want to lose the benefit of having something famous in their store. like Chicken Tikka Masala everyone wants to sell that. It is kind of, I think we are going better in terms of waste and in other words. Waste is one of our main KPIs and we always focus on that. Every day we discuss it every day what we wasted and how much and how can we reduce it and what are the root causes. In our company every site is running the food wastage projects and every year from last 15 years, senior management is leading those projects and we are getting better every year. So, focus is there, hope is there.

How consumers culture is important?

From the consumer side, I would say 70-80 percent they have their own standards and routine 20 percent is affected by the circumstances like if something is on sale or um people think lockdown is coming so buy even tissues or toilet rolls. That kind of panic culture, I think every year once or twice that time come people go panic otherwise is like I am from India my family love Indian food, we hardly buy any other food. So, consumer side if we talk about it happens if we fill up the freezer otherwise, we do not waste food products. And sometimes people see their fav food on the promotion and they buy lots of it of course industry is benefitted with it. Otherwise, consumer I am not sure they can utilize everything from the freezer. They can fill up but lately they do not like them after defrosting or reheating. Mostly I think awareness is required. Sometimes people go buy the longest life product especially from the chilled those products are short life products, they are not then to take the older life products and there are some products with short life left on the shelf, no one wants to buy them. So, at that stage, retailers shelf management needs to be much more effective. It should have sufficient products and not the mix of use by date. And sometimes it is

more expensive for them than their manpower cost so it is kind of Just In Time ... So if you go to some stores, like some cost effective stores, there will be very limited people managing those stores. And they are doing either cleaning or counter, they can fill up the shelf. During the busy period. If there are lots of customers, the shelves are empty they do not bother because they have done there prioritize work. So, these are the limitation everyone has first in first out product on the shelf needs to be managed. We do here in manufacturing to utilize the older date products. I am not sure how much they will affect the retailers.

Are there any hindrance factors related to structure?

All the organizations have their KPI's for reducing carbon footprints mainly reducing the waste. I am not sure what is output in term of the circular economy at carbon footprints so some researcher like you could be working on it. At the end, how can it be assessed. This more about running the business effectively having that growth in the business and making money and developing that business empire. If I give you one example like Amazon, they are the biggest company in the world at the moment. Once you order something, the product will be 2inch by 2 inch and that is coming in 1 feet cardboard So that waste in packing. So, I don't think they bother about because there main focus is on to the sales and making more money, generating revenue improving the profit. That's the way the businesses are, and every aspect is try to consideration but at the same time few things they are prioritise to those things on the lower list so we need to have that bigger picture to be seen, I am not sure. At the moment what's going on everywhere that kind of stuff so I can umm if you are selling the old car after certain stage it will go for recycling , no one wants to buy that might be very good car but that might be chopped off and we don't know what is the environmental aspect of it there might be perfect tyre perfect engine. That might be sold out in other economy where people are having difficulty. Umm but the systems are developed in a way that it can only be dumped or chopped off so like in India the plastic bottle people intestinally keep that secured and sell to kavadi. So here people do not care about it because that is not generating revenue to them. It can be done if councils start working on it even if they give double pounds for that but that can reduce lots of landfills. These are the ways to change the mind sets of the mass of the public, so I think food industry has big focus on the waste because expenses and ingredients or transport is expensive. So, drive is massive and focus very deep. But there is a lot of work needs to be done on various stages.

Is government playing any role to support circular supply chain management kind of business models?

I think umm everywhere the political scenario is kind of vote attraction activity. Government is doing various activities having environment friendly activities, reducing carbon footprints, reducing landfill umm and better utilisation of the food waste and charities work many things are happening but government is too busy to focus on other priorities. I don't think that is on their top list so and I would say the government is made by those political parties they do have their own agendas and that agenda is how they can come into power next time. So, their ethe focussed activities are which will keep them in limelight but the circular economy still does not have that kind of impact on people's mindset that can drift. I this could be like carbon foot topic is part of their main agenda I am just giving the example people and political parties are driven by the factors of their own time so I think there is still time to think about circular economy> Like you people have started talking about may be in near future it will be the main measure and there will be more people and more supporters. Few councils are doing good work I mean giving different bins for different kind of waste but like my council do not focus on that. Most of the councils are not working in that manner. This kind of work should be done by all. The councils because only few like some councils are doing. Why gov cannot implement same measure everywhere.

What are the capacities in food manufacturing industries to accept circular business model?

See the more awareness is required for that. And many times, we generate the food which is more eye appealing or based on the customer demand or market leading product so in those scenarios it becomes more focussed on to that product not on to the waste coming from that. What is liable for the surplus stock so these factors are not considered at that imp level because the focus is more on to that supply of product which is in demand. But yes umm for example if any product with bread crump coated that would be wasted but what we can to with that coated product coz everything is not going to be used up so there coz that is contaminated. So, you cannot use that with another product with different spacious and different allergens. So, there is issue there. No one wanted to produce market leading product because there is limited waste. So, these kind of stuff which many time people think what purpose of the business is. So, we have to consider and eliminate all possible risk before we send to the customers.

Which is major challenge for manufacturing stage:

The main issue is food safety regulations, because this industry is making food for human consumption. Every human could be different so we can take our focus out from those safety controls they have to be there coz of those controls there is ingredient waste and we cannot produce only one product whole day and utilize the related ingredients all the time. We are in the market we have to make the variety of products with different ingredients different allergens present to them, different groups, end consumer group we have to consider all the aspects. So, there would be some waste and also coz of this life restrictions of the product itself because they are natural ingredients and they have the limited life span so these are factors and at the moment and I don't know what else could be done in that. Chinese or Thai product we use soya sauce or sesame sauce, but we can't use it veg samosa. So, if in the same isle we are producing the products with allergen, we cannot produce anything else in there. So, there are some limitations.

This industry is more focussed, highly sophisticated, and complex.

What can be the drivers to adopt this model?

I think the moment it's not that much in that limelight, you are the first person who is talking to me about this, so we were not even thinking about that. So, I think massive awareness program should be the first option. When people know, they will start think and when they start thinking they will find the ways. It's not ends of the world that nothing can't be done there will be lots of ways to do it. That will happen when challenges will be coming. If you start talking, people will start thinking about it

Anything else you would like to add?

The government is implementation vehicle. But people have to make others aware. And the government has to work around what is in the limelight or which is seen as working to make people's life better. That awareness is there, something happens somewhere and if people know that there are some elements to make our life better and then government will react to that. Like 2 different councils have different strategies because it cannot be the same because no one is making them aware. Here the governmental vehicle has to come into effect and when they make it effective for everyone every council will follow, council cannot refuse. But those things are on

hard priority I think till the time they do not see them. Circular economy has a better future, but people have to be made aware.

RM (Consumer- Interview duration 30 minutes)

What is your view about circular supply chain management?

Circular Supply Chain Management is very interesting topic, I could understand and relate to as being from India which is developing country with majority of population is middle class and it is one of family belief to live with means, like it was understood that elder's clothes will be passed over to youngers etc. While growing up, I saw many shops like TV repair, fridge repairs and list goes up to repairing of slippers, utensils which made a consensus person towards natural resources. But with modern times, Repairing is almost obsolete as everything is easily available and not many professionals are interested in those tedious trade due to time consuming & many a time it is not successful and rewarding as to selling a brand equipment with less hassle. But we are not realising that those equipment's, extra clothes are becoming the part of waste and manufacturing consumes natural resources. I am sure there are ways to recycle or upcycle almost every and anything but lack of information, proper channels towards the directions is becoming the issue on customer level. As a consumer, It is crucial to understand scarcity of natural resources and Sustainability is the best preventive measure against pandemics and for future generations.

What are the challenges from manufacturing side and What initiatives you think can be taken from manufactures?

Manufacturers should invest in clean, green, renewable energy sources and designing the products with whole lifecycle in mind including re-using elements of worn off products. It should be standard practice of each manufacturer to really use the eco – friendly products, recyclable plastics. They should be innovative towards making the product eco-friendly and affordable. Clearly recycled plastic items can be fashionable too, like Emma Watson wore a black-and-white, off-the-shoulder dress with pants underneath made of recycled plastic bottles. Calvin Klein and Eco Age worked with Emma Watson to design the stunning and environmentally friendly gown.

What is the culture related challenges?

As a society, we all should play part to achieve sustain economy. We need to have changes in shopping habits, as customers we all like to have deals and without realising the real requirement of buying the fruits, vegetables pre-packeted, multi-buy like e.g. £1 can get you 1Kg Potatoes,

most of it goes unused and as soon as roots start to grow on them, we make it part of waste. Same things happen with multi pack crisps, snacks, canned food. As soon as we see the expiry date, without checking we just throw everything. I think the manufacturers should reduce pre-packaged food & on canned foods use by date should be there, not just expiry date. Many restaurants, small high street grocery shops, cafes have now started the initiative to reduce the food waste by participating in apps like Too good to go. I am sure these can be adopted by major retailers (although each supermarket does reduce the price etc of those items) but spreading the information is limited, they should use these apps or should find way to make customers aware.

Global Warming have become daunting yet imminent, therefore we all have taken active part whether as parents, teachers, counsellor we should do more efforts to make children, students aware of recycling, utilisation of resources. There are a lot of channels or ways to make everyone aware but the information about how we can achieve sustainability is limited, specially at consumer level. It took a while for me to find about difference in pastured eggs or chicken and organic /free range chicken. I had impression that this is healthy choice but eating/buying local grown vegetables, pastured livestock can make huge amount of difference than just jumping to Supermarkets for getting deals for cheap food, again it is not good for any of us in longer run.

What is your view about government? What are the challenges from institutional side? How can it be overcome?

The government of course plays a big role in any country's economy, and they can bring a lot more changes at faster speed than anyone else. Recently I have come across in news that UK Govt is looking to do Free Trade deal with Australia, one hand the deal shows a lot of advantages for UK economy, but some UK farmers have concerns there will be no meaningful safeguards in place to stop them being undercut by cheap imports.

Farmers in Australia are allowed to use some hormone growth promoters, pesticides, and feed additives that are banned in the UK. The UK Trade and Business Commission is worried that Australian farming operates on a scale that UK counterparts cannot compete with, saying Australia contains eight of the 10 largest farms in the world, including one which is larger than Israel.

According to the UK's National Farmers Union, Australian farmers are able to produce beef at a lower cost of production and could undercut farmers in the UK. On one hand this deal should

boom the export and will help the economy but import from Australia could have adverse result on health, local farming and will lead to more wastage and carbon footprints.

Jamie Oliver's campaign on cutting down sugar in drinks – Govt imposed Sugar Tax on soft drinks manufactures, so clearly Govt. have all the power to introduce new laws like to which can help the economy in achieving sustainability.

To control and maintain the population, China imposed one child policy (after many year it was reviewed) which helped them to overcome the problem of high population. There are numerous examples of Govt intervention – which changed the Country's social, economic and infrastructure.

Human have reached to Mars and Moon with developed technology, connectivity has improved drastically which means we have the infrastructure and technology to achieve almost anything, more and more manufacturers should work towards sustainability and Govt should support the manufacturers for it by may be allowing tax relief/rebate etc. But there are only few big companies who does upcycling of foods. Some of the supermarkets are making progress like changing the packaging which can be recycled but that is not enough, we all have to work towards 0% wastage specially food by buying absolutely necessary grocery and cooking in right amounts to avoid pilling up the fridges.

Interview VS (R&D Manager- Interview duration 1hr 15minutes)

What is your role in the organisation?

I am basically R& D manger and I look after M& S accounts. With me team and chefs we develop recipe for the supermarkets. We develop the recipe, take it down to the factory and make sure it lands up to the consumer's shelf. So that is my major role to control back of the team.

What are your views about circular economy term?

We have been working with customers around the circular economy as how it opposes to linear economy and working process of linear economy. So, Manufacturing side the food is the product that we produce and get it. In regard to co2 emission we have started to look to more of local supply chain which definitely starts to reduce those footprints. From the wastage side we have started linking up with different charities by giving away the food to needy people rather wasting it. This is a piece of work that needs to be done in food manufacturing. Another thing to look into will be how to use those things can be used up. Many supermarkets have already started clearing the shelf kind of strategy. They have started looking all the products those are coming close to the shelf life, they have started selling it on the reduced price., Those kinds of activities will definitely close the loop by not waste the food which can be used up by something. Obviously, councils are getting more aware of the fact. And you have seen some of the apps coming up which are linking up restaurants and small-scale restaurants retailers as well which are planning to do is to take certain amount of money. What they do is whatever the food left at the end of the say they will bag it for you and give it away to you. So, this also another way to close the loop from linear. Other than that, there is an element of educating the people as well. For example, in our business we have seen all supermarkets are throwing the plastic out and using more of cardboard packing. However, nobody realizes the fact or compared it with the model of circular economy. For people plastic seems to be much better way of packing however we need to educate the people, educate the retailer that about the carbon footprint.

If you see circular economy, there are subscriptions available, for instance our cell phones devices if we have contract, we can send them back. So, it does exist, but it is about the awareness fact.

Now many people have come out with Service as well and other piece of things. Fortunately, the food boxes although they were not started with intention of circular economy, but it fits very well in the model of circular economy. And they tend to be turn out extensive because it tends to be bit appointment for many of the people and this restrict some of the people to go for it.

What circular economy for you?

It definitely is a sustainability strategy and obviously a business model and how you apply this model into your business model. If take example of my company, we are generally look out for the local who reduces the carbon foot prints in that scenario. The biggest part is energy thing of it that goes into energy part of it. The machinery that has been installed for making those food products can that be worked on subscription base can that be looked upon like generally company sold out or the machines which are not working dump in the dump yard that will land into the landfill. This is part which has not been cared or looked up of. So, manufacturing business can be worked on the subscription base where you have care repair for them rather them you are finding out that it's not working and you r dumping into the dumping yard. Third thing is food wastage, again the for the food waste we are linking up with the different charities trying to reach out to local company not necessary that it has to go to the supermarket. If the things are not working. For instance, if we have 100 kg rice by error rather is there any possibility rather than throwing them out can we reuse it or giving them to local communities or to the people who cannot afford. We are making more and more leaner so obviously trying to reduce the carbon footprint when it comes to supply the product. So, at the minute we generally send to one depot then it gets distributed to different places. So that is are which can be worked upon to reduce the carbon footprints. For the retailer side it again come to the education piece how they are managing. Like the app I was taking about is a fantastic app, I go and but from that app. The name of the app is Too good to go, So if you use that app and put your location they find out your nearby small restaurant like Costa and all. You have to pay them certain amount £3- £4 whatever is required, and the box of goodies will be given to you. We do know what is there in the bag you just pick up the things which about to go to the waste. So that is the brilliant idea. So, these are the factors which can be looked into. Then obviously piece of education, plastic and card comparison. This is again with the supply chain management toward the fact that with our suppliers in the food supply chain, there is a gap where all these containers produce can they develop the unit where they can recycle it. Because it

end of the day their business which is going to suffer. So, if link up with councils and start working on it and try to get recyclability models to get included in their business there it will be big thumps up.

What role technology play? How can it help to bring these changes?

From the food retailing side, talking about that kind of apps, if you give people an option of those things, they might wait for that option. i.e., I have quite stopped going and buying the food straight away I wait for the offers to come. That affects over all the business or the profit model of business. Although I don't go with the intention of hampering the food or saving money but its more about saving the food. The demarcation that we need in order to make the people understand that it is more to not to wasting your food, will not come across sensibly to many of the people they will still wait for the offers to come in. Then the products on the shelf will eventually go to the waste. So, there are two things to improvisation to it one thing you are saving them from go to waste by introducing those apps from where you can buy. It can be sensible for many of the people for the people who cannot afford the food they can go out and have the food. Food industry is a short-life products industry, which is a major obstacle for circular economy implementation. Talking about new techniques, there are many techniques which are already in the market, by which you will get longer shelf on the products but obviously that does not go very well with the consumers. Eventually, it comes on the fact that what consumers like or doesn't like. Secondly, we keep looking into the techniques by which we can keep increasing the shelf life of the food products. There is an option of freezing the products when it comes to frozen products. Then there is another element that I mean there some E number that can boost up product life but that is not very consumer friendly, so we don't want to go to that root.

There is another option or technique is not restricting ourselves to what we need to produce. If there are certain element where we can work out with the retailers that we have certain surplus of food left out. Do you mind to buy on very essential rates and you can price it very low price just to use that food up and that will be at very short shelf life as well? But saying that it looks like there is bigger framework which need to be worked or framed out. Because we will have to take it to the parameters like how it affects the sales of another products.

For the food products, actually it is not like electronic products. Linear economy does not fully apply to food products, as it is an element that you take it, consume it, if you are not managing your recycle bin in an efficient way you are still falling in some the essence of circular economy. What happens when it comes supply chain or in our manufacturing side, when you start to waste it. That is where you break the link then you move more in the linear economy side of it. So, if you address the issue to linear economy focus can be shifted toward how we can reduce the waste and how the resources can be used more efficiently. It will benefit everyone.

Do you think these sorts of technologies will be needing investment? So, finance is barrier for companies?

If you start reducing waste out, you will have to work out. But challenge I would say that It will be hampering the sales of other products as well. We all be giving more options to the....

And not convincing in the other side. So, finance will be the biggest challenge. Also, to produce those things so that they do not to the waste you need to have fair calculations on it. On other resources as well if you see, to produce 100 meals so that they don't go the waste, we need calculate how much electricity we going to use, how much of other resources you need to use. There is fair balance you need to keep. So, from the food supply chain that's what I have seen form the finance side of it, I was thinking how fringent you can be for the processes of food supply chain or food manufacturing, the better it will be.

I don't see, I should not be financially viable. There is need of close approach from both side of parties, from our end and from retailers as well. If you compare both the ways, like if you recycle bin them in a good way that it will not go to landfill and don't get waste, like if you send them for compost so it may work in this way. But if you have to purely use it and not account it to wastage you might find ways but obviously that will have financial implications.

From economic side, if I see, it is about how you source your material, where you get the raw material. So, linking up with your local supplier would help. Now the tendency of the people is going more towards far east and the Brexit thing, which has happened. People are more incline to go to east side like Vietnam and China. So, what that will impact is, that will increase the carbon

impact which used be as 300mg carbon emission, getting this implemented that significantly changes to 3000mg by getting from Vietnam. From economy side if you see all these factors, that can help. The other factor was also, if you consider the pricing of those products as well, that is the way how the conversation happens. Getting the products from Vietnam without considering circular economy or considering all those factors it still works out to be cheaper you get it from UK. It is bit of pitch over there that what is stopping us to that and what are the challenges. We can understand those, and we can utilize those.

Profit generating approach is also a factor, that is what it is at the end of the day that t how businesses can make the money. But now it is more about as I said initially that there has to be sustainability model in the business and that is where you start asking the questions and answer those questions. Like generally we have tendency of getting things from far east countries, even sometimes without knowing that things may be available withing the same price in the UK. Just because we have existing supplier, he supplies for the number of years. We never go out and explore the options that might be available within your country. So, when a supermarket or food manufacturing company or food chain implement those models into their working standards or start defining their goals there then you become more of asking the questions to yourself that ok the resources, I am looking from far east are they available in the UK or not.

Do you think management is a hindrance to bring circular economy approach in the company?

To some extent, I do believe that management is a hindrance. Obviously, it all comes down to numbers and money making. But most the management has started realizing it importance. It is not from the perspective of circular economy but from the perspective of sustainability. So, It will will an element that how can you make people more educated about circular economy. I myself, keeping on linking with people in supermarket so I do know what circular economy is and how it works and how it should work. But there are many people who are not aware of it. As initially, I gave example of comparison of plastic packing as compared to card packaging. All the supermarkets are in goal of reducing it by 2022-23 but they don't realize the fact that it is not the right thing to do. That is how management comes into picture that management might not be aware

of it or they might not have seen the picture of it. They are just trying to get customers on that board, more and more customers to come to their market. Having those sustainability ideas, is not right, it is more hampering than having a right idea. So, Management whenever they release the policy for reducing the plastic or something because there might be a big noise at that time that they are giving the advertisement that they are reducing the plastic by 2022 but without realizing that what will the impact of any different packaging. So, I do personally believe that there is blame on management side as well that how they deal with the situations or they are more about money making business by achieving the targets or achieving the goals.

Do you think company's culture play a role?

Yes, I do believe company's culture play a part. When I used to work in different company where giving the products to charities was not pronounced. So, there was a different culture over there. Whereas this company coming from Indian background, they do have tendency of not wasting food. This thing is embedded from India in our culture. So, working in this company I learnt that people realize the value of food. For instance, in our department, R&D anything when which is coming out of date. We take it out and give people for free. We don't give it to dispenser machine, just give it for free. But in our old company we never used to see that. The food, which is expiring nearly, we used to dump it. That's what it is. We constantly challenge ourselves that how many trials, we have to do or how many samples do we need so that we are absolutely closed to the numbers. We are not over-producing. Unfortunately, part of the game is, there is bigger picture, we still stay with the same mentality to do the things in certain way. It will take a while to understand. For instance, if we cook the rice, we have to cook 400 kg rice, out of which we will use only 100 kg and 300 kg will go to the bin and the is purely for the trials. So, there is an element of educating the people, that 300 kg which you waste is a bigger picture not something very small thing. This is the example of only one trial. If I go and calculate the numbers for all through, the numbers are far-far bigger. So, although we are working in it but there are still elements there. My old company, which was more a British company, these elements were not there.

What barriers are there in the consumer side?

Consumer side, yes, the awareness is there but awareness is not in regard to circular economy. So, the awareness around the customers is stopping the food waste and recyclability. That is what my

understanding is from consumer side culture. Because people are not aware of circular economy or linear economy. There are more concerned about the concept that they are wasting the food and what is the cost for it. We have seen the shopping bags are now going smaller. People are becoming more sensible about what they are putting in the shopping bags. So, awareness is there but they need the right education. Because people who are shopping from the supermarket might think that supermarket is doing the right job by switching to card packaging. They are not aware that this is not right from the circular economy and carbon footprints perspectives.

To some extent, it depends on the retailers to retailers. We do have segmentation of consumers of different supermarkets. If you put same thing in Aldi or Lidl or Asda or Tesco as well. People will take it as long as it is a good food on better price. But if you put same thing in the Waitrose or M&S, they might not like it. They will start questioning, if the existing products are on the shelf. It can be promoted. Then, again the element of educating and social behaviour will be a hindrance when it comes to implementing it.

What are structure related barriers?

On the moment, this more about the mind set within the structure. It is more about understanding by the people within that culture that what is CE is all about. It may hold on to the way as well, having the teamwork for the CE and sustainability. There is a need to build the 3 years or 5 years plan on how to implement the things. At the moment, I think none of the company do have that type of structure in the business which is ready to do it but there is a good awareness but again not for the CE but for the waste management and sustainability.

It will be a complex thing. It is about challenging your core ways of working. It is about challenging the social behaviour of staff. There will be many aspects where you need to educate the staff. It is not an easy thing, when you see implementing the circular economy. It is very big things to be honest. Then, it can be embedded with different people in the organization. But having a goal and having the team kind educating the people with different managers within the organization, we need this kind of pack.

Is government playing its part?

At the current scenario, I do not think government is doing very to implement the circular economy. Because when it comes to educating the people about it. By going circular people actually trying to make money out of it, challenging core thing. That is the start of government plans, they should start introducing thing. There will be many things which might work for circular economy, but they might not work with their own agenda, political agenda so I don't think that government is doing good job. Going back there is hell lot about the awareness of sustainability but there is a need of awareness about circular economy and linear economy.

Going back to 2010-12, how many people were aware about recyclability, about the tray etc that what can be recycled or what not now all of sudden there is awareness. There is come the role of government because there are the one who can implement it very well. They are the one who can educate people about it. But when it comes to circular economy, the scenario slightly changes because it becomes bit if challenging because you know how to make the relationship with big stockholders of the company or the financial people of the country so you will be challenging the huge supermarkets by selling or I mean how the supermarket will react on it. Will they support the supermarket in their agenda? Might not.

What can be the drivers, you think to overcome these barriers?

Government can make it happen by controlling the food wastage itself. I am not very close to it but I don't think we have accountability on how much food we throw out. That is what council can pick up. I many times the food oil or food itself goes by the drain; huge fines are imposed by the council but other than that there is nothing. If you put those examples in the picture, if government starts putting / imposing good fines on the supple chain thing or on the manufacturing about what they are wasting and how they are wasting and controlling their waste then definitely it will sort some part of it. But the other element like how government try with the retailer side of it or educating people about it, how to do these things. How can it be managed from economy side of it. That is something government can look into.

What do you think from the factors discussed earlier, or any other factors, affect directly your department?

If you see in my department itself, I will take bigger picture over here. I will put it in the developing of products altogether. Right now, there are some technical standards like how to buy the things or how to do the things and how you justify the things that element has thought us to be more efficient in regard to controls. So, let's say for instance producing the meat product we sherd out the bones, we sherd out the fat and just use proper lean piece of meat but what happens to that waste so if a supermarket or authorise allow us to use those things or start including in the recipe then outcome can be better in the terms of circular economy. who's a properly piece of meat ok but then what happens to from the developing perspective challenges that we have our technical and updating the technical understanding? Using cauliflower or ice florets to certain dimensions We don't even counter that the pieces can go through kind of things. Those kinds of intension that I personally feel that when it comes to developing the products. So, if a super market or from an organization perspective you start taking more towards reducing the food waste kind of thing for developing products, so those kind of model, it will definitely help. Yes absolutely, you might have seen Prets and all these people they are doing certain range of products and they say like they are from the leftovers. There are companies who make soup out of leftover. So having that kind of leftover, for instance If we do cauliflower, I mean obviously it's a bigger picture generating in the retailer side. If you see cauliflower, we are using only florets and throw away the stem whereas the stocks can be used up as well. Going back to my childhood, my mom she never used to throw away anything. Having those principles applied over years in current scenario, nothing bad, I think. additionally educating people on the bold like British consumers do not like the meat with the bones but again what happens to the bones are they used up or let say developing a range of products that completely made from leftovers, need to bring in the market. Again, people are aware about it there is awareness but looking from the circular economy No, they are only form the food wastage side.

What initiatives you are taking to ensure the sustainability in your department?

At the moment, I am trying to implement a lot taking my team, but we do struggle we do have challenges. Now what we are trying to do widening my specs to do. That helps to get more and more vegetable in there. There is another element breaking down of compound ingredients. This is again breaking down the ingredients when you buying full source from a company like when you buying a light source from a company all they do it they add water and send it to you so just

part of it is that they are saving money for company and the company is very happy about it what I feel, falling into circular model basically 3 tiers of food for having 2 different task on fleet. Having those carbon emissions, you are cutting one of them. SO if you see in that Way I feel my manager will see in that way that they are saving money for the company but this is the different perception of like from 2 different people. So, we do have issue, or we have e uniquely stuff ingredient or we have widening up the specs making sure that the food is not getting wasted from our kitchen. We have to cook particular of sauces we have stocked it up upstairs we ... up to 3 kilos. I did not happen overnight It did take a while. We tale challenges we take it down to the factory where we have to readjust at the end of the day. Because obviously, even 3 submissions of 3 kilos risk.

Anything else you would like to add?

It is like a loophole are dots need to be connected at the minute at money you are aware of the wastage, you are aware of the suitability, but nobody picturising it that how this model will fit into circular economy. You might be doing this, but you do not know what are doing is right thing to do. I might have different impact. Ok you are not filling up landfills by the plastic but are your aware of the impact you are having former. Like from the Carbon emission side of it that is the one thing of it that it is not landing into the landfill, There is one element you can work with the suppliers or packing companies or supplier let them set a unit, recyclable unit where they can use the containers, take the responsibility from council to recycle those and then things can be use like 30 percent less plastic or 50 percent less plastic bringing those number down. That is the pool way of circular economy looks like not like you take it and you take or you take this one out because it is filling our land elusions. It is impact is other way round. Government should be educating the circular economy to people make their mindsets.it needs bit education needs to. Be there. Initially when these things like reducing plastic started. There used to boards where we used to see how the elusions are getting filled out and animals are getting killed, I mean I can be done for circular economy. In the way of making people more aware not just. And finding the people who want to do it.

SR (Technical Manager Interview duration-52 minutes)

What is the circular economy for you? Business strategy, Sustainability Strategy, or an environmental strategy?

All of it. It should be a business model, this is how the economy should work, this is how manufacturing of the product should work. This is how businesses should work. It is need of the hour. Right from the beginning to end stage of product, it should be in- built in company's processes. It not only saves the resources which benefits the businesses but saves environment also. So, it is everything I guess it is an environmental model and business strategy, if want to be efficient. If they are concerned about their turnover etc. So, there is a lot of money to be saved with it and benefits nature as well. It should be both general economy nature, environmental as well as business.

What is the supply chain model of your organization?

I am probably not the right person to answer that we have specific department to deal with supply chain management only. We are the one part of whole business model. I can tell you about my own department. I know we deal with various companies(retailers) and food is dispatched from our company. All I know that many lorries lined up in the morning when products are shipped to company depots and from depots products are transferred to stores.

What are the possibilities to apply circular supply chain management practices to your company's supply chain model?

I am not sure if the whole circular model can be adopted but certainly, there are a lot of improvements can be made. In terms of, where I fit in to product itself. I am looking after the area of product sampling, labelling, I can only talk about the area that I deal with. It all starts with retailers asking us to create the range of products. Just to keep it simple, if they asked us to 10 products to launch in a day in the supermarket. Then our R&D department consisting mainly chefs and all they start the process of submitting these products to retailers till it is approved. It goes through various rounds of product submissions, then probably at one stage retailer will say yes,

we loved this recipe, go and launch it within the given time frame. Then we for trial. We do factory trial, which means we need to generate a lot of information in order to launch that particular product. So, we do quite a number of trials we need to get done. Anyway, 1 factory trial to 5 factory trials we do in order to get the product launched. It takes about 5-6 months for the range of products launch. So, in the means the meanwhile, we have to do factory trials. The things with factory trial are, when chefs and R&D department submitting the products to retailers, they do it in small batches in their development kitchen. It is of 1 kg or 2 kg of batches, and they will make whatever is sufficient for them to show to the customer. So, it is trial on small scale. So now when the product is approved, we are asked to do it on the large scale. This is the gate when you do a proper product launch. In order to make your recipe, from taking it to a small kitchen to the big factory kitchen, there are obviously some treats needs to be done to the products when you are cooking from a small to a large scale. You need this much water, or you need less chill in order to balance it out. This whole process is done to the whole products. So, from these 2 kgs batches we will go anywhere to 60kg, 120 kg or sometimes 200 kg in order to scale up the product. I guess there is some hope on saving there. We need to do it on large scale in order to see how the product needs to be modified once launches. You can't really skip that completely. You have to do it on the large scale so that the retailer can see that there will be consistency in the product when they approve to go on the large scale. Unfortunately, this cannot be skipped, it needs to be done. Now all of that material is not necessary used up to do things, some may go to waste as well. Obviously, the trial is not only done for sculler proposes, some samples are used to generate a lot of information like what the shelf life of that product is going to be, what the nutrition information needs to be on the packing sleeves. How does it perform organoleptically, for example how does it taste change when it used after 10-12 days or the cooking instructions, so we need that trial? But not all the batches which were used for scaling up is used. So, some of it may be going to waste. So, it required within the trial to reduce the waste over there. Like the samples we are ordering, is it the optimum number of samples or are we ordering too much which ending to waste. Usually it does not, we always try to improve on all the stages because we try to use optimum number because we lack the storage space as well in NPD. So, we try to get optimum or as less as possible. But also, the question is how many times we need to do the trials. We could end up doing trial for a specific retailer for at least 3 times so that is a lot of food right there. And as the trials go on, you use a lot from 1 sample but from the following samples not the lot of it is used. So, I guess there is something to be done

there, the company is looking to reduce the number of trials but some time it is customer demand we need to comply to that because us to do that is there requirement is to follow. If their requirement is to do 3 trials, we need to do that. But yes, I think is there some sort of conversation needs to happen with the retailer as well. To see what the optimum batch size is we can use. So that it does not into wastage and serve the purpose on the same time as well. I am sure kitchen process department investigates these things. I am saying what my thought process is. So yes, from the development point of view that could help in some for this saving. In terms of how much food is getting wasted. It might be the way of doing trials.

What are the technical barriers, come in the way to accept circular model in supply chain of food industry, you think?

One of the technical barriers would be the shelf life of the product. The longer the product can stay on the shelf the more optimum use it can have. But obviously we have restrictions our kind of product would be on the shelf for 10- or 11-days max because it develops micros. We have bacteria control which allows us to have product shelf life for up to the 11 days but cannot go beyond that because we don't have clostridium control. So, I guess you need some sort of technological advancement there. You can do certain things like at the moment we do is we cook our product and chill it and pack it and that gives the listeria control. If we were to cook and hot fill it, we have certain clostridium control, and the product can be used up to 14 days. We do not have that facility in our organization, we do not have facility to hot fill at all. I do not whether it is most suited to our kind to products or not, but you would see that kind of things in the bottling industry for different kind of food. Potentially, it is possible to do that if we have that kind of advancement in technology. Potentially, we could have a longer life of products and then lead to less the wastage. I think shelf life is one of the key things in food industry and requirement of the trials and the scaling up from small batches to big batches is a huge area as well. Also, some element, components, often get dumped because in the factory we have only 48 hours WIP life which is low. I guess if we have the longer WIP life, how that could be achieved that is a question. Whether it is by equipment, or by design so if PH is lower you could have longer shelf life in components, so you make the product more acidic or you add the. In our company we do not use preservatives because it has got different impact. So, these are the tumbling blocks we have.

Do you think finance play a part to bring circularity in food supply chains?

I think, a key chain will be required to make it. I guess finance is not a barrier as such, but you need finance to support to make those change, there would be huge amount of investment would be required. But if that investment outweighs the benefit that you to get from this model. I do not think it would barriers, but the main thing is to identify someone who can identify what benefits they would to have. What investment Its requirement if they were to go down that root. It thinks project needs to be done end to end. I do not think it a barrier, but businesses just need to see business sense in it. Now it is impacting overall. I am sure it does require considerable investment. I am there are easy wins which you can as well the things I talked about trials and samples, we look into products design, talking with retailers already. Change can be made, and our company is constantly striving to do that. But some of the other things where you probably need equipment to change machinery, so finance is involved there.

Is management a barrier?

I do not think it will a barrier all. I think the management is very do don't these things. We got our own suitability targets and Kerry as a company constantly looking at those things. Recently, we are told about our sustainability target, which are really impactive. I think management is sorted.

And how about cultural aspects? Existing literature says changing existing company's culture is a big challenge. What do you think? How can it be overcome?

What come to my mind is, I think the trend of recyclability, or reusing is catching over more than ever. The country I come from there we re-use and recycle a lot and number when I was a lot younger. I am sure that also a part of supply chain model when bottle of thumps up. Parents used to buy crate of thumps ups and used to leave some deposit and we needed to return those empty bottles and get the deposit back. I think that was the perfect circular supply chain model example in terms of packing where crate as well as bottles used to returned. So, I think that trend is catching on more here now. But yes, there are barriers here in terms of thinking about recyclability or reusing something that somebody has used already.

And consumer side of culture?

I think people are coming around to it more now and gradually it is going to improve. But I guess there are still some barriers. Like for example we were moving from the tray we use trays we use, and we use natural tray and that comes with the black pigment in the tray which helps the recyclability of the tray and tray can be of any colour from the pink, green to cream in colour because they are made to proper recycled material and then people started asking questioning why these colours. So, then they understood it is a mix of different base material. But the first reaction was like ewe. I don't want to use these trays. So, I think there some mental barriers about recyclability or reusing the materials is still there. But as we educate people more about it that how it is the need today and how the waste is destroying the planet. People are listening more but slowly and gradually. So yes, there are cultural barriers there.

Do you think lack of structural is a barrier?

Yes, it can be.

How about your company? Does your company have appropriate structure to bring this model?

What I know is company and management is always trying to find the ways that how we can reduce things like that. They are always pushing how we can reduce or manufacture leaner and more efficient. In some companies, it is like to happen that some may have a good idea but no ears to listen to that idea. Not true for Kerry I would say, there is a possibility that some ideas may be suppressed or taken seriously or not taken forth. So, it is possibility.

Do you think law, regulation and legislation or government can help to bring these changes in the economy?

I suppose there should pre- determined targets that you need to do on by that certain day and date. This is how companied would be forced to look at these things. I know are sustainability targets that are out their company's org can choose to be the part of that programme, but it is not imposed on the orgs. Sooner rather than later some king of improvisions are requires and will push the business to look at their business models and look into proper utilization of their resources. Government as a part of play or practically everything, I guess. Whether it is by way of

encouraging or by way of regulating or imposing. Government can choose at the end. Definitely I would say.

If we talk about your stage 'Product Development stage' of supply chain or your department, which barriers directly impact you stage to bring sustainability or circularity? And how?

Going back to trial, resources utilization for the business I guess in food manufacturing. Say for example we need to generate cooking instructions for a product. We need to have repeated kind of work on triplicate or sometimes six times. for example, any product needs to be cooked for 20 minutes. we have to do it 6 times on each setting. Like you got a fan oven, you got a electric oven or you got a gas oven you need to do it 6-6-6 (18) times before that cook time can be approved so you know it is not the waste of resources but the waste of time as well.

Food safety restriction are here. But the barrier here is the system that has been laid by the retailers. Even if we have set the cooking time for particular product, sometimes retailers still send the products for validation again to another company or to their own lab. Sometimes have to send 5 samples of each setting and we end up sending 30-60 samples just for them to approve the work which we have done. That is a big barrier for me, if they rely on our own cooking instructions, we can save a huge amount of food from samples. We tried to bring down the triplicate trials to duplicate or a single trial. Which did not actually work. It worked for the existing products but not for the new products. As triplicate trial model gives extra time to retailers to gather the information which is need. So, it is to do with retailers' policies as well. If they look and keep sustainability in mind, then we can get huge reduction amount of wastage we get out the trials.

If there anything else, you would like to add?

It is really interesting concept, definitely we should be looking into it more and more from planet sustainability point of view and there is a lot of gain for businesses as well. Every department needs do their own letter as you said it is every step of the way, every piece of the process of business, it is its own circle basically. I mean talking to you makes me think more about it that how we can do it our department.